

***‘What are Those Grunts and Growls Over There?’
Computer Game Audio and Player Action***

By

Kristine Jørgensen

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Section of Film and Media Studies

Department of Media, Cognition and Communication

Copenhagen University

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Supervisor: Torben Grodal

Abstract

This dissertation concerns the functionality of sound in computer games, with focus on the relationship between game audio, player actions and events in the game. The central questions of investigation in the project centre on *how game sound affects player actions*, and *how auditory information enables the player to take action in the game world*. On this basis, the focus lies on the relationship between the use of audio and the player, with emphasis on the player's actions and responses.

The point of departure is that the functionality of game audio depends on the dual nature of computer games as a *game world* and a *user system*. As a game world, the computer game is seen as a coherent virtual environment in which the player acts and which utilizes sound to enhance the sense of presence in this game world. As a user system, the computer game is manipulated by the player through an interface consisting of input devices such as game controller or mouse/keyboard and audiovisual output. This user system emphasises sound as a usability feature that provides reactive and proactive information to the player. Computer game audio combines these roles by making usability sounds merge into sounds that seem to be motivated by a sense of presence and the illusion of realism in the game world.

The project draws on theory primarily from two different angles. The first is *film theory on sound and music*, which studies the use of sound in an audiovisual context where it seeks to emphasise a specific fictive world. The division between *diegetic* sound that appears to belong naturally to the game universe and *extradiegetic* sound that seems to comment on what happens within the game world from an external perspective has been central in understanding how audio works to support the virtual game world. The second theoretical angle is *auditory display studies*, which derives from ecological psychoacoustics and human-computer interface studies. Auditory display studies research and develop systems that utilize sound for communicative purposes in computer systems, virtual simulators and the everyday life. The ideas of how different types of sound signals may be used to provide different kinds of *responsive* and *urgent information* have been fruitful in understanding how game audio works for usability purposes.

The study is also based on empirical studies of computer game players and game audio developers. Game developer interviews have revealed purposes and intentions behind audio in computer games, and pointed out possibilities and constraints in connection with game audio development, while the interviews with and observations of players of two different games have demonstrated how actual players understand and utilize sound in the gaming context.

Resymé

Denne avhandlingen behandler lydens funksjon i dataspill, med focus på forholdet mellom spillyd, spillerhandlinger og hendelser i spillet. Problemstillingen i prosjektet dreier seg omkring *hvordan spillyd påvirker spillerhandlinger, og hvordan auditiv informasjon gjør spilleren i stand til å handle i spillets verden*. Ut fra dette grunnlaget ligger fokuset på forholdet mellom bruken av lyd og spilleren, med vekt på spillerens handlinger og responser.

Utgangspunktet for diskusjonen er at lydens funksjon avhenger av dataspillenes doble opprinnelse som *spillverden* og *brukersystem*. Som spillverden blir dataspill forstått som en virtuell verden der spilleren er en handlende agent, og denne spillverden bruker lyd til å forsterke spillerens følelse av tilstedeværelse. Som brukersystem blir dataspillet manipulert av spilleren gjennom et grensesnitt bestående av input-mekanismer som spillkontroller og mus/tastatur, og audiovisuell output. Dette brukersystemet vektlegger lyd som et viktig element i forbindelse med brukervennlighet, og som et system som gir spilleren informasjon om tidligere og kommende handlinger. Dataspill kombinerer disse rollene ved å la lyder motivert av brukervennlighet smelte sammen med lyder som ser ut til å være motivert av følelsen av realisme og tilstedeværelse i spillets verden.

Prosjektet tar i hovedsak utgangspunkt i to forskjellige teoretiske retninger. Den første er *filmteori med fokus på lyd og musikk*, et felt som studerer lydbruk i audiovisuelle sammenhenger. Et konseptuelt skille som har vært viktig i forståelsen av hvordan lyden støtter følelsen av en virtuell verden, er skillet mellom *diegetiske lyder* som har kilder i filmens verden og som tilsynelatende eksisterer naturlig i denne verden, og *ikke-diegetiske lyder* som ser ut til å kommentere hva som skjer i filmverden fra en ekstern posisjon i forhold til denne. Det andre teoretiske utgangspunktet er studiet av *auditory displays*, et felt med røtter i økologisk psykoakustikk og HCI-studier (human-computer interaction). Auditory display-feltet studerer og utvikler systemer som benytter lyd for kommunikative formål i datasystemer, simulatorer, og hverdagslivet. Ideer omkring hvordan forskjellige lydsignaler kan benyttes til forskjellige *responsive* og *alarmerende* formål har vært viktige i forståelsen av hvordan spillyd fungerer i forbindelse med brukervennlighet.

Dette prosjektet er også basert på empiriske studier av dataspillere og utviklere av spillyd. Intervjuer med spillutviklere har gitt innsikt i formålene og intensjonene bak utviklingen av lyd i dataspill, i tillegg til å poengtere ut en rekke muligheter og problemer i forbindelse med utvikling av lyd i spill. Observasjoner av og intervjuer med spillere av to forskjellige dataspill har på sin side vist hvordan faktiske spillere forstår og benytter seg av lyd i en spillkontekst.

Preface

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1. Introduction

Already as a child in the 80s, sound and music in games spoke to me through systems such as the Commodore 64 and the Nintendo Entertainment System. Regardless of how primitive the melodies were, audio seemed to be important for what went on in the game, and turning off the sound was never in question. I shared this passion with a generation of game enthusiasts, who still sing the melody from games such as *The Legend of Zelda* (Nintendo 1987) although none have heard the music in years. The same now 30-somethings even remember such oddities as the melody of the music in *Super Mario Bros.* (Nintendo 1985) that told the player to hurry up.

Although these auditory features have contributed to my experience of computer games from an early age, it was not until I became a student that game audio caught my attention as interesting theoretically. In 1998 I played the 1-year old *Final Fantasy VII* (Square Enix) on the Sony PlayStation, and after having played through this roleplaying game once I played it again. Why did I do that? Although it is a good game, it certainly does not have the greatest replay value due to its pre-planned event structure and the fact that the player discovers every secret during the first play-through. It was the music that kept my interest. The tunes made the game really worth playing again, not because of the way they were implemented or their indirect way of communication, but simply because they were so catchy. It is no wonder that the soundtrack's composer Nobou Uematsu is hailed as a pop star in Japan.

After my experiences with *Final Fantasy VII*, I began to focus my attention on game sound in general and game music in particular. When playing Black Isle's *Planescape: Torment* recently after its release in 1999, I realized that I became aware of incoming enemies before they actually turned up on the screen. As a media student, I understood that it was the computer game version of the leitmotif (Gorbman 1987:3, 26-29) at work. First appearing in Wagner's operas, the leitmotif is a musical theme that accompanies or denotes specific characters in the audiovisual narrative. While it is often used as an auditory support that emphasises the character's emotions, personality or fate through its mood, it may also work as a reminder or a hint related to that character. In *Torment*, on the other hand, it works as a warning that tells the player about approaching danger. The use of music as information system is also found in the next game that attracted my auditory interest, *The Elder Scrolls III: Morrowind* (Bethesda 2002), and this was the game that made me seriously consider researching computer game audio academically.

However, in *Morrowind* music may work both *proactively*, as in *Torment*, by informing the player of an upcoming event, or *reactively* by adapting to a situation which has already started, such as battle. In *Morrowind*, music informs the player about off-screen events, and environment sounds are also designed for this purpose. In this respect, the players may hear the grunts of an approaching monster and prepare for combat although they have not yet seen the enemy. During playing the game I saw the similarities between these uses of sound and film sound, but what struck me most of all was the differences in functionality due to the presence of a player responsible for progression in the game world.

1.1 Themes & Problems

Except for the existence of some articles on the subject, there is at the time of writing no comprehensive academic study of sound in computer games. There are a number of books on the subject game audio, but they are exclusively game industry handbooks and not theoretical considerations of the role of game audio or how audio functions in a larger game context. This makes the project an ambitious one in two respects. Firstly, it is a difficult project since there is no paradigm or already established ground on which to develop the argument of the project. Secondly, the ambitions lie in the fact that this project is one of the first that seeks to traverse the landscape of game audio; thus it is an early attempt at outlining a theory of game audio. In this respect, the project is clearly a pilot study by being explorative both methodologically and theoretically, and also in the sense that it shows the early results of doing research on a subject that has not yet been addressed by scholars. Every consideration in this dissertation is therefore subject to change, by later research done by me or other students of game audio.

This project on computer game audio seeks to reveal the *functionalities of sound in computer games*, with focus on the *relationship between sounds and events in the game*. The questions that have worked as the main motivators for this project are related to *how game sound affects player actions*, and *how auditory information enables the player to take action in the game world*. In this respect, it is the functionality of sound in relation to actions and events in games that is the primary concern, with a special focus on how sound affects player actions and reactions. In addition, because the sounds have a close relationship to the game world and the experience of it, the project is also concerned with how sound contributes to defining different spaces of action, and how sound may provide information about spaces that it does not seem to originate from.

This thesis is therefore a study of the relationship between the *game world* as a coherent environment in which the player acts, and the game as a *user system* that is manipulated through an interface consisting of input devices such as mouse/keyboard or game controller and audiovisual output. The fact that games have a dual nature as virtual world and user system has specific consequences for the realization of game audio. This dual nature means that sound has two overarching purposes, which is to work as a usability system at the same time as it conforms to the reality status of the game world. Sound should therefore increase the feeling of a lifelike universe and the sense of presence in the world by being connected to sources in the game universe in a credible manner. In this thesis I will explore how game sound works to combine these two roles into a coherent sound picture. I will demonstrate how game sound supports the virtual world and the usability of the system simultaneously and coherently. The thesis will also demonstrate how sound interplays with the gameplay activities and the game mechanics, and becomes a necessary part of the overall game design.

It is also important to emphasise that this project concerns the actual sound implemented as an aesthetic and functional part of the game. The project studies sound as part of the game artefact, which leaves certain features outside, such as the use of voice-over chat add-on programmes, player implemented mp3s from the computer hard drive, and direct player-to-player communication when the game is played together in the same room.

1.2 Methodological & Theoretical Background

We can ask why sound has been ignored so far in computer games research. It turns out that we find many of the similar reasons as to why sound was long ignored in general psychophysical research as well as, for instance, film research. Sound is not only non-physical but also non-visual, which means that it is difficult to study it closely (Maasø 2002:1-2, 12). It is not possible to put it on the table in front of you and study it. Neither is it possible, as with film images, to pause the image and study its contents closely. Here we also touch the transitory and temporal aspect of sound in general, which is another reason why it is hard to study. Sound is something that passes a person by without leaving any trace, except in memory, which again is untrustworthy. As far as film and media studies have been concerned, sound has not been regarded as having the same importance as images (Altman 1992a:35-45), and it has therefore not been viewed as having the same research value. Another reason for the lack of interest in sound in general is that sound is an omnipresent

feature which is easy to forget exists at all. And as Arnt Maasø points out, we can never choose not to hear anything at all since we do not have any earlids (Maasø 2002:46).

This project has studied game audio from two angles, an empirical and a theoretical. The empirical part has been carried out because computer game audio has not yet been thoroughly studied, and there is a need to ground theoretical assumptions in a specific empirical material. The empirical studies have also been done in order to build a theoretical framework based on actual game play and actual players' experiences of game audio. Because this is new theoretical ground, existing theories on related subjects have been utilized as a point of departure in order to illustrate the subject matter and guide research questions. But these theories cannot and have not been used uncritically to describe and analyse computer game audio. Instead, they have been used as a frame of reference, and in comparative respects, in order to say something about what makes computer game audio different from the use of sound in other contexts. In this respect, no theoretical "colonialism" (Aarseth 2004:49) is taking place in this research. The thesis has a clear focus on its subject matter, and uses empirical studies and theories on related subjects to illustrate not only how game audio differs from other phenomena, but in which respects existing theory may and may not be relevant.

The empirical part of this project concentrates on the study of two modern computer games belonging to different genres. This small selection does not mean that the project's argument as a whole is based on two games only. A range of games supports the argument and will be used as examples throughout the dissertation, but in order to remain focussed, only two games have been chosen as in-depth studies. These games are the real-time strategy game *Warcraft III* (Blizzard 2002) and the stealth-based action game *Hitman Contracts* (Io Interactive 2004). The two games have been studied in several ways. An in-depth analysis has been done in both cases in order to identify the different roles of sound in the games, but since basing the evaluations of the role of sound in these games on my own analyses may be too subjective, the project has also involved qualitative conversations with and observations of computer game players of the two games in question. This has given the project the value of being a study of how actual game players react to and use game audio in context. Last but not least, the project has involved interviews with game audio designers of *Hitman Contracts*. This has been done in order to get insight into what intentions game designers may have concerning the role of sound in games, as well as to understand the working processes for game audio design.

The theoretical background for the project is also diverse. As a study of computer games, a necessary starting point has been *theory on computer games*. In order to base the argument in a specific understanding of how action/events and game audio influence and relate to each other, the theoretical discussion starts with

reviewing definitions of what a game is. Concepts such as *gameplay* and *agency* are also evaluated in this context. Another influential school of thought is film theory concerned with *film sound and music*, not because of the similarity between games and films as audiovisual modes of presentation, but more because of the difference between the two. In this respect, film theory on sound has mainly been used for comparative purposes. The film theoretical conventions *diegetic* and *extradiegetic* sound (Bordwell & Thompson 1997:330) have been particularly important for discussing how computer game audio works as a usability system at the same time as it conforms to the reality status of the game world. The concepts are related to how film theory separates between two kinds of film sound based on its origin and relation to the universe presented in the film. *Diegetic sound* is sound that originates from a source existing within the film world, and that the film characters therefore would be able to hear. *Extradiegetic sound*, on the other hand, has no direct connection to an actual source within the film world but stems instead from an external source. By utilizing and disrupting these conventions, computer game audio questions their traditional roles, and utilizes them for usability purposes. In such cases, I call the sound *transdiegetic*, a concept that will be developed and discussed during the course of this thesis.

The third important theoretical influence has been *cognitive psychology on auditory perception*, and most of all the subfield *ecological psychoacoustics*. This subfield has proved more fruitful than the general studies of psychoacoustics and cognitive psychology on auditory perception. While the more traditional fields tend to study sound in the laboratory and with unnatural stimuli such as artificially created sounds in isolation, ecological psychoacoustics studies the experience of sound in natural contexts and environments (Neuhoff 2004:1-13). Most relevant for this thesis, ecological psychoacoustics also comes in the shape of applied research known under the names of *sonification* or *auditory display* studies, a young field that studies how sound can be applied for informative use in daily life (Kramer et.al. 1999). This theory also derives from the studies of human-computer interaction by a certain focus on the use of sound not only in real life environments but also in computer environments. The use of sound as informative system in the industry as well as in interfaces is invaluable for the study of use of game audio.

The combination of such diverse theories from such different disciplines will hopefully illuminate the concept of computer game audio, and serve as a background for understanding the empirical data as well as supporting this project's development of a theory of computer game audio. This theoretical background will work primarily to provide concepts and ideas for how to understand sound in games, as well as providing academic and theoretical ways of thinking about sound and its role in our daily life.

1.3 Objects of Analysis

As mentioned above, two games have been used as cases in this project, both being scrutinized as objects for analysis and for the purposes of empirical studies of game players. The games used for the studies are the real-time strategy game *Warcraft III (W3)* by the California based developer Blizzard Entertainment, and the stealth game *Hitman Contracts (HC)* by the Danish developer Io Interactive.

These games were picked for several reasons. Both games are popular within gaming communities, which means that finding subjects for player studies would be relatively easy. Also, being widely accepted by players, they exemplify games with a coherent and intelligent gameplay, which may indicate that also functional sound has been carefully designed to correspond with how the games play. Moreover, representing different genres, the games were expected to portray different ways of utilizing audio in games, and the study therefore demonstrates the variations that exist in sound between different game genres. This great variety has the potential to reveal a range of different functionalities of game audio, thereby making it possible to establish theoretical overview of the role of game audio in general. By revealing that game audio may be used for many different purposes, the study may encourage the use of sound as a feature of game design which is necessary in connection with successful gameplay.

The two games are very different in many respects, initially because *HC* provides the player with an avatar in the game, while *W3* does not. The avatar is the player's personification in the game world, and the controllable character through which the player acts (Murray 1997:113). Although the avatar does not have to be visually represented in the game world, the avatar is perceived as an existing individual in the game world since other game characters react to its presence. *HC* puts the player in control of a specific avatar and in this respect also in the role of the professional assassin Agent 47, while *W3* gives the players a top-down map view of a world in which they manage the construction of a military environment and strategic movement of military units. These games also present the player with very different forms of challenges. While *HC* requires the player to be patient and use tactics when trying to reach the objectives without being disclosed to the enemies, *W3* requires fast strategic action on the part of the player in developing a military base and forces in order to conquer the enemies. More importantly, both the player position, as well as the type of challenges presented, have direct consequences for how sound is utilized in these games. *HC* tries to hold on to a life-like representation of the environment, and in this respect provides sound reminiscent of how sound appears in real world. Also, diegetic sound communicates indirectly to the player in *HC* since the presence of an avatar allows sound to communicate directly to a character within the game world. Extradiegetic sound, on the other hand, addresses the player directly. Due to the player's indirect access to *W3*'s game world, this game uses

sound in a less naturalistic way, where units and objects in the environment must communicate directly to a player that has no manifestation within the game universe.

Since actual players have been observed, these studies have revealed not only how game audio communicates, but how actual game players experience the sound and how they use it to make sense of the game space and what goes on within. Interviews with game audio designers have also been carried out, but unfortunately, it has only been possible to do interviews with the audio team behind *HC*. While this may seem a weakness on part of the argument concerning *W3*, the interviews done with the game audio team have proved helpful for understanding sound use in both games. The knowledge of game audio developers has relevance for the understanding of the functionality of computer game audio on a general level, not least concerning what is technically possible or problematic, and how sounds may be implemented in relation to events and objects of the game environment. Also, gaining insight into the intended functionalities of sound in one game introduces the researchers to a specific mode of thinking which may enable them to map additional and different functionalities that sound may have in other games.

1.4 The Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is separated into 7 chapters, including introduction and conclusions. Although the main sections have titles that suggest that the section in question consists either of theoretical or empirical material, in reality there will be a mixture between theoretical and empirical discussions throughout the dissertation. The reason for this is that there is no existing theoretical background for doing studies of game audio, and all considerations need to be theoretically evaluated during the course of the argument. Theory and empirical analysis work in concurrence and influence each other, and the theory is developed on the background of the empirical data, which again is based on the theoretical evaluation.

Chapter 2 takes on a historical perspective on sound in computer games, both from a technological and a social point of view. An overview will be presented with a specific focus on the development of the functional role of sound in games, and how this has influenced the actual realizations of game audio as it exists in modern computer games. Also, this section will be concerned with a formal description of *HC* and *W3* and their uses of sound, where the games will be more closely related to genre historically.

The theoretical background for the project is presented in **chapter 3**. The section will cover introductory discussions about how we should understand games and computer games in this thesis, and also specific points about how computer game audio should be understood in a wider context as a usability system that

also supports the sense of presence in the virtual world. Following, the chapter consists of three larger theoretical discussions. The first concerns the relationship between sound and image in audiovisual presentations generally and computer games specifically. The second discusses the relationship between hearing and listening, and separates different methods that we use in the listening process. The third part goes more into detail about games as user systems, and studies game audio in connection to auditory display theory. The last theoretical discussion in this part will concern the idea of transdiegetic sounds and discuss how game audio problematizes the concepts of diegetic and extradiegetic in computer game contexts.

Chapter 4, 5, and 6 are dedicated to the empirical data collected through interviews with game audio designers as well as interviews with and observations of computer game players. Chapter 4 is an introductory part that presents the methodology used in the player and designer studies. In addition to discussing the methodological choices made, the procedures are described and evaluated in connection with each case. Chapters 5 and 6 present the analyses of data collected through the game designer interviews and the player observations and conversations. These analyses are closely related to the theoretical assumptions made in chapter 3. The analyses are filled with quotes from the informants, and the actual mapping of specific functions of game audio will take place in this section. In this respect, this section is as much a theoretical part as an empirical part, and may be the most interesting part for readers interested in the “hard-boiled facts” of this research.

The last main section of the thesis, **chapter 7**, is the concluding chapter in which a summary of the project will be made. The main theoretical points will be revisited and emphasised, and the relations between computer game audio and actions and events will be pointed out. The goal of this chapter is to identify a theory of the functionality of game audio, and this may be the most interesting chapter for those interested in the short, but essential version of the central argument of this thesis.

2. Computer Game Audio - a Historical Perspective

This chapter discusses computer game audio functionality from a historical perspective, and contextualizes the two games used as case studies in this project historically. Contrary to the history of films, sound has been an intended part of computer games since the very beginning. Although sound was not implemented in the first playable version of *SpaceWar!* (1962), which is regarded as the first computer game, it is reported that sound was included in an earlier test version (Weske 2000). This suggests that the relationship between audio and visuals in connection to computer games has been viewed as important since the beginning, and may be an expression of the idea that sound should have a functional and informative role in these games.

2.1 The History of Game Audio

This part of the chapter discusses the development and history of computer game audio from a functional perspective. This is important in order to understand the background of today's game audio, and why audio has its current role in computer games. Understanding this may also provide insight into which potentials are in future development of game audio. However, the technological aspect will also be considered since there are good reasons for arguing that the technological development of computer audio has been important for its functional development. Before computers were able to reproduce digital versions of actual sound, the artificially created computer sounds had limited value in terms of providing detailed information such as language. This made the use of sound in computer context, including games, limited to certain functionalities that still are found in today's computer games.

The history of computer game audio can be separated into four different phases. The first concerns the origin of computer game audio, with reference to early electronic game machines and the earliest developments of computer games in which sound was rarely implemented due to limited hardware and storage capabilities. The second phase is the period during which computer games became commercial products, and in which sound was added in order to draw attention towards the presence of arcade games in public areas. During the third phase, game audio found its functional shape due to careful game design and technological improvements. This also paved the way for sound that was functional at the same time as it created a sense of presence in the game environment. The last phase concerns the most recent technological and functional developments that allowed for improved implementation of game audio.

Phase 1: Earliest Developments

Two games are commonly mentioned when talking about the first computer game. These are the 1958 tennis simulation later known as *Tennis for Two* created as a curiosity feature for the annual visitors' day at Brookhaven National Laboratories (DeMaria & Wilson 2004:10, Poole 2001: 29-30), and the 1962 space ship game *SpaceWar!* created by students to demonstrate the processing power of the new mainframe computer, the transistor-based PDP-1, at MIT (Poole 2001:30-1, Weske 2000). However, it is *SpaceWar!* that is commonly seen as the first authentic computer game, because it was the first computer based game that could not exist outside the computer in any recognizable shape. On the other hand, although it hardly resembled original tennis, *Tennis for Two* is regarded as an adaptation and a simulation of an analogue game, namely tennis. While *SpaceWar!* may be viewed as a simulation of the behaviour of objects in space, it is not a simulation of an existing game, but a new autonomous game form that spawned a new genre not available outside computer environments.

None of these games actually included sound, although it is reported that sound was included in an early test version of *SpaceWar!* (Weske 2000). The sound in this game was removed before the version was realized due to technical constraints, but it is interesting to note that sound was an intended part of games from the very beginning. This suggests that the relationship between sound, visuals, and gameplay has been viewed with a degree of importance since the start, and may be an expression of the idea that sound should have a functional role in computer-based games. Although primitive compared to today's standards, *SpaceWar!* had features that come close to what makes the gameplay of today's computer game genres. Firstly, it included a virtual world with physics in the form of gravity. The player had to adapt to this other reality in order to play this game, which is similar to how people experience modern computer games. In addition, it included the challenge of mastering a consistent system that works on the basis of simple rules with complex possibilities for combination (Poole 2001:31). Also, with the intended implementation of functional sound related to specific events in the game, *SpaceWar!* resembles modern computer games on the level of game mechanics, as well as on the informative level.

Another device of historic interest in relation to game audio is the pinball machine. Already in the 1930s, mechanical pinball machines included artificial sound effects to intentionally give players responses to their actions. Until this time, coin operated game machines were mechanical and did not produce any sounds besides those caused by the operation of the actual machinery (Weske 2000). The inclusion of sound in this context underlines a desire for having specific feedback signals that did not put any demands on the visual system. Also, inclusion of artificial sound indicates a want of having sounds that was not confused with the

default sounds of the machinery; thus, the autonomous informative value of such sounds seems to have been acknowledged already from the days of the pinball machine. Thus, utilizing sound for informative usability purposes has actually existed since before the birth of computerized games.

Phase 2: Games Go Commercial

The second phase of the history of computer games spans from the first commercially available computer games in 1971 until the game market crash in 1984. There was no such thing as a separate all-purpose sound chip at the time, and the computer engineers behind the games had to create individual hardware circuits for each sound heard in the games (Weske 2000). This technological constraint may have been the reason why sound was not an obvious inclusion in many of the first games and game systems. The first home video game system, the 1972 Odyssey by the company Magnavox, for instance, was primitive from both a technological and game perspective, and the original version did not include audio. It did, however, become a success due to its low price, and consisted of a limited number of tennis, hockey and maze games (Weske 2000).

In 1971, the arcade version of *SpaceWar!* was released under the name *Computer Space* as the first commercially available computer game (DeMaria & Wilson 2004:16). It did not, however, become very successful since people found it too difficult to play (Weske 2000). It is interesting to see that this first commercial release did offer the debut of computer game audio, however primitive. According to Weske (2000), the original leaflet that accompanied the game stated that the sounds of the moving spaceships, explosions and firing of missiles could be heard, but there is no detailed account of the sound system. Besides, it is hard to say whether the sound of *Computer Space* were functional sounds connected to actual in-game events, or whether it was used to draw attention towards the presence of the game machine in the locales in which it was situated.

The real breakthrough of electronic games came with Atari's debut computer arcade game, *Pong* (1972). This tennis simulation was the first computer-based game to become a real success, proving that electronic games represented a new and lasting form of entertainment, and it also demonstrated the breakthrough for audio in games. The game played a sound when the ball hit the pad or bounced into a wall, and the game was named *Pong* after its characteristic "pong" sound (Weske 2000). While the aesthetic value of the sound arguably was small, the functional value was greater. It provided response information to the players that the ball had bounced into something and would turn around in the opposite direction. Also, the sound added a new

dimension to the game by giving the less-than-realistic visuals a physical or material touch. *Pong's* release as a home system in 1974 launched the game industry, and its success led to many clones being developed as well as different kinds of game concepts (Weske 2000).

Remarkable audio also followed the second great arcade success. *Space Invaders* (1978) had an addictive gameplay due to the inclusion of a new high score list. This list created a competitive element although the game itself could never be won, since completion of a level ultimately led to a new level with higher speed. But the sound of the game was possibly also a reason for the game's popularity. In noisy arcade halls, a distinct soundtrack meant that people would notice the game more easily. *Space Invaders* is also regarded as the first computer game featuring a real soundtrack, although it is hard to label the few sounds heard as music. Instead there was a steady pulse consisting of four tones of different pitch that accelerated as the alien invaders came closer. It was also the first game that used situation dependent melody that increased in tempo the closer the aliens got. In addition, it was the first game to use extradiegetic sound to affect the player's engagement in the game (Pidkameny 2002). Thus, *Space Invaders* already put emphasis on the importance of computer games to have a functional soundtrack, as well as utilizing extradiegetic sound to influence action taken internal to the game world.

In 1984, the computer game dream came to an end. Success after success in the computer game business resulted in an overflow of the console market. Companies produced more copies of their titles than the market could bear, in addition to the fact that the successes inspired the establishment of companies seeking to jump on a band-wagon, and who generally released games of questionable quality (DeMaria & Wilson 2004:105, Weske 2000). Also, home computers became increasingly more common in the early 80s, and in the industry there was a growing fear that the computer market would be a threat towards the game console industry (DeMaria & Wilson 2004:105). This, together with other social and technological factors, contributed to the video game market crash of 1983-84. Established game companies went bankrupt as a result of not having taken into account the increasing competition from new companies, and the new companies did not sell enough games and ran out of cash.

On the technical side, home computers were indeed a potential threat towards the game consoles. Technologically, they were not just a tool for word processing and calculation; they were also able to cope with everything that games demanded. When the best-selling home computer Commodore 64 was released in 1982, its graphics was comparable with other home computers on the market, but it included a dedicated sound chip that was much more sophisticated than any other computer system at the time. The chip called SID 6581 was developed by Bob Yannes who later co-founded the synthesizer company Ensoniq, and was a

taste of the technical capabilities of future sound systems (Weske 2000). Designed for music, this chip opened up for composing for games, and was probably the reason why the Commodore 64 music got more attention than music for other platforms.

At the time of the console market crash different characteristic features of game audio were already taking shape. Not only had *Pong* introduced sound for usability purposes, but *Space Invaders* had demonstrated that sound could follow the rhythm of the game and indirectly influence the player's behaviour. In addition, the Commodore 64 created an understanding of the importance of music in games.

Phase 3: Establishing Functionality

The third phase of computer game history starts in 1984 when Nintendo takes over the Western game market and lasts until the 32 bits consoles with CD-ROMs became standard in the early 90s. In terms of game audio, there were two interesting incidents in this period which contributed to establishing the functional role of computer game audio. After the console market crash, the game industry needed to re-establish the consumers' trust, and due to this, games and their accompanying audio was carefully designed. Also, digitalization of real world sounds opened up a new focus on audio fidelity^a in creating sounds.

The arcade game business was still running during and after the console market crash, and demonstrated that people still wanted games. The Japanese company Nintendo saw this as an opportunity to introduce their new successful home console on the American and European market. In 1985, Nintendo's Famicom was released as Nintendo Entertainment System in Europe and the U.S. (DeMaria & Wilson 2004:231-2; Weske 2000). Nintendo dominated the market for several years, due to their quality assurance policy that all games developed for the platform should be approved by Nintendo before release. The first Nintendo console is interesting, not only because of its high quality games, but because of its innovating game audio. Since storage was a primary concern for computer games, the limited space available was used to secure good graphics and durable gameplay. Sound only got the small amount of storage space that was left, which resulted in a stripped, but creative sound design. Since only a few sounds could be played simultaneously, usability functions became prioritized, and game music had to be composed over a limited set of tones.

^a *Fidelity* is a concept from audio engineering that refers to the precision of reproduction of mediated sound (Nyre 2003:13). *Audio fidelity* refers to how accurately a recorded or mediated sound resembles the corresponding natural sound, and is thought of as a physical feature that can be measured with electronic equipment.

Nintendo's classic *Super Mario Bros.* games demonstrate the use of sound for response and urgency purposes. A response sound is heard each time Mario jumps or catches a power-up, and certain off-screen explosions can be heard before the dangerous bullet is seen. *Super Mario Bros.* also uses music for other usability purposes, for instance to signal shortness of time. Role-playing games series such as *The Legend of Zelda* and *Final Fantasy* use situation-dependent music such as special pieces of music in dungeons, and at the location of especially powerful monsters. In this sense, these games demonstrated early on how sound could be used for usability purposes while also being connected to events in the game world, in addition to exemplifying the use of music for informative purposes.

1985 saw the release of the first digital sound chip, Paula, first presented by the Commodore home computer Amiga 1000. Stereo had been introduced to computers in 1983, and Paula was able to produce 4 channels of stereo sound, in addition to digital instruments for composing as well as the ability to sample real world sounds (Weske 2000). This opened the way for new functionalities within computer audio. It was now possible to create sound and music with high fidelity or precision compared to real world sounds. This meant that game audio could strive towards using sound not only for usability purposes, but also in order to create game environments that were reminiscent of real world environments. However, it took some time until this technology became standard in the game industry due to limited power and storage capacity. The focus on fidelity in audio over usability was further supported by the coming of separate add-on sound cards for IBM compatible home computers in the end of the 80s^b. This meant that computers which earlier could only reproduce primitive sound through the internal pc speaker could now reproduce more sophisticated sounds for those obtaining a sound card and a pair of speakers or headphones. According to Weske (2000), the first SoundBlaster card that appeared in 1989 became the first sound card for gamers, due to price and the inclusion of a special game port that enabled joysticks and other game paraphernalia to connect to the

^b Another challenge for auditory fidelity at the time, was the computer audio standard MIDI (Musical Instrument Digital Interface) from 1982, which specified how musical sounds in a software programme should be interpreted by the sound card (Weske 2000). This was a necessary development, since it allowed complex musical pieces to be stored as small files without the need to store qualities such as timbre. After the introduction of sound cards, the problem with this standard was that different sound cards would interpret the commands differently, so for instance a pan flute could sound very different from one computer to the other. This did not, however, affect console and arcade computers, since the hardware was specified for each type, but it was long a problem for games on home computers. However, Microsoft DirectX's sound standard DirectMusic (Weske 2000) helped standardizing sound and secured that sounds always would sound like its real world counterpart was. This enabled sound and music to follow directions from software such as games instead of being guided by hardware interpretations by the sound card. This meant that the MIDI standard became less of a nuisance for computer game sound designers and composers. With the DirectMusic standard, the game developers could now define not only which instruments that should be used in game music, but also exactly how these instruments should sound in a given context.

computer. However, it was not until 1992 that sound cards could produce CD quality sound when Creative's first 16-bit sound card, the SoundBlaster 16 was released.

Following the new technology, a couple of interesting game titles were released with auditory focus on creating believable virtual environments. The first shooter game set in a three-dimensional virtual world, *Wolfenstein 3D* released in 1992, was not only remarkable for its graphics, but also for its use of stereo-panning that indicated the movement of sources relative to the player and the use of sound volume to indicate distance to enemies, and the 1994 *Duke Nukem 3D* offered real-time audio effects to simulate the virtual game environments (Weske 2000). These titles pointed out new uses of game audio beside the usability function, connected to orientation and the sense of presence.

Phase 4: Towards Modern Times

The inclusion of CD-ROM in new consoles such as Sony's Playstation allowed for heavier applications with more sound and graphics. This allowed larger and more photo-realistic virtual worlds supported by increased audio fidelity. Functionally, fidelity, sense of presence, and atmosphere were still in focus, but these features also came to merge with the use of sound for usability purposes.

For a long time, games utilized stereo speakers to create the sense of three-dimensionality in game by making the sound move from one speaker to the other. The first sound card to offer hardware-accelerated 3D sound was Diamond Monster Sound from 1997 (Weske 2000), which allowed the positioning of virtual sound sources around the player in game space, and also provided the acoustic properties of rooms and spaces. Later years also saw the coming of what has been known as true surround systems which allowed the positioning of different channel speakers around the player in real space. This allowed greater focus on using sound for navigational and orientational purposes in computer games, since the player now could hear the direction from where a sound was coming, as well as the approximate distance (Menshikov 2003).

Another of the latest successful developments within game audio is *adaptive music* (Brandon 2004, 2005:85-91; Whitmore 2003), which is one of the more challenging auditory features today. It is a technique used within game audio development to make music change according to the player's behaviour and actions in the game (Brandon 2005:85). The use of adaptive audio has many interesting potential functions. Already today, adaptive music is used as a response, notification and warning system that will inform the player about his status.

Two games that demonstrate new auditory functionalities and realizations in modern computer games in different manners are *Thief 3: Deadly Shadows* (Ion Storm 2004) and *Tomb Raider Legend* (Eidos 2006). *Thief 3* is a stealth-based game in which voices and footsteps from other characters are used to signal enemy presence and awareness towards the player character. While notifying the player about potential dangers and underlining presence, sound in this game is used for both orientation and usability purposes. This game also utilizes ambient music which merges into the background environment noise, emphasising a specific atmosphere at the same time as maintaining the sense of presence in the environment. *Tomb Raider Legend*, on the other hand, combines adaptive music with the use of volume for providing distance information. In this sense, the music does not only inform about specific dangerous situations, but it also tells the player the direction and the relative distance to these situations.

This historical discussion of the development of computer game audio with respect to technical features, actual realization, and functionality has shown that technical constraints in the early days led sound to work functionally. The sound was used primarily to give the player feedback on actions, but sound was also used to make the crude graphics seem more alive. Visual objects that produced sound when something hit it gave the feeling of substance, which was important when it was difficult to see what the graphics were supposed to be. However, when later games featured virtual spaces, it was intuitive to include sounds that reflected this space as well. This meant that people and animated beings could talk and produce footsteps, machines would make humming sounds, guns would have an exploding sound when fired, and so on. Thus, the history of game audio development reveals that the origin of game audio is two-fold: first, it is the pure *functional* role of sound; and second, it is the role of creating a *sense of a space* for action. Today, these two roles are still present, and often they merge together, creating a soundscape that is both credible to a specific virtual environment while also having clear usability functions.

2.2 The Games of Study: Formal Description & Historical Contextualization

As noted in the introductory chapter, two games are used as cases in this project. These games are different in terms of genre with respect of what challenges the player meets, the player's positioning, and the use of sound. This subsection will concern formal descriptions of the two games, including a historical background for each of them. However, games consist of a range of features that work together in creating a specific game experience, and making a formal description of a game can be difficult. Jesper Juul underlines that

getting a full understanding of a game means knowing the surface layers of audiovisual information, as well as the underlying system (Juul 1999:64-5). He specifies this by saying that computer games consist of two layers, namely the *game as rule system* and the *game as imaginary world* (Juul 2005:6). Both of these need to be studied when wanting to understand a computer game. Lars Konzack, on the other hand, separates between *virtual space* and *playground* when describing a game before its analysis (2002:90). The virtual space is the space of action within the computer game setting, including the characters and locations. The playground is the interface, controls, and game console; or in other words, the gaming aspects from the point of view of the player's real world space. If we want a full analysis of a game, Konzack states that the game must be analysed on the basis of the seven layers that he separates games into (2002:89). These layers are *hardware*, *programme code*, *computer application functionality*, *gameplay*, *meaning*, *referentiality*, and *socio-culture*. However, since this project does not seek a full analysis, but an understanding of game audio specifically, it is not necessary to take all the layers into account. Instead, this formal description will concentrate on issues that have specific relevance for the interplay between game audio and gameplay.

Contrast to Juul and Konzack's view that computer games must be studied as an opposition between technical features (hardware) and aesthetical features (software), is the view that games in general consist of a range of features that define the game internally according to its own system structure and how this interacts with player actions and behaviour. One such method of studying games is found in Avedon & Sutton-Smith (1972). They identify elements in games by combining ideas from economical game theory and behaviourism (1972:422). These elements are *purpose and result*, *procedures for action*, *rules for action*, *player roles*, *interaction patterns*, and *number of players*. Avedon & Sutton-Smith's method is fruitful when describing both traditional games and computer games since it concerns detailed information about challenges, the player role, and system features. However, since this method of analysis does not include the aesthetical layer characteristic for today's computer games, Konzack and Juul's focus on the virtual surface needs to be added in order to make a comprehensive description of the games. From this we can separate *game system features*^c, *player activities*^d, and the *aesthetical surface features*^e; all of which work together to create a specific gameplay and thus create the game. These are the axes on which the two games central to this study will be formally described.

^c Avedon & Sutton-Smith's *purpose and result*; *rules for action*; and *player roles*.

^d Avedon & Sutton-Smith's *procedures for action*; and *interaction patterns*.

^e Konzack's *virtual space*; and Juul's *fictional world*.

2.2.1 Genre & History. Classification of Two Games

Genre classification is a delicate issue. It seems that a genre is easy to recognize by those familiar with its conventions, but it is hard to define a genre exactly (Bordwell & Thompson 1997: 51). The reason for this is that genres are flexible. A range of conventions are utilized in a given genre, but any one game, film or novel does not have to utilize all these conventions. Also, they may borrow conventions known from other genres. In this sense, a genre is best understood as a rough category shared by audiences, and instead of trying to make a narrow definition of what a genre is, it may be better to identify how different pieces of work have been distinguished by audiences and creators (Bordwell & Thompson 1994:52-3). Film theorists Bordwell and Thompson point to different conventions that seem to reappear in several films and that contribute to frame different genres. According to them, features such as plot elements, themes and meanings, characteristic film techniques, or iconography are important conventions that help identify a film genre, but conventions associated with a certain genre can also be revised or removed without dismissing the work as a representative of a certain genre (Bordwell & Thompson 1997:53). Subgenres and crossovers may also appear when conventions cross.

The genres we meet in the cinema or at the computer game retailer are what we typically would call a *historical* genre (Todorov in Gripsrud 1999:123), or a classification commonly used in the communication between producers and audience. It can therefore be seen as consumer information used for marketing purposes. The computer game genres we meet today are also examples of this, and should be taken as a starting point when identifying what conventions are at work in computer game genres. In the shop we meet genres such as action, strategy, roleplaying and racing games, and subgenres such as action-adventures, first-person shooters, real-time and turn-based strategy games, massively multiplayer online roleplaying games, and car racing games. Although genres like action and adventure seem to match corresponding film genres, it appears that the conventions behind the names are different from those behind film genres. In computer games, what kind of *challenge* the game presents the player with is an important convention. If a game is classified as a strategy game, tactical movement and planning is expected as a major part of the challenge in the game, and if a game is classified as a shooter, the player expects that most challenges will be overcome by using firearms. A roleplaying game suggests that challenges revolve around the development of a character, and possibly that the players should enact or empathise with the character they are playing. The genre names may also suggest what kind of *activity* the player will engage in when playing the game. An action game may be called thus because it has certain similarities with the film genre action such as high pace, a certain degree of violence, as well as a large degree of movement and sound. The name racing game

suggests that the player will be in a racing competition. However, when the game genres are more specialized as subgenres, we may also see that conventions are based on other features. *Setting* is one such convention, commonly found in names like military strategy game, science fiction shooter, or horror game – the last genre also refers to the desired emotional effect that the game should have on the player. Often subgenre names also refer to more *technical aspects* of the game, such as the point of view (e.g. first-person and third-person shooters, or when the player may act in the game (e.g. real-time and turn-based strategy games). Below I will describe the games in this study according to the marketing genres defined by the developers, identify the conventions behind these labels, and contextualize the games historically. In addition, the games will be described formally according to the above defined features.

Warcraft III (Blizzard 2002) is classified as a real-time strategy game by the developer^f. According to Steven Poole's overviews of different genres of games, the real-time strategy game (RTS) is a game where opponents take on different parts in a setting controlled from a top-down position overseeing all military and logistical operation (2000:49). The player does not have an avatar of which he is in complete control of every single movement. Instead, the player controls a number of units for both military and management uses. These units are semi-autonomous in the sense that the player gives each unit, or a group of units, commands about which actions to take, but once the command is given, the unit will be in control of its own movements and actions until the player gives the unit a new order. Also, what makes these games different from traditional board strategy games and war games is that they are in real-time instead of turn-based. This means that the players do not take their move then waits while the opponents take their moves. Instead, time is constantly running, and the players move simultaneously and without pause. The players cannot sit down and carefully plan their decisions, but must move and react quickly during the course of the game (Poole 2000:50). The consequence of this is that RTS is one of the game genres that put the greatest cognitive demands on the player by merging together logical, combinatorial thinking with fast reflexes (Poole 2000:51).

Historically, all strategy games, including the RTS, may be traced back to war games (Poole 2000:50) and the strategic maps used by generals in planning tactical moves in warfare. After the birth of the computer, we can also see links to the development of computer simulators for military purposes. However, the documented use of the computer for the purpose of strategy gaming can be traced to 1947 when the programmer Arthur Samuels created a computer programme that played checkers, and developed better strategies by playing against human opponents (Aarseth 2000). This game was a simulation of an existing board game and not a true computer game in the sense of being a game that could not exist in its true form outside the computer.

According to Poole, the first strategy and management game of this authentic kind was *Hammurabi* from the 1970s, where the player was in control of a feudal kingdom and the objective was to administer tax rates and manage resources (2000:32). However, these strategy games were turn-based, and in order to find the first strategy game in real-time, we must move on to the 1980s. According to Poole, the origin of the RTS is a 1980 arcade game based on a military simulation that tested how many nuclear warheads a human operator could track (2000:50). The game was called *Missile Command* (Atari 1980), and the purpose was to protect six bases from missiles. Another early game that deserves attention in connection to the history of RTS is *Stonkers* (Imagine Software 1983), in which the player controlled different military and supply units that tactically need to support each other^g. A more recent game that contributed to putting the RTS genre on the map was *Dune* (Cryo Interactive 1992). Based on the science fiction novel by Frank Herbert, the game blends adventure and military strategy to create a story driven strategy game similar to those we know today.

According to the developer's web site, the *Hitman* series consists of "thinker-shooters" that expect the player to overcome challenges by the use of stealth, disguise and intelligence to tactically plan each move^h. In this game series, the player has an avatar, or a personal figure, which is defined not as a random individual with no set personality, but as the contract killer Agent 47. The player's view of the world is close up from behind the agent, who navigates a three-dimensional space as a character within a virtual world. In contrast to *Warcraft III*, the player controls all the avatar's actions and movements, and the avatar will be completely immovable without the player's continuous input. As "thinker-shooters", the games are most intuitively seen as belonging to a subgenre of shooter games; games that present conflict in its purest form – namely via violence. With the term "thinker-shooter", the developers of the *Hitman* games put emphasis on the games as having other challenges apart from shooting. The thinking part is underlined by the developer's focus on stealth, disguise and tactical planning. Games with this focus are also popularly known as stealth games; games that demand patience and planning by the player. Part of the challenge in these games is to not be exposed by your enemies and to fulfil the objectives of the game with as much discretion as possible. *Hitman Contracts* takes the player through a series of scenarios where the objective is to locate and assassinate certain enemy targets without sounding any alarms. In order to accomplish this, the player must discover

^f Official *Warcraft III: Reign of Chaos* website at <http://www.blizzard.com/war3/>.

^g Wikipedia's entry on real-time strategy games at <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rts>.

^h Io Interactive's description of their four *Hitman* games at: <http://www.ioi.dk/games/hitman1.htm>, <http://www.ioi.dk/games/hitman2.htm>, <http://www.ioi.dk/games/hitmancontracts.htm>, and <http://www.ioi.dk/games/hitmanbloodmoney.htm>.

patterns in the enemies' movement, and show discretion by the use of disguises. When the player must kill the enemies, this should ideally be done by sneaking up on them from behind, or poisoning their food or drink. From a historical point of view, stealth games are young developments. The online encyclopaedia Wikipedia which allows anyone to add information about a subject, suggests *Metal Gear* (Konami 1987) for the Nintendo Entertainment System as the first game to define this subgenreⁱ. *Metal Gear* is a game of infiltration, where the player must avoid both visual contact and direct confrontation with the enemy. Instead the player should sneak up to enemies from behind and pacify them. Games of this series are still being released, although not all have had the same focus on stealth. The genre started to make itself significant with the release of *Thief: The Dark Project* in 1998, which cast the player in the role of "the best thief in the world". In the *Thief* series, gameplay is focused on picking locks, avoiding guards, and staying hidden in the shadows. Attacks must be ranged or by the use of mines, because the avatar is likely not to survive direct confrontations.

2.2.2 *Warcraft III: Reign of Chaos*. A Formal Description

a) Gameplay & Interface

Warcraft III (W3) is a real-time strategy game featuring a fantasy medieval setting. The player chooses to play one of four teams that are featured by different classical fantasy races of humanoids. These are the *humans*, the *orcs*, the *night elves*, and the *undead*. Each team has its own set of units, its own special abilities, and its own "heroes" or special dynamic characters that improve through battle by gaining experience points. The game may be played in two modes, where one is single player only, and the other allows the player to play against either the computer or human opponents, or a mixture of human and computer opponents. This mode also allows for cooperative play.

The single player only mode is a series of scenarios, known as a campaign mode, that works as a tutorial with increasing difficulty from one scenario to another, and introduces the player to the different playable races. The scenarios are linked together by cinematic cut-scenes that tell the history of the world of Azeroth and how it became invaded by the demons of The Burning Legion and the undead Scourge. These narrative sequences have no relevance for the gameplay within the individual scenarios, but work as flavour to contextualize the scenarios and link them together. Also, they work as a motivation for the player who wants

ⁱ Wikipedia's entry on stealth-based games at http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stealth_game

to know what happens next, and who wants to see the consequences of an event described in the preceding cut-scene. Each scenario has specific objectives that need to be fulfilled to win the scenario, such as establish a base, defeat the enemy, or survive for 30 minutes, in addition to sub-goals that may be accomplished at will in order to give the hero unit more experience points or receive special items.

The second mode of play is to choose a map or scenario, and to define some parameters for play, such as choosing races, and number of computer and human players up to a maximum of 12. The players play on their own previously agreed terms until one team or one player eliminates all opponents. This is also the case when playing with or against other human players, where one can choose either to play over a local network or play on the internet via Blizzard's online game servers at *Battle.net*.

Concerning the dynamics of the game, and the way it is played, it is possible to call *Warcraft III* an *emergent* game (Juul 2002; 2005:73-79). In terms of the game system, this means that the game consists of a limited set of relatively simple rules that combine into extreme variations. A typical example of this is chess where simple rules of movement creates advanced tactics and moves that the experienced opponent did not foresee. In *Warcraft III*, the set of rules may be stated quite simply by referring to the movement of units, their special strengths and weaknesses, properties of buildings, and the time of production for each object. However, when the player gets familiar with the system and acts within the limits and possibilities of these game system features, a great variation can be spotted in the style of playing. Also, utilizing the rules, the player may take tactical moves that come as a surprise to the opponents. In effect, the player may take on a range of different strategies that always pose different challenges to the opponent. In this sense, the game is virtually never exhausted because it is not possible to find the one and only winning strategy such as may be the case with the 9-square version of tic-tac-toe. In this game, many strategies may lead to success, and whether one wins or not is dependent on how one is able to utilize the chosen strategy.

Compared to other real-time strategy games, *W3* is a high-paced game. In this respect, an offensive and aggressive strategy is likely to be optimal. Arguably, strategy games consist of three phases that have different weight from game to game. These phases are the initial *build and gather phase*, followed by a *development phase* where forces are being built and research is carried out to improve the forces. The last phase is an *attack and conquer phase* (Jørgensen 2003a:81-84). These phases will partly overlap, so development may start already in the build phase and continue into the attack phase, and gathering or resources will normally not stop after the first phase, but continue throughout the game. In *Warcraft III*, the initial phase needs to be short and intensive in order for the player to have a sustainable amount of resources for upgrades and for constantly having the opportunity to produce necessary units. It is important to reach the

attack and conquer phase as fast as possible, and when reaching it, the player should have access to the strongest units in the game, as well as resources enough to produce a sustainable number of these units. These gameplay features are supported by the game system. First, the number of buildings that can be built is limited, and it is only possible to upgrade the base twice. Also, the number of units is limited, and the player is encouraged to have a small military force due to the upkeep system. This system states that from the thirtieth unit the player produces, the player must pay upkeep. In other words, some of the resources collected will be spent on maintaining a high number of units. The more units the player has above thirty, the higher upkeep is paid. A third method the system uses for supporting a fast-paced game is by the use of special units called *heroes*. These units are stronger than the ordinary units, and will gain experience points (xp) from fighting. When the hero has received a certain amount of experience points, it will gain a level, which gives it more health and magic energy, as well as allowing it to upgrade one of his magic abilities. This unit is the most important one in the game, and due to its power, the player may focus on building a small and supportive force of additional units.

Figure 1. Warcraft III: The Reign of Chaos (Blizzard 2002). Interface, building

W3 is only available on the PC, and the input devices are mouse and keyboard. The player's closeness to the screen allows for a more detailed graphical environment in contrast to console games which are played on the television and with a certain distance to the screen. The game environment is in 3D, which means that it is possible to zoom and change the angle freely in relation to how you see the environment. However, the

players have a top-down view where they by default see the game from a bird's eye perspective. The view is quite close to the ground compared to simulation management games such as *Sim City* or *Age of Empires*, but it still maintains a greater distance to the action than typical avatar-based games do. The interface is a point-and-click interface where the players use the mouse to click on the spot where they want the units to move or attack. The players may also select individual units and use their special abilities by clicking an icon in the graphical user interface menu surrounding the diegetic game space. However, since the players most of the time must control a relatively large number of units simultaneously, it is also possible to use keyboard shortcuts for some core actions, a feature that further supports the high speed of this game.

As noted, the game is in real-time, which means that everything internal to a scenario happens continuously, and all players move without break simultaneously. It does not mean that time is one to one compared with our perception of time. A day and a night in the game does not last the same as in our world, but in less than half an hour. So real-time means that the pace of the game is constant, and that there will never be any time jumps or waiting while the opponents do their turns. It also means that there is no such thing as a separate build mode where the player can enter to build and plan town layout with no time constraint, as we find for instance in the dollhouse simulator *The Sims*. Instead, every action that the player takes happens within diegetic time, with the risk that the opponent may attack while the player is producing units or building a new structure. In connection to this, it may be pointed out that the game only has one location for game activities. Within a scenario, there is only one continuous space in which everything happens, and the player never enters new screens in order to take specific actions, such as often is the case in turn-based strategy games. Turn-based games often move the player to a special battle interface when fighting, and another special build interface when constructing new structures or producing new units. In *W3*, on the other hand, everything happens within the same space in real-time. However, the space is also larger than what may be seen on the computer screen at any point in time. What is seen on the screen is only a selected part of the available space, and the player may move the mouse cursor or units to the edge of the screen to move further to unseen spaces. The total space is seen in a miniature version in the lower left corner of the screen, and will become visible during the course of the player's exploration of the space.

b) Sound Features

In this formal description of the game, it is also necessary to say something about how sound is used. I would like to present the soundscape according to Alex Stockburger's (2003) categories of sound objects in order to

make a comprehensive and objective overview of the sounds with relation to the game environment. He separates *score sound objects*, *zone sound objects*, *interface sound objects*, *speech sound objects*, and a range of different *effect sound objects* connected to the avatar, objects usable by the avatar, other game characters, other entities, and to events. The detailed categorization of sounds, not least in relation to effect sounds, makes this overview suitable for a thorough description of the sounds present in a game. It is also important to point out that sound in *W3* has a very clear functional role and strongly supports gameplay. This will also be mentioned in this section although the ultimate analytical observations will be presented together with the analysis of player experiences.

The *score or music* in *W3* is extradiegetic in the sense that it originates from a source outside the game world (Bordwell & Thompson 1997:330), and works as a background commentary for the setting. The music is characterized by different music for the different races. This music plays repeatedly with periods of silence in between. The musical pieces vary in intensity throughout a music file, and while some parts are very melodious, other parts are ambient in nature, and consist of subtle music that merges with the ambient background sounds from the environment. The music has no clear relation to events in the game or to player activities, but work ultimately as mood enhancer.

Zone sounds are sounds that categorize a special location, and in *W3* this means that different scenarios have different background ambience because they are set in different environmental locations. Ambient sounds are not meant to be listened to closely, but are low in volume and work as background noise specific for a location. In other words, when playing a scenario set in the forest, the player will hear the background ambience that characterizes this kind of environment; namely the sound of birds and animals, as well as the sound of wind blowing in the trees. Night and day also have different kinds of ambient sounds. While daytime in the forest is characterized by a lot of birds singing, night time is characterized by being more silent, with perhaps an owl howling now and then. As with the music, these sounds have no direct consequence for player activities or gameplay.

Sounds connected to the graphical *user interface* are limited to small response clicks every time the player selects a new command in the command menu, and work as responses to player commands. However, as we will see later, there are many sounds that have diegetic sources that also seem to have similar functions as the interface sounds.

Speech sounds are one good example of sounds that have diegetic sources in the game, but still work as responses to specific player actions. Addressing the player situated external to the diegesis, they are also to

be system messages and have a *transdiegetic* aspect. All units in the game have their own voice which characterizes the unit in question. Units talk when the player selects them, gives them commands, and when they become idle. In this situation, it is not the *content* (Chion's *semantic* meaning (1994:28)) of what is said that is important, but the *functional value* of the sound (Chion's *causal* meaning (1994:25)). However, the content of the speech sounds is important in other uses of the voice in this game. The game uses voice-over speech in order to give the player warnings about attacks. Thus speech is used to support gameplay by being either direct responses to player actions, or by providing information about events that the player has no control over.

There are different kinds of *effect sound* objects in *W3*. Connected to units are screams when they die in battle, and there is also the sound of footsteps when the units move over special terrain such as shallow water. Concerning objects usable by the units, there is typically the sound of weapons during combat, and also the sound of magical items and the use of magical spells. Similar sounds may be heard from other units in the game, both friendly and hostile. Effect sounds are present to create some substance or the feeling of realism to the game world, but they also work functionally to give the player an auditory overview in a situation that may be difficult to control visually. Buildings also have sounds in *W3*, and a sound is heard whenever the player starts building a new structure. Each completed building will also produce a sound of recognition when it is selected, so the player may hear the sound of a chain saw when selecting the lumber mill, and steel against steel when selecting the barracks. Certain events will also be emphasised by the use of sound. The best example is probably the one above of the voice-over warning. Additionally, another important aspect of effect sounds is to provide feedback on running and timed tasks, such as the sound of workers chopping wood to signify that resources are still being gathered.

2.2.3 *Hitman Contracts*: A Formal Description

a) **Gameplay & Interface**

Hitman Contracts (HC) is a stealth-based action game in a modern European setting, featuring different locations. The player's avatar is a character in the game world, namely the contract killer Agent 47. Playing as a contract killer, the player should reach objectives related to locating certain villains and eliminating them, while getting as little attention as possible. Technically speaking, the avatar is a static character, in the sense that his skills does not improve throughout the game. The only improvement available is finding new

equipment such as weapons, disguises and items specifically relevant for the present scenario. Although irrelevant for the game mechanics, Agent 47's personality does change from game to game, creating a different motivation for each game in the series related to the overall narrative that binds the game and the series together. In the background story for *HC*, Agent 47 has returned to his profession as contract killer to find out more about his origins after discovering he is the result of a cloning experiment. This background leads to *HC* being a rather gloomy game concerning both the overall soundscape and the visual style.

HC is single-player only and consists of a series of scenarios that increase in difficulty. Each scenario has unique objectives and is set in unique locations, and, though similar tactics are used for each scenario, the player must regard each scenario independently in order to determine how the challenges can most effectively be overcome. When planning moves, the player must use an in-game map to gain knowledge of the layout of the surroundings, the location of important items and the location and movement patterns of his targets. The player must use that information in order to plan how he should move without generating more attention than necessary.

Using Jesper Juul's terminology of games of *emergence* and *progression* (2002; 2005:72-79), *HC* may be seen as a progression game with emergent components (2005:72, 82). A game of progression is a game where the player must perform a predefined set of actions to advance in the game. From a design point of view, a game of progression is designed as a series of specific challenges that have specific solutions that need to be found in order to progress in the game. Thus, the challenge is to find out what actions to perform, and progression games are therefore only challenging the first time they are played and before its possibilities are exhausted. However, some progression games allow the player the freedom to choose between a limited number of ways to overcome a challenge. Alternatively, the game may be progressive on a macro level and emergent on a micro level, where the solution of getting on to the next stage in the game demands one specific solution, but where all or most challenges within a certain stage may be solved in many ways. *HC* must be regarded as a game of progression since there are certain goals internal to a scenario that must be fulfilled before being allowed to continue. However, it also has emergent features in relation to how these goals are reached. A typical scenario includes goals such as: 1) find and reach the persons responsible for a certain crime, and 2) eliminate them. These goals are progressive in the sense that the responsible cannot be eliminated before they are located, and these actions must be taken before the avatar may leave the area to move on to next mission. However, finding the targets and eliminating them may be done in different ways. The player may choose to shoot his way directly to the villain, and if the player is lucky, he will be able to eliminate the targets before they escape the area. Alternatively, the player may opt for a stealthier method,

which may be realized in a number of ways depending on the scenario in question. There is normally one intended optimal way to do a scenario, and if this was the only method that would lead the player to the goal, the game would be strictly progressive. However, the player may choose different paths, choose whether to use a disguise or not, choose whether to sneak past guards or knock them out, and what method to use when killing the target.

The gameplay procedures for each scenario are fairly similar. Once started, the player receives information about the current mission from “Diana from the Agency”. She provides Agent 47 detailed information about the objectives of the mission, such as targets and their approximate location, as well as what kind of situations the player will meet. This information can be accessed at any time during the scenario. The player will then access his map to get an overview of the layout of the scenario as well as the location of important items and the movement of the targets, enemies and civilians. On the basis of this information the player will start moving, preferably to the easiest accessible important item. The map is marked with an exclamation mark for each important item, but it does not say what kind of item it is; thus, the player is likely to plan his moves one step at the time until he has found enough important items to complete the main objectives effectively.

HC is played in real-time, which means that the avatar moves around in the game environment simultaneously to all other characters and events. Concerning spatiality, each of the scenarios in *HC* consists of a specified and limited location. Its borders are defined by for example being surrounded by a fence, or the action may be limited to a specific house. Access between different locations internal to the scenario is seamless in the sense that there are no loading screens between two rooms or two houses in the specific location. However, action will take place within rooms of the scenario that the player is not currently situated in. This means that the whole space of a scenario must be considered at all times and taken into account when planning moves.

As emphasised, *HC* is a stealth-based game, but it is up to the player to choose exactly how stealthy he wants to be. It is possible to reach the goal by being violent, but stealth is supported by the system in several ways. First, the player will get a ranking after each completed scenario, ranging from “mass murderer” to “silent assassin”, depending on how stealthily he has accomplished the mission. If no-one but the specific targets have been killed, the player is rated “silent assassin”, and if the player has played the game aggressively, killing everyone in the location, he becomes “mass murderer”. There are also other ranks between these two extremes. The goal of the game is to be ranked as closely as possible to “silent assassin” on each scenario. Second, although Agent 47 most of the time is armed with guns and is capable of using them, a suspicious or aggressive person will sound an alarm that makes all guards and ultimately the targets aware of the danger unless the player is able to pacify the person as fast as possible. Other game characters’

attention towards Agent 47 is monitored in the graphical user interface by the use of a radar that visualizes whether other characters' attention is directed towards the avatar, and whether the characters are alarmed by the avatar's presence or not.

However, it should be noted that although this is a stealth-based game, its focus lies more in blending into the environment than on staying hidden. The avatar should not be dressed or move in any way that may raise suspicion, thus, using the right disguises in certain environments and acting as naturally as possible, are important parts of the gameplay. This means that the player should not be spotted climbing through windows, or carrying a gun unless he is dressed as a guard in the presence of other similarly dressed guards, or generally acting in a way that would be likely to arouse suspicion. Due to this focus, the game also demands planning and tactics on part of the player, and the player must also be able to see patterns in how guards move, how the targets move, and how people move in relation to each other.

Figure 2. Hitman Contracts (Io Interactive 2004): Interface, getting to important location

HC is available for the PC, the PS2 and the Xbox. The version used for this study is for PC, which means that the player sits close to the screen and uses input devices such as mouse and keyboard to move around and perform actions in the game. The game environment is in 3D, and the player controls the avatar from a close-up view from behind. This means that the player sees the world in approximately the same manner as the avatar, and from approximately the same angle as the avatar sees the real world environment around him.

The camera angle is fixed, so the player can never freely change the view of the world. The player accesses his inventory of items already picked up (weapons etc.) by the use of the right mouse button, and he manipulates objects and picks up items from the ground by using the mouse wheel to access a scroll menu with all available options. Contrary to many other games, *HC* only allows the player to save the game seven times during the course of one scenario. This is probably due to its relationship to console games that normally can only be saved at certain defined save points in the game. However, in this game it also works as a game feature that supports stealth since limited saving possibilities makes the player plan his moves more carefully.

b) Sound Features

In the same sense as the description of sound in *W3*, the formal description of sound use in *HC* will be based on Axel Stockburger's (2003) categories of sound objects. Although the soundscapes of both games are described by the same tools, this description will demonstrate many of the differences between the utilization and functionality of the sound in the games in question.

The extradiegetic *score or music* in *HC* is characterized by being partly ambient and partly melodious. The base music differs from scenario to scenario, but there are certain pieces of music that are related to specific events and may be heard on several scenarios. In this sense, there are a number of music files that are mixed into each other depending on the situation. The ambient music is discreet background music that merges with the actual environmental sounds on the location, and works both as a mood provider and in order to link the situational music pieces. The situational music, on the other hand, consists of clear melodies that the player will recognize, and provides feedback or hints about a certain situation from an external position, thereby having a transdiegetic character. In this sense, a certain piece of music plays when the player has solved a problem in an optimal way related to the "silent assassin" rating, when the avatar enters a room of certain importance, and when combat starts. Different pieces of music are also used to signal whether the player is doing well or badly in a fight. However, this game also utilizes diegetic music, or music that stems from a source within the game world, and which, consequently, the characters in the game world are able to hear (Bordwell & Thompson 1997:330). Diegetic music is used to characterize the specific setting, so when Agent 47 enters a nightclub, the player hears music from the dancefloor, which decreases and increases in volume depending on how close the avatar is situated in relation to the source.

Concerning the game's *zone sound* objects, diegetic and extradiegetic music often serves to characterize a location, as well as putting emphasis on important locations. However, there are also ambient environment sounds in *Hitman Contracts*. This means that when Agent 47 is, for instance, walking in a rainy city, the player will, when listening closely, hear the drumming sound of raindrops that merges with the humming sound of distant motors. When Agent 47 tries to merge in at an aristocrat's mansion party, the player will hear mumbling, distant voices and soft music in the background.

There are several types of sounds connected to the game's *user interface*. First, there are small clicks whenever the player selects weapons from the inventory, and whenever the player selects actions in the options menu. These sounds are response sounds and add a sense of physicality to the interface. There are also sounds connected to small visual messages that pop up in the upper left corner when there is a status update. There are three kinds of these messages, negative, neutral and positive. A negative message may inform the player that the guards are looking for a suspicious person, a neutral message may be information that a certain object important for the objectives on a specific scenario has reached a certain destination, and a positive message may inform the player that an earlier poisoned target is now dead. These messages are accompanied by a small electronic beep that works to support the onscreen coloured messages.

Speech sounds are used both for causal and semantic purposes (Chion 1994:25-28). The use of speech for causal purposes is central to the soundscape of *HC*, as well as for gameplay. When guards are suspicious towards the avatar and get aggressive, they will shout after him, and targets will also start shouting for the guards if the player is not able to pacify them unseen. In this sense, it is not the content of what is said that is important, but the fact that there is someone present who shouts when seeing the avatar. In this respect, the sound is used as a warning signal. The semantic use of speech in this game is limited, and is only used in cinematic cut-scenes and in the briefing from the Agency. The briefing informs the player verbally and textually about the mission's exact objectives, and it has the format of being a recorded audiovisual message from Agent 47's intelligence agency. In the cinematic cut-scenes found in the beginning and sometimes in the middle of missions to provide narrative information to the player, the player may also hear the voice of Agent 47. This is typically the case when the avatar talks directly to other game characters, and when the avatar contacts the Agency with updates. In these situations, the content of the speech is of importance and is likely to provide the player with new information.

As in the case of *W3*, there are many different kinds of effect sounds in *HC*. Concerning effect sounds connected to the avatar, there are two important ones. The first are moans and shouts produced when the avatar is hit, which provides the player with information about changes in health level. Since the player is not

able to feel the avatar's physical pain, these sounds work as substitute to the lack of haptic perception in the game. Another important sound related to the avatar is the sound of footsteps. Footsteps have louder sounds when the avatar runs compared to the sounds produced when he walks, which again sound louder than the footsteps of the avatar in sneak mode. These sounds are redundant in relation to the mode that the avatar is currently in, but together they work to provide information about other character's relative attention level. Concerning objects usable by the avatar, all weapons have their sounds, but some weapons have a less subtle sound than other weapons. The wire used for strangling people from behind typically has a discreet sound that does not raise the attention of people without visual range, while guns are more likely to alert people. Similarly, the presence of off-screen non-player characters is typically marked by their use of voices or gun shots. Objects in the environment typically produce sounds when the avatar or other characters interact with them, thus, doors creak when being opened, and objects on the ground make a noise when being bumped into. Also, as mentioned above, events are typically marked with extradiegetic music.

2.2.4 Summary: *Warcraft III* vs. *Hitman Contracts*

W3 and *HC* are very different games in many respects. Their connection to separate genres, both historically and as commercial products, has put different constraints on each of them in terms of aesthetics and gameplay. The game systems put different demands on player behaviour, and in this sense, the games present very different challenges on part of the player. *HC* focuses on step-by-step planning, the players' ability to see and understand patterns, their ability to merge into the environment, and their discretion in relation to movement and choice of items. In order to ensure successful accomplishment, the game needs to utilize audio to provide the information necessary for the player's evaluation of the different situations. *W3*, on the other hand, is a fast-paced game that demands strategic thinking, and a player that is able to work fast and to monitor different simultaneous processes at the same time. In order to be able to coordinate everything from a certain distance, it is important that the game is able to provide detailed responses to everything that the player does through the auditory and visual channels.

Separate genres have positioned the player in very different situations in the two games. *HC* gives the player a personal identity within the game world, which again means that the player is completely in control of only one element in the game; whereas *W3* does not have an avatar at all, but allows the player to be monitor and manager of a number of semi-autonomous units as well as having an overview of several interdependent processes. This has consequences for the realization of sound: The presence of an avatar allows *HC* to utilize

diegetic sounds to communicate to the avatar. Since the avatar is not only the player's access point into the game world, but also a character and a person within that world, sound may communicate to the player indirectly by addressing the avatar in a naturalistic manner. In this sense, *HC* tends to include sound as diegetic features that merge as naturally as possible in with the game as a whole. In *W3*, on the contrary, the absence of an avatar forces all sounds to communicate directly to the player, who is situated external to the game world. This means that the game often must break the illusion of a consistent world by letting units react to the player's commands. This creates a distance between the player and the game world which demands auditory information that guides the player in relation to further choices of actions.

3. Theoretical Background

This chapter concerns the theoretical aspects of this project. Since the study of computer game audio is in its infancy no specific approach has yet been established. Therefore, the theoretical background for this project is based primarily in two camps, namely that of *auditory displays* which derives partly from ecological psychoacoustics and partly from human-computer interaction studies, and *film theory* on sound and music. Neither of these has been used uncritically, and both have been evaluated in relation to how well they can explain certain aspects of computer game audio. This means that the two approaches are not equally relevant for the thesis as a whole. Instead the different approaches contribute to different aspects of computer game audio. Auditory display studies contributes to a greater understanding of how game audio works as support for the usability of a user system, while film theory helps providing an understanding to how game audio relates to the virtual surroundings and defines different spaces for action.

The first part of this chapter will focus on some fundamental discussions and conceptual delimitations that will help provide an understanding of how games, computer games, and computer game audio are regarded in this thesis. After this initial part, the chapter consists of four parts that delve deeper into specific theoretical discussions in which computer game audio is the central aspect. The first discussion concerns the role of sound in an audiovisual context, and in this respect the section will be a revisit to the debate from film theory that discusses the relationship between auditory and visual elements in films. The next theoretical discussion will take into account listening and hearing, and discuss the relevance of different listening modes in relation to computer games. Following this are the two most important parts within the theoretical chapter; namely that which discusses game audio in the context of auditory displays and identifies specific functions of game audio; and that which reviews the film theoretical concepts of diegetic and extradiegetic spaces in the light of computer games, and explains how computer game audio is able to connect conceptually differentiated spaces of information.

3.1 Games, Computer Games & Players

3.1.1 Understanding Games

Understanding computer games and computer game audio needs clear delimitations of the concepts of games, computer games, and what characterizes the experience of playing games. This thesis will find

support in the definition of games proposed by Elliott Avedon & Brian Sutton-Smith in *The Study of Games* from 1971. The book studies games as a cultural and social phenomenon, but is also coloured by mathematical game theory.

Avedon & Sutton-Smith's socio-cultural bias originates from the first two classical works on games that were written from the point of view of ethnology and anthropology. The first work is Johan Huizinga's *Homo Ludens*, first printed in Dutch in 1938 and in English in 1949, and discusses play and games as important ritualistic elements of modern cultures, and as activities that take place in a conceptual space separate from other "serious" real world activities. The next work is Roger Caillois' 1958 work *Le jeux et les hommes*, published in English as *Man, Play and Games* in 1961, which in many ways takes Huizinga's work further by describing game and play as two extremes on a continuum, and separating four super-genres of games.

Avedon & Sutton-Smith's book is also partly based on *game theory*, which is a branch of applied mathematics. In this view, games are strategic situations in which agents choose different actions in order to maximize their own profit, and these situations appear when agents act in a rational manner. The work that defined game theory as a unique field is John von Neumann and Oskar Morgenstern's *The Theory of Games and Economic Behavior* from 1944, and this version as well as following expansions of the theory have been applied to both economic and political theory. In game theory, games are clearly defined situations consisting of a number of players, possible moves or strategies, and specifications of the payoffs that the combination of strategies will produce. This enables game theorists to create algorithms with which to make calculations about what will be the outcome when certain strategies are used (Binmore 1992:3-21). Game theory separates games into different forms, and important variations include distribution of information, whether players move simultaneously or sequentially, and so on. However, this theory is static in the sense that it regards games as strict mathematical functions where the hypothetical players always understand all aspects of his chosen strategy and how it will affect the game as a whole.

Avedon & Sutton-Smith couple the anthropological and the mathematical views and define games as:

"[A]n exercise of voluntary control systems in which there is an opposition between forces, confined by a procedure and rules in order to produce a disequibrial outcome" (1971:7).

There are three interesting points in this definition, namely that games consist of an 1) *exercise of voluntary actions*; that is regulated by 2) *rules and procedures for action*; and are based on 3) *competitiveness related to the outcome*.

The first point focuses on the fact that games are situations in which the player takes *voluntary actions*. *Voluntary* points out that the player is attracted to the game because of some recreational aspect, and that the player wants to play the game. The word *actions* seems especially important for Avedon & Sutton-Smith, since they put emphasis on games as “an exercise of [...] control systems”. The word *exercise* underlines that the activity is taken in an operative manner, and that an effort is made on part of the player. In this sense, skills related to a challenge thus seem to be an important part of games according to this definition.

The next interesting point of the definition is games as guided by *rules and procedures for action*. This means that the skills in question are spent on taking action according to a specific rule system that decides which moves are legal and which are not. The rules of a game provide information about what procedures the player should use when progressing towards the goal of the game. According to Jesper Juul, the rules of a game also constitute game responses to player actions (2005:56). In order to do accomplish these two aspects, game rules need to be definite, unambiguous, and easy to use (2005:5).

The last important point in Avedon & Sutton-Smith’s definition concerns the idea that there is some kind of *competitiveness related to the outcome* of the game, which can be found in the wording “an opposition between forces [...] in order to produce a disequilibrium outcome”. Opposition between forces means that there are different parts in the game with different interests and that work against each other; and the disequilibrium outcome puts emphasis on the idea that a game ends when the power balance between the different parts has positioned one as winner and the others as losers.

This definition is a good general definition of games by being open enough to include most activities we call games while also including some formal structures, such as being regulated by a defined rule system and being dependent on a power balance between the different players. However, there are also weaknesses connected to the definition. It does not take into account the fact that the rules may be subject to change, and it does not elaborate on the power balance, but more importantly, the *experience of playing* is not in focus. Also, by being a general definition, it does not take account for computer games specifically. We therefore need to elaborate on the definition in order to understand computer game activities specifically.

3.1.2 Player Experiences of Games

Avedon & Sutton-Smith’s definition of games does not take into account the *game as a system in relation to the player’s experience* of the game. However, in order to understand what games are, we do need an understanding of the player’s experience of playing a game. It is important to keep in mind that what

characterizes games is the fact that they are activities, and in order to understand what a specific game is all about, these activities must be understood. Janet Murray has used the concept of *agency* to explain the role of computer game players and readers of interactive narratives. She defines agency as the power to take meaningful action and see the consequences of one's own actions (1997:126). However, the concept of agency in connection with computer games is more specific than the power to take meaningful action and see the consequences of these (Jørgensen 2003a, 2003b). Originally, this use of the concept *agency* comes from the philosophically based *action theory* which defines the term as intentional, meaningful action that has a certain effect. The concept presupposes a conscious and rational agent who understands the meaningfulness of the actions taken. However, the theory also states that the specific outcome of the action does not have to be expected (Davidson 1971:43-6). It is important to note that the concept of agency refers to the capacities of the active subjects or agents who through their actions are able to make things progress, and that understand the causality involved.

In connection with games, *agency* must be seen in relation to other game internal activities and the progression of the game. Agency in computer games is dependent on the player as an agent who takes action directly connected to the progression of the game. Thus, only actions that have a *meaningful effect on the system by taking the player a step further in the progression of the game* are covered by the term agency (Jørgensen 2003a:121; 2003b). In this sense, computer game agency is always situational, and needs to be seen in context with other player activities that separate themselves from agency. In this context we may separate three main categories of activities, in which only one depends on agency (Jørgensen 2003:121-2). 1) *Activities* may be any kind of participation that is regarded active in any sense, including mental activities such as interpretation and the making of hypotheses, as well as the turning of pages when reading a novel or the movement of the hand when playing computer games. Activities are prerequisites for completing tasks in a game, but do not progress the game alone. 2) *Simple actions*, on the other hand, denote actions which are meaningful and realized as physical actions within the game, but that do not progress the game forward. This includes exploration of the game environment, modification, configurations and manipulations of elements as long as they do not directly contribute to the central problem solving process. 3) At last, there are *progressive actions*, which are actions important to the progression of the game. These may physically be the same as those named simple actions above, but they depend on player agency by having a certain *effect* on the progression of the game.

However, agency only helps us to understand the mechanisms behind the players' traversal of games, and the concept does not provide further understanding in how a player experiences the game in the sense of

learning to play and learning the mechanisms behind the game system. The more the players play a game and explore its mechanics, the better they become in playing the game because they learn the dynamics of the specific game system. During this mastering process, a special relationship between game system and player actions comes into being, and this experience contributes to the characteristics of games as activity. Emotionally the player becomes closely attached to the game when playing, and the psychological state is in many respects similar to what Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi describes under the umbrella term *flow* (1990:4, 1998:28-30). *Flow* is the feeling of being intensely engaged in an activity for its own sake, and during flow nothing except this specific activity seems to matter. The sense of time passing seems to disappear, due to the flow's deep focus where no distraction is able to interrupt the sense of flow. As an example of flow, Csikszentmihalyi points to the experience of playing games. Here the players face goals that require certain responses and that create a certain dynamic in the interaction between player and game system, and in order to overcome the challenges set before them, the players need to fully involve their skills and attention (1998:29-30).

While Csikszentmihalyi's concept of *flow* is general and does not concern the gaming activity in particular, another term is commonly used in connection with the specific game experience. This is the concept of *gameplay*, which is a term used by the game industry, players, and game reviewers when they talk about issues such as the dynamic relationship that comes into being between the player and the game system. Some uses the concept to put emphasis on the *activity of playing*, while others focus on the usability of the game system and its interface as well as how well the system is balanced. Because of the variations in meaning, the term *gameplay* has not gained a dominating definition in game research, but Jesper Juul has provided a starting definition by claiming that gameplay is used to describe the way the game is actually played. He points out that the specific *challenges* posed by a game are important for the essence of gameplay in that particular game. Thus, it is neither the rules themselves, nor the game's representation that is the essence of gameplay, but the dynamic nature of the game (2003:83). A problem with this description, however, is that this suggests that the game alone creates and defines gameplay. Another view comes from the game designers Andrew Rollings and Ernest Adams, who note that game challenges must be understood in the context of the player's experience, and that the nature of the challenge suggests the nature of the player's response (2003:13). In this sense, they add a player perspective and claim that the gameplay of a specific game cannot be fully understood without playing the game. However, an important point ignored by both views is that understanding the dynamic of the game system is dependent on becoming familiar with the game mechanics and the way the game rules interact with the player. Increased familiarity with the game thus

also increases the player's comprehension of the gameplay of a specific game. My view is that gameplay depends both on the game system and the player's experience of the game, and that gameplay comes into being when the game system meets the player's actions, strategic choices and problem solving processes. Gameplay is thus the dynamic nature of the interplay between game and player, and the gameplay of a specific game can only be understood by familiarity with the system in question.

In order to understand the experience of computer games, it is important to understand how gameplay comes into being when the player and the system interact with each other. However, it should also be noted that the psychological state of flow is a prerequisite for the gameplay experience. Also, gameplay assumes that the players feel that their actions contribute directly to the progression of the game.

3.2 Computer Games as Virtual Worlds & as User Systems

When trying to understand computer games, we should keep in mind that computer games are a blend of two different worlds. By being games set in virtual environments, computer games are computer user systems and virtual simulated worlds at the same time. This duality is a prerequisite for how computer games and computer game audio are understood in this thesis, and the two aspects are simultaneously present and work together in providing the specific experience that computer games are. In connection with game audio, this duality means that sound is utilized for usability purposes at the same time as it is implemented in order to create a sense of presence by making the game environment sound alive and credible.

Jesper Juul also separates computer games into two realms in a similar manner (2005:5-6, 163-96). However, instead of pointing out the relationship as one between a user system and a virtual world, he argues that computer games are *rule systems operating within fictional worlds*. However, my point does not contradict Juul's point. Instead, talking about a user system instead of a rule system makes my claim more general than Juul's. The computer is a complex system with the ability to react to and process user input as well as to calculate large quantities of data, and it is therefore a sophisticated tool suitable for working with complex game rules. However, since this user system is not limited to the game rules, my point is more general. In another sense, the point is also more specific than Juul's. The complexity of the computer system has made it possible for modern computer games to also implement interface functions into the rule system. Since my argument directly concerns system features connected to interface and usability, it is aimed towards a specific part of the rule system, whereas Juul's argument concerns the rule system as a whole. In the case of Juul's use of the term "fictional world", I am using "virtual world" instead because it allows me to emphasise the

relationship to computer environments, while also avoiding connotations connected to the word “fiction” such as “narration” and “storytelling” (Juul 2005:122). It also evades the idea that the actions taken within the game are “fictional” and consequently not real actions.

As mentioned above, the fact that computer games are part user system and part virtual world has consequences for the realization of game audio. The usability function of sound is central, but sound has also had an important role in relation to supporting a sense of presence in the game environment. Thus, this thesis aims at a somewhat different angle than Juul by focussing on a) that aspect of the game rule system with closest contact with the player and b) the computer-specific features that allow very complex game rules to be processed with ease. It also aims at avoiding the film and literary theory connotations of the word “fiction”.

3.2.1 Games as Virtual Worlds

The virtual worlds of computer games are often very similar to the fictional worlds found in for instance narrative film and literature, but game worlds are also different from such worlds in ways that will be explained below. I will use Jesper Juul’s understanding of computer games as *real rules in a fictional world*, and Marie-Laure Ryan’s theory of *possible worlds* in order to explain how “virtual world” should be understood in this thesis.

For Juul, playing computer games means interacting with real rules while imagining a fictional world (2005:1). Juul explains that engagement in a game world depends on understanding how the game relates to the real world. Since the rules of a computer game and the fictional world are implemented into each other (2005:121), computer games have a dual origin that allows us to describe computer games as *fiction* at the same time as they can be described as a *real activity*. According to Juul, in the fictional world of the fighting game *Tekken 3*, “Eddy Gordo is Brazilian and fights using the martial art of capoeira”. But in the real world, it is also true that you can choose the character Eddy Gordo in *Tekken 3* and control that character so that he attacks with capoeira moves (Juul 2005:167-8). However, Eddy Gordo does not exist as a person in the real world, and is therefore a fictional character (Juul 2005:1). Juul claims that this shows that computer games are not only about fiction, but about actual movements and actions set in a fictional world. With reference to Salen and Zimmermann’s discussion of game spaces, Juul believes that the reason we understand this dual origin of computer games is because of our awareness of the *magic circle* that defines the border of what should be interpreted as part of the game and what should be seen as part of the real world (2005:164). The magic

circle is defined by the game rules and puts emphasis on games as a subcategory of the real world, and therefore as a separate space.

However, this space may be better understood with reference to Ryan's theory of *possible worlds*. *Possible worlds* is originally a concept from philosophy adopted by literary theory to describe the logic of fictionality and how we come to understand the environment of narratives as separate from the real world environment (Ryan 2001:99). Ryan's point of departure is that reality is the sum total of the imaginable, consisting of an *actual world* in the centre and a number of *possible worlds* as satellites around the central world. The *actual world* is the ontologically existing world of historical facts, and the only one that exists independently of the human mind (2001:100). *Possible worlds*, on the other hand, are products of mental activity, and include dreaming, imagining, forming hypotheses and reporting these thoughts in the form of fiction (2001:101). As satellites, possible worlds are located at various distances to the central actual world, depending on how difficult they are to realize. This means that a social-realist drama would be placed close to the centre, while a fantasy story containing dragons, orcs and magic would be placed further away. In this sense, possible worlds are separate frames of reference that are regarded as actual worlds for its inhabitants, and characters of the possible world will also have possible worlds based on their own thoughts and dreams. When people meet a possible world through film or literature, they relocate their focus to this possible world, which then becomes the centre and the actual world of a new universe for the time being. Ryan calls this process *recentering* (2001:103).

Ryan's theory takes into consideration the idea that there are a lot of things in the world that does not exist, but still cannot be regarded fictional, such as hopes, future plans, and ideas. A central point in her theory is that all worlds, both possible and actual, are parts of reality although they have a different origin by being either constructs of the imagination, or existing ontologically independent of the human mind. This questions the general understanding of the concept of fictional worlds, but it also means that talking about real rules operating within fictional worlds becomes a contradiction since the so-called fictional world also is a part of reality. Also, when the rules are real, and the actions taken are regarded as real game actions, it becomes problematic to speak of the space in which these actions and rules operate as being fictional. Instead, we should say that the specific game rules and the actions are operating within another frame of reference of reality. However, this is not only a revision of Juul's theory, but it is also a revision of Ryan's theory, since when adding actual movement and activity, possible worlds become *potential* worlds since the player can choose which one to pursue and realize.

To avoid the problematic connotations of the word *fictional*, I will instead refer to the game environment as a *virtual world* instead of a fictional world. According to *Webster's New Millennium Dictionary of English*, a virtual environment may be seen as "a computer-generated three-dimensional representation of a setting in which the user of the technology perceives themselves to be and within which interaction takes place"^j. Although today the term *virtual* is popularly connected to anything we experience in connection with computers and cyberspace, Ryan points out that in computer lingo, *virtual* was originally a technical term expressing the simulating powers of the computer (2001:26). This connection to the computer as a simulation system is an important reason for using the word virtual. It underlines that in the virtual world of computer games, a lot of what is going on is controlled by the computer. The computer takes on specific tasks such as managing most of the rules, and controlling the environment and specific opponents. This is a very important property of the virtual computer-simulated world, and that functionally separate the game environment from the worlds found in films, literature, and pen-and-paper roleplaying games.

However, the word originates from the Latin *virtus* meaning strength, manliness or virtue, which became the philosophical idea of force or power. The derived concept *virtualis* in scholastic Latin came to stand for the *potential* or "what is in the power of the force" (2001:26). Although *virtual* also later came to stand for the fictive and nonexistent, the original meaning of the concept refers not to "that which is deprived of existence [,] but that which possesses the potential, or force, of developing into actual existence" (Ryan 2001:27). Although the definition above is central to the understanding of virtual world in this thesis, the reference to the *potential* should also be added, as it points to the idea that the game world is not a possible world, but a potential world in which actions taken are real actions with consequences for the game world.

3.2.2 Sound in Virtual Worlds

The game as virtual world also guides the realization of game audio. In order to secure the player's sense of presence in the game world, game developers strive towards making the game environments sound as lifelike as possible. However, in many respects it is not *realism* that is wanted in this context. Instead *credibility* is the goal of a certain soundscape. *Fidelity* is a concept from audio engineering that refers to the precision of reproduction of mediated sound (Nyre 2003:13). *Audio fidelity* takes as a starting point that recorded sound always is an interpretation in the sense that some aspects will be filtered out. This means that recorded sound

^j virtual environment. (n.d.). *Webster's New Millennium™ Dictionary of English, Preview Edition (v 0.9.6)*. Retrieved September 12, 2006, from Dictionary.com website: <http://dictionary.reference.com/search?q=virtual>

can never be an exact replication of the real world, but that the recording always will have a certain precision, accuracy or exactness (Nyre 2003:21) compared to the real world. Audio fidelity is thought of as a physical feature that can be measured with electronic equipment. The more traces there are of the recording, the lower fidelity. This means that an old musical recording will be of low fidelity because of its crude sound quality, while a modern digital recording of high sound quality will be of high fidelity. However, Lars Nyre points out that if we want to discuss the reality status of recorded sound, we should look at the *perceptual fidelity* and not the audio fidelity. Instead of pointing to the qualitative resemblance between the recorded sound and the original, perceptual fidelity relates to the trustworthiness of a sound as representing a specific time and/or place (Nyre 2003:22). In exemplifying the difference between audio and perceptual fidelity, Nyre refers to the Lunar transmission in 1969. This recording was of low audio fidelity because of the technical constraints. Machine humming, microphone noises and disturbances resulting from the long transport through space could be heard in the broadcast, but paradoxically this low audio fidelity was what made the broadcast seem real, since it created no doubt about the fact that a live transmission over a great distance was going on..

Perceptual fidelity is what game developers are striving for when adding sound to a game for the purpose of creating a lifelike and naturalistic environment. When a spell of magic is accompanied by a sound in a computer game, it makes no sense to talk about audio fidelity since the sound is not a recording of a real world event. As a matter of fact, it is most likely a computer generated synthetic sound, or the result of mixing a number of sounds recorded from different real world events. However, it makes sense to say that the sound is of high perceptual fidelity in the sense of being a credible sound of a spell of magic in a fantasy world. Perceptual fidelity thus demonstrates how sounds can support a lifelike and credible environment without conforming to standards of realism. It should also be noted that in computer games, perceptual fidelity goes further. In many cases it is the *functional* value of the sound that is of importance, and in this sense it is not whether a sound seems credible or suitable for an environment which is in question, but whether a sound seems suitable for what a specific object can do or what a specific event means for the player. An example of this can be found in *World of Warcraft*, where monsters make a sound the moment they attack the player. While the growl of the lion may be of high audio and perceptual fidelity, the situation in which it appears may seem a little awkward since one would expect an attacking animal to sneak silently up on its target. However, regardless of the quality of the sound or whether it contributes to a lifelike universe, the sound does provide the player with information that a monster is attacking. In this sense, the functional value is central, and we may therefore speak of a sound's *functional fidelity* in computer games.

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3.2.3 Sound as User System Feature

The integration of sound in software and computer environments for functional and operational purposes has been an issue for as long as the computer has existed. Even the earliest computers used the internal speaker to play a beep as an indication of illegal actions and not executable requests. In many circumstances it turns out that the auditory perceptual system has certain advantages over the visual regarding usability. Based on a 1972 overview by Deatherage, McCormick & Sanders make a list of situations in which auditory displays would be preferable to visual (1986:133). The most important points include situations in which the visual system is overburdened or limited by external factors, or when the message is simple and short or deals with temporal or continuously changing events. Other situations appear when a message calls for immediate attention or works as a warning, and when the receiver is in movement. In this respect, utilizing sound is a method for making the interface more intuitive and more user-friendly in situations where the visual system is busy, overburdened, or limited in other respects. Carrie Heeter and Pericles Gomes (1992) provide additional reasons for the implementation of auditory cues in computer environments. The inclusion of sound seems to ease the ability to pick up and interpret information, as well as relieving the user from attentive tasks. Heeter & Gomes also put emphasis on the idea that providing redundant information through both the visual and the auditory channel, increases the likelihood that a certain message is received. On this basis, sound may be implemented in two basic ways as support for usability; either *proactively* or *reactively*. The proactive implementation is emphasised by McCormick & Sanders (186:138-40), who point to the use of sound for providing information about situations that need immediate attention. In such cases, sound is used as notices, warnings or alerts. The reactive implementation is in focus in Heeter & Gomes (1992), who advocate the importance of making computer systems provide responses to user input. This can be done in three ways: either the system can simply execute the command; it can provide a visual cue to inform the user that a command is received; or it can provide an auditory cue to indicate that the command is received. These ideas are also applicable to computer games, which ultimately also are software applications. They have the same limits concerning the number of perceptual channels through which they may communicate to the player, and needs to utilize the same opportunities that other computer systems utilize. This means that utilizing the auditory system can relieve the visual system to other tasks, thereby enabling the game to provide information to the player through several channels simultaneously.

3.4 The Audiovisual Alliance

This section will revisit the sound versus image debate from film theory, where the role of sound has been discussed in relation to image with focus on how a film gains its meaning (Altman 1992:35-45, Langkjær 2000:17-98, Maasø 1994:5-31). Although the debate on the role of sound in an audiovisual context is old, this section will today's point of view on the subject matter as a starting point. However, since this work is concerned with computer game audio, that debate will only mark the starting point for how we should understand the role of sound in a game context. As we will see, the relationship between auditory and visual information in games is different than that of sound and image in films.

3.4.1 The Unity of Sound & Image

New theory on sound in audiovisual contexts criticizes the view that sound is secondary to visual information, but states also that sound should not be seen as a complete equal to the visuals. In this connection, Birger Langkjær emphasises that the critique is aimed towards the idea that audiovisual meaning comes into being through an opposition between sound and images (2000:17). He claims that this is a classical and erroneous statement that has contributed to discussing sound in audiovisual contexts on the wrong terms. To discuss the matter as if it concerned a struggle between two forces, where either one or the other may take a winning position, pushes the debating parts into three categories: namely those who believe that the image is more important than sound for creating meaning; those who believe that sound is the force in the meaning making process; and those who believe that sound and image have equal roles in the meaning making process. According to Langkjær, all of these positions are faulty because they assume that sound and image are two independent semantic units that may be comprehended isolated from each other (2000:19). Making such an assumption is expanding a technical difference to a semantic difference, which ignores the fact that in an audiovisual context, sound and images work together as a complex unity that cannot be reduced to independent carriers of meaning (2000:21). Langkjær calls this confusion of transferring a technical difference to a semantic difference a *modal fallacy*, with reference to Rick Altman's overview of four and a half fallacies found in the general argumentation that point to the image as the primary creator of meaning (Altman 1992:35-45).

The viewpoints of two scholars concerned about the role of sound in audiovisual contracts will be discussed as a starting point for the understanding of the role of sound in computer games. Birger Langkjær and Arnt Maasø represent the modern view of the role of sound in relation to the image, and their conclusions are also

relevant for understanding how sound works in a gaming context. Arnt Maasø is a researcher within sound and music in the media who does not want to underestimate the role of sound, but at the same time he is careful about not putting too much weight on the importance of sound (1994:30). With a neology, he argues that we “hear-see” rather than hear and see in audiovisual contexts, and with this term he wants to focus on the idea that any interpretation of film and television is a hermeneutic circle where two sensory processes work together and simultaneously in an endless interactive interpretative process. In this context it becomes both impossible and unnecessary to isolate auditory and visual elements (1994:31). He goes on to argue that a study of the essence of the film medium must include studying all elements that carry meaning, and not single features, such as the image or sound, in isolation (1994:14). In this argumentation lies the idea that sound and image are both representational features (1994:17-18), since they both contribute to the process of meaning making. Maasø is putting emphasis on this point as an answer to the *reproductive* fallacy that erroneously claims that film images are *representational* while film sound is *reproduced* (Altman 1992: 39-40; Maasø 1994:17). This statement implies that a *reproduction* is an objective registration that remains unchanged in its new format, while a *representation* is an interpretation where choices have been made in deciding which elements should be presented and how. The reproductive fallacy states that images are representational since they have been recorded as a two-dimensional version of a three-dimensional reality, while sound does not change when being recorded but are simply reproduced instead. Maasø argues against this by underlining that film audio is equally manipulated as the image. The audio is seldom recorded on location, and is therefore not connected to the image in time and space (Maasø 1994:17). Also, sounds are post-produced and manipulated (Altman 1992:40), and there is therefore no reason to state that the origin of audio is any different than the origin of images.

Cognitive theory is also an approach that has been adopted into the debate on the relationship between sound and image in the audiovisual contexts. This approach sees perception as a system that struggles with interpreting different and often conflicting data (Branigan 1989:317, 1992:38). In the process of perception and cognition, the perceivers register all information available and uses their cognitive abilities to manage the data and discriminate which parts are relevant for comprehending a specific context. In order to make sense of this diverse and conflicting material, the cognitive system works in two different ways, namely *bottom-up* and *top-down*. Bottom-up processing is the perceptual system’s way of registering input and automatically organizing it into meaningful entities such as duration and pitch in the case of auditory perception, and colour and shape in the case of visual perception. Top-down perception, on the other hand, is based on knowledge and schemas, and utilizes the perceiver’s expectations when organizing data. Bottom-up processes are thus

automatic functions that make the brain register and understand specific sensory data, while top-down processes treat data as composite information and work to test the data according to different frames of reference (Branigan 1989:316-7,1992:37). These processes work simultaneously on the perceived data and enable the perceivers to make meaning out of what they see and hear.

In his studies of film sound and music, Birger Langkjær takes as a starting point the cognitive view of the relation between sound and image in the audiovisual context. He argues that sound is experienced and comprehended through schema-based top-down processes, and that our understanding is guided by a network of general knowledge (2000:34). Langkjær explains the relationship between auditory and visual information by referring to two simultaneously working perceptual processes, which he describes as a *synthetizing* and a *synaesthetic* perceptual process (2000:34-5). The synthetizing perception is the process that makes us comprehend composite events as one instead of separate entities. For instance, when someone speaks to us, we process this as one incident, and not as two events consisting of moving lips and simultaneous sounds. Synaesthetic perception, on the other hand, concerns a dislocation from one sensory experience to another, which comes into being as an associative process when experiencing something through one sensory modality. For instance, the smell of oranges makes us want to eat an orange, or the sight of a dog makes us remember the sense of touching the dog's fur. The synthetizing and the synaesthetic processes work together when we experience the world around us in everyday perception, and they are also present in the comprehension of audiovisual fiction (Langkjær 2000:35). The combination of these processes seems to be an advantage in audiovisual contexts, since the synthetizing process enables the connection of auditory and visual information into one perceptual unit, at the same time as the synaesthetic process enables the perceiver to indirectly experience sensory modalities that are not actually present. According to Langkjær, this means that we still will remember the blood in a monochrome film as red due to synaesthetic perception, and we also remember getting scared by a certain scene although we do not remember the specific music that scared us due to synthetizing perception. Since these processes work together, image and sound cannot be interpreted as two separately working elements that provide different understandings of the world. Instead these are working simultaneously in making a complete comprehension in which both sensory modalities contribute.

Thus, Langkjær's point is that the film experience contains both more and less than the film alone (2000:36), and that meaning therefore cannot be extracted from individual elements, but comes into being from the combination of all elements. In this connection, he also puts emphasis on the idea that meaning does not belong to specific elements in the film, but that it is contextually created on the basis of the perceiver's

changes in interests (2000:37). These ideas provide the comprehension of film as a representational system consisting of audiovisual information, and where the auditory and visual information cannot be seen as separate sign systems with different content. Instead of separating sound and images as distinguished elements that contribute in different ways to the comprehension of audiovisual contexts, auditory and the visual perception should be seen as two perceptual features that both contribute to organizing a complex material consisting of often conflicting data. In this sense, sound and image work together in guiding the meaning of a certain audiovisual situation. Depending on context, however, situations may occur in which individual elements have a greater impact on the comprehension of events. This view finds support in cognitive psychology by building its theories on the relationship between top-down and bottom-up processes, as well as putting emphasis on the fact that all perception happens as a combination of synaesthetic and synthetizing processes. However, although this point of departure also applies to computer game audio, there are differences between computer game audio and film audio both in realization and in function. The discussion needs to be taken further in order to get deeper into what the role of sound in computer games is.

3.4.2 Films vs. Games as Representational Systems

The argument in this section is based on the idea that sound and image are cognitively experienced as two perceptual features that work together, and that cannot be separated as two distinguished features in the meaning-making process.

Although both films and games are audiovisual representational systems, they differ in several respects. A first formal difference is related to the argument against the reproductive fallacy in film theory (Altman 1992: 39-40; Maasø 1994:17) which was discussed above. This assertion states that film images are representations while film sound is reproduced. Arguments against this belief claim that both images and sound are representations, a point which becomes even more convincing in connection with computer games. In games both images and sound are clear constructs. Since the visual representation is never a recording but constructed computer graphics^k, the sound will always be artificially assigned to the visuals. In films sound will normally not be recorded on location either, but there is always a possibility that it could have been and it is often hard for the audience to tell whether it was. However, this does not mean that films are less representational than computer games, but it does mean that it may be easier to accept the argument that

^k There are some interesting exceptions, such as computer games where the visuals consist of photographic images.

both image and sound are representational constructs, and it does put emphasis on the fact that image and sound are equally representational.

It is also important to point out that film and games are different kinds of representational systems. By this I mean that representation is not limited to the visual aspect. Films are regarded representational first and foremost on the visual level, since they have a close iconicity, in the Peircian sense of the word, to what it wants to display. Although computer games are moving closer to an iconic relation between a sign and its object on the graphical level, it is not the visual representation which is important in connection to games. As computer simulations, what is important is the *functional* similarity. Instead of seeing a similarity between a game's audiovisual surface and the corresponding audiovisual aspects of objects in the real world, it is important to see the similarity between what activities they model and how these are realized in the game. Thus, when we look upon computer games and computer game audio as representational systems, we should instead focus on the functional aspects.

In his cognitive approach to sound in films, Birger Langkjær claims that the most valuable way to explain representation is to go beyond the assumption that there is representational relation between sound and image. Instead we must look at what they refer to together. In this sense, the focus changes into understanding sound and image as two aspects that work in the service for something else in films, namely a *situation* such as an *event* or an *activity* (Langkjær 2000.117). He explains this by pointing out that effect sounds often identify their sources in films, but that this is not always what is of relevance or importance for the audience. Instead it is often more important to understand the *situation* or the whole *context* that sound and image appear in. This also applies for computer games and game audio, especially in connection with unseen or hidden sources, or in situations in which a sound works communicatively to inform listeners about something other than its origin. To say it with an example, when we hear the sound of a gong in *Warcraft III*, it is not important to know where this sound originates from, but it is important to know that the sound signals a change in status.

This situation-oriented perspective may be further elaborated by referring to James Gibson's notion of *affordances* (1979). According to Gibson's ecological perspective on psychology, any object that we meet in our environment will present for us ways in which we may interact with it. For instance, a door will present us the possibilities for opening and closing. In Gibson's terminology, the door affords opening and closing, and it is hence *openable* and *closeable* in Gibson's terminology. A chair is *sitable*, while a tree may be *climbable*. It is important to note that although Gibson's focus was on visual perception, all perceptions may contribute in providing information about an object's affordances. This means that in the case of a closed container, visual

and auditory information may or may not provide information about its *fillability*: visual information may provide information about the general capacity of the container, but auditory information provided by tapping on the container may tell whether the container is full or empty, and hence whether it is fillable at this precise moment. Translated to a game context, the sight and sounds from a monster will together provide the player with information about a situation that is *run-away-from-able* or *fight-able*. Thus, it is the dangerous situation which is of importance in this respect, and not the presence of a certain monster which may or may not act aggressively towards the player at a certain point in time.

However, since this situational aspect is equally relevant for representations in film and games, we should continue further in explaining what kind of representation we talk about in connection to game audio, and exactly how the situational aspect is realized. On the surface, a *simulation* may look like a representation, and in a way it is also possible to see simulation as a subcategory of representation. However, simulations model the behaviour of a system which means that the specific functional aspects are demonstrated instead of the visual aspects connected to the word representation. It should be kept in mind that games are simulations. In this respect, simulations are situation dependent systems that users learn by testing its behaviour in different contexts and over time (Frasca 2001). Game audio should be understood as part of a simulation system, which means that a sound always has a functional role which is understood from the specific game situation.

In connection to the functional and situational aspects, it is also important to keep in mind that the cognitive processes related to playing games are focused on the simulation aspects. In connection to film sound, Langkjær describes four psychological levels that are at work in the active processing of the film audience (2000:50). With some adjustments, these levels also apply to how computer games and computer game audio is processed when the player is making meaning of the computer gaming situation. However, Langkjær separates a *sensory* level, a *perceptual* level, a *receptive* level, and a *diegetic and narrative* level, which all work simultaneously in interaction with each other. On the *sensory* level, individual expressive elements are perceived, such as recognition of musical style, individual effect sounds and images. This level is an analytical one which automatically is synthesized into the next *perceptual* level. On this level, the different auditory and visual elements are experienced as different aspects of the same fictional reality. This level is closely related to the *receptive* level, which consists of the audience's cognitive and emotional responses and evaluations of the audiovisual information presented. The receptive level relates interactively to the sensory and perceptual level, but is also guided by the *narrative and diegetic* level. This level is a mental model which activates the receiver's knowledge about time and space relations, what situations and actions are likely to happen, etc. in the course of the film. In this context, both auditory and visual information is at work.

These different processes are of course at work in any kind of comprehension of what we experience, including computer game play. However, due to the fact that games include a different kind of engagement on part of the player, different processes are at work, especially on the receptive and the narrative and diegetic levels. On the *receptive* level, responses and evaluations are not limited to interpretative issues and hypotheses about how the situations will develop. On this level, the game player also builds an understanding of the fact that progression does not happen automatically or as a consequence of some other agent's actions; but that the player is that agent that is responsible to set progression in motion. In other words, this is the level where the player must move from seeing computer games as first and foremost representations to seeing computer games as first and foremost simulations. In relation to sound, this is the level on which the player understands sound as more than simply ornamental and as part of the simulation. The players understand that an animal growl in the game means danger and that it is up to themselves how to confront that danger.

On the *diegetic* level, player knowledge about features such as genre and the game in question becomes applied contextual knowledge. This level enables the players to make situation-dependent evaluations about what actions to take, and it also makes the players able to comprehend a situation to such a detail that they understand why a certain reaction or action may be the right one in a specific situation although it does not apply in a different situation. Related to sound, on this level the players understand not only that the growl means danger, but they also understand from the specific context exactly how they should respond. Is it safe to stop to fight, or should I run? This is also of importance to sound in computer games, since sound works as a feature that supports functional and operational roles and cues player action. In this sense, Langkjær's detailed overview of how cognitive processes work provides an account of how different perceptual inputs simultaneously work in connection with audiovisual media, thus demonstrating that auditory and visual information cannot be regarded as two systems communicating separately. Moreover, since the overview is fairly general, it is also fit for describing cognitive processes that differ from the film experience. This means that it is possible to use the overview for understanding computer games and computer game audio by pointing out the differences in the receptive and diegetic levels. Game audio must be seen as part of the overall simulation or game system, and not as an aesthetic feature in servitude of the visual features. This is emphasised by the fact that computer game audio is closely connected to usability in the sense of easing the use of the system as well as providing better understanding of how the game mechanics work.

3.5 Hearing & Listening

Another discussion relevant for the functionality of computer game audio is related to hearing and listening. There is a perceptual difference between these in the sense that *hearing* is an unintentional activity while *listening* is intentional and focused towards specific sounds. This thought has led to further discussions about listening and hearing, based on the idea that there are different listening strategies based on the specific relationship between a listener and a certain source. This part of the chapter will take into consideration two views of listening, and use these as a point of departure for discussing what kind of auditory perceptual activities are at work in computer games. These views are both partly based on Pierre Schaeffer's early work on sound and music in the book *Traité des Objets Musicaux* (1966), and come from two different fields of sound studies. The first is Michel Chion's separation of four different listening modes in audiovisual cinematic contexts (1994:25-34) and Denis Smalley's separation of three kinds of relationships between listener and source in connection with musical listening in general and electroacoustic music listening in particular (1996:81-2).

Schaeffer separates four different listening modes, where the two first basically correspond to the difference between listening and hearing. Among these two, the first mode is an information-gathering mode, and the second is an unintentional mode where the perceiver cannot help but hear the sound. Thus, the first mode is *objective* by being centred on the sound-producing object, while the second is *subjective* by focussing on the listener's reaction to the sound. In addition, Schaeffer identifies two modes that are specifically directed towards musical listening. One of these modes is concerned with the intentional activity of musical appreciation and responses to attributes of sound, and the second mode is concerned with the process of responding to a musical language as opposed to everyday sounds (Smalley 1996:79).

Chion takes Schaeffer's listening modes as a starting point for separating three forms of active listening processes (as opposed to hearing), namely *causal* listening, *semantic* listening, and *reduced* listening. Closest to Schaeffer's information-gathering mode of listening is 1) *causal listening*, which concerns listening for the origin of a certain sound in order to gather information about its cause (1992:25). Chion states that when the source is visible, sound may reveal additional information about the source, as would be the case when a person taps a container to find out how full it is. When the source is not visible, sound may be the primary source of information about a certain object. 2) *Semantic listening* concerns listening to a certain code or language to interpret the content of the message, such as is the case when listening to language or Morse code (1992:26). This is adapted from Schaeffer's mode about responding to musical language, but the semantic listening mode is more general by including non-musical codes as well. 3) *Reduced listening*

focuses on the traits and properties of the sound itself, and is adopted from Schaeffer's listening to attributes within musical sounds. In Chion's terminology the concept is relevant for all kinds of audio, and reduced listening takes the sound itself as the object of study instead of a vehicle for something else (1994:27). In addition, Chion identifies a fourth mode of listening called *acousmatic listening*, which also is a term adopted from Schaeffer, but which Chion gives different emphasis than Schaeffer did (1994:32). Acousmatic listening separates itself from the other modes by referring to a situation in which one hears a sound without seeing its source. Schaeffer argued that this type of listening encourages reduced listening by provoking the listeners to separate themselves from what causes a sound. However, according to Chion, the opposite occurs since the absence of the source will make a listener ask what the origin is. Thus, the acousmatic tends to intensify causal listening instead (1994:32).

Smalley also takes Schaeffer as starting point when defining relationships that exist between a listener and sound, but in addition he takes into consideration the relationship between *subject-centred* and *object-centred* perceptual activity as presented by Ernest Schachtel (Smalley 1996:80). This view separates a subject-centred or *autocentric* perception and an object-centred or *allocentric* perception. In relation to music, the *autocentric* attitude is concerned with basic positive and negative responses and feelings to the sounds. The use of muzak is a perfect example of commercial use of *autocentric* perception, in the sense that the music is supposed to provide a certain mood that may stimulate acts of purchasing on part of the customer. In connection to music, *allocentric* perception is a more intentional and active form of perception than *autocentric* perception. Here listening is directed towards the music in question and concerns the apprehension of the musical structure specifically. The allocentric and autocentric perceptual activities work simultaneously and together. It is possible to switch between the two, and some listeners will tend to focus on one while other listeners focus on the other (Smalley 1996:80-1). Smalley merges the idea of allocentric and autocentric perception with Schaeffer's listening modes, and the result is a somewhat different view on listening than Chion presents. Smalley identifies three basic relationships between the perceiving subject (listener) and objects of perception (sounds) in order to provide an understanding of different listening modes in relation to musical perception. The first mode is 1) the *indicative relationship*, in which sound is understood as a message or information about events or actions in the environment. In this context, the focus is on the sounding object, and listening may be either active or passive dependent on whether the listener actively seeks out the sound (i.e. expects it) or the sound impinges the consciousness of the listener. 2) The *reflexive relationship* concerns the listeners and their emotional responses to the sound, and may be either active or passive, although it tends to stimulate passive hearing instead of active listening. The third listener-sound

relationship that Smalley identifies is the 3) *interactive relationship*, which involves structural listening and aesthetic attitudes towards the sound. The reason for calling this mode interactive is that the perception happens top-down where the perceiver actively listens to structures and properties of the sound (Smalley 1996:82).

Before looking at how the two scholars' listening modes exist in the context of computer games, I will make a comparison of Chion and Smalley's understandings of listening in order to make a thorough list of the listening activities in question. It is important to note that Chion and Smalley's overviews focus on different objects: Chion is talking about sound in general, and Smalley is discussing music specifically. Also, Smalley's model is problematic because it changes focus from the *listener's experience* to the *sound as an object*. Chion's view, on the other hand, is problematic because it does not take into consideration the *passive or indirect listening* mode present in Smalley's *reflexive relationship* and the *autocentric* perceptual activity. However, although both scholars define three modes of sound perception, it seems that we are actually talking about four central modes. This is also supported by the original views of Schaeffer and Schachtel.

Chion and Smalley's overviews differ in two respects. The first difference is that Smalley seems to combine Chion's *semantic* and *reduced listening* into the *interactive relationship*. In other words, Chion keeps Schaeffer's separation between listening for the meaning behind certain sounds and listening for the properties and timbre of sounds, while Smalley does not separate between two listening modes that focus on different kinds of content. Both choices seem rational in the context of what the two scholars are studying. Chion is studying sound in general in films, and needs to point out that listening for the meaning of language is something different than listening for the properties of sound or the origin of sounds. Although the difference is crucial to the understanding of *semantic listening* in the world in general, it is especially important in connection to films since linguistic information is an important contribution to the film's narrative. In the case of Smalley, his musical perspective does not make it necessary to isolate linguistic comprehension since understanding the lyrics of a song is not a prerequisite for appreciating it.

The second difference between the views of Smalley and Chion, is that Chion does not include in his overview emotional responses to sound, and how perceivers are affected by sounds that they do not actively listen for. In one respect, it seems strange that Chion has not included the kind of sound that perhaps has greatest impact in modern films via film music. Arguably, film music is present to emphasise moods, and although many disagree with Gorbman's view that film music is "unheard" (1987), fact is that very many film viewers do not focus their perception on the extradiegetic music. However, the reason why Chion has excluded this mode from his overview is that it presents *listening* modes only and no *hearing* modes. In other words, Chion

focuses on intentional listening that is directed towards the object in the sense of Schachtel's *allocentric* perception. This does not mean that Chion ignores the existence of this kind of sound and this kind of listening in connection with film perception, only that this is not the focus in his book.

Characteristics	Chion:	Smalley:
<i>Listening for the source of the sound, gaining information about source. Active listening – allocentric.</i>	Causal listening	Indicative relationship
<i>Listening for the content of source, conscious understanding. Active listening – allocentric.</i>	Semantic listening	Interactive relationship
<i>Listening for properties and traits of the sound itself. Active listening – allocentric.</i>	Reduced listening	
<i>Emotional responses to sound. Passive hearing – autocentric.</i>		Reflexive relationship

Figure 3: Comparison of Chion and Smalley's overviews of listening.

In connection to computer games, Smalley's understanding of the relationship between sound and listener seems to be more fruitful than Chion's version, due to the fact that the overview both includes sounds that need attentive listening and sounds that are passively impinged in the consciousness of the listener. Also, computer games very rarely utilize what Chion calls reduced listening, and Smalley's idea of the interactive relationship therefore covers semantic listening which is the only important active listening type where the perceiver listens to the content of the sound. It should be kept in mind though, that Smalley's interactive relationship does consist of two different modes. Another issue that is important to keep in mind in the context of computer games, is that the use of language does not necessarily mean that the player should listen to its content and aim to understand the semantic value of the sound. The voice is often used indicatively by making the player attentive to the presence of other characters, and in such cases it is not necessary that the player understands what is being said. This is the case in *Hitman Contracts*. In other cases, the sound of a voice may be used as a signal sound where the semantic content is not important. We see this use in *Warcraft III*. However, the voice is also used to provide linguistic information in these and other games, but when it is used to provide information relevant for further progression in the game, it tends to be supported by subtitles, and it very often appears in cut-scenes instead of play sequences.

In *HC*, sound is used both to provide information about specific events (the *indicative relationship*) and as a mood enhancer (*reflexive relationship*). Only rarely the *interactive relationship* is used to provide semantic information. The use of the *indicative relationship* is discussed in relation to games as auditory displays where game sound is described as an information system, and it will not be repeated here. The *interactive relationship* is used for semantic purposes in cutscenes where it is supported by subtitles, and in this context it is used to provide updated information related to Agent 47's assignments. For instance, Agent 47 calls the agency to inform them that he has found the mutilated body of a girl he was supposed to bring out alive. Since he has not been able to fulfil the mission in the intended way, he calls the agency to get an update, and the conversation provides the player with new information about what the objective of the scenario is. It seems that the voice is not needed in this example since the information is already provided in writing, since easier for the players to fully understand the objectives when they are able to carefully read through it than if they have to listen to a recording. However, the reason why the information is also provided by the use of voice is that the player should get an increased sense of presence in the scenario. The characters seem more alive, and the setting seems more believable when language is actually spoken.

When moving on to music, we see that it plays a different part in *HC*. As we have seen above, music is often connected to specific events, and it is therefore possible to argue that it supports the *indicative relationship*. However, in these cases, it is what the music means that is of importance, and thus, we may argue that it is the *indicative relationship* at work for semantic purposes. The music is used for specific communicative purposes and its meaning has to be learned by the player, who otherwise will interpret it as non-informative atmospheric music. Besides, it may seem absurd to say that this music demonstrates the use of the *indicative relationship* when it is not connected to the sources diegetically or in a perceived naturalistic manner. However, there is a second use of music in this game, and that is using music to provide moods. In this case, the *reflexive relationship* is at work. The music in *HC* vacillates between providing information and not. When it is informative, it becomes melodious and up-beat, but in other situations, the music is ambient and non-melodious. It also merges with ambient environmental sounds, and works to give the player the feeling of unease, and the player normally does not listen actively to this music.

In *W3*, sound is used primarily to give information related to specific objects and events (*indicative relationship*), but sound is also used for mood enhancing purposes (*reflexive relationship*) as well as for presenting semantic information (*interactive relationship*). These three are very closely related in this game, since semantic information often is connected to specific events, and since sounds connected to information about sources are also loaded with atmospheric value. While the *indicative relationship* is used in connection

with all objects in the format of response sounds, the *interactive relationship* connected to semantic use of language is used to provide urgent information about a situation or event. Examples are the voiceover messages “our forces are under attack” and “our town is under siege”. In these cases, both sounds work as a warning, but in order to decide whether it is the forces out in the field or the buildings in the base that is in jeopardy, these messages also carry important semantic content.

Also the *reflexive relationship* work together with the *indicative*. Extradiegetic background music works for mood enhancing purposes only, and is a prime example of the pure use of this relationship. The music is not adaptive in any sense, and does not change according to a specific situation. Instead, it is connected to the specific team played. The music contributes to the atmosphere by being thematically adjusted to the specific race, i.e. the music accompanying the orcs is supported by war drums and battle shouts to enhance the sense of orcs as savage killers, while the human music is more epic in nature, and consists of more traditional symphonic music. Also, the *reflexive relationship* is used together with both the *indicative* and the *interactive relationship* in *W3*. The meeting of the three different listener-sound relationships takes place in connection with player-controlled units. As noted in the game description, all units have unique lines that they produce as responses to player commands. These are basically providing information about the status of a certain unit, but they also carry information on the semantic level which contributes a further understanding of the relative status between the units. In addition, these utterances contribute to the atmosphere of the game. Concerning the relative status between units, the different units have different utterances based on their location in the hierarchy, i.e. a worker will say utterances such as “all right” and “more work?” in an accepting, but subserviant manner, while an officer will say “ready for action!” and “you want some?” in a highly motivated and almost aggressive manner. The hero unit will mark his dominating rank in the hierarchy by stating self-reflexive comments such as “noone orders me around”, directed to the player. However, the fact that these utterances mirror stereotypes within feudal societies as well as often including intertextual references to other cultural phenomena especially within science fiction and fantasy discourse, the utterances also adds a humorous layer. In this sense, these sounds are on the surface responses that reflect the indicative relationship, but it should not be ignored that both the *interactive* and the *reflexive relationships* are present here due to the fact that the sounds also contain different kinds of information that gains specific value based on humour and hierarchy.

3.6 Games as Auditory Displays

As should be clear by now, games mix conventions from both audiovisual fiction and user interface design, and this merge has specific consequences for game audio design. This paragraph will be a theoretical overview of how game sound is utilized for usability and user interface purposes. It is important to note that in a game context, the virtual world and the usability aspects are not separate; instead sounds that seem to be diegetically motivated also have usability functions, and sounds that seem to be motivated by usability are anchored in the virtual environment.

As mentioned in the introduction, *sonification* and *auditory display studies* are applied studies of the use of sound for communicative purposes in virtual and real world environments. These studies descend from ecological psychoacoustics, which appeared as a reaction to psychoacoustics and its rigid methods of understanding and studying sound. While psychoacoustics traditionally focuses on laboratory studies of human sound apprehension, using isolated pure tones and sound bursts as stimuli, ecological psychoacoustics uses complex sound environments and more realistic listening settings in their experiments (Neuhoff 2004:2). Ecological psychoacoustics emphasises the fact that the human auditory perception has evolved to deal with sounds in context in a natural environment, and we are therefore able to process many sounds at the same time, in addition to filter out which sounds are relevant in a certain context (Neuhoff 2004:5). The studies of sonification and auditory displays take these ideas coupled with ideas from human-computer interaction studies as starting point when doing research and developing systems that support the use of sound for informative and communicative purposes. They claim that sound is especially suitable for presenting data without creating information overload for users, and it is also suitable for environments in which complex information needs to be monitored (Kramer et.al.1999), as the same time as it does not compete with the visual system. In this respect, the studies of sonification and auditory displays advocate the use of sound both in computer systems, virtual simulators, industrial settings, public areas, and private homes.

3.6.1 The Use of Audio as Sign System

It is important to emphasise that the use of sound for usability purposes is intended to be highly informational and communicative, and that sounds in this respect are representational by pointing to specific situations in the environment. Thus, auditory display and sonification projects may indeed be seen as applied sound semiotics. Peter Keller and Catherine Stevens outline a taxonomy that explains how we come to understand auditory signals (2004:3-5). The taxonomy is applied from Peircian semiotics in that it has two levels that

concern the recognition of an auditory sign and the associative process where the listener comprehends what the sign in question refers to. In this sense, they follow Peirce's understanding of a sign by separating it into three parts; the *sign itself* (auditory signal), the *interpretation* of it (the associative process), and *what it refers to* (event, activity or situation). I.e. a fire alarm is an example of a sign, which is recognized and interpreted as the sound of a fire alarm. The referent is the situation that this sound refers to; namely a fire.

Figure 4: Keller & Stevens' taxonomy of auditory signals

Following an earlier taxonomy by Familiant & Detweiler, Keller & Stevens make a classification scheme for the description of auditory signals (2005:4). As illustrated above it consists of three levels, although only two of them will be present depending on what kind of relation there is between sign and referent. The classification is described as levels because the authors assume that learning and recognition of these auditory signals happen in stages. The lowest level concerns the identification of the sound signal in question, while the higher stage involves an associative process in which the relation between sound signal and referent situation is established. The lowest level allows the listener to decide whether the sound signal used is speech, an abstract sound, or a sound recognized as a real world sound. Within auditory display studies, artificial noises and music with arbitrary or symbolic relationship to its referent are often called *earcons*, while characteristic sounds that can be recognized as sounds of corresponding real world events are called *auditory icons* (Friberg & Gärdenfors 2004; McKeown 2005; Suied et.at. 2005). Speech may either be classified as a separate category if it contains semantic information, or it may be classified as auditory icons if used as a recognizable sound without any important linguistic content.

On the higher level that concerns the user's interpretation of the auditory signal, Keller & Stevens take their starting point from Familiant & Detweiler's separation of *direct* and *indirect* references. In the case of *direct references*, there is an immediate relation between the signal and its referent, which makes the association process very simple. The relation between the two needs only to be established in order for the referent to be recognized (Keller & Stevens 2004:5). This means that when the users understand how the specific sound is

connected to the event, situation or activity, they also understand what it refers to. The relation between the signal and its referent may be measured on a continuum of *iconicity*, according to how similar the auditory signal is to its everyday counterpart. The continuum spans from *iconic* via *non-arbitrary* to *arbitrary*, in which *iconic* means that the signal is the exact same sound as is produced from the natural counterpart; *non-arbitrary* means that the relation between signal and referent is based on physical similarity, proximity, or context; and *arbitrary* means that there is a manufactured relationship between the signal and the referent (Keller & Stevens 2005:4).

Indirect references are more complex in that they concern a double referent. This reference is used when the referent is hard to portray directly, and implies understanding the reference in terms of something else, also known as a *surrogate* (Keller & Stevens 2004:4). An example is the trash can on computer desktops, which utilizes an indirect reference in both the visual and the auditory domain. The file removal programme is represented by an image of a trash can. The image of a trash can becomes then the surrogate of the image of the removal programme. However, since an image of a removal programme would be very abstract, the surrogate trash can is added instead. In the case of audio, the removal of a file is signalled by the sound of paper being crumpled. According to Keller & Stevens, the relationship between the surrogate and the referent is *metaphorical* in that it is based on equivalence (Keller & Stevens 2004:4), in this case a *functional* equivalence, since the file removal programme and the trash can both are used to dispose of unwanted material. In other cases of indirect reference, the surrogate and reference may instead have what Keller & Stevens call an *ecological* relation, which means that they are identifiable because they coexist in the world.

Keller & Stevens' taxonomy of direct and indirect references in the context of auditory displays is also relevant for computer games and computer game audio. However, it should be noted that direct and indirect references exist on two different levels in connection to computer games generally and game audio specifically. First of all, it is a question related to the relationship between the game as rule system and game as virtual world. On the level of the audiovisual surface we do in general only find direct references, although some are more arbitrary and less iconic than others. However, if we consider the rule system as the core of the game that everything on the audiovisual surface refers to, there is a double referential system. The example with the trash can as referring to the removal programme is a good way to explain this. In computer games, the whole audiovisual surface and hence the virtual world is equal to the trash can, and the game system is equal to the removal programme. In any level-based roleplaying game, this means that a certain monster has an indirect reference to getting a more powerful avatar, since killing a monster gives experience points and loot such as money and items. In *W3*, getting the building upgrade *Blacksmith* is an indirect

reference to the possibility of getting stronger units, because the *Blacksmith* provides armour and weapon upgrades. In terms of game audio, we may say that when a worker in *W3* says “ready to work” at the moment it is produced, this is an indirect reference to a higher production rate since the worker will take care of tasks such as resource collection and building. Then we are left with the idea that direct references exist on the level of the virtual world presented. To be more precise, this goes for everything that is audiovisually available to the player, and includes the graphical user interface, extradiegetic music as well as the game world environment.

I will now illustrate how game audio works on the levels of recognition and association, but since this thesis concerns the audio as communicative system on the surface level, indirect references will not be discussed in the following. Recognition of an auditory sign will be separated into two overarching categories *auditory icons* and *earcons*, which point to whether the sound signal used is a natural recognizable sound or an abstract or musical sound. The associative process concerns the listeners’ interpretation of a certain sound and goes into detail on whether or not the relationship between sound sign and referent is intuitive or not, and to which degree it is possible to understand the sign based on its relation to the referent. In this sense, *iconicity* and *direct references* will be discussed in connection with the associative process.

a) Auditory Icons & Earcons

Computer games use both earcons and auditory icons extensively. The terms refer to what kind of signs is used, and whether or not they need to be learned by the perceiver. They do not, however, state anything about their actual relation to the referent. In this respect, *auditory icons* denote the use of naturalistic sounds which do not have to be learned but are recognized intuitively, while *earcons* denote the use of non-familiar or abstract sounds such as artificial noises and short musical phrases that are not intuitively recognized and that the perceiver must learn. In computer games, auditory icons are typically utilized for all kinds of diegetic sounds, while earcons are typically used in connection with extradiegetic music and sounds connected to the graphical user interface. It is important to keep in mind that the labels *auditory icons* and *earcons* cannot be applied to natural sounds or musical sounds in a real world environment, but that the sounds must be used for a specific informative and communicative usability purpose in order to receive these labels. Also, these sounds are semiotic in that they refer to specific situations. In games, then, it is not possible to label ambient background noise as auditory icons. In general, auditory icons are nonverbal, but in the case of computer games there is an exception to this. When voices are used in order to identify human presence and not for its

semantic qualities, they have a similar status to naturalistic sounds since they do not produce detailed linguistic information. In such cases it is valid to talk about the use of voice as an auditory icon.

A problem about *earcon* as a category is the fact that as conventions become established, an earcon may glide into the category of auditory icons. An example is the use of the door bell. When it first was introduced, the sound had an arbitrary relation to the fact that someone was at the door. Now the sound has become conventionalized, and people that hear the sound will immediately recognize it as the sound of a door bell. In computer games, the same goes for sounds of magic. Strictly speaking, such sounds should be regarded as earcons, since they are not naturalistic sounds that are automatically recognized. They are artificially created and are not sounds of anything that exists in the real world. However, within the fantasy paradigm, magic does exist, and spells of magic do make sounds. In this sense, in early fantasy films, sounds of magic did work as earcons because the listener had to learn the sounds. However, today sounds of magic have become more or less conventionalized, and are recognized immediately, and on these grounds it is valid to call them auditory icons in games. This example does demonstrate a problem about labelling some sounds either auditory icons or earcons, and it is not only in the context of non-naturalistic objects and events that only exist in a specific fantasy world. This problem also puts focus on the use of music, which have been labelled earcons both in my understanding of it and in the field of auditory display. Music has universal interpretations, exemplified by descending melodies being connected to negative emotions, and ascending melodies being connected to positive emotions. Also, musical rhythm will affect a listener's sense of tempo. Thus, the difference between auditory icons and earcons is perhaps not so much whether they are intuitively recognized or not, but whether they are adopted from originally real world events, where the sound was not created for communicative purposes by human intention, or whether they are aestheticized artefacts created for a specific informative purpose.

In order to illustrate how auditory icons and earcons can be used in games, I will provide from *HC* and *W3*. In the case of auditory icons in *HC*, it could be argued that these are used for the purpose of creating an auditory sense of presence in a specific environment, but when studying them closer, we see that these have clear communicative functions. This is also the strength of auditory icons. They merge discreetly into an audiovisual virtual environment while at the same time being signals that point to specific situations. In *HC*, avatar sounds such as footsteps inform the player whether the avatar may be heard by other characters or not due to a difference in volume between running, walking, and tiptoeing. In this game, the voice is most of the time not used for its semantic qualities, but on equal terms as natural recognizable sounds, and is therefore valid to

label auditory icons. The voice is used to signal the presence of living human characters, and the player will hear shouts and short sentences in languages other than English.

W3 uses auditory icons, including speech, extensively. As in *HC*, speech is often not used for the semantic content, but as a sound of recognition with the same status as auditory icons. All units in this real-time strategy game have a short line or utterance that is produced each time they are manipulated. The content of the lines is not important in order to understand what the sound communicates, but the sound provides information to the player that the specific unit has accepted a certain command. Since each unit has individual lines, they are easily separable, which also enables the use of sound for identification purposes. A similar auditory icon not connected to speech comes from buildings. When the player selects a certain building in order to i.e. make it produce something, the building will produce a sound of recognition, in order to inform the player which building is selected. If the barracks is selected, the player will hear the sound of marching feet, and if the lumber mill is selected, the player hears the sound of a saw.

Continuing on to earcons in *HC*, we see that music is the best and most obvious example. The game utilizes music that adapts according to specific situations and locations. Although this kind of music often is added as an aesthetic feature that emphasises the dramatic development of a game, it turns out to have important informative characteristics. For instance, when the avatar enters a room that contains important items, manipulable objects, or where specific events may happen, the music will change into being more distinct. Music related to combat is also interesting in this context. When guards direct negative attention towards the avatar, the music will change into a higher-paced up-beat melody. This music will continue as long as the situation is tense or the combat is going on. What is interesting with this music, is that the melody changes according to how the player is doing in the specific situation. In this respect, the music works to give the player feedback on the combat status.

Moving on to the use of earcons in *W3*, we do not find many examples of this in the game. The best example is the sound that follows illegal actions. When the player tries to build a structure on an illegal spot, there is a disharmonic squeak signalling this. It is a purely abstract sound created for this exact purpose, and it needs to be learned since there is no equivalent to this sound in the real world.

b) Iconic & Arbitrary Sound Relations

Having provided examples of how the level of recognition is realized in the two computer games studied in this project, I will now go on to the level of associative processes. I take a look at direct references and

discuss the degree of iconicity that the game sound has to the objects and situations to which it refers. Computer games very often utilize sounds that are suitable for and have an intuitive relation to a certain object, but when taken into scrutiny we find that these sounds do not fit the specific situation to which it is assigned. In this case the sound has neither an *iconic* nor an *arbitrary* relation to the referent, but a *non-arbitrary* relation in that it lies somewhere in the middle on the continuum between iconic and noniconic.

It is very common to utilize sounds with a non-arbitrary relationship to its source in connection with computer game inventories. The inventory is the part of the interface in which the avatar holds its belongings. This is visually presented as a separate menu with slots for different items that the avatar is holding, such as potions, weapons, and other items picked up on the way, and may be compared to a bag that the avatar carries around. In *World of Warcraft* (Blizzard 2004), each item will have a generic sound in relation to the inventory, regardless of whether the item is picked up, removed, or just moved around between the different inventory slots. A similar example from *Sacred* (Ascaron 2004) is the sound produced when picking up a piece of chainmail from the ground. This action is followed by the rattling sound you would expect when an item like this was dropped to the ground, and not picked up. It is obvious that the exact same sound cannot be the result of two different actions, but in these cases, a singular sound that is easily identified as originating from a certain object is attached to it regardless of the situation. Also, a computer game inventory is a somewhat abstract idea that has no actual real-world equivalent apart from a functional similarity to bags and backpacks¹, and there is no defined or remarkable sound connected to putting items into a bag in the real world. This means that the computer game inventory needs to utilize another sound that still is easily identifiable as belonging to the object in question.

We can also find many illustrative examples of this in *W3*. Whenever the player selects a building, there will be a certain sound of recognition. In a natural context this does not make any sense, since buildings alone do not produce any sound. However, activities taking place in a building may produce sound, but in such cases, sound is produced at all times when the specific activity is going on, and not only when bystanders focus their attention on that building. In the real world environment, the sound of a lumber mill will be present throughout the process of lumber sawing, not only when a person comes over to check on the building. In the example of the barracks, this becomes even more evident. We see the connection between barracks and marching soldiers, but the idea that soldiers only march when someone inspects them, makes no sense. Both examples

¹ For instance, a game inventory may typically hold more and heavier objects compared to what could be carried in real world bags; in addition, game inventories often allow certain similar items to stack, thus taking up less space compared to real world items.

demonstrate sound linked to objects that they naturally exist together with, but the situation in which the sound appears does not seem to fit. In this sense, the sound has a non-arbitrary relation to what it refers to. Of course this use of sound could be described as a simulation of selective listening, since we tend to consciously register only what we listen actively to, but since measuring iconicity on a continuum, it is fruitful for our purpose to see this as an example of non-arbitrary iconicity.

3.6.2 Functionality: Urgency & Response

As a field that wants to increase the awareness of how sound may be used to provide information in situations where the visual system is either busy with other tasks or not available, auditory display studies is also concerned with specific informative auditory functions. The studies of auditory displays focuses on two important functions that also seem to be utilized in computer games, and these are the use of sound for *urgency purposes* and for *responsive purposes*.

An *urgency signal* provides urgent information; that is, information that the user needs to respond to or evaluate shortly, and the sound should be able to attract a person's attention as fast as possible (Guillaume et.al. 2002; McKeown 2005). Urgency signals are often alarms and other alerts pointing towards emergency situations, and they are commonly separated into different priority levels based on whether they demand immediate action or need to be evaluated only. Based on a model by R.D. Patterson, Robert D. Sorkin separates three levels of urgency based on priority, namely *highest*, *second* and *third priority*. The highest level is used in emergency situations and demands immediate response; the second refers to an abnormal condition where the purpose of the sound is to make the users immediately aware of the situation; and the third is an advisory alert that asks the users to get an overview of the situation (1987:564). It is believed that the higher the urgency level, the more distinct and informative the sound signal should be (Guillaume 2002, Sorkin 1987:563-4).

Using sound to provide *responses* to user actions is another important function. Because of lack of any physical connection to computer environments, all information from the system to the user is provided through the use of the auditory and visual perceptual systems^m. This has made the use of sound common in order to provide confirmations and other responses to user's actions in computer interfaces (Drewes et.al.2000; Friberg & Gärdenfors 2004; Heeter & Gomes 1992). Providing responses to player actions in games, the system informs the player that a certain action or command has been registered. Thus, the player does not

have to double check visually whether or not a command is being carried out. Broadly speaking, we can separate two important response sounds that are at work in most computer games, one that provides *negative feedback* and one that provides *positive feedback*. In this respect, response and urgency sounds both relate to player actions, but in a different manner in the sense that urgency sounds are *proactive* and response sounds are *reactive*. In other words, urgency sounds are sounds that demand some kind of evaluation, and ultimately action, on part of the player, while response sounds are sounds that are produced by player activity and work to ensure the player that an order has been registered.

Both the urgency and response functions are very legible in *W3* and *HC*. However, *HC* is able to separate two channels for providing urgency and response signals through the utilization of both earcons and auditory icons. The channel that utilizes auditory icons is able to merge the response and urgency functions into the natural environment of the game world, thus making the sounds seem more naturally communicative instead of communicating specifically designed alarm and feedback messages. This is emphasised by the fact that all auditory icons in *HC* are placed towards the iconic end of the continuum. The channel that utilizes earcons for urgency and responsive purposes works less transparently, since it uses changes in music to point to important locations and status in battles. In this sense the communication is more direct at the same time as the game maintains the stylistic feature adapted from film. *W3* does not utilize earcons to an extensive degree, but instead the game utilizes auditory icons and speech in a non-arbitrary way in order to put emphasis on the specific communicative function that these sounds have when providing urgency and response messages. In this respect, the sound environment of this game does not try to convince the player that the sounds are natural to the virtual world. However, the choice if non-arbitrary instead of arbitrary auditory icons maintains a close connection to the virtual world by posing as natural to the game environment.

In *W3*, the player receives a responsive sound each time he selects a unit or gives an order. There are three different kinds of responses, exemplified below: When the human peasant is selected for a task, it immediately responds with an utterance such as “yes, milord?”. This example is an *inquiry* signalling that the unit in question has been selected, but has not yet been assigned to a specific task. A positive response sound or *confirmation* can be heard when the peasant unit is given an order, and immediately responds “allright”. This is a signal to the player that a certain order will be carried out. The third response is the disharmonic squeak produced when the player try to build a structure on an illegal spot, and this is a negative response or *rejection* that informs the players that their request can not be carried out.

^m For newer game consoles, vibration feedback in the game controllers is sometimes also utilized.

HC only separates between two kinds of response functions. The response sounds in the game may be separated into positive and negative responses, which we may call *confirmations* and *rejections*. An example that demonstrates both is heard in connection with knife fights, where different diegetic sounds may be heard depending on whether the target is hit or not. When the player hits an enemy, the sound heard indicates that the knife hits something soft and the enemy screams in pain. When the player misses, the sound of a knife hitting air is heard instead. Music works in a similar manner. When the player does something in an optimal manner, there is a short musical theme or jingle as confirmative response to this. If the player on the other hand does something that puts the chances for success in jeopardy, a jingle descending in pitch will be the rejection response to that.

Concerning urgency sounds, there are two priority levels in *W3*. The highest priority messages are *warnings*, which are exemplified by the message “our forces are under attack”, which via voiceover informs the players about an event that they need to act upon. *Notifications*, on the other hand, make the player aware of events that do not demand immediate response. An example is the sound “ready to work” which signals that a unit has been produced. However, this message could also be viewed as a response since it occurs as a reaction to an action that the player performed some time earlier when he ordered the production of the specific unit. But since there is a substantial time gap between the order and the product, the primary function of the sound is to make the player aware of the fact that the unit is ready.

Concerning urgency messages in *HC*, there are also two priority levels in this game. However, whether a sound works as *warning* or *notification* may depend on the situation in this game. If the player hears the sound of a door opening offscreen, the sound will basically be a notification on the fact that someone is about to enter the room, but it may be interpreted as a warning depending on the avatar’s clothing. In this game, it is important to merge into the surroundings, and if the avatar is dressed in the same way as any other person in the specific setting, nobody will react negatively towards him, thus the sound only works as a notification of someone’s presence. If the avatar on the other hand is dressed differently from the setting’s dress code, the sound of a door will work as a warning by informing the player that someone who will react negatively on the player’s presence is about to enter.

However, as we have seen from the description of urgency messages in *HC* above, it is not always clear whether a sound actually works for response or urgency purposes in a game. Often it depends on the specific situation that the player is in at a specific moment. *W3* has also two kinds of sounds that seem to lie in between responses and urgency messages, in that they appear immediately after a certain action on part of the player, but at the same time provide information that points to future situations. An *instructional* response

provides information that the player must evaluate before he decides how to react on it. An example is the voiceover “we need more gold” which appears as an immediate response when the player tries building another structure or unit when there are not enough resources available. This sound also instructs the player to do something about the situation, either by waiting for more gold, or putting more workers to work at the gold mine. The second is the *neutral response*, which seems to provide neutral information about the situation by not demanding any reaction from the player. An example is the written message “low upkeep” accompanied by the sound of a gong. This message informs the player that there will be expenses due to a high number of units, and appears immediately after the player orders the thirty-first unit. Although the sound informs the players that they will have fewer resources, it does not demand any action on part of the player. Since both the instructional and neutral response may be said to belong both to the response and urgency camps, it is possible to regard these as representatives of a third urgency level that is given third priority.

3.7 Transdiegetic Soundsⁿ

In the previous section sound was treated as primarily a usability function for communicating specific information about actions and events, and for making the software and game system easier to use. However, in this section I will focus on game sound as a feature that defines different game spaces and the relation between them, and puts focus on games as virtual worlds in which the player acts. In a similar manner as the previous section saw game audio as a usability system feature which also supports games as virtual worlds, this section will see game audio as a virtual world feature that also supports the usability aspects.

Computer games often questions the division between what should be understood as belonging to the virtual game world, and what should be seen as messages from the system or the interface. This can be explained by the presence of a player, who is allowed to step into the virtual game world while still remaining on the outside. This positioning enables the game to transcend information from the outside and into the virtual world, thereby creating a communicate channel with the functional purpose of easing the player’s choices of actions in the game world. In order to explain how these conceptual spaces relate to each, other and how they function in computer games, this section will give an account of the concept *transdiegetic* (Jørgensen 2005, 2006, 2007). *Transdiegetic space* will temporarily be understood as the conceptual space that comes into being when communication in a game questions the boundaries of the virtual world. The concept is

ⁿ Another version of this section is published in Fetveit & Stald (eds.)(2007): *Northern Lights 2006*. Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanum.

closely related to the film theoretical ideas of *diegetic* and *extradiegetic space*, which must be elaborated on before going on to explain transdiegetic as concept.

The concept of the *diegesis* refers to the hypothetical world presented in a recounted series of events, such as films and literature (Bordwell 1985:16; Bordwell & Thompson 1997: 92; Branigan 1992: 35). In this sense, a film's characters can only be said to experience what is part of the diegesis. The diegesis is thus a concept that defines and separates spaces of action and information, and the information that is presented in the diegesis is of another kind and relevance than information presented in extradiegetic space. Related to this, film theory separates between two kinds of sound based on its relationship to the film world. This distinction is commonly known as the difference between *diegetic* and *extradiegetic* sound (Bordwell & Thompson 1997: 330). *Diegetic sound* originates from within the fictional universe, where we assume that the characters perceive the sound as natural to that world, while *extradiegetic sound* is a commenting aesthetic feature with no direct connection to an actual source within the fictional universe, and consequently, the characters do not seem to be able to hear it. Thus, dialogue between two characters in a film is an example of diegetic sound, while the background theme music is extradiegetic.

However, sound in computer games often deviates from these categories, and the most fundamental difference between game audio and film audio is the effect that sound may have on events internal to the diegesis. In films only diegetic sound has the potential to influence the choice of actions of the film characters. In the case of extradiegetic film music, it is not regarded as part of the world presented in the film and is therefore virtually not heard by the film characters. Extradiegetic music is therefore only valuable to the audience, which has no power to utilize the extradiegetic sound for the purpose of influencing the course of action in the film. Consequently, the audience cannot warn the young girl when the music signals the presence of a murderer in a horror film. In computer games, on the contrary, extradiegetic sound may have a direct effect on what happens in the game world. The player may use information available in extradiegetic sound when evaluating the avatar's possible actions, and he may thus influence the course of action in the game. The reason for this ability is the player's dual position: Although the player is physically situated outside the game, he has the power to influence the game world through the avatar and the interface. In addition, the avatar and units controlled by the player are portrayed as actual characters within the game world. This double player position allows computer games to utilize extradiegetic sound to provide the player with information relevant for game-internal choices of actions. This leads to the interesting situation that although the game character does not hear extradiegetic sound due to its game-internal position, in effect it may react

to extradiegetic sound because of the direct control link between player and avatar. In this respect, the game character can evaluate and act upon information that it should not be able to hear.

The fact that extradiegetic sound has the power to influence diegetic action in computer games, makes it impossible to directly apply film theory's division between spaces. The distorted versions of extradiegetic and diegetic spaces will be defined as *transdiegetic*, and it is characteristic for transdiegetic sounds that they cannot be posited as clearly diegetic or extradiegetic. Instead, they seem to place themselves somewhere in between the two, either by being extradiegetic sounds that communicate to entities within the diegesis (i.e. music in *HC* that informs Agent 47 about important locations), or by being diegetic sounds that directly address external entities (i.e. when a unit in *W3* responds "all right" to the player when it is given a command). These transdiegetic sounds are central for the comprehension of the positioning of sound in computer game spaces, and work as a bridge between the game world and the player's world. In this respect, these sounds become part of the interface, and provide usability information at the same time as they are stylistically and functionally connected to the game world.

3.7.1 Branigan's Spatial Understanding of Music in Film

In order to better explain the term *transdiegesis*, we need to go deeper into film theory's understanding of the relation between diegetic and extradiegetic. As illustrated above, it is not possible to transfer these concepts directly to computer games, since there are sounds that seem to vacillate between being diegetic and extradiegetic. Edward Branigan discovered a similar problem in film theory, and describes what he calls eight levels of narration based on the space from which information can be said to originate (Branigan 1992: 86-107). He understands narrative information to belong to eight different levels on a continuum, which spans from a fictionally external category *text* to an extreme internal category consisting of a fictional character's *thought*. In between these extremes, information can be distributed to the spectator on six levels that gradually move into the fictional space of the film world and eventually into the characters' perception. However, while Branigan's overview cannot be transferred directly to games, his way of thinking is fruitful for understanding how the border between spaces is erased in games. This is especially important for the auditory dimension, which in games combines usability functions with the sense of presence in a virtual world.

Transdiegetic sound in games will be elaborated on by an explanation of Branigan's account of how sound moves between different narrative levels in film. Branigan exemplifies through his description of the opening scene of Hitchcock's *The Wrong Man* (1956), where he claims that the music can be interpreted in three

different ways related to the context (Branigan 1992: 96-7). A certain piece of music plays during the film's initial credit sequence that presents title, actors and creators. Due to its simultaneous presence to the credits, the music is likely to be interpreted as support for the credit sequence. In this sense, it seems to frame the film story and may be seen as a statement about the fiction that refers to the film as fictional (1992: 88). According to Branigan, this interpretation makes the music *extrafictional*. However, while the credits are being shown and this specific piece of music is being played, the camera moves from the exterior of a nightclub and inside, where we see different clips from different situations, suggesting that we see excerpts from the whole evening at the nightclub. In Branigan's view, the new experience of the music provides us with a new understanding of it. The music becomes typical for an evening at the nightclub, and should therefore be seen as *extradiegetic* since it is only an example of the kind of music that would be played at this club, and not the actual music heard at the club. Only the spectators will hear the music in this exact form, while people at this club will hear specific music at specific times (1992:88). However, the music continues as the credits fade out, and the camera pans towards a band on stage playing this piece of music, underlining that the music we hear is *diegetic*. This is also emphasized by the fact that it stops when the band stops playing (Branigan 1992: 97).

It is the different contexts that enable the same piece of music to have different roles in respect to the spectator's experience, and the reason why the music so easily can change spatial status is that we create hypotheses about the meaning of the music related to the filmic context on screen (Branigan 1992:97). I would now like to discuss computer game audio in the light of Branigan's concepts in order to demonstrate that the traditional way of separating conceptual spaces in films is inaccurate in connection with games. This discussion will be the starting point for an understanding of the concept of the *transdiegetic*, and why this is an important concept for understanding spatial information in computer games in general, and for understanding computer game audio in particular.

3.7.2 Diegetic & Extradiegetic Spaces in Games

While Bordwell & Thompson's separation between diegetic and extradiegetic sound puts emphasis on the extradiegetic as being everything that is part of the presentation but not part of the film world, Branigan divides this category further into the *extrafictional* and the *extradiegetic*. In his view, the extradiegetic is related to the diegesis, but it is not experienced in this format by the characters in the fictional world. Extrafictional sound, on the other hand, is posited outside the portrayed reality and allows statements about the diegesis as fictional (Branigan 1992: 88-9).

When talking about game sound, we may say that sound appearing in the start menu of a game is what Branigan would call *extrafictional*. This means that the sound is not part of the game world, but instead part of the frame that surrounds the game space and presents the game as a product in a similar way to the credit sequence in a film. In a game, the start menu allows the user to select a new or previously saved game, and lets the player configure graphics, controller, and sound settings. This start menu has sounds that work as responses on the choices the users make, such as the sound of a click when the users highlight either of the options available, and when they actually select something. This menu will often also be accompanied by music, in a similar manner to Branigan's description of extrafictional music in *The Wrong Man*.

What is typical for *extradiegetic sounds* is that they are perceived as having no source in the presented universe. In this sense, *extradiegetic sounds* in computer games should be understood as sounds that do not exist in the presented universe, and consequently, that characters in that world cannot hear them. Still, they do often in some respect concern specific situations in the game universe. Extradiegetic sounds in games may be separated into different types of sounds: As with film, games often include background music and voiceover speech. Unique to computer games, however, are the sounds connected to the graphical user interface. An interesting feature of all types of extradiegetic sounds is that they often tend to disturb the traditional concept of extradiegetic space. Voiceover speech typically disturbs the notion of the extradiegetic by bringing information about dangerous situations that the player must evaluate. An example from *W3* is the disembodied voice that warns the player that "our forces are under attack". This sound has no source in the game world – that is, no specific character can be seen making the announcement – but it still has a clear and direct relation to events within the game world.

In the case of the background music, it may be clearly extradiegetic in some situations, while in other situations it seems to provide information relevant to the player's choice of actions in the diegesis. In *W3* the background music is not influenced by events or actions in the game environment, but has the role as a background feature that stylistically fits the game and works simply as a mood enhancer. This means that the music does not question its own role as extradiegetic. In *HC*, on the other hand, music adapts to certain situations, thereby having a clear relation to in-game events. In this sense, the music is situated as external to the game world, but by being adaptive, it provides information relevant to the player's choice of actions. Although it is the player and not the avatar as a character in the game world who hears the music, it questions the concept of extradiegesis by affecting the behaviour of the avatar who acts according to information it could not have received from the game world. A similar problem is found in connection with ambient music. When music merges with environmental sounds, it seems to give the impression of originating from the game

universe, although it technically is not. The scenario called “The Shalebridge Cradle” in *Thief III: Deadly Shadows* (Ion Storm 2004) describes a haunted and empty mansion formerly used as an asylum and an orphanage. The ambient music includes the sound of reverberating children’s laughter played backwards, and the player is left to ask whether this can be interpreted as the actual sound of a haunted house.

When talking about user interface sounds, we see that these can also disturb the understanding of extradiegetic as that which exists outside the game world. A good example is inventory sounds, which is traditionally presented as a separate menu with slots for different items that the avatar is holding. Each time an item is placed in or removed from the inventory, a sound is heard in response. The items are clearly part of the game world since their origin is in that world, and they can be used in the game world, but what about the inventory? And what about the sounds accompanying all actions related to it? Typically, there is a boiling sound from any potion added to or removed from the inventory, and this can hardly be viewed as a naturalistic sound for adding or removing an item from a bag. Instead the item and its sound seem to be somehow detached from the game world once it is added to the inventory. Obviously, this problem is not only related to sound, but to the spatial positioning of the interface in general.

Diegetic sounds in games are also subject for a similar conceptual problem as extradiegetic sounds. Diegetic sound is defined as sounds with a source within the game world. Since characters within this universe are not perceived to have any awareness of the space beyond, the only reality they know is the virtual world. Thus, diegetic sounds are those sounds that the characters would be able to hear. This typically refers to sounds connected to specific diegetic sources and it includes sounds from the avatar and other characters, and from objects and events in the game world. However, certain sounds deviate from this by being placed in the virtual world in a fashion that does not seem to be in tune with the virtual space as a conceptual frame of reference and a consistent world. An example is the use of unit voices in *W3*. These have clear diegetic sources by being connected to military units in the game, but they only speak when given a command by the player who does not exist as an entity within the game world. Obviously, the reason for this is that sound in games is used for usability purposes, but it also problematizes the concept of a consistent virtual world, since the soldiers seem to be aware of and to speak to an entity that does not exist in their world.

Ambient environmental sound effects that characterize certain locations in the game may also in some respect question the concept of diegetic sound. Some games include environmental sounds into the game in a naturalistic fashion, as is the case in the MMORPG *Lineage II: The Chaotic Chronicle* (NC Soft 2004-2006). Here every single environmental sound is defined as a sound object, which means that every single bird and every single insect we hear in the game can be listened to individually and located to a specific tree or bush.

However, when looking for what makes the sound, the player never finds a visual source. It must still be regarded as diegetic since we must assume that the fictional characters would hear the sound in this form. The far more common way of creating ambience is to create a full soundtrack for each setting that includes a mixture of environmental sounds that would typically be heard in this kind of setting. This soundtrack is then played in a loop. An example of this is found in the roleplaying game *Sacred* (Ascaron 2004), where a soundtrack consisting of domestic animals and children's laughter is played in the villages, while forest animals and wind through the trees are played when the avatar is in the forest. Since these are not sounds originating from actual sources in the game space, it is hard to assume that this is exactly what the diegetic characters hear. Thus, this kind of ambience also raises questions about diegetic space.

According to Branigan, *focalization* implies that we receive information about the diegesis through access to a fictional character's awareness of it (1992: 101). Focalization comes in degrees: in a film we may have an eyeline match with a character, which implies that we see what the characters see when they see it, but not from the exact same position. Alternatively, we may temporarily gain access to the characters' exact angle and in this sense see what they see, from the exact angle and position of that character. We may also be allowed access to the characters' inner experiences, such as thoughts, hallucinations, or dreams. This is also possible with auditory information. In computer games, this may be done to provide the player with information about damage taken by the avatar. For instance, when an avatar is hurt, the player will commonly hear the avatar moan or scream. In *HC*, the avatar's thoughts are also used as hints of how to solve a certain problem. In the start of the mission named "Deadly Cargo", the player hears the agent's voice: "Gotta find that car. Gotta keep close to it." Since the agent has no-one to speak to in this situation, and he does not seem to have the habit of speaking to himself, we must conclude that we are positioned inside his head at this point, hearing what he would be thinking as a living character in the game universe. Since this use of voice also is a system message about the objectives of the scenario masked as the character's thoughts, this also implies that the player should be thinking this – or at least act as if he were thinking this.

3.7.3 Transdiegesis as Concept

From the discussion above, we understand that the line between diegetic and extradiegetic sounds in computer games is not easy to draw. The presence of an external agent with direct access to take action in the game world contributes to this distortion by situating the player in a double role that questions the existence of a coherent game world. Below the concept *transdiegesis* will be used in order to explain the

spatial relationships in computer games. Transdiegetic sound will be further divided into two functions according to whether the sound is understood to have an internal or external source.

In the above discussion, we encountered several examples of game sounds that do not seem to fit perfectly well within its categorization as diegetic or extradiegetic. These sounds are either diegetic sounds that do not seem to have a natural relationship with their sources in the virtual world, or extradiegetic sounds have relevance to what happens within the game world. In addition, there are interface sounds that work on a level that functionally bridges the game world with the real world space of the player. These are all three versions of *transdiegetic sounds*. The transdiegesis should not be regarded as a clear-cut “space” that always is easy to identify in computer games, but rather as a *property* of many diegetic and extradiegetic sounds found in computer games. *External transdiegetic sounds* are sounds that strictly speaking must be labelled extradiegetic, but that seem to communicate with characters or address features internal to the diegesis. *Internal transdiegetic sounds* do the opposite: they have diegetic sources, but do not seem to address any other diegetic features. Instead these sounds seem to communicate directly to the player situated externally to the game in real world space. These sounds therefore seem to have some kind of self-reflexivity, where they seem to be conscious about their own existence within the game world.

Adaptive background music in computer games is typically *external transdiegetic* sounds. It does not have a perceived source within the diegesis, but provides the player with information about certain states, and the player may influence the game on the basis of this information. The music in *HC* that starts playing when the avatar enters a room of certain importance is *external transdiegetic* since it provides information about the scenario which the player can respond to. It is important to note that it is the fact that the actions of the avatar are influenced by these virtually extradiegetic sounds that makes the music externally transdiegetic. Although the player is the one who hears the music, it is the avatar’s actions within the diegetic game universe that are affected. In this sense, it is a character in the game world that indirectly reacts to a piece of extradiegetic music. In the same game, different music will play related to how the player is doing in combat. This works as external transdiegetic responses to the player’s actions. Thus, it is characteristic for external transdiegetic sounds that they work either as an urgency signal about an upcoming event or as a response to already executed actions.

Concerning the ambient sounds found in the haunted house in *Thief III*, this is also an instance of external transdiegetic sound. Strictly speaking, the ambient sounds of ghosts are extradiegetic – even if we imagine a world where ghosts do exist and may be heard, this part of the soundtrack is formally defined as music when taking a closer look in the sound and music folders of the game. However, the sound can be transdiegetic in

two respects. The sound may be interpreted as focalization, which means that the sound illustrates the fictional character's emotional state and should not be interpreted as a sound that the fictional character actually hears in the specific location. Alternatively and ultimately, the sound is uncomfortable and suggests that there are ghosts or other abominations everywhere. It contributes to Smalley's reflexive relationship by making the players a little nervous, and thus, they will move around the scenario in a careful manner. In this respect, this is an example of extradiegetic sound that affects the behaviour of the avatar.

Internal transdiegetic sounds are often heard in games where the player has no avatar, such as simulation and strategy games. The reason for this is that in the presence of an avatar, there is no need for internal transdiegetic sounds that communicate directly to the player, since the game sound has the opportunity to address the avatar instead of the player. In *W3* utterances are produced by the units in response to the player's orders, and the interesting thing in this context is that diegetic characters communicate directly to the player who is situated in real world space externally to the game universe. Although the utterances come from characters that exist as individuals in the game world, the fact that they address the player when they speak, and also speak when the player selects them, distorts their existence as pure diegetic characters. A more sophisticated utterance in connection with *internal transdiegetic sounds* comes from the warlord Arthas who is one of the strongest units in the game. When the player gives him a new order, he claims that "no-one orders me around". This statement puts even stronger emphasis on the self-reflexiveness in internal transdiegetic sounds since the unit seems to understand that he is under the command of a greater power, at the same time as he points out that as the leader of the forces, no-one else can – or should – give him orders.

I also want to point out that the use of auditory focalization in games may be an example of internal transdiegetic sound. In general, the player is not told what (if anything) goes on in the avatar's head, so when that happens, we must assume that the information has a usability purpose and therefore is addressed to the player. For instance, in *World of Warcraft* the avatar will respond with the utterance "not enough mana!" when the player tries to cast a spell of magic but the avatar does not have enough magical energy left. Although this is an online game where other players are present, they cannot hear this utterance coming from other avatars, so we must assume that this is something going on in the avatar's head and which is communicated directly to the player. This is also an excellent example that shows how the virtual world merges with system features, as this is clearly also a system message to the player.

An illustration describing transdiegetic space in relation to extradiegetic and diegetic space is found below. It shows diegetic and extradiegetic space as two separate entities divided by two transdiegetic functions. The internal transdiegetic function has game world sources but moves towards extradiegetic space by addressing

entities internal to the diegesis. Also, the external transdiegetic function points to extradiegetic sources but has game world relevance by providing information relevant for the action of diegetic entities. The border between diegetic and internal transdiegetic sound is marked by a dotted line to emphasise the diegetic nature of the sound, in the same way that the border between extradiegetic and external transdiegetic sound is dotted to emphasise the extradiegetic nature of these sounds. The dotted lines also suggest that transdiegetic spatiality does not have clear limits, but may work differently in different contexts.

Extradiegetic	Music in <i>Warcraft III</i>
Transdiegetic (external)	Adaptive music in <i>Hitman Contracts</i>
Transdiegetic (internal)	Unit voices in <i>Warcraft III</i>
Diegetic	Voice of guards in <i>Hitman Contracts</i>

Figure 5: The relation between diegetic, transdiegetic and extradiegetic sound

3.7.4 Why Transdiegetic Space?

How can we explain what is going on concerning informative spatiality in computer games? The solution lies in the fact that computer games are user-controlled systems at the same time as they are virtual worlds. As a computer-based system, computer games need to utilize the visual and auditory perceptual system for usability purposes due to the fact that the remaining perceptual systems are not available. This is especially important in relation to tactile perception. It is important that the user receives information about executed commands, as well as about specific events in the environment. Also, as virtual worlds, games try to use sounds in a manner that seems natural to the game world in question, often inspired by the film industry's use of sound. However, this unique combination between virtual world and user system is one of the primary reasons why computer game sound seems to disturb the relation between diegetic and extradiegetic space in general and sound in particular.

Thus, games as a mixture between user system and virtual world is what explains the use of transdiegetic spaces, but this does not explain how the player is able to comprehend the relationship between these two. Anne Mette Thorhauge points out that Gregory Bateson's concept of *metacommunication* may explain this (2003). Bateson uses this concept in order to explain fantasy and play as frames for communication separate from the rest of the world. During play, a separate frame of reference is established in which actions have a certain status. When animals play, both animals and watching humans understand that although this looks

similar to fighting, in this context of play it is something different (Bateson 1972: 180). The reason why we understand this complex relationship between the actions is because of our ability to engage in *metacommunication*, or in other words, communication about communication. In this process, we are able to reflect on the communication as such, and thus, we become able to focus on the context of the action. According to Thorhauge (2003), metacommunication therefore has to do with our ability to comprehend several frames of reference at the same time, and it explains why we have no problems interpreting the relationship between diegesis, interface and extradiegesis in computer games. We understand that the interface works on another level than the diegetic game action, and that diegetic game world and the interface are different frames of reference. Also, because of its functionality we understand that the interface works to connect the real world environment of the player to the diegetic space of the game, and that in the attempt of connecting the three layers – diegesis, interface, extradiegesis – a transdiegetic space comes into being. Thus, in connection to sound, when extradiegetic and diegetic sounds work transdiegetically, the player is not confused, but understands that this is a situation in which the usability function of the sound precedes sound as support for the virtual world. However, due to the fact that computer game players become familiar with the functionality, it is also possible to refer to different levels of the communication at the same time. This is what happens in connection with adaptive music that is placed extradiegetically, but still works as an urgency or response system in relation to actions and events in the diegesis.

3.8 Conclusions

This chapter has presented theoretical angles relevant for the project's view on computer game audio. The study understands modern computer game audio as an interface feature that connects the virtual world with a usability system. The virtual world works together with the usability system in order to ensure an auditory experience that enhances the sense of presence in a specific virtual environment, at the same time as it eases the usability of the system by providing information with relevance both for actions that are already performed and for upcoming choices of action. This means that the usability function of the sounds is masked by integrating the sounds into the virtual environment, and that sounds that seem to be motivated by a sense of realism also have a usability function.

The theoretical discussions have been characterized as belonging to one of two overarching themes. The first theme has concerned event structures and player action in connection with computer game audio, while the second theme has focused on the reality status of computer game worlds and especially of computer game

audio. In the case of the first theme, the fact that games in general and computer games in particular have different ways of engaging the user compared to traditional media, has guided the understanding of how sound is utilized in computer games and how it interacts with the game player. In this respect, it is important to see how development of tactics based on a growing understanding of the system makes the players understand their own role in the progression of the game. Further, in order to be able to interact with and manage this kind of system placed in a virtual environment, it is important to utilize a coherent usability system that is able to provide the player with necessary information about his own condition as well as the status of the environment. The use of sound is crucial in this respect, since it has the ability to provide information to the player without demanding visual attention. Thus, the player may register data through different perceptual systems at the same time. In this sense, sound is used as a representational system to provide information with both proactive and reactive relevance to the player, through utilizing different auditory signals. In addition to utilize the human voice to transfer specific messages, games use both *auditory icons* and *earcons*. Auditory icons contribute to establishing a credible game world by being sounds that are recognizable to the situation in question, while earcons – especially in the format of music – expand the virtual world by providing information that could not be transferred by the use of diegetic sound (Whalen 2004). When a game utilizes auditory icons with close iconicity to its referent, the sounds disguise its functional role as a signalling system. Instead they seem to appear naturally from events in the diegesis, and are therefore not referring to anything besides the specific process or event that produces it. In this sense, such game sounds are often not interpreted as functional signal sounds added for a specific purpose other than increasing the sense of presence and the feeling of realism. When the game utilizes earcons and noniconic auditory icons, on the other hand, the functional aspect is easier to discover, since the connection between the sound and the situation it refers to is less naturalistic and less intuitive.

In the case of the second theme, it has been emphasised that modern computer games are concerned with a virtual world, and that the concept of a separate game world and a simulated hypothetical reality is important. With respect to game audio, this means that sound also has the role of supporting the sense of presence in the game environment. Sound contributes to the sense of presence not only by adding a general mood to the game and to the specific scenarios, but also by implementing usability sounds into the game environment through the use of auditory icons. Also earcons may contribute to the mood of the game, especially when musical earcons are used to dramatically enhance different situations. Not to mention, sound may contribute to the sense of lifelikeness to the game environment by providing a sense of physicality to objects in the game. In this sense, usability sounds become masked as motivated by the projected virtual world. However,

although games project virtual worlds, it would be inaccurate to regard games and game audio as representations in the same manner as audiovisual fictions. Nevertheless, it has been demonstrated that game audio is used as a semiotic system in order to communicate specific information to the player. This means that the function aspect of sounds is in focus, and that the sound should be seen as referring not to corresponding real world objects or events, but to game situations.

By connecting the two roles of game audio, we get a grasp of what is the essence of this project: namely to identify and describe how game audio works with respect to the virtual world and the game system, and how this relates to the players' understanding of the relationship between game audio and their actions in the game world. This takes us on to the *transdiegetic* sounds. The function of transdiegetic sounds is to connect the atmospheric and the functional role of game audio, thereby working as an interface between the game system and the game world. Auditory icons work transdiegetically by having a defined and recognizable source in the game world, but at the same time providing the player with information relevant for the usability of the system. Earcons are transdiegetic by working the other way around. The use of artificial noises may contribute to a certain auditory message becoming very noticeable or even disturbing because of its unexpected relation to a certain source. On the other hand, the use of game music does not seem disturbing because it utilizes accepted conventions from film music and adds mood to the game. This is why the player accepts music that changes according to the situation.

It is important to see that the transdiegetic function is an overarching property of different elements in computer games. Although it is possible to argue that all games by definition are transdiegetic systems since they are user systems that exist solely on the basis of allowing the player to execute agency in a virtual environment through an interface, it should be kept in mind that computer games also utilize a range of features that support the classical division between the diegetic and the extradiegetic. A good example of purely extradiegetic sound is the use of music in *W3*. This music works for primarily atmospheric purposes, and provides no action-oriented information that would give it transdiegetic properties. Also, ambient background sounds are purely diegetic, since they appear as natural environment sounds in the game world with no specific informative qualities. Since they do not address any features external to the game world, this kind of sound has no transdiegetic quality.

The below illustrations demonstrate the functional roles of computer game audio. They are the same illustrations found above in the section on urgency and response sounds, but here they have been expanded by adding the concept of transdiegetic sound. In this respect, the illustrations present a schematic overview of

how the relationship between virtual world and user system should be understood in connection with computer game audio in *W3* and *HC*.

Response	Rejection	1) <i>Knife does not hit</i> : auditory icon (iconic) 2) <i>Descending melody</i> : earcon	1) Diegetic 2) External transdiegetic
	Confirmation	1) <i>Knife hits</i> : auditory icon (iconic) 2) <i>Ascending melody</i> : earcon	1) Diegetic 2) External transdiegetic
Urgency	Notification	1) <i>Opens door in disguise</i> : auditory icon (iconic) 2) <i>Green message (poison kills target)</i> : earcon 3) <i>Blue message (hint)</i> : earcon	1) Diegetic 2) External transdiegetic 3) External transdiegetic
	Warning	1) <i>Opens door when not in disguise</i> : auditory icon (iconic) 2) <i>Red message (guards are suspicious)</i> : earcon	1) Diegetic 2) External transdiegetic

Figure 6: Game audio as support for virtual world and user system in *Hitman Contracts*.

Response	Rejection	<i>Disharmonic squeak</i> : Earcon	External transdiegetic
	Confirmation	1) <i>Mouseclick</i> : auditory icon (iconic) 2) <i>"Allright"</i> : voice as aud. icon (non-arbitrary)	1) External transdiegetic 2) Internal transdiegetic
	Inquiry	<i>"Yes milord"</i> : voice as auditory icon (non-arbitrary)	Internal transdiegetic
Response & urgency	Neutral	<i>Gong</i> : earcon	External transdiegetic
	Instruction	<i>"We need more gold"</i> : semantic use of voice	External transdiegetic
	Notification	<i>"Work complete"</i> : semantic use of voice	Internal transdiegetic
	Warning	<i>"Our town is under attack"</i> : semantic use of voice	External transdiegetic

Figure 7: Game audio as support for virtual world and user system in *Warcraft III*.

4. Examination of Empirical Data

In this chapter and the following the empirical data of the project will be in focus. Whereas chapters 5 and 6 will concern analyses of the actual collected material, this chapter will be an introductory chapter in which I would like to discuss the methodological decisions and procedures of the project, as well as evaluate the collection of the data.

Since no close studies of the functionality of game audio have been done before, I have found it necessary to triangulate data sources and methods (Gentikow 2002:250; Patton 2002:247-248). In addition to making analyses of the games in question, two data sources have been utilized, namely players and game audio developers. As this project examines the functionality of game audio in relation to actions and events in computer games, it has been necessary to study how empirical players interpret sound in the gaming context. Also, investigating how a game audio development team understands their work and their intentions behind a specific game audio design has been another way to gain insight into the role of game audio. Two qualitative methods were utilized in the player studies. The players were observed while playing the game in question, and also subjects to a semi-structured qualitative research conversation. The members of game audio development team were subjects to qualitative interviews.

The purpose of carrying out qualitative studies in this project has been to compensate for the lack of a comprehensive theory on game audio, and to contribute to the development of an experienced-based theory of the functionality of sound in games. However, existing theories on related subjects have been taken into consideration as a starting point for these studies. The theoretical viewpoints in question have been used with the intentions of being modified into a specific theory of game audio based on the empirical work, and the role of these viewpoints is to illumine the subject matter and guide research questions. Nevertheless, these theories cannot and have not been used uncritically to describe and analyse computer game audio. Instead, they have been used as a frame of reference, and in comparative respects, in order to explain what makes computer game audio different from the use of sound in other contexts.

The research is therefore inductive by being the result of direct observation of the environment in question for the purposes of generating new theory, but it also has a deductive touch by taking into account existing theories. However, the fact that the existing theories have served as a backdrop that has cued a certain way of thinking, suggests the use of *sensitizing concepts*. Sensitizing concepts are used as starting points in research where the researcher lacks definite notions or concepts for theory development. This means that sensitizing concepts work as guidelines that provide an initial direction of the study and help the researcher

get a general idea of what may be relevant in the investigation of a certain subject (Jankowski/Wester 1991:67, Patton 2002:278). However, the idea of sensitizing concepts seems to be somewhat fuzzy. It is unclear whether they are background ideas and hypotheses used to support the collection of data (Charmaz in Bowen 2006; Patton 2002:278), or whether they are used as tools for guiding the interpretation of the data (Bowen 2006; Patton 2002:456), or whether they can be both.

This research started with the idea that sound does influence player actions, and the interview guide was based on this assumption as well as on the thought that concepts and ideas from film theory on sound and music to a certain degree could be used in an initial conversation about game audio. However, these thoughts did not materialize themselves into specific concepts or categories that guided the interviews, and may therefore be seen as sensitizing *ideas* more than *concepts*. Hence, semi-structured interviews became the most valuable format, where the informants themselves talked about what they found relevant within the borders of general themes. However, during the analyses of the collected data material, more specific concepts appeared and made the comprehension of the data and the application of existing theory easier. In this sense, we can talk about sensitizing concepts that came into being and worked as tools that guided the interpretation of the data. Also, the analyses further revealed a connection I had not been able to see before; namely that between games and auditory displays. This insight allowed me to see game audio in a different way that opened up the possibility to utilize a specific theoretical framework.

In this sense, the empirical studies and the utilization of existing theories are based on each other in the process of developing a theory of the functionality of computer game audio. The interaction between empirical data and theory has consisted of three phases. The empirical studies were carried out in the winter of 2004-2005, relatively early in the project, and consequently, they are based on early comprehensions of the theory presented in this thesis. This means that the design document for the qualitative studies were based on an early analysis of how audio related to objects in the two games in question (Stockburger 2003), as well as an understanding of sound from the perspectives of cognitive psychoacoustics (Blauert 2001, Bregman 2001, McAdams/Bigand 1993), and film theory on sound and music (Branigan 1992:86-124, Branigan 1989, Chion 1994, Gorbman 1987, Langkjær 1997, Langkjær 2000). This may also be traced in the interview guides and the transcriptions (see digital appendix), which focus on general aspects while at the same time not being biased by specific theoretical assumptions. However, the following analyses of the data reveal an issue that the theories above did not cover: namely that game audio tends to work as a user interface that supports the usability of the system, although this is often masked by the fact that the sounds have diegetic sources. This

finding opened up for including auditory display theory into the project, which provided new theoretical understanding relevant for reviewing and partly rewriting the analyses.

4.1 Selection of Informants

The qualitative studies are concerned with two games, the stealth-based action game *Hitman Contracts* (Io Interactive 2004), and the real-time strategy game *Warcraft III* (Blizzard 2002). Originally, the plan was to interview players of each game, as well as the audio development team behind each game. However, after repeated inquiries to Blizzard's office centrally as well as directly to their lead audio designer with no positive response^o, interviews with the audio team behind *W3* have been left out of the study. At this point selecting another RTS was not an option since I already had contacted the informants for *W3*. However, I did consider doing interviews with audio designers of a different RTS, but since games and game developers have individual approaches to audio, using the team behind a different game could provide misleading information. In any case, I decided that finding and contacting a third game audio development team, and preparing and doing interviews with them, would take too much time compared to the information I believed to gain from it. In addition, audio developers of a third game were not believed to provide any information that the audio development team behind *HC* could not.

Therefore, instead of discarding the interviews with the audio team behind *HC* because of this imbalance, I have chosen to utilize insights from these interviews in order to get a general understanding of how sound is implemented into computer games, what kinds of problems that occur during the development, and how these issues affect the evaluations done when deciding on a specific audio design. In this respect, the interviews with the audio team behind *HC* are relevant for understanding game audio in general. This will be supported in the analyses of the interviews with game audio designers by a focus on the generally valid aspects as well as those valid specifically for *HC*. However, it does of course have negative consequences that the analysis of *W3* is not based on direct information about evaluations and intentions behind the audio design of that game, while the analysis of *HC* is based on this kind of information. Therefore, it is also important to point out that the audio development team behind *HC* is not the only source of information used on game audio development. Also literature on game audio development has been used (Brandon 2005, Marks 2001, Sanger 2003), most

^o After 2 emails to Blizzard centrally, I received this negative reply: "Unfortunately, I am unable to provide any contact information." This led me to send 3 emails directly to Glenn Stafford, the lead audio designer behind *Warcraft III*. I got no reply to any of these inquiries.

as a background for the developer interviews, but also in order to understand the practice and theory behind game audio development in the industry.

The whole audio development team behind *HC* has been subjects to interviews in this study. Most of the individuals have been involved with the audio development on the two earlier *Hitman* games (*Hitman: Codename 47* (2000), *Hitman 2: Silent Assassin* (2002)) as well as on the recently released *Hitman Bloodmoney* (2006). The team consisted of five individuals; one *composer* who works with the musical features of the game, two *audio programmers* involved with the overall arrangement of the game soundscape and the implementation of audio into the game, and two *audio designers* who create all auditory content except music in the game. All of these are in-house employees, with the exception of the composer who lives in the US. The composer was interviewed by phone, while the remaining members of the team were interviewed individually at Io Interactive's offices in Copenhagen.

Concerning the player observations and interviews, ten individuals participated in the study. Three of these participated in the study of both games, with the result that there were altogether thirteen studies carried out, divided on seven *W3* studies and six *HC* studies. All informants were males between the age of nineteen and thirty, and had previous experience both in relation to the specific game and computer games in general (see digital appendix for details on the individual player informants). Experienced players were preferred as they have a vast knowledge of the game in question and games in general, which means that they would not need to spend time and attention on understanding the game mechanics and the interface in the same way as a novice player would. Because of this, the informants could instead focus on how sound relates to events, actions and the overall gameplay of the game in question. It was also considered to be easier to find informants that already were interested in specific games than informants with little experience with games. However, it should be noted that this is not a study of experts or the small gaming elite, but of persons that see games as their hobby and that are familiar with the use of computers and gaming environments. In this sense, they represent the average "gamer".

Further, the informants were recruited on the basis of self-selection and the snowball method. Self-selection means that the informants themselves contact the researcher on the basis of information about the project (Gentikow 2002:118), while the snowball method implies that the researchers ask already known contacts to pick additional informants among their own acquaintances (Gentikow 2002:118, Patton 2002:237). The project was announced via a range of different channels. First of all, information was distributed on thirteen

Norwegian, Danish and international web forums on gaming, computers and the specific games in question^p. Also the student mailing lists at two Danish and one Norwegian university institutions were used for recruiting purposes^q. In addition, a Norwegian high school^r and a Norwegian cybercafé^s were contacted in order to recruit informants, and I personally presented the project at a Norwegian roleplaying games convention^t. Last but not least, I utilized the snowball method in connection with my own personal network to find player informants. Of language and logistics reasons, I preferred Norwegian participants, but as I encountered problems getting enough informants, especially for the *HC* study, I decided to recruit Danish players as well.

The use of web forums, a school, and an Internet café were of meagre success. The announcements at the roleplaying games convention and via my own network were on the contrary very successful, possibly due to the fact that the informants got a name and a face to connect the research with. This may have made the informants more devoted to the project, and none of the informants acquired via the snowball method dropped out before or during the project. In comparison, of all those who signalled interest in the project by reading about it on web forums, none were actually interested in participating in person. However, the most important negative consequence of having informants who already knew about me through their acquaintances or by seeing me at the convention, was that their friendly attitude may have influenced them into having a confirmative stance towards the questions asked in the project. However, through the use of detailed and many-faceted procedure of information collection, I hope that these negative consequences have become minimal.

4.2 Procedure

4.2.1 Game Audio Designer Studies

The interviews with the game audio development team took place in December 2004 at Io Interactive's offices in Copenhagen, a month before the player studies. The only exception was the composer interview that took

^p gamer.no, games.no, gamereactor.no, gamersmix.no, itavisen.no, itpro.no, war3.no (Norwegian forums), debat.sol.dk, dr.dk/skum/debat, gamereactor.dk, gamersplace.dk, playwright.dk (Danish forums), hitmanforum.com (international forum).

^q IT University of Copenhagen, Section of Film and Media Studies at Copenhagen University, and Department of Information Science and Media Studies at the University of Bergen.

^r Årstad Videregående Skole in Bergen.

^s Cyberhouse in Bergen.

^t Regncon in Bergen.

place as a telephone interview in February 2005. The purpose of the developer interviews was to gain insight into the intentions behind game audio and its functionality, and how developers see the relationship between game audio development and the remaining parts of the game development process. The information gained was supposed to work as background for the conversation themes for the player informants.

The studies of the audio development team were semi-structured research interviews which may be described as a structured conversation with a purpose (Gentikow 2002:123-4). A range of conversation topics were prepared in advance, but the exact order of the topics was adjusted according to how the actual individual conversations developed. However, since the informants had vast knowledge of the practical work of game audio, whereas I was the exploring researcher with little knowledge about how sound design actually happens within the game industry, the informants role was to provide information about some processes that I wanted to know more about. The interviews were individual, and although the same overarching themes were present in each case, the exact topics were adjusted according to the individual informants' expertise. Each interview lasted approximately 45 minutes, and was divided into three parts, which are described below:

- 1) The session started with general questions about what information sound in general provides us with in the everyday life, and moved on to concern the relationship between game audio compared to other listening experiences. This was done in order to get insight into the background of the informants, and into how they regard game audio compared to other listening experiences. Another purpose of this topic was to get insight into the awareness and attitudes of game audio designers towards sound in everyday life.
- 2) The second part of the session concerned the audio in *HC* specifically, and the informants were asked to describe what characterizes the soundscape of the game, as well as to describe the purposes of the present sound design. This part was the most extensive, and was centred on the relationship between the game audio and the player. Although this part is clearly directed towards *HC* specifically, issues about how game audio designers want sound to affect the player is also applicable to *W3*.
- 3) The last part of the session concerned the relation between sound development and other parts of the game in the development process, and focused on when in the process the sound became part of the game design. It also concerned the cooperation between the different individuals of the audio team, as well as the cooperation between the audio team and other teams in the development process. The

purpose of this part was to gain insight into the development process as a whole, and what role audio plays in a broader perspective.

4.2.2 Player Studies

The player studies took place in January 2005, at the Department of Information Science and Media Studies, University of Bergen, with the exception of one Danish interview which took place at the Division of Film and Media Studies, Copenhagen University, in February 2005. During the planning process, I considered doing the observations and interviews in the homes of the informants, but due to technical issues, this idea was discarded. It was more important to make sure that the playing conditions were the same for all the players, and that the computer used was able to run the games during the video-capture, than making the players feel at home. Since the purpose of the project was to get insight into the relationship between game audio and player action, the player interviews must be seen as the core part of the empirical studies, and consequently, a specific interview design was developed. This design also supported the initial belief that it would be difficult to make the player informants talk about sound, not only because of their perceived inattention towards sound, but because people in general are not consciously aware of how they are affected by perceptual stimuli and are also not used to put these experiences into words.

The main part of the session consisted of a conversation with the informant, based on a recording of the playing carried out by the informant. The *W3* informants played a map named "Booty Bay" from the original *Warcraft III: Reign of Chaos* game, a map chosen because it is smaller than the average map. It would therefore be likely that during the course of the session the player would progress all the way to the last phase, which arguably was the most interesting part because it is more chaotic with a lot of sounds. The *HC* informants played the scenario "The Meat King's Party", found as the second scenario in the game. The reason for choosing this map was partly based on recommendations from one of the informants from *Io Interactive*, who saw the scenario as one where sound and music were used very consciously. Another reason for choosing this scenario was that since it is placed so early in the game, the difficulty is not too high, and it was likely that the informants had played the scenario, but not since long. This made most informants able to traverse most of the important areas in the scenario, but not flawlessly.

The player informants were subject to methodological triangulation, in which observation and semi-structured interview and conversation were in focus. Each session lasted for 60-75 minutes, and was divided into five parts, described in closer detail below:

- 1) At this point unaware of the fact that sound would be the focus of the study, the informants were introduced to the session by information about the fact that the research concerned the relationship between game audio and gameplay. They were also informed about the procedure of the session. In this introductory phase, I asked the informants general questions concerning their memory of the use of sound in the game in question, in order to attune them to give special attention to sound during the following part of the session.
- 2) The informant played a specific scenario from the game in question under my observation, and the playing was recorded by video-capture software Fraps, which enabled the recording of both sound and visuals during the progress. The recording of the session allowed the player informants to play the game the way they normally did without interruptions, and enabled them to explain their own choices on the basis of an actual play session. While the informant was playing, I acted as an observant carefully attentive to the performance of the informant, and to whether or not he seemed to be affected by the game audio. I also took notes that were formulated into questions and discussion themes during the conversation phase. These notes were added to a list of pre-planned questions or themes that would be central to the discussion in the conversational phase. The informant was allowed to play for approximately 30 minutes unless he finished the scenario earlier, and after 15-20 minutes play time all game sound was turned off. This made it possible to compare individual informants' difference in performance according to whether sound was present or absent.
- 3) After playing, the informants listened to three different sound clips from the game in question and they were asked to identify source and situation for the specific sounds. The informant was also asked to mention three auditory features he found remarkable about the game audio. The purpose of this phase was to gain insight into whether the informants could remember and understand game sounds out of context. Also, this was done in order to make the informants understand what kind of information I was interested in.
- 4) Since playing games is a very subjective experience, it is hard to say anything exact about how sound works on gameplay on the basis of observations alone. Due to this, the fourth phase was concerned with watching and discussing the capture together with the informant. This discussion concerned the sounds in the capture, what events and actions they referred to, and the informants' comprehension and experience of the specific situations in which the sounds appeared. The purpose of this part was to have a dialogue related to the actual playing in context, although in retrospect.

- 5) The last phase was a more general concluding phase, in which unclear issues were discussed, as well as the informants' understanding of how audio in the specific game differs from that in other games, as well as from other media such as the cinema.

4.3 Review of the Study

Although this study draws on a specially designed methodology, no problems were detected in relation to this design. The player studies were highly successful in the sense that all parts spawned fruitful results, and the informants had no problems putting their experiences of game audio into words. Also, the game audio developer interviews worked well as a fruitful background for deciding how to approach the player interviews. However, there were some specific events which did not turn out the way they were planned, and these will be reviewed in this paragraph.

In relation to the game audio developer interviews, there was a problem related to the microphone during one of the interviews. The 10-15 first minutes of the interview with one of the sound designers were not recorded due to this, and we had to start the session over again. The informant expressed that this was fine by him, and his new answers corresponded very much to the answer he originally gave. However, this was problematic in the sense that his second answer was not as spontaneous as the original, and he already knew what questions would be asked at the beginning of the session. Still it seems to be a problem of minor significance for the interview as a whole, and for the analysis specifically, since the content of the recorded answer was similar to the original. As long as this study was carried out for the purpose of getting knowledge about specific processes instead of studying human reactions and behaviour, this error does not have consequences for the study as a whole.

The interview with the composer also deviates from the remaining interviews by being a telephone interview, and by the fact that it lasted approximately 30 minutes due to time constraints. The fact that this interview would be carried out by telephone was already known in the planning process, and the different setting and situation for the interview was not regarded as a major problem. Since the interviews concerned insight into the process of composing for a game and not an informant's specific ways of expressing himself, doing this interview via telephone seems as an equally fruitful method as doing interviews in person. However, the shortness of the interview does have the disadvantage that it may not include the same amount of details as the other interviews. This has been taken into account by the fact that the audio programmers also were asked to elaborate on the use of music in the game.

In connection with the player studies, there were more deviations compared to the original plan. One positive deviation was related to the first interview, which originally was meant to be a pilot study to test whether the design of the session worked as intended. This study was so successful that I decided to include it in the analysis. Although this session was a little shorter than the remaining studies, the insights provided by it had the same level of relevance. There was thus no need to discard this interview when it included valuable information worth analysing.

However, there were also a couple of negative encounters. In connection with the recording of one of the conversations, the tape recorder went dead in the middle of the fifth phase of the session. Since we were in the middle of the conversation, I considered that interrupting the interview and carrying on later would ruin the informant's line of thought. Instead we utilized the voice recording function in Windows XP, which only records for 1 minute at a time. This meant that the informant could only speak for a minute at a time, which obviously created some unnatural breaks in the conversation. However, as this was in the last phase of the session where additional comments and comparative perspectives were discussed, I did not lose any important parts of this interview.

Another problem appeared during the study of the Danish player. This study was done with different equipment, and the computer used was not able to run both the game and video-capture software simultaneously without a certain visual lag. This forced us to lower the resolution as well as other visual properties of the game. Also, save game files were corrupted during the transfer between the two computers used in the empirical research, with the result that some strange non-player character reactions were discovered initially in the playing phase. I decided therefore to turn off the video-capture software after some problematic trials, and the informant were allowed to play with no capturing. However, the first faulty trials were used as a basis for our conversation, which turned out to be quite interesting since we got the opportunity to talk about an erroneous sample. Moreover, several aspects in the actual video-capture, as well as in the session that was not recorded, posed as good samples that did not differ notably from the other interview sessions. In this respect, the results spawned from this interview sample do not seem problematic compared to the rest of the interviews. Also, since the informant already was familiar with the game, and knew the specific sample scenario very well, he was able to present interesting and relevant information. An important consequence of this derogation is that much of the interview is based on the informant's general memory of earlier playing, as well as the fact that the errors distracted the focus of the conversation to a certain degree. However, as with the other informants, we were able to base the conversation in a specific game performance, which was the central aspect of the study. Also, as every game session differs, this one

was no exception. The data from this interview will be treated in the same manner as the other interviews, but a comment on the error will be made where necessary.

The last problem encountered is not connected to any deviation from the original plan, but is concerned with a shortcoming in the planning process. I mentioned above that the player informants were not informed that game audio was the specific issue for the studies. However, two of the players were acquainted with my research, but since I did specifically state during the recruitment process that the project was connected to an understanding of game playing, it is not certain how well prepared they were for talking about game audio specifically. Also, the three informants who participated as informants on both games obviously knew the whole procedure during the second session. However, it is not certain whether this affected the results in any negative manner. Although the first interview might have influenced their interpretation of the sound in the second game, this might have strengthened the interview since the informants knew exactly what kind of insight I was looking for. However, the major weakness in relation to this issue was probably the fact that the second game for all the players who played both games was *HC*. This might have caused imbalance in the sense that the informants had clearer answers in relation to *HC* than they had in relation to *W3*.

A note should also be made on the treatment of the collected data material. All conversations and interviews were manually transcribed by myself, and the informants were allowed to read through the transcriptions to verify it. Then the transcriptions were categorized according to theoretically and analytically relevant features. Concerning the video-captures of the player informants' playing sessions, these have not been formally described or analysed, although they have been carefully watched in order to support the analyses of the conversations. The reason why the video-captures have not been taken into the same degree of scrutiny, is the fact that they were not recorded for analytical purposes beyond the analytical observations made together with the informant during the conversation.

A last issue concerns the generalization value of the empirical studies, and in that respect, it should be noted that this research is not an example of *statistical generalization*, but instead a piece of *analytical generalization*. While statistical generalization enables the researcher to make assumptions about a population on the basis of empirical data collected about a larger sample of informants (Yin 2003:32), analytical generalization allows the researcher to use a particular set of results when making a general theory (Yin 2003:37). This means that statistical generalization is used when a large sample of studies points in the direction of a general truth, while analytical generalization is used when a particular study can be used to formulate a theory. Statistical generalization is recognized because it is possible to quantitatively evaluate the confidence of the data (Yin 2003:32). In the case of analytical generalization, the theory developed during the

first case is used as background for further case studies, and if the following cases support the same theory, the theory is viewed as plausible (Yin 2003:33). Statistical generalization is not possible based on this study since this project has aimed for theory generation based on case studies. But on the other hand, analytical generalization is. Also, the fact that two cases as well as triangulation of sources have been used, it is possible to claim a certain degree of plausibility related to the theory.

5 Game Audio Development

As noted in chapter 4, the developer interviews were carried out before the player interviews in order to get a better understanding of the intended purpose of the specific audio environment in the game. Another reason was to get insight into game audio development processes and to get an understanding of how developers believe game audio functions in connection to gameplay. This makes the interviews with the Io Interactive team relevant also for the interpretation of the functionality of sound in *W3*. Also, the development of the interview guides used during both *HC* and *W3* player interviews were based on these designer interviews. In this sense, this analysis will serve as a background for the player interviews, as well as a base for the outline of functionalities of sound in the two games of study.

As a general remark, the interviews with the designers are very different from the player interviews. They are closer to standard structured qualitative interviews, where all questions are planned beforehand, and the interviewees have longer uninterrupted monologues. Also, these interviews were not rooted in a specific game event in which questions were directly related. The difference in methods was based on the fact that different results were desired, and that the two groups have different qualifications for understanding the functionality of the sound.

There is a clear division between the roles of designers and programmers in the audio team. The designers are the creative force of artists who are creating the individual sounds, which then are implemented in the game by the programmers. The programmers are also responsible for the technical tools and engines used for doing this. One of the programmers also has the role as head of the team. In the case of the composer, he is not an in-house employee, but a freelancer who works on projects from Io Interactive at his office in New York. In the following, certain abbreviations are used to identify the informants. The two programmers are identified by the abbreviations *PA* and *PB*, while the two sound designers are identified by *SDA* and *SDB*. The composer is identified as *C*.

5.1 Game Audio Development as a Trade

This section examines the game audio developers' relationship to sound, and discuss how this influences the understanding of its role in computer games. Conscious awareness of sound and listening is a prerequisite when working with game audio development, and audio developers establish an analytical understanding of

the role of sound in the environment around them. One of the sound designers reports how he consciously processes the sounds in the environment around him:

“[...] Because sound interests me, I’m interested in how sound comes into being, and how it’s created. So I notice things easily. For instance, some times while walking down by the water you can clearly hear the water. But other times when walking down there you can’t hear the water. [...]” (SDB-2)¹ (quotes in original language in endnote)

The informant tends to reflect on sounds in his surroundings in order to get a deeper understanding of how sound can be utilized in computer games. He listens not only to the presence of sound and what causes it, but he listens to the quality of the sound and what makes it important for the total experience. This ability has an advantage for people working with creating credible soundscapes for virtual environments, since reduced listening (Chion 1994:27) seems to become an important tool to start off the creative process. A very special relationship is established between the person working with audio and sound in general, and developing audio for games is therefore a *trade* that demands that those working with it have a sophisticated awareness of how sound works on human beings in daily life and what kind of role it has in the environment. In this respect, game audio development follows the premises of *ecological psychoacoustics* in that it understands sound as a feature that cannot be regarded as isolated from the situations in which it appears (Neuhoff 2004:2-3).

This analytical and conscious awareness of sound is what enables the game audio developer to decide what kinds of sounds are suitable for the game, and what sounds are not. In order to avoid sounds that may cause irritation, it is important to understand the balance between a noisy soundscape and a soundscape that satisfies aesthetic and functional needs. One of the programmers states:

“[...] I’m very aware of avoiding irritation, it can often be annoying when too much sound is included, sound that’s not relevant, or that doesn’t provide the right mood. Or that just sounds bad. So if there’s anything that sounds bad, I’ll do everything to avoid including it. [...]” (PA-5)²

Examples of sounds that should be avoided are sounds that break with the situation, provide conflicting information, or otherwise create an auditory overload. The game designers should carefully select the sounds they want to add, and in some respects, a discreet soundtrack may be most effective. One of the sound designers points out that silence could also be used as a powerful rhetorical figure. He describes an example from a documentary on Danish television from the 60s, in which a WWII resistance fighter tells his story without being accompanied by any music:

“[...] There was no music at all on it, there was only his voice, [...] there was complete silence, there was a focus, respect, there was... depth in it, because you came into the core of what he really was talking about. [...]” (SDA-3b)³

Adding music to this serious interview would be a cheap way to add additional emotional content to a story that already has emotional value in itself, thereby contributing to making the theme seem less serious and

more like any other piece of television entertainment. By not having any additional sound, the interview focused on the resistance fighter's voice and what he is actually saying. Although this example is taken from a time when television as medium was young and audiovisual standards were not fully developed, the informant praises the use of the interviewee's utterance as an important message in itself that did not need additional music to be emotionally captivating. This example demonstrates that it is important for audio development professionals to understand how sound can be used and not used in different situations.

The game audio developers emphasise that it is important to have concepts about sound and listening as phenomena when working as a game audio developer. The fact that humans have selective auditory perception, commonly known as the *cocktail party effect* (Eysenck & Keane 2000:121, Langkjær 2000:101⁴), is one of the concepts pointed out as especially important. One of the audio designers mentions that although there are a lot of different sounds in the real world environment, humans seldom find this disturbing since we have the ability to filter out which sounds we want to pay attention to (SDB-3c)⁴. This ability of selective listening can be utilized in computer games in different ways. It can be imitated by the use of different volume levels, where important sounds are given a higher volume than less important or ambient sounds, and by the absence of certain sounds. Also, since we automatically filter out the sounds of lesser importance in the real world, the players will not find this difference in volume disturbing.

This point takes us on to the idea that sound can still be effective even when it does not demand attentive listening. One of the programmers believes that humans do not have the same focused attention towards auditory information that we have towards visual information (PB-2c)⁵. This is further emphasised by one of the sound designers, who points out that in the presence of physical and visual stimuli that demand a lot of attention, we lose focus on the present auditory stimuli although it still seems to work subconsciously:

“[...] If you suddenly become very scared on the street, for instance, and you start running. [...] In that kind of situation we're very visual[ly oriented], and very physical, because we can sense that we're up and running in our own body. But if someone asks you afterwards how it sounded when you were running down the street, we can't answer. [...]” (SDA-8)⁶

He compares this human property to how sound may be used in computer games, and suggests that a soundtrack does not have to demand attentive listening in order to be effective. One of the audio programmers elaborates on this idea, and points out that a good soundtrack may instead be one that communicates indirectly:

“[...] We can take the player into a mood than emphasises the situation. [...] We can present some hints, and we can also almost reward [the player] when the player has done something correctly. [...]” (PA-11)⁷

⁴ The cocktail party effect was identified by Colin Cherry at MIT 1953.

The communication may happen through hints or by emphasising a specific mood, one that supports Smalley's *reflexive relationship* that focuses on passive hearing and the emotional responses to sound. In this respect, the programmer emphasises that as developers, they should not underestimate the functional value of ambient and subtle use of sound. However, although one of the properties of sound is that it can communicate indirectly without demanding the listener's attention, it also provides information on a more direct level. The second programmer points out that sound in the real world works as a provider of both moods and information about the environment. He identifies three different roles that sound has in the real world. Sound may work as an *urgency signal* that informs "if something dangerous is going on", it may work as a *navigation and orientation tool* that enables the listener to "get a picture of the surroundings", and as a system that provides the listeners with *spatial information* by informing them "what kind of forum or context" they are currently in (PB-2a)⁸. The first programmer adds another more general function, namely that sound in the world works as attention attractor towards different features by "tell[ing] me where I am [...], whether I should be attentive towards something" (PA-2)⁹. These ideas underline that sound is valuable for different kinds of communicative purposes that may or may not speak directly to the player about the current situation.

Although sound in games is experienced in a very different setting compared to everyday life, it is important to understand the roles that sound has in the real world. The reason for this is that real world sound is an important frame of reference when game audio developers create audio for games. This point is made by one of the programmers, who elaborates that when creating game sound, the goal is to recreate how real world sound describes the surroundings and provides information about events:

"[...] We try to recreate what we hear when in everyday life. Perhaps more or less exaggerated, but... in the first place, we try to describe the surroundings in terms of sound in order to get information about what happens, where you are, and so on. At the same time we also use it to, what should I say, boost the atmosphere. [...]" (PB-7).¹⁰

This understanding is interesting since it underlines game audio as an *artefact*, which is emphasised by calling the game audio development process a process of *recreation*. The use of this term suggests that game soundscapes are imitations of natural soundscapes, and that game soundscapes are results of a selection process where the audio developer must decide what aspects of natural soundscapes that should be adopted, and what should be left out. This is further emphasised by the informant's note that game audio also exaggerates natural soundscapes. In this lies the thought that audio designers adopt sounds from natural environments, and change or configure them in order to communicate a specific meaning. In this sense, it is not realism, but credibility, that is in focus, and instead of adapting to auditory fidelity, game audio design adapts to *perceptual fidelity*. It is more important to make audio sound suitable for a specific situation than make it sound like it would in the real world. One of the programmers explains that this exaggeration is done

in order to avoid that the computer game sounds boring or like everyday life, but is careful to point out that the exaggeration is never taken too far:

“[...] In Hitman we have done a lot to make the sound fairly authentic, and we do of course try to work on it so we get the expression we want. But it happens within specific borders – it is never taken too far [...]” (PB-9).¹¹

It is crucial to find a balance where the sound seems to belong to the situation in which it is found, while still communicating a specific expression. This thought supports the idea of utilizing *auditory icons* that appear to be motivated by having a natural relationship to the virtual world while also working as usability signals.

Film sound is also a major influence when designing audio for games. However, there are certain differences between film and games that makes it impossible to directly adopt features from film sound and music realization. One of the programmers points out that in games, the player can be said to “create the soundscape when playing, [since] it changes according to what you’re doing [...]” (PA-6)¹². In other words, the player influences the actual realization of what sounds are being played since both sounds and music will adapt to the player’s actions. In terms of music, this means that the composer must create music that supports this. Since “you never know exactly when people reach different places, how much time it takes people to reach the different places” (C1-b)¹³, how long a player will spend at a certain location, or whether the player will get to a certain spot at all, it is important to create music that is not annoying after having been played repeatedly, and that may be triggered to play at very different points in time. The inspiration from film is instead on the level of rhetorical figures. One of the programmers describes how they have utilized the cinematic technique of *counterpoint*. *Counterpoint* describes a relationship between music and image, in which the image and the music seem to contain different meanings (Chion 1994:37-8). This technique has been used in the scenario “The Meat King’s Party”, where a woman is found mutilated accompanied with Paul Anka’s classic 60s love song “Put your head on my shoulder”. The informant explains:

“[...] It’s nothing you haven’t seen before, that you have a somehow macabre scenario and then the sound image doesn’t really fit. But it’s more, what should I say, to emphasise the insanity in the situation [...]” (PB-10a)¹⁴

The reason why counterpoint was successful here was because it emphasised the insanity found in the situation, and thus gave information about the murderer’s state of mind. In this sense, using a technique known from film allowed the game developers to add a very specific mood that enables the player to get a deeper understanding for the motivation behind the murder.

5.2 Sound in the Development Process

This section concerns the development process and how it affects the actual realization of sound in games. A central issue in that respect is that working with game audio development is working within a range of restrictions. Although there are also resource constraints such as time and money, the most dominating are technological constraints, which also reach into the creative and cooperative processes. One of the most important challenges in this respect is to create audio that sounds well within the limits of the allocated memory (RAM). Limited storage capacity creates a range of restrictions that makes it difficult for game audio production to conform to standards of audio fidelity. Instead games strive towards perceptual and functional fidelity. In order to create a soundtrack that does not include too few sounds to be convincing, it is common to decrease the quality of the sound files to make them fill less space instead. One of the sound designers describes this process as *down-sampling*:

“[...] Of course that means also that the sound [quality] becomes worse, and this is something we have to do in order to for instance play the music in CD-quality, and then we must have all the footstep sounds in a little lower quality. But there aren't many who can hear that [the sound quality has been decreased] when the music is playing. And this is how we're always calculating quality versus what is working. [...]” (SDA-6)¹⁵

When different layers of sound are playing simultaneously, some sounds have to be reduced in quality and size due to memory constraints. Although the average player does not generally hear that sound files are down-sampled, it is always a challenge to decide what sounds should have the quality decreased in order for the totality to sound as good as possible. As a central issue that needs to be taken into consideration during the whole process, this is a constraint that affects the audio production at all times.

However, the audio development process also includes constraints on other levels. Due to the nature of computer game development process, the game concept needs to be developed before any sound can be added. This means that it would not be fruitful to focus on game audio before central gameplay ideas and certain graphical features have been developed. In this sense, audio development becomes the disciple of gameplay and graphics development. Nevertheless, it is desired that audio should be part of the process from an early stage, and the idea during the development process is that sound should be supportive of what is going on in the game. This means that sound is not added as flavour in the end of the process to enhance the mood, but that it each sound added is evaluated for its functional value.

“[...] Well, it's a desired scenario that [audio] is there from the very beginning, but that only happens rarely. So it's something that enters some time into the process [...]. I think that it typically enters late, when we're actually started to see how the gameplay will be.” (PA-23)¹⁶

Game audio is being developed on the basis of what kind of game it is, what challenges are set up for the player, and how these are visualized in the virtual world. Before starting to develop audio for a game, there is a need to know what situations and objects will produce sound, and what moods to emphasise. Not least, the

genre of the game is an important factor. Since *Hitman Contracts* is the third game of a series, there is already a lot of information about the gameplay in the sense of what challenges the player will meet and what kind of interaction there will be between the avatar and the NPCs. This means that it has been possible to start working on the audio at a relatively early stage. In addition to creating sound objects that they already knew would be part of the game, the audio designers spent a lot of time in the early phase of the development on creating draft versions of sounds that wanted as part of the final product:

“[...] And we start focusing on features we know will be included. And we can say, we know that there should be some doors, for example. [...] And we also start developing some features, which also belongs to this job, yes, kind of, progressing, [...] become more skilled to some things, and keep our eyes open about what is going on other places.” (SDA-23)¹⁷

It is possible for the audio designers to start work on generic sounds such as the sound of doors opening and closing, footsteps, and weather effects at a quite early stage, but the audio designer above also points to another part of the job that does not result in a specific product. This is getting to know audio design and how audio is utilized in other situations, as well as experimenting with different kinds of sound systems and different potential realizations of sounds that could be added to the game at some later stage.

Due to these constraints, the actual audio development comes into the process at a relatively late stage. Although the audio team has the creative power over what sounds will be added, and how the sound objects will actually sound, the audio development is first and foremost the result of specific needs pointed out by the level designers that create the actual layout of the game world. In this sense, level designers are responsible for the quantitative audio content of the game, while the sound developers are responsible for the qualitative content of the audio files. The level designer commonly has a list of animations and objects that need audio, and the audio team works according to that scheme. In this respect, the collaboration between the audio team and the level design team is in fact an ongoing process throughout the development. One of the programmers describes it as a “ping-pong process” where the programmer implements a sound, gets feedback from the level designers, alters the sound a little, and together they finally settle for a compromise:

“[...] There’s a lot of talking back and forth, they look at the game and test play the level, does it sound the way they want it and stuff... talking about the things we would like to change. [...]” (PB-28)¹⁸

The level designers are responsible for suggesting what sounds are needed for the game, and they also have to evaluate the sounds already added by the audio programmers. In this respect, they also make an estimation of whether a sound should relate to player behaviour and events in the game in the desired manner. However, the audio team is free to suggest additional sounds whether they feel it is needed, as well as suggesting other kinds of sounds than they already have been asked to do.

Music production in *HC* is a special case, since the composer is not an in-house employee, but works freelance on projects from Io Interactive. The composer lives in New York, where he writes music for the *Hitman* games before sending the files to Io Interactive in Copenhagen, where the programmers and the level designers add the music to the game. The distance influences the possibility for day to day collaboration between the composer and the rest of the team. This may be seen as a weakness, because if broader cooperation had been possible, the music and the remaining soundscape could have been more closely integrated with each other. However, it does give the composer complete freedom to add music to situations of his own choosing, and to compose the music he feels is best. When the programmers have added the music to the game, the composer receives a playable version of the scenario including the music, which allows the composer to evaluate whether the actual result became the way he wanted it:

“[...] I say, I think we should play this kind of music here, then it’s programmed, then I receive a version of the game where I test whether I find it good or not. But well, it’s like, I come up with all the ideas to where the music should play, and then we tweak it. [...]” (C-14)¹⁹

This emphasises that although there is great distance between the composer and the rest of the audio team, this does not seem to hinder the creative process. In fact, it provides the composer with time to work on the music without pressure from programmers and level designers, and by being allowed to test play the game after the music has been implemented, it also allows him the power to decide whether the implementation has been to his satisfaction or not.

5.3 Intentions and Functions of Game Audio

When developing for computer games, the audio developers have certain ideas about the role of audio, both with respect to how it should affect the game environment and the game experience. These notions are the focus of this section, which discusses the intentions behind game soundscapes in general before moving on to see how it is realized in *HC*.

The game audio developers believe that game audio has a dual role in the sense that it should support the feeling or mood of the game environment, at the same time as it should provide some information to the player. In this sense sound works both as a usability feature and as support for the sense of presence in the game environment. According to one of the programmers, “the purpose is to tell the player what is going on, also in terms of sound, and to create an atmosphere that suits the situation [...]” (PB-21)²⁰. The player is expected to utilize auditory information when playing, and sound is viewed as a valuable system that may help the player’s performance and ability to accomplish a scenario, although it is not strictly necessary for

successful performance (PA-17-18)²¹. More specifically, it is pointed out that in addition to working as an *attention attractor* (SDB-11b)²², sound and music can be used to provide *hints, responses* (PA-11)²³, and *warnings*, as well as informing the player about *objects and events outside line of sight* (PB-14b)²⁴. In this sense, game audio is an important information system on different levels. It provides spatial information that aids the player's orientation and navigation in the game world, and it provides a sense that there is a space beyond what can be seen at any given point in time. It also works as an important usability tool that provides both proactive and reactive cues to the player.

As support for the atmosphere, sound is used to create a sense of presence in the game environment. One of the programmers explains that sound is used "in an attempt of making the player believe that he's actually present where he is [in the game][...]" (PB-19c)²⁵, and in this sense, sound is used as a tool that enables the virtual world to become alive. The composer goes further in his description of how sound supports this sense of belonging in the game environment by stating that music should add more depth to the game world, and thus make it seem more alive and dynamic. He wants to make:

"the player feel that he connects with the game, that he has some feelings for the story. [...] That suddenly all the characters and what goes on in the game, it's not something you just run through to get to the next scenario. But it's something, where you suddenly get this complete sense of being in the world. [...]" (C2)²⁶

He believes this feeling makes the players involve themselves in the game on an emotional level, and he introduces the word *immersion* to describe this engagement in the game world. However, according to his description of the experience, it seems that he talks about *presence*. Strictly speaking, *presence* and *immersion* are two different senses of belonging in the game space. The composer's description that the player gets a "complete sense of being in the world" is best suited for *presence*, which is the sense of being situated in an environment. In VE terminology, presence is understood as perceiving a different space in a way that goes beyond the limits of our sensory organs. In natural space, presence is taken for granted, but mediated presence forces an individual to perceive two environments simultaneously (Steuer 1992:75). Another way to see this is in the view of Lombard and Ditton who see presence as the user's sense that a mediated space is unmediated (Lombard & Ditton 2000). This differs from *immersion*, which is another kind of engagement in an imaginary universe, but which demand that the appreciator detaches from our world just to be submerged within the different world (Murray 1997:98-103). Immersion is often exemplified by the psychological state one enters when reading an especially engaging novel, where the reader becomes so attached to the plot, the characters and the universe that they appear as autonomous and real. The opposite of presence, the appreciator does not perceive two spaces simultaneously when immersed, but gives up the natural space in order to become deeply involved in the imaginary world. For Murray, it is important not to

break down the fourth wall-convention set up by the immersion, because then the illusion will break. Presence allows for a full awareness of two spaces simultaneously, because there is not the same kind of illusion. Many writers confuse or choose not to distinguish between the two terms when writing about experiencing imaginary worlds, but it seems fruitful to distinguish the two in computer games, or specify what sense one talks about, since these are two different modes of experience. In any respect, it seems that presence is what the composer sets as a goal when composing music for *HC*, since there is no urge for the player to get inside the game world and forget the real world around him.

However, one of the programmers emphasises that the way sound is used for atmospheric and usability purposes is dependent on genre. He describes how the use of confirmative voices of units in Io Interactive's *Freedom Fighters* (2003) not would be suitable for the *Hitman* series; because it could lead to confusion:

“[...] When you did something correctly [in *Freedom Fighters*], you heard in the background someone saying “yeah” and things like that [...]. But this would just sound wrong in a game like *Hitman*, where we perhaps should use some music. [...] (PA-12d)²⁷

A reason why different genres prefer different uses of sound may be the general style that a game tries to conform to. Relying on hints, the *Hitman* series wants to communicate in a subtle manner, and since the series is very much inspired by how films use sound, it would easily feel disturbing if the game deviated too much from the auditory expression found in films. Also, the style adopted from film is further emphasised by the focus on a central character that the player is in control of. One of the sound designers also points out that sound is a very important feature in the stealth genre since they rely on careful navigation and problem solving in an environment in which the challenges rely on not being discovered by the enemy:

“Well, *Hitman* is kind of a, well, I don't know if I can say stealth game, where you're supposed to sneak around. So it's important that the sound is there to guide the player. [...]” (SDB-14a)²⁸

Using sound as a navigation tool is a particular advantage in stealth games since discretion, hiding, and ambushing are primary challenges. In these situations, sound may be a useful information provider, such as when the player listens for enemy sounds around the corner. In this sense, sound can be used as an important information system that provides the player with knowledge about events and objects outside his line of sight.

5.3.1 The Realization of Game Audio in *Hitman Contracts*

As mentioned above, *HC* is a game that provides information to the player in a subtle manner, or through hints. The most important technique utilized for this purpose is to let music work as an informative system.

One of the programmers suggests that music may be more important than environment sounds for clear usability purposes in *HC*:

“The music is typically dependent, well, on what area you’re in. and typically dependent on whether you’re busy or not. Typically dependent on whether you just did something that was an objective in the actual scenario. But perhaps we don’t use this [technique] very much in connection with environmental sounds. [...]” (PA-19)²⁹

By this he points out that music works to provide urgency information to the player, such as responsive messages, and other kinds of meta-information about what is going on in the game environment. This is pointed out by one of the sound designers and the composer. The composer methodically describes all instances in which music is used as an informative system by adapting to the situation:

“[...] If you for instance *walk into, there’s this swimming pool in the Budapest bath hotel, then the music changes to some more relaxed sounds, swimming pool-like*, so if you go down to the pool, this guy lies in the swimming pool sleeping or floating a little, relaxing. So if you go down there, *you sneak down there and kill him, then the music changes*. Kind of to support that what you did was correct, you could say. But if at the same time, *if you try to kill him and are exposed, then the guy screams and the guards come running, and then the music changes into something more action-like* where you should be attentive, and now things are really about to happen. [...]” (C-7)(my emphasis)³⁰

In this quote, the composer describes in detail four different uses of game music in *HC*. The first example describes how the game uses *location-based adaptive music*: When entering the specific room, the player can hear the music adapting to the location, following the mood in the new area.

The next two examples include a situation in which the player tries to assassinate a person. In this situation, he may be exposed by the target, or he may not. The two different situations will start different pieces of music. If the player is not exposed, a *reward jingle* will appear as a confirmative response that underlines his successful move where he only killed the specific target without raising any attention from others. But if the target notices Agent 47, he will call the guards. This situation will start another piece of music that supports the dramatic situation. This *action-music* works as a negative response that also warns the player about approaching danger. This last piece of music also works to put the player under stress, not only because the player will have learned what the music means during the course of the game, but also because of the change in melody, tempo, and rhythm.

At another point in the interview, the composer also mentions a fourth example of adaptive music that demonstrates how objects of specific relevance have their own leitmotifs:

“[...] If you take something, if you change clothes on some of the levels for instance, for instance the first level when you take the SWAT suit on. Then the music changes.” (C-7)³¹.

When Agent 47 puts on the SWAT suit or another kind of disguise, the music will change into a theme specifically composed for this suit. This is also done in order to tell the player that the specific object is of

special relevance for the game, and that putting on the specific suit demonstrates the optimal way of solving a particular problem.

When music is used for usability purposes, it also has strong atmospheric attributes in that it communicates through moods. The purpose of this use of music is not to give the player unambiguous and clear-cut information, but to communicate through subtle changes that follow the development of the music in a consistent manner. One of the programmer points out that this use of music is

“not a defined set of rules you can look up in the manual and say that when these sounds appear, you’ve done something correctly, right. It’s something you should discover, like one does in games” (PB-15c)³².

This means that the informative function of this music is something for the player to discover through the process of playing, and until that point, the atmospheric function of music may seem more important to the novice player than the information function. The relationship between the usability and atmospheric functions of music in this respect can be further illuminated by Nico Frijda’s separation between *emotions* and *moods*. In his view, *emotions* involve a focus on a specific event or object, and that it tends to involve a notion of response to the event or object in question (1993:1-6), whereas *moods* are not focused on a specific event or object, and are fleeting in the sense that they can attach themselves to different objects in a less strict manner (1993:59). Thus, we may say that emotions may appear more suddenly in response to specific events and objects, and may therefore more directly cause an individual to react to this emotion by taking specific actions. Moods are more general, and since they are not directed towards a specific object or event, they seem to create an atmosphere or state of mind on a more overarching level. In the case of the music in *HC*, it activates both emotions and moods in the player. By being connected to usability, and consequently, to specific objects and/or events, the adaptive music is meant to activate emotions. However, until the point that the player learns the informative function of the music, the adaptive music activates moods since it puts the player into a state of mind concerning the game setting and theme. When the emotions are being activated, though, the already established mood will still follow the general understanding of the setting, thereby giving the music a dual role as provider of both emotions and moods.

The use of music for the purpose of activating moods at the same time as it activates emotions in a subtle manner, emphasises that atmospheric sound is in focus in this game. As seen above, this focus is pointed out by the informants, and it is stated that an important idea behind the soundtrack was to let it support and further emphasise the mood already hinted to in the thematic and visual aspects of the game. Words used to describe the soundscape of the game are for example “distaste, darkness, generally unpleasant” (PA-9a)³³, and “gloomy, macabre, perhaps a little morbid” (PB-10a)³⁴. One of the sound designers elaborates by stating

that creating “a somewhat dreamlike universe, where you add a lot to the canvas [...]” (SDA-11)³⁵ has been an important goal for him. A very specific mood has therefore been wanted from the developers’ perspective, and there is a belief that moods can be successfully created by audio. By describing this as “adding to the canvas”, the sound designer suggests that the dreamlike soundscape works as an added layer or a filter through which the player experiences the game. In this metaphor also lies the idea of the *added value* of sound (Chion 1994:5). Chion describes this as the informative value that sound brings to a given image in an audiovisual context, and underlines that the information provided by the sound has a tendency to be interpreted as coming from the visuals itself. In the context of the game’s dreamlike universe, the sound gives the game an extra dimension that is not possible to read from the visuals alone. This dreamlike universe is also encouraged by the fact that the game is built up as a flashback, and the dreamlike audio design also seems to have been successful as one of the players interpreted the soundscape of the game as rising from Agent 47’s mind instead of the game space (Geir 23e)³⁶.

Another technique used in support of the subtle communication and a cinematic style is to utilize sounds with a classically diegetic origin and that seem to be motivated by the sense of a lifelike game world. These sounds can be seen as symptomatic by giving the impression of arising naturally from the game universe in the sense that they appear as auditory effects of physical events. They are therefore in the Peircian sense indexical symptoms on events instead of symbolic features found in the interface, and should be classified as iconic auditory icons. Although being motivated apparently by a sense of lifelikeness, these sounds also have a functional purpose. According to one of the programmers, effect sounds contain information relevant for the player’s orientation and attention, since “the sound of doors that open and close can [...] be used by the player to be attentive towards the presence of another character in the area or whether he is dangerous or not” [...] (PB-16a)³⁷. In this sense, the player may treat this information as urgency signals of different priority levels. Related to the specific context, the player will decide whether approaching characters demand that the avatar removes his gun or tries to hide. In this context, sounds from off-screen sources are of special importance³⁸. When the source is off-screen, the only information available about that object is auditory, and sound becomes a very evident information provider. In such cases, the informative role of symptomatic sounds become less masked than in redundant cases in which the visual presence of an object alone provides enough information about the situation.

However, the use of voices is also an important method of providing information to the player in a way that seems to be motivated by a sense of a lifelike game world. In *HC*, the voice is sometimes used to provide linguistic information, but it also works as a notification system and an auditory icon that informs that NPCs

are aware and suspicious of the avatar. As we will see, the voice may also be used for atmospheric purposes. One of the programmers makes a detailed overview where he points to different ways in which voices are used in *HC*:

"[...] There's *pure information* that's just delivered on a screen accompanied by some text where also speech is added. And then there are some small film sequences where there may be some dialogue between persons, mostly also to pass on some information and to get the player into the situation. And when you're playing the level, there's some *smalltalk that the different characters say but it doesn't really mean anything*, just to in a sense create some life and some atmosphere. And there are these *exclamations that the characters produce when they see Hitman with a gun* for instance, or they find a dead person or something. And this is used to tell the player that [...] the guards have detected you. [...] Then there are also *Hitman's lines* that appear in conversation with the person or character in the game that he gets his mission from. [...] (PB-8a)(my emphasis)³⁹

From this quote we can abstract four different uses of the voice. The first is an example of the *interactive relationship*, or more precisely Chion's semantic listening, in which voices provide specific linguistic information. This may be provided in two forms, either as text supported by speech, which is found for instance in the briefing menu where Diana from the Agency supplies new missions for Agent 47; or as dialogues in cut-scenes where information is provided by what both parts in the conversation say.

A second way to use voices is for the purpose of creating a *sense of presence and making the player aware of nearby non-player characters*. This is done by letting non-player characters talk to each other, while having no important semantic content in the conversation. In this sense, the sound may work as a mood enhancer, or it may emphasise the causal relationship between the voice and the speaker by signalling the presence of other characters.

A third way is to use non-player character voices that function as *warnings* about the fact that they are aggressive towards Agent 47. In this case, shouts, screams, and other raised voices are used to signal this change in the NPC's level of attention towards the avatar. Both the second and the third uses of the voice illustrate different examples of the *indicative relationship* that focuses on listening for the cause of a certain sound instead of listening for its content.

The fourth use of voice that can be identified in the quote is *Agent 47's own voice*, for instance when receiving missions from other characters. This last use of voice is similar to the first in which semantic information is provided through the interactive relationship, but while the first is external in the sense of belonging to non-player characters, this fourth use is internal, since it is the player character's voice that is used.

The informant also mentions a fifth use of voice later which further emphasises the focus on using sound for atmospheric purposes in this game. This use is related to how technical constraints inspire a completely different use of voice. Limited storage space for sound makes it difficult to add as many parallel voices as *Interactive* often wants to do, and this problem is solved by making *voices part of the ambient background*

noises of the game. Instead of giving sounds to each object, they have chosen to create an ambient track consisting of the sound of many voices:

“[...] So... this thing about creating a large group of people standing there. Then we should cheat a little, we can perhaps for instance have a large amount of background mumbling, and then spice it up by having some understandable speech every now and then. [...]” (PB-19c)⁴⁰

In this respect, the audio developers add a new use for voices, while also being able to work their way around a problem that would decrease the spatial presence and the aliveness of non-player characters. Thus, this use of voice demonstrates the *reflexive relationship* in which moods are provided to the listener.

In this section, naturalistically motivated sound has come up several times. This is an expression of the fact that the developers want the players to get the sense of a living environment that they can believe in. In this sense we talk about trustworthiness or credibility – *perceptual fidelity*. However, as we have seen, atmosphere and usability are two sides of the same coin in this game, and it should be kept in mind that although sounds seem to be naturalistically motivated, they do not conform to standards of realism in all respects since they also need to conform to some kind of informative role. The point is not to create a soundscape that is a copy of real world soundscapes, but to focus on what is important for the specific game setting. In this sense, there is an emphasis on the role of sound in terms of usability and the overall function of the sound:

“[...] We try to make realistic how far away we can hear the sound, distance atmosphere related to reality, how far away things can be heard, and so on. [...] [Concerning voices] we do it because there's some important information, so it can't be as realistic as we perhaps wanted it. [...]” (PA-13)⁴¹

When sound contains some kind of information that the developers want to emphasise, the functionality is more important than a sense of a natural environment. Since it is important that the player receives the specific message, the sense of a naturalistic environment is pushed into the background. However, a close relationship to the game world is still kept since – in the quoted example above – the voices are still attached to sources in the game world, although the volume is distorted. This could be seen as a case in which perceptual fidelity is high, but this is only part of the truth. Since the sound provides information that is regarded as important to the player, it is not the trustworthiness of the sound as representing the game world that is in focus. Instead it is the sound's positioning in the game world related to what events it is connected to that is important. Compared to the real world, it is therefore the *functional aspects* of sound that is imperative, and we should therefore talk about *functional fidelity*.

5.4 Summary

It is obvious that game audio developers have a very attentive relationship to natural environment sounds. Since they are working with sound on a daily basis, they seem to have an increased awareness of auditory information than what most people have. They are not only aware of differences in soundscapes and its relevance for orientation as well as its informative features, but they also have a deep knowledge and experience of how sound works rhetorically to convey specific moods in perceivers. This knowledge is brought to their work with computer game audio, which they try to design as credibly and convincingly as possible. The goal is to create sound that is qualitatively as good as film sound, which is one of the greatest inspirations, but in the same way as film sound, the aim is to make the sound close to naturalistic sound. In order to open up for specific moods and communicate specific meanings, however, the audio developers exaggerate or de-emphasize audio features dependent on what the specific situation demands. The game audio developers are also aware of the challenges posed by the dual nature of games as both virtual environments and user systems, and put emphasis on creating a soundscape that supports this duality. In this sense, the focus seems to be not on perceptual fidelity, but more specifically on *functional fidelity*.

In this sense, the audio team has a greater focus on the atmospheric role of sound compared to the functional role of sound. For the game audio team, it is important to first and foremost influence the players on the level of mood, by providing them a sense of presence and an understanding for the kind of environment that Agent 47 is in. However, the focus on the atmospheric properties results in a strict division between sounds that have a perceived “naturalistic” connection to the setting by having clear diegetic sources, and background music that follows the dramatic properties of the action in the game. This has also opened the way for using sound to communicate in a discreet manner by providing the music with informative purposes such as working as a response and urgency system.

Because audio becomes part of the game development at a very late stage, we may get the impression that sound is a secondary feature that only works to confirm what is already present in the visual expression of the game. However, the audio team puts emphasis on the importance of sound, and notes that the sound in their game further emphasises the moods that are thematically present in the game concept and graphics. In this sense, sound does provide an additional layer of meaning to the game by making the moods in the game clearer. The audio team points out the late inclusion of sound in the development process as a necessity due to the nature of computer game production. Although sound is implemented at a late point, it is emphasised that this does not mean that no sound production takes place early in the development phase. Instead the

early phase of game development is a phase for creative experimentation and the making of drafts of standard sounds they already knew would be needed in the game.

6. Players' Experiences of Sound in Games

This chapter presents my analyses of the data from the conversations with and observation of computer game players. As an introductory note, all players demonstrate a thorough and sophisticated understanding of the roles of sound in games. Since the informants are experienced players with an established understanding of the challenges of the games in question, this finding supports ecological psychoacoustics in several respects. It demonstrates that existing knowledge about the environment in which auditory perception takes place enables us to easier understand and interpret the sounds we hear (McAdams & Bigand 1992:2). It also supports the view that auditory perception needs to be studied in context if one wants to understand the process (Bregman 2001:1, McAdams & Bigand 1992:5, Neuhoff 2004:1-13). However, it should be kept in mind that this study does not examine computer game players' direct experience with game sound, but that it tries to unveil the most important functionalities of game audio. In this respect, it is not their experience of sound that is studied; and neither their comprehension of their experience. Rather, it is game audio functionality that is under scrutiny, based on the players' ability to articulate their own comprehension of it.

This chapter is organized into four parts. The first two parts are analyses of the functionality of game audio in the two cases in this project, and the third part examines the players' memory of game audio and how they experience specific game sounds in isolation. The last part contains a comparative part that contrasts the functionality of audio in the two games.

The two case studies are structured around four overarching functions that were identified through the analyses of data from the conversations with and observations of computer game players, and further illuminated by existing theories. The functions have been limited to four in this study due to the fact that the project has focused on two specific games, but it is likely that further research will reveal that game audio has additional functional roles. Here I will make a short introductory outline of the different functions for pedagogical purposes:

- 1) *Usability functions* are adapted from auditory display studies and concern sounds that have a direct relation to actions in the computer game, either by being proactive or reactive. Modern games utilize this function to an extensive degree, although it is not always evident that this is the formal and intended function of the sound. This depends on how auditory icons and earcons are used and implemented in the game world.

- 2) *Orienting functions* concern information about the existence, presence, and relative location and distance of objects, events and situations in the game environment. The role of such sounds is to extend the player's visual perception by providing information about events that the visual system for different reasons cannot process. In this respect, the orienting function also has the potential to work as a control system.
- 3) *Atmospheric functions* work in a more subtle manner than the two action-oriented functions above and serve to provide moods to the game in order to increase the sense of a lifelike universe, player engagement, and the sense of presence in the game world.
- 4) *Identifying functions* are related to sound as a system of recognition. In addition to enabling the player to identify single entities, sound has the ability to imply an entity's relative value compared to other entities. In this sense sound becomes a system tool that provides the player with information about game mechanics.

It is important to note that these functions may work together. If a specific sound has a responsive function, this does not exclude the fact that it also may have important atmospheric qualities. Which of the functions that is most important at any specific time is dependent on context (Friberg & Gärdenfors 2004). Although both games in the study utilize sound for the all exemplified purposes, the two games have different ways of communicating to the player, and consequently, the functions are realized in different manners. *HC* can be seen as a concrete world since navigation, the ability to manipulate objects, and the NPCs awareness of the avatar reminds the player of the real world. *W3*, on the other hand, is abstract in the sense that the players' access is from a map view from which they work with managing a greater system. This has consequences for the realization of game audio, as we will see in the following analyses. In connection with the usability function, which is the most extensive, it is not always crystal clear whether a sound works for reactive or proactive purposes, or both. Often a sound's usability function depends on context. Because of this, it becomes difficult to separate usability functions into categories dependent on how it relates to player action. For the purpose of consistency and a clearer presentation, usability functions will be separated according to which kind of sound signal that is used. Also, as will become evident, the two games put different emphasis on different kinds of sound signal. Nevertheless, both games utilize variations of earcons, auditory icons, and the semantic use of the human voice when utilizing sound for communicative purposes.

6.1 The Functionality of Sound in Warcraft III:

6.1.1 Usability Sounds

Usability sounds are very important in *W3*. This is demonstrated by the large number of subcategories identified, and by the frequent use of non-arbitrary auditory icons and earcons that draw attention to themselves by detaching themselves to a certain degree from the consistency of the game world. Four different sound signals are used in support of usability in *W3*:

- 1) *Earcons* are signal sounds that do not have any real world counterpart, but are aestheticized artificial sounds created for specific informative purposes. In this respect, the listeners have to learn the function of before they can recognize. In *W3* these are found in connection with the graphical user interface, and in the role of negative responses and notifications.
- 2) *Non-arbitrary auditory icons* are typically response and notification sounds from units and buildings. These sounds can be recognized as having a natural connection to the source, but the situation in which they appear in the game seems to be distorted compared to how the sound and its source causally relate to each other in the real world. It is interesting to see that also voices are used for this purpose by addressing its cause instead of containing important linguistic information.
- 3) *The voice used for semantic purposes* are found in situations where specific information must be conveyed to the player. This use of voice is distinguished from the causal use by its semantic value, and by the fact that it is not connected to a specific identified source in the game world the way auditory icons are.
- 4) *Iconic auditory icons* are signal sounds that have a strong relationship to the game world by being game sounds connected to their source in a close to identical manner to their real world counterparts, or in a way that is convincing from the perspective of the fantasy world. They spring out of events in the environment and seem to be informative by default, and appear therefore as *symptoms* of something more than being designed as communicative sounds.

These different signal types will be used as point of departure for discussing the usability functions of sound in *W3*.

a) Earcons

In *W3*, earcons are used first and foremost for different *responsive purposes*, but as we will see, they are also used in connection with messages that signal low-level urgency. Starting off by discussing reactive sounds, we see that one of the earcons in this game provides *negative response* to a player action. We may call this a *rejection sound*, characterized as a response that immediately informs the players that the action they try to execute is illegal. There is only one commonly used rejection sound in the game, a squeak that appears when the player has selected a certain object, such as a building, and wants to place it in a location where this is not possible. This sound is as useful, but alien to the setting:

“[...] It’s like. I was about to say that... it’s like you derail. Or [the sound is] similar to twisting a pipe, or the wheel on the end of it, then “eech!” It’s a kind of sound that doesn’t really fit into any situation of what happens in the scenario. None of those [units] arriving will have that mechanical sound. So it is actually good, it’s good in the sense that it shows that this is something external to the scenario, not within the game itself, but outside the front.” (S25)⁴²

It is an unpleasant sound that does not seem suitable for the setting, and the use of a foreign sound that is hard to identify makes Stian interpret the sound as transdiegetic, which he points out by claiming that it seems to be “external to the scenario”, but still with relevance for a player action in the game world. He appreciates this reference to an external space, since it provides a clear indication that the action is illegal. The sound is alien to the game, and so is the action he tries to accomplish. Also, the sound distinguishes itself from other sounds in the game, and the unfamiliarity of the sound makes it very noticeable. It is also interesting to see that Stian explains the sound as an auditory icon, since he describes it as the sound heard when turning a wheel that has not been greased. Although this comment can be seen as a verbal interpretation of what he hears, and as a metaphor he uses when describing the sound, the sound could also be understood as a non-iconic auditory icon that has no relation to the game world. Regardless of how we see it, this demonstrates that it is not always easy to see the border between auditory icons and earcons, since it is possible to interpret an earcon as something one already knows from the real world.

Moving on to the graphical user interface of *W3*, we find earcons with the function of providing positive responses or *confirmations*. When the player wants to build or produce a structure, he does not select these options from the in-game building, but indirectly from buttons in the interface menu in the lower right of the screen. The sound is a small click that due to its neutrality and subtleness seems separated from the virtual world. In *W3*, these confirmative interface sounds are important because of the high pace of the game. Since it may be difficult to see whether a certain command has been carried out, it is necessary to provide information without relying on visual attention. In this situation, the use of sound provides a useful auditory response. Nils explains:

“[...] I’m moving [over the map] at a quite high pace. It’s been a long time since I played, but you see the difference when I play a lot, [the speed] is like, ratatatata. Then the sound of a click can be quite alright, just so you hear you’ve got the unit.” (N14a)⁴³

The use of sound provides a useful auditory response in this situation. Nils points out that player’s previous experience is important, since experienced players play at a high speed that does not allow for any ruptures such as visually double-checking if orders have been carried out. But would it not be possible for the game to use confirmative in-game voices or auditory icons that would be more in touch with the game setting instead in this situation? Nils rejects the idea:

“No, because... then you might believe you’ve got troops you don’t have. So the fact that it’s a neutral sound...” (N14b)⁴⁴

The neutrality of the click in these confirmations is valued because they clearly separate what already exists in the game world from what does not. Units or buildings that are not produced are not yet realized in the game, and are regarded as potentials. Thus, as long as they remain potentials available from interface, they are marked by a different confirmative sound that underlines that they are not yet part of the game world reality.

Lars, however, feels that these sounds break with the feeling of the game space:

“Well, they’re kind of annoying, I don’t think they fit in there. Well, they don’t follow the rest of the sounds in the game at all. I think it’s better to have them, than not having any sounds at all, otherwise it becomes like, “did I select anything at all?” Otherwise it becomes, “did I select anything? Yes, it is upgrading. Good”. But they could very well have had a different sound than a fucking mouse click.” (L17)⁴⁵

Lars appreciates the use of sound as a computer response, since it provides the player with information whether a certain process has started, without relying on his visual perception. But for Lars, the sound of a click also creates a disturbing rupture in the game world. The sound emphasises that the game consists of different spaces of action, and although Lars does not appreciate it, it is most likely a very conscious choice from the perspective of the designers. As Nils suggests, the sound needs to separate itself from the rest of the game space because of its potential status compared to other realized objects in the game space. To realize this as a click is therefore a way to inform the player that this belongs to the interface which is distinguished from virtual world by working as a threshold between the player and the game world. Also, interpreting the sound as a mouse click, Lars sees the sound an *auditory icon* instead of an *earcon*. This may feel disturbing for him because auditory icons in this game are clearly connected to diegetic entities and specific events in the game.

A third earcon used in *W3* is a *neutral informative response* providing information about the current upkeep. *Upkeep* denotes the cost of maintaining a certain number of units in the game. Once the upkeep limit is reached and the player orders another unit, the message “low upkeep” pops up on the screen, accompanied by a low pitch “gong” sound. This is information to the player that the normal income of gold will be lower than

if there was no upkeep. The sound is also heard when the status changes from upkeep to no upkeep (i.e. when units die). The upkeep information is regarded *neutral* since it does not seem to be negatively or positively biased by the situation, and it does not demand anything from the player. Instead it informs the player neutrally about a change in status. Although the sound is reactive by appearing immediately after a player action, it also has proactive properties by emphasising a specific cause-effect relation (the upkeep starts because the thirty-first unit is ordered). In this sense, the functionality of this message is stronger related to the *effect* of the upkeep as such: namely that the player will have less resources. This new situation immediately affects Stian's further actions:

"[...] Then I have to adjust, and be much more economical in my spending. I start calculating immediately what I can buy and what I can afford to buy and things like that. [...] When it's the other way around, like... then I'm usually only happy because I get more money. Or sometimes I'm sad when it happens, since maybe I lose a battle or something like that." (S21)⁴⁶

Stian's reaction demonstrates that although sound follows a certain player action, the message actually informs about a more meagre situation upcoming, which has certain consequences for the player's choice of actions. In this sense, the message is more like a low priority urgency signal that notifies the player about an upcoming event. It is also interesting to see that Stian reflects on getting the message "no upkeep", which tells the player that the economy is back to no extra money being spent on a large number of units. However, as the message only arrives when the player already has upkeep, it also means that the number of units has decreased, which only happens when they are killed in battle. In this respect, the "no upkeep" message is an urgency signal about the fact that the player loses units, but it also gives the player information about better economical times.

Earcons are also utilized as a *low-priority urgency signal* that notifies the player that the hero unit has gained a new level and increased its skills. The moment the hero advances from one level to another, a bright light surrounds the hero accompanied by a sound. Sverre explains that

"[...] the sound when he [gains] levels, "wewewe", [tells me that] something exciting has happened." (Sv10b)⁴⁷

This sound is a *notification* informing the player about a positive, or "exciting", event that signals that the hero becomes more powerful. As a positive marker, the sound becomes a reward more than an indication of an event that the player must evaluate. Also, the sound informs the players that they may choose a new ability for the hero to learn. In this sense the message informs the players about increased strength which may be relevant for how they choose to act.

b) Non-Arbitrary Auditory Icons

As pointed out in the introduction, *W3* utilizes two kinds of auditory icons in the service of usability. In this game, *non-arbitrary auditory icons* are used for both response and urgency purposes, and they are sounds of recognition connected to the different buildings and units. While sounds from the buildings are typically the sound of marching feet in the case of the Barracks, and cows and hens in the case of the Farm, units produce verbal statements. These verbal statements should be regarded as auditory icons since the utterances do not contain important semantic information, and are used to provide causal information instead.

When selecting and moving his units around, Anders points out very early in the interview how non-arbitrary auditory icons are used to provide two kinds of responses in relation to unit manipulation:

“[...] You have the sound of, more inquiring, like “yes - what do you want”, and more like confirmative sound, “yes – I’m doing”...” (A15a)⁴⁸

The two responses appear in different situations. The *inquiring* response appears every time the unit is selected, while the *confirmative* sound is heard each time the player clicks on a new spot to move the unit. The inquiring response informs the player that the unit is selected and available for further commands. The confirmative responses are valued as important and helpful since they mark the difference between selection and command. Without this division, the player would risk believing that a certain order is given when it is not. In this sense, the inquiry can be compared to visually highlighting or marking the player’s target, while the confirmation can be compared to movement.

Non-arbitrary auditory icons are also used together with *low level priority* messages. *Notifications* are typically heard when new units and buildings are finished. In a strict sense, these could be regarded as response sounds, since they are sounds that appear when a player-initiated activity is finished. However, due to the time difference between the initiation and accomplishment of the order, the sound’s value as a response is decreased. Instead, the function of the sound is to notify the player about a certain event. Anders points out that usability sounds are a trademark for this and other Blizzard games, and sound as notification system is the one aspect he mentions when he immediately after playing is asked what aspects of sound he found noteworthy:

“Er, that you get a sound when you start building a troop or a building or something, and then you get a sound when it’s complete. That’s very convenient to get. Because you often focus on different areas and then you hear the sound of what you just built which is ready and then you can, you go back and focus on that troop. The same goes for building and... and when you’re under attack. Then you’re notified.” (A6)⁴⁹

As a notification system, non-arbitrary auditory icons provide information about what is going on off-screen. It also allows the player to be in control of what happens outside his own visual range, and in this sense the sound works to extend the player’s visual perception. The auditory system becomes similar to a radar that

monitors what is not in the immediate presence. Anders also points out that the notification sounds work as a reminder that refreshes the player's memory of earlier orders that might have been temporarily forgotten because he is busy somewhere else:

"[...] If you're working on one part [of the map], doing many things and then you get "summoning complete" or "building complete", then perhaps you start thinking, what was that I was building which should've been finished [by now].[...]" (A16)⁵⁰

The existence of these notifications allows the player to redirect his attention to other tasks, while still not losing overview. The use of sound as notification system opens for being in control of many places at the same time, since attention is easily raised by the use of sound. Non-arbitrary auditory icons used for low priority urgency purposes may also work as a tracking system or a counter, as Richard points out. He starts the production of a number of Night Elf archers, which each one notifies the player about their completion with the utterance "I stand ready". As there are quite a few of them, and they all make the same statement during a limited time span, it becomes easy to track the production without attending visually to the actual space.

Richard explains:

"[...] When I'm doing something else I can hear, okay now they're getting piled up, as I hear each of them appear. Like "I stand ready" all the time. Then I notice, okay. Now I've heard that a few times, now I have approximately that size of army." (R16)⁵¹

In this situation, the notification sounds keep the player updated on how the army grows. This makes it easier for the players to fetch the army when it has become the right size without leaving what they are currently occupied with.

c) Semantic Use of Voice

It is noted above that the voice is used both for causal and semantic purposes in this game. The causal use is exemplified by non-arbitrary auditory icons above, while the following exemplifies how the voice is used to provide specific semantic information to the player. *W3* typically uses the voice for this purpose in connection with urgency messages.

Instructions in *W3* are responses that convey information that the player needs to evaluate before reacting to them. They serve a double function as both response and urgency signal by being played as a direct response to a player action, while also giving information about upcoming situations. Verbal instructions such as "We need more gold", "We demand additional lumber", and "Build more farms" are played in response when the player tries to order new buildings or units and the amount of resources cannot allow it. These messages inform the player about a certain state and why a certain order cannot be carried out right now, and

appear as direct responses to player commands. At the same time, these messages state a further need that demands a player response, but allow the player to evaluate how to handle this situation. Thus, they do not instruct the player to take a specific action, but allow the player to respond in a number of ways. In this sense, these sounds also work as low-priority urgency signals that inform the player of an upcoming situation: if the player is not aware of and evaluates the situation, he might have a problem quite soon. Stian describes different ways to handle instructive responses:

“Well, when I hear “build more burrows” then - it depends on when it is in the game. If it’s like here, in the development phase, then it’s, then I have to act on it at once. If I wait ten seconds, it means there are ten seconds where I can’t build more stuff. But it’s annoying that each time I hear it, it’s like, damn, now I can’t build units for a while. [...] But in the end, when I have built burrows and everything, when I have 90 [units] which is maximum... then it’s just an indication that tells me that, okay, now you’ve produced too many units, then you can just go out and slaughter some of them and hopefully you’ll also crush their base.” (S17)⁵²

The instruction is very much based on context. Stian evaluates the situation when it occurs, and chooses a follow-up action based on what phase in the game he is in. Stian describes two situations, one that concerns the development phase, and another that concerns the game at a later point in which he has maxed the number of units. In the development phase, the message is a source to stressfulness since it tells the player that the unit production rate is at a halt due to lack of buildings to house the units. It also tells the player that he is at a strategic disadvantage since no more units will be produced before this problem is solved. In this sense, it is a very critical message in the early phase. At the later phase, however, it tells him that he cannot get more units and that the only available advancement now is to use his forces to beat the other army.

Sometimes, the player does not have any realistic action to take in response to the instruction, and in such cases, the message becomes a source to annoyance. Petter has been impatient in the development phase, and has been overproducing. Now he has reached the maximum limit of how many miners can collect gold at the same time. He frowns upon the message “we need more gold”:

“Annoying! I haven’t, and I won’t receive, more gold, I think I should get a loan actually. [...] Now I have to wait for more gold, because the way it is now, a queue forms at the gold mine. So it is, like, okay, I have to wait, so I find something else, I find someone to play with. [...]” (P15)⁵³

It annoys Petter that he really cannot do much about the situation. He cannot produce more miners since he does not have gold, and he cannot increase his income since he does not have more miners. He has reached the limit of how many miners can collect gold at the same time, and his only option directly related to the situation is to wait.

Language is also used for *high level priority* purposes in *W3*. The most obvious example is the *warnings* “our town is under attack” and “our forces are under attack”. They demand immediate attention and evaluation, although it is up to the player to decide how to react. However, since warnings are communicating very clearly

with semantic information that does not allow the player to neglect it, the warnings may in some cases also provide more information than needed.

[...] If I've built a line of defence structures down on the map here, and blocked all the entrances. Then I would've seen that the attack was down there, and I would actually just ignore it. Unfortunately, defence structures are regarded as town, that's why you get that sound. [...]" (A27c)⁵⁴

Anders is a defensive player, and often experiences that warnings appear when defence structures raised to prevent attackers from coming too close to his base are under attack. Since he is very much aware that these buildings will be under attack during periods of the game, he feels that it is unnecessary to have a warning sound connected to attack on defence structures. In such cases, the warning sound becomes redundant and also annoying, since the player cannot use the sound to distinguish whether it is the defence structures or his base that is under attack. It should be mentioned that warnings also appear when the player changes focus from a battle to another part of the environment. In this situation, the warning provides increased security for the player since:

"[...] there are situations where you don't know that you're whole army is lost, and they [the enemy] still stand there striking you. [...]" (S14)⁵⁵

Here, the warning system works as a security that informs the player that his forces still are fighting when he thinks he has withdrawn them all, or all are dead. This might be important to his further progression of the game, and absence of a warning sound in such situations would likely result in annoyance for players. A system that informs about continuous attacks works as an extended control system that allows the players' overview of areas that they leave.

d) Iconic Auditory Icons

As noted above, informative sounds may also be iconic auditory icons that seem to exist as sounds occurring naturally from events in the environment. These work primarily to create a living and believable environment, and become informative on other terms than the above discussed transdiegetic sounds. Since these sounds are diegetic, the fact that they also are created for a specific communicative purpose is more hidden than with the transdiegetic sounds, which with their artificial presence are highly communicative. These sounds may often work to warn the player about situations such as fights, but it is more fruitful to talk about them on a general level as potential *attention attractors*. For example, on the video-capture we can see Anders moving over the screen towards his gold mine, but suddenly and abruptly he changes direction. He explains:

"[...] I was down here doing something, then I heard the sounds. Which made me, woops!" (A15c)⁵⁶

In this situation, the sound seems to *raise attention* about the fact that something is not the way it should be. While Anders probably expects such sounds to appear at any time due to the nature of the game, he does not know at which moments they do appear. The sound therefore comes as a surprise, as it is a disruption in how it would sound like if he was in complete control. Here the sound is a symptom of a disequilibrium as far as Anders' status is concerned.

Iconic auditory icons can also work as a *reminder* of activities happening offscreen.

“[...] If I'm out with a couple of men and my hero's hunting xp [experience points] for the next level, and I don't hear anything from the town, I would've ignored the town. Would have had like, three thousand gold and three thousand trees and five buildings.” (L18)⁵⁷

In this sense sound works as a radar that constantly reminds the player of offscreen activities, and the processes cannot be ignored as long as the player hears it. Lars also suggests that absence of such sounds would make the player feel placed inside some kind of safe bubble where the only thing that matters was what happened right now, or the actual location in focus. The lack of the ability to monitor many spaces at once would thus actually make a different game, since the need to keep the whole environment under constant surveillance is a trademark for *W3* and other real-time strategy games.

Iconic auditory icons may also be used as a system that allows the player to easier monitor what goes on in otherwise chaotic battles. Richard explains:

“[...] I recognize attack sounds and death screams to some of the units. So I notice, if I hear lots of bow things, some sounds from archers attacking, then I know they're attacking now, so if I suddenly hear the death scream to one of the heroes I think, haha. There! My archers got him.” (R27)⁵⁸

It is often very hard to see what exactly happens in a battle since there might be quite a few units from both sides fighting. While it is possible for the player to visually monitor the health level of his own units in the lower part of the screen, this does not give him overview of how the enemy is doing, or who is getting hit with what weapon or magical spell at what moment. As also Richard suggests, this is information provided by sound. In this respect, the sound provides more detailed information than the visuals can do alone.

6.1.2 Identification & Value

It has already been pointed out that sound is used as a system of recognition in the sense that each unit and building has its own distinct sound. But there is more to these sounds than the fact that they identify specific objects in the game. It also turns out that they signal the relative value of specific objects compared to other objects in the game. In addition, sound provides different meanings to the different teams, and provides personalities to the units. The voices also help some players choosing between units and heroes.

Different sound pictures follow the different kinds of teams available to the player. Each team has individual background music, in addition to the individual sounds of units, buildings and the voiceovers. Although it is easy to see the difference between the teams, each team's sound picture emphasises this and deepens the individual differences. The sound gives each team an identity that suggests what kind of people they are and how they differ from each other. In this sense, the sound provides the teams with a "feeling of culture", to paraphrase Richard, who describes the different sound pictures of three of the available teams:

"Well, when they speak [...] they get a sense of, a feeling of culture. The different races [...] have different ways of talking. And the orcs sound a little barbaric, and the humans are noble creatures that walk around and, the night elves talk in a very mysterious way... so it gets kind of, it provides atmosphere and character to the different races." (R-7)⁵⁹

The sound picture also suggests how the races presented by the different teams react to different situations and what their behaviour is like. An interesting feature in this respect is the fact that while most teams have male voices and voiceovers, the Night Elves have a female voiceover which speaks in a subtle, calm and soft way regardless of what kind of message it delivers. In this sense, the race gives the impression of having a relaxed attitude about any situation. Richard believes that the Night Elves are almost indifferent about what is going on compared to other teams:

"[...] It seems like it's not very.... "yes –we're under attack, but everything will be just fine, it doesn't matter". (laughter) While the orcs, they scream: "we're under attack!!" Like all men on guard, jumping out of their beds and "now we're going to fight". (R-8a)⁶⁰

This attitude may also to a certain degree also influence the player's behaviour in the game. According to Richard, the relaxed voices of the Night Elves do not put the player under pressure in the same way as the other teams (R-15a)⁶¹. This may have both positive and negative results: the player may be able to focus more on the game, but messages provided by a calm voice may also run the risk of seeming less urgent than messages delivered with a clearly agitated voice.

However, going to a more local perspective when studying team specific sound in *W3*, the individual voices also indicate personality, value, and function of the different units. The different voices of recognition help the player estimate the relative value of the different units. The unit hierarchy as stated by the game mechanics is in this sense reflected through the use of sound, so the player does not have to study a unit's precise abilities to know whether it is a preferable unit to bring to battle or not.

"[...] The way I've been thinking with Warcraft is that the higher unit – for instance if it is a swordsman, a knight, or a hero, the higher rank he has – the more "holier than thou" are his expressions. A peasant is like, "yes lord", while the paladin is like [...] "for king and country", the guy is totally James Bond." (L-21a)⁶²

Lars describes how peasants have the obedient voice of a servant, while the paladin's voice reflects a more important position in the hierarchy. The peasant does whatever one tells him, but what the paladin does is only for the nation and its ruler. This reflects the actual value and function of the unit in the game since the

paladin is a powerful unit fit for battle, while the peasant is a worker that builds structures and collects resources.

The use of sounds that indicate position in the hierarchy also affects the player's relationship to the different units. Since the stupidity and naivety denoted by the peon's (orcish worker unit) voice indicates lower value in the hierarchy than other units, Petter does not care very much when they die. They can be cheaply replaced compared to other, more powerful units:

"I don't really care about the peon. He is an idiot, a stupid little peasant. But I'll have greater love for a hero, or something [...] that seems more useful." (P-30b)⁶³

However, Lars does not agree with Petter here. In his view, the naivety and innocence in the workers' voices tell him that they should be protected by all means:

"The first impression is that they are really stupid, like peasants are supposed to be in these kinds of games that are not a hundred percent serious on all levels. The second thing, which is good, is that you don't want to put them directly in front of the enemy so they... in other strategy games you put the most useless troops in the front so they can be mashed. But here it's like, they are stupid and innocent, you don't want to sacrifice them."(L-11)⁶⁴

The reason for Petter and Lars' different interpretation may be explained by the fact that they play different races. Petter plays orcs, which in fantasy discourse are regarded as a simple-minded and savage race, which strength lies in the physical more than the mental capacities. Lars, on the other hand, plays humans, which are more noble and gallant like the traditional image of the heroic medieval European knight. This is also reflected in their voices. The desire to protect may also be due to the fact that the workers actually have an important role although it is a very different one compared to the military units: without the workers, structures will not be produced, and resources will not be collected.

6.1.3 Sound & Atmosphere

In *W3*, usability sounds work to provide the player with specific information about what goes on in the game world, as well as information relevant for the player's game performance. Atmospheric sounds, on the other hand, are more subtle in their communicative function, and serve to provide Nico Frijda's (1993) moods that only indirectly influence the player's behaviour in the game. This means that atmospheric sounds can influence the player's sense of presence, feeling of stress, as well as other moods. In *W3*, we can formally separate atmospheric sounds into *music* and *ambience*.

Although there are clear melodies, the music in *W3* is quite subtle in different ways. It lies in the background with no direct relevance for what happens in the game, but at some points it changes into more noticeable melodies which make the informants react. Nils describes how the music takes him into a very specific mood:

“Well, it is like this, you’re not safe. Even though it’s right at the beginning. And, well yes, it’s like, it’s just much the same as they use in *Who wants to be a Millionaire*, that heartbeat. To increase tension. [...] The tempo has a lot to do with it, but the fact that there are sounds that get a more powerful rhythm creates a little more intense feeling.” (N13)⁶⁵

Nils compares the music in *W3* with the ambient sound effects in “*Who wants to be a Millionaire*”. He has noticed that this and other television entertainment shows have ambient sound/music with an intense rhythm that creates tension in the audience. Nils finds this tension rising from the music in *W3* already from the start of the game. This fits very well with the game in general, which is high-paced and thus urges the player not to begin the game calmly if he wants to succeed.

However, the difference in melodies concerning rhythms and intensities gives the informants the impression that the music adapts to different events in the game. While it does adapt according to which team the player chooses to play, its adaptivity to other situations is not consequent. The music does not adapt to situations of danger, and it does not have the ability to work as response to player performance or as warning about upcoming dangers. However, the music seems to make Anders nervous and suspicious:

“[...] Suddenly music started playing when nothing else happened. Which made me a little suspicious, is something happening now. [...] You will most likely see that, and here – when that music appears I start looking around on the map, checking my borders.” (A24-25)⁶⁶

The music affects his behaviour, but since he does not notice any immediate danger, there is nothing directly to act upon. However, the function of the sound in this respect is to keep the player extremely aware and attentive to the sound and his own activities. Not because the music signals an actual upcoming danger, but because it gives the player an understanding of the fact that in this game, anything can happen at any time.

But not all informants are happy with this apparent overuse of music that creates suspiciousness:

“Well, it’s this subtle background music. Which probably would be damned good in a *Lord of the Rings* type of movie. But it’s not everything that works in movies that works in games. It’s very good when you have music, games where rhythm changes according to what happens in the game [...]” (L22g)

When playing computer games, Lars expects informative music that adapts to the situation. Since the music changes in intensity according to some inner musical structures instead of the game’s structure, the music works as a mood-enhancer that provides no information relevant for actions and events. In this sense the music provides false information about what is going on in the game.

However, in addition to the constant feeling of insecurity, the music adds a sense of presence in this specific fantasy environment. By adapting to night and day, it emphasises the actual feeling of a living environment in which activities of different animals affect the soundscape during the day. However, the atmosphere provided by the music does not work alone: also ambient background noises merge with the music to create a specific atmosphere.

"[...] But something I also noticed in the music, it changes between day and night [...]. Then you also have the background music, and it's like, at least some sound that... ordinary sounds that change [...], started to hear owls during the night and stuff, while during daytime there were hens and different things. So that makes a special atmosphere." (R-5)⁶⁷

What Richard here observes is *transdiegetic space* where noises from the diegetic game world are mixed with extradiegetic music in order to enhance the sense of presence while also adding a more stylistic feature that may direct the mood into a specific tendency.

The perhaps most interesting feature related to ambience is already mentioned above, where environmental noises blend into the music and create an atmospheric symbiosis. Ambient sounds in *W3* are all the natural environmental sounds that do not have a direct usability function in the game, but serve to create the feeling of a living environment. These are for example sounds of wind through the trees, and animals in the forest.

Anders underlines the atmospheric function of ambience:

"Well, birdsong and stuff are just to kind of show that... just to add more atmosphere. You notice... you also notice that, there's more absence of birdsong in a landscape like this than in a thick forest. I noticed that when I played elves for the first time, then there were much more sounds, and much more forest sounds, and you notice that they disappear the more of the forest disappears." (A43e)⁶⁸

The ambient sounds add an atmosphere, but they also follow the actual environmental features of the game space. Anders underlines that these sounds are necessary for the general sense of a living and dynamic environment, or more specifically for the player's sense of presence in the game space. However, ambient sounds are not really meant to be closely listened to, and serve the function as being unheard background sounds. This is underlined by Stian who mentions that he has a selective attention to sounds in *W3*, and he distinguishes between sounds that are important for his performance in the game from those that are not:

"Er, yes, quite standard. I'm so used to the sound that it's... But, there were quite indistinguishable sounds more than... They actually have the standard sounds. I couldn't really hear the sounds of lumbering and melting of metal and those things. So... I kind of heard just the most important, like you don't have gold and... you're building's complete. [...]"(S4)⁶⁹

Stian is quite hesitant about the environmental sounds, which he also underlines by saying that he did not really hear sounds without a direct communicative function. For him, there is a clear distinction between the informative sounds and environmental sounds, where he cognitively regards the first group as more important, and focuses his attention towards these. However, he does not articulate any specific atmospheric functions related to the ambient sound. This comes as no surprise though, since we have already seen how the ambience merges into the music and together create specific moods.

6.1.4 Sound & Orientation

Sound is also utilized to support orientation in *W3*, a role that was very fruitfully demonstrated when the informants played with the sound turned off. Since the informants played almost half the session with no sound, this is an aspect of game audio which has been illuminated quite extensively in this study. In this respect, the chapter on orientation will primarily focus on the informants' experiences of playing without sound.

The discussion of sound and orientation includes three aspects. First, I discuss what the lack of sound does to player performance and to the feeling of the game in general. In terms of orientation, the players find themselves out of control, and they also need to refocus from auditory to visual perception concerning their orientation related to activities and tasks. The second aspect concerns the informants' relation to the mini-map, and how the lack of sound influences this. The last aspect discussed here is the informants' attention and apprehension are affected by sounds and lack of sounds in *W3*.

a) Playing Without Sound

With the exception of Petter, no-one knew that the sound would be turned off in the latter part of the playing session. Petter was the very first informant coming for the session, and during the introduction to the procedure, he was told that the sound would be turned off. However, since he admitted keeping it in mind during playing and planning by getting used to looking at the mini-map, I decided not to tell any other of the players about it to keep the playing situation as ordinary as possible up until the sound was turned off. However, it came as a surprise on all other players, and their immediate reactions to this was that they thought playing without sound would be problematic. Petter describes it as being left completely in the dark (P31)⁷⁰, while Nils compares it to losing a leg (N46)⁷¹. Similarly to Petter, Anders feels as if he has become blind (A30)⁷². It is interesting to see that they use metaphors based on other perceptual systems. The visual metaphor is perhaps not unexpected, since visual perception is better developed than auditory perception for precise orientation in the world. Also, visual and auditory perception are often looked upon as complementary, so lack of one may easily lead to the conceptual exchange with the other. However, Nils compares the lack of sound to kinetic perceptions, by describing it as losing a leg, but uses the relationship between auditory and visual perception in his elaboration of the experience:

"It's like you become dimidiated because you loose half of your perceptions. Because you have sight and sound... you have like, yes. You have two senses you use mainly, which are sight and hearing. And you loose one and it has become quite vital in games. And here, it's like..." (N48)⁷³

The comparison to other perceptual features emphasises how crucial the informants find the sudden disappearance of sound. For Nils, an important perceptual feature is missing when the sound is gone, since one of the two senses through which he receives output from the game is cut off. What happens is that the interface is reduced, so the interaction between game and player becomes severely restrained. Thus, a very important feature related to player performance is taken away, and this gives an immediate sense of helplessness and lack of control. It is also interesting to see that Nils was surprised how much the absence of sound actually mattered to his performance. His hypothesis was that sound matters for the atmosphere and presence in the game, as well as the entertainment value, but not so much for actual performance:

“I knew I thought it’s duller to play without sound. But I didn’t know I would think it affected the game so much. But it’s like, I have seen people play Counter-Strike without sound and that doesn’t work. (laughter)”(N38)⁷⁴

Nils has had previous assumptions about the functionality of sound in games, but these did not include sound as important to player behaviour in strategy games. However, with shooters he has already experienced that this is an important feature. The reason for his belief that sound might not be of the same importance in *W3* may be that all informational messages are also presented in writing, and the sound may therefore on the surface feel redundant.

The game’s playability also changes when the sound is removed. Anders experienced that many distractions disappeared:

“Well... sometimes the sound can take away some of your concentration. You’re working on something and then you hear that a building you’ve been waiting for is finished, then you want to jump right to it although perhaps you should’ve done other things. So it may help to... it may be a little too much sometimes. [...]”(A39)⁷⁵

By playing *W3*, Anders has learnt that sound is important for the performance in this game. When too much information is provided through the use of sound, the player is easily saturated. Therefore the absence of sound appears for Anders as a sudden opportunity to be forced to concentrate about what is important at any given moment, instead of trying to react to all sounds that seem equally important. An overload of sound decreases the player’s ability to distinguish the most crucial pieces of information from the less crucial ones.

Stian elaborates on this by underlining that the absence of sound makes his actions more systematic:

“[...] It becomes like, you become more systematic, it becomes almost like numbers. Like, that unit fell, that unit fell, and then I lost one and stuff, it is almost no feeling behind the fact that someone’s falling.” (S36)⁷⁶

The virtual world disappears without sound, and the game becomes any kind of abstract and symbolic game board. The units lose their personality and individuality and become pawns, or in Stian’s words “numbers”. When the virtual world falls apart, the player becomes less emotionally engaged, and as a result of this, Stian feels that he becomes more systematic when playing. As also Anders suggests, it becomes easier to

concentrate on important tasks instead of being misled by distracting sounds that either communicates the individuality of the units, or informs about other upcoming situations.

b) The Mini-Map

All informants report increased use of the mini-map in the absence of sound. The mini-map is a small map placed in the lower left corner as a reference for events and locations in the game space. Usability sounds are accompanied by a blink on the mini-map indicating the exact location for the event signalled by the sound. To go directly to that location, the player may push the keyboard space button immediately after hearing the sound or seeing the mark on the mini-map. The informants report little use of the mini-map when the sound is on, but there is an increase in the utilization of it during the absence of sound. Both Anders and Lars note that in ordinary circumstances, the mini-map is used immediately after a usability sound is heard, in order to locate the event. Anders is asked how he notices a certain event, and emphasises that the sound is an attention attractor, while the mini-map works as a reference for the already noticed sound:

“Er, I notice it first and foremost by the sound in combination with the mini-map. First the sound, which indicates that something is wrong, and then I move down to the mini-map to see where.” (A22)⁷⁷

The sound works as *attractor*, a point that is quite important in *W3* since the player does not have the opportunity to paying attention to the mini-map all the time. Also, the textual messages are not always easy to notice when the player is busy. In this sense, the mini-map is not sufficient as information system, since only certain kinds of information can be found by using it. Lars notes that the mini-map is limited to information about where resources can be found and where the opponent’s base is situated, but it is not possible to get information about armies wandering about, or what kind of development process that was recently finished (L31b)⁷⁸. The mini-map is therefore not a major source for information in ordinary circumstances, but this is changed when the sound is removed. Without sound, the focus is immediately turned from the primary attention attractor which is audio, and to the secondary which is the graphical mini-map (A31a)⁷⁹. This attention shift is necessary in order to still be able to pick up information. Petter describes it as the *mini-map replacing the audio*:

“It becomes immediately important. Because, you get a graphical representation of where something is going on, in the shape of a pulsation in some colour. So it replaces the sound in many ways. Because [in the presence of sound] you would get a message telling you, hey, I’m finished working or hey, I’m here. Now I have to look at the map to see when something pulsates. [...]” (P33a)⁸⁰

In the absence of sound, the mini-map adopts the functionality of usability sounds. It is interesting that one perception replaces another, and it leads to vision getting more features to attend to than is the case when

sound is present. We may expect that it also becomes more difficult to keep track of everything that happens since vision has gotten additional unfamiliar tasks, while the auditory system is left with nothing.

c) Attention & Apprehension

What happens to the players' perception of what goes on in the game in the absence of sound? The informants report that their reaction time increases, and that certain informative messages are harder to apprehend. The player has to utilize visual perception on data that earlier would be provided through auditory information. Also, this sudden new focus is unfamiliar and contributes to decrease the player's performance. The informants are discontent about having to read messages instead of listening to them because they more often fail to notice them in the absence of sound:

"I noticed that I had to start looking much more at the messages displayed down here, and that was annoying sometimes and I didn't always notice things happening."(R26b)⁸¹

To change attention from the auditory to the visual perceptual system is disturbing for Richard, because it becomes harder to actually notice and comprehend the messages. The player has to utilize visual perception on data earlier provided through auditory information, and this sudden new focus seems unfamiliar and contributes to decrease the player's performance. Although much of the information is also provided by text, it seems harder to register these messages in the absence of sound.

"[...] Text can only, it passes quickly by. Sound can become, there you receive [the message] in another way. Your eyes cover the whole screen here, right, and you... you are active and work with it. So sound... uses a completely different perception, makes you observant in a totally different way than if it were only a small text down there I wouldn't notice if I was paying attention to those." (P27)⁸²

Petter tries to explain why it becomes more difficult to attend to the written messages and refers to differences in the visual and the auditory perceptual systems. His point is that vision only focus on one spot at a time. The utilization of sound frees the visual system from attending to these things, and thus it becomes easier for the player to process more information at the same time.

However, the informants more specifically express dissatisfaction about not getting responses and warnings from the system. Richard describes how he repeatedly clicks on an object because the game does not provide any response to the fact that he already has been able to select the specific object:

"Yes, sometimes I sit like, I often hear, "click", then you hear "not enough gold", then perhaps I click once or twice more. But now it was just, click-click-click-click-click. Oh, shit. (laughter) Nothing came up. So it took me a little time to.. a little more time to notice things."(R34)⁸³

In normal situation, the verbal notification "not enough gold" will appear at once the player tries to order new productions. However, in the absence of sound, Richard experiences clicking several times without really

understanding what goes on. The response system disappears together with the sound; and together with it the player's ability to know whether a certain order has been executed or not. Anyway, also the lack of warnings is frustrating for the players. Petter does not think that sound disables him from taking specific actions, but he feels that he becomes less observant about what actions are available:

"[...] Well, I'm able to do everything, but I'm not as observant on what I'm allowed to do. And on what I should do. Because I don't hear, I don't get the warning that something is wrong or something is about to happen. [...] And I will have some features and I can see on the map that I'm in a fight, but I cannot follow anything specifically."(P32)⁸⁴

Urgency signals are inaccessible to Petter, which makes him unaware of situations on which he should somehow act immediately. Also, the mini-map does not provide helpful information to this kind of situation, since it is limited to showing fighting only. Of all the information provided by sound, the only information still available is the location of fights, but all details about events are inaccessible. Petter has therefore only limited information when evaluating situations and which actions are suitable for them.

However, the absence of sound does not make the game unplayable. As it did not take him long time before he got used to having no sound, Stian believes that his familiarity and experience with the game would still enable him to play *W3* successfully:

"Er, yes in fact, the first seconds when I... the first seconds I became a little, like, woah, what's happening now. But I soon got used to it, so... my reaction became much slower, I'm certain about that. But I don't know, it... [...] it isn't the greatest difference really. I'm so familiar with what's happening, I'm so used to attacking in a specific manner if a spot turns up, then I have to do this and that..." (S33)⁸⁵

Experienced players will already have a certain routine in their playing, and this is emphasised by Stian's last sentence. He claims that he knows the system of the game so well that he always attacks in a specific manner when the mini-map signals enemy presence. He has found an optimal strategy related to his playing style, and this is executed every time someone attacks him. Because of this knowledge, absence of sound does not affect his playing style very much, except from the fact that he feels that his reaction becomes much slower.

6.1.5 *Warcraft III*: A Summary

In this section, we have studied the functions of sound in *W3*, based on players' own experiences of the game. For usability purposes, the informants find it fruitful to separate different kinds of auditory signals according to whether they seem suitable for the setting or not. In this respect, it is not only the difference between the use of language, auditory icons and earcons which seems to have attracted their attention, but also the functional difference between sounds that provides reactive or proactive information to the player.

The informants demonstrate a conceptual understanding of the role of sound as both being connected to usability at the same time as supporting the virtual world, and their interpretation of the relationship between auditory icons and earcons suggests that they understand the functional aspects of transdiegetic space in computer games.

Using sounds for usability purposes is extremely important in *W3*. The high tempo and the many simultaneous processes demand that the game presents important information to the player as effectively as possible, which means taking advantage also of auditory information. One of the most important functions of audio in this game is therefore to work as a control and orientation system that keeps the player updated and aware of events and processes that may be hard to manage by the visual system alone. Sound as an important control system is demonstrated clearly by what happens when sound is removed from the game. Without sound, the player loses one of two perceptual outputs from the game, thereby having a harder time receiving necessary information from the system.

It is interesting to see that all the sound signals with the exception of iconic auditory icons are transdiegetic. They have all a close relationship to events and objects in the game, either by having diegetic sources or by indicating an action that has consequences for in-game events. But they are also system messages that inform the player about game mechanics, system status or are reactions to player commands. This fusion between system and virtual world makes it difficult to decide whether the sounds are understood as diegetic or extradiegetic in the classical understanding of the terminology. By vacillating between the two, they are better understood as transdiegetic.

6.2 The Functionality of Sound in *Hitman Contracts*

6.2.1 Usability Sounds

Four different kinds of sound signals are used for usability purposes in *HC*. However, instead of utilizing two kinds of auditory icons like *W3* does, this game focuses on two different uses of earcons:

- 1) *Iconic auditory icons* are diegetic sounds that seem to be naturally motivated by the game environment, and that have the same intuitive relationship to their sources as their real world counterparts. Also, voices and human shouts are classified within this category of sound signals when they refer to a causal relationship to a source instead of providing important semantic information.

- 2) *Musical earcons* are pieces of music that do not have a natural source existing within the game world. They accompany a specific situation or location in the game, thereby working as information system.
- 3) *Non-musical earcons* are signal sounds that originally do not have any real world counterpart. Instead they are artificial sounds created for a specific communicative purpose. The listeners have to learn the function of before they can recognize. In *HC*, these are primarily used as responses connected to the graphical user interface.
- 4) *The voice used for semantic purposes* is found when the game needs to communicate specific linguistic information to the player. This category is rarely used in *HC*, and when the voice is used in this way it is commonly associated with cut-scenes accompanied by text.

These sound signals are used both as response and urgency sounds, which will be explored in detail below.

a) Auditory Icons

All auditory icons in *HC* must be classified as iconic due to their close correspondence to their real world counterparts. Consequently, they work subtly and seem to have a natural relationship to the situation they refer to. This is due to two reasons. The game strives towards a photo-realistic style concerning looks and locations, and in order to emphasize this, sounds with a recognizable relation and close correspondence to their origins are utilized. Also, the player has an avatar that appears as a character in the game world, and that is acknowledged by other game entities as existing within the game world. This avatar reacts to in-game features, and works as interface between the player and the game. This means that sounds can communicate to the avatar instead of directly to the player, thereby upholding the illusion of a consistent virtual world.

Auditory icons are used both for responsive and different urgency purposes in *HC*. When auditory icons work for responsive purposes in *HC*, they provide both negative and positive feedback. When the avatar is fighting an enemy, sound indicates whether he hits or not. The sound of a knife that hits a body accompanied by screams from the wounded enemy works as a *confirmative* response, while the sound of a knife hitting thin air is a *rejection* response in this context. Anders identifies these functions:

“[...] The sound is very nice for something flying through the air. Well, the sound of kitchen... [...] A knife and the meat hook. And it's ok, since then you know you've done something. Also because... yes, there it was again. That sound when I fail to hit something, too.” (A10)⁸⁶

When sound is used for these purposes, the player does not need to see his enemy get hit – he can hear it. Besides, there is no visual metre that monitors the health level of enemies, so the sound is actually the only

way to know whether an enemy is close to death or not. In order for the confirmative sound to be functional in this context, there is also a rejection response that appears when the player does not hit his target.

Rasmus points to a second example of how auditory icons work as negative responses. The screams from scared civilians when Agent 47 draws his gun in public inform the player that he has been exposed:

“I also think you take on that kind of role when playing Hitman that you’re very much aware of the fact that it’s you who are the murderer. People always get scared when you draw the gun. So... I think it’s good that they react; it’s good that you... get responses when walking around with your gun drawn. Then everyone shouts and screams or there is some music or something. They talk to me, and there is talking around me, right. [...]” R14b⁸⁷

Since the civilians get scared and start screaming and running, the player is immediately made aware of the fact that drawing a gun in public is not a preferred action. In this respect, the screams work as a negative response. However, Rasmus has noticed that also music may change when the avatar draws a gun, as if to underline the fact that he is prepared for action, or to tell the player that this is not the preferred way to do things. In this case it is music that works responsive, which will be elaborated on in a separate chapter about musical earcons below.

Footsteps and doors slamming work as an interesting informative system in *HC*. They are directly connected to whether the avatar walks normally, is in stealth mode, or runs. When the avatar is in stealth mode, these sounds become more silent, and the enemies are less likely to hear the avatar moving. Equally, these sounds become louder when the avatar runs, making the enemy more likely to hear him.

“Er, the difference between stealth and usual mode, and I was about to say, running, run mode. I noticed especially well when I sneaked in and opened one of the doors, then it opened much more silently compared to when I walk normally. The same goes for footsteps and all those things. [...]” (A4a)⁸⁸

This works as a confirmative response to the player that he has activated another mode, although the difference in volume is so discrete that many players might not notice this. However, as we will see below, the sound in this situation can also be interpreted as a notification to the player whether the enemies are likely to detect him or not.

In *HC*, auditory icons also have an important role as urgency signals. These exist on two priority levels, namely as *notifications* and *warnings*. The use of voices is the most utilized system for providing urgency information. In some cases the player may hear off-screen or distant voices of non-playing characters talking together. This works to notify the player about the presence of non-playing characters outside the line of sight:

“Well, it helps you to, you know there is someone in the distance. And that’s typical and... that you can hear if there is someone else in the room perhaps. Keeping a distance to sounds is very good.” (A13)⁸⁹

In this situation, Anders does not only receive new knowledge of the status of off-screen or distant spaces, but he is also informed about the relative distance between the avatar and other characters. This notification may influence player behaviour in different ways, by for instance making the avatar walk instead of run, or to

holster his guns. Also, depending on the context the player may decide to try to find another route in order not to be seen by anyone, or he may see the voices as a hint that this is the entrance to a specific location and that he should make a plan how to get past the people at the door.

In other situations, however, non-player character voices may sound aggressive. Shouting voices is a signal that the player has been exposed and that guards are after him. In that case, the warning function of the sound is suddenly evident. Nevertheless, context will decide exactly how the player should act, and whether the sound should be interpreted as a warning or a notification:

“I’m exposed, now I’ve got two alternatives. [...] Well, it depends very much on the situation, because you know they’re searching for you. If you were walking down the street and they started shouting at you, you would probably not bother very much.” (G15b-c)⁹⁰

According to Geir, this message does not have the same priority level urgency in all kinds of settings. If the avatar is walking slowly past a restricted area when addressed by guards, he could continue walking without taking any precautions. In this case, the voices are a notification to the player that he will not be able to get past the guards. But the message is of no high priority, since the avatar is acting like any other bystander. As long as he does not provoke the guards in any respect, they will remain on site. However, if the avatar was trespassing when hearing the shouting voices, the situation would be different. In such a situation, the guards would probably have an aggressive stance towards the avatar, and the sound would therefore be a high priority urgency signal demanding immediate action. Thus, a violent behaviour is likely to be chosen.

The game also utilizes diegetic music. This music should be regarded an auditory icon, since it is being played by a source within the game universe, and has informative value by pointing to its cause. The music has an orienting function by varying in volume depending on the avatar’s position related to the source. Also, the diegetic music provides hints or notifications about the setting. Diegetic music often signals the presence of human beings, and in *HC*, it suggests that civilians – and possibly also targets – may be close to the source. When suddenly hearing distant club music, Jonas starts making hypotheses about what is going on. He points out that the diegetic music provokes curiosity:

“[...] It very much aroused my curiosity. What is really going on here? I don’t think I connected the pieces very well.” (J16b)⁹¹

He does not immediately understand what is going on, but since the music notifies him about possible upcoming encounters, he remains attentive to the situation. Also, since it is likely that he will find the targets among other people, the music motivates him to seek out the source.

Diegetic music also masks other sounds, which means that screams and gunshots are less likely to be heard by non-player characters. In a room next to the discotheque, Anders finds one of his targets, who starts

screaming when Agent 47 enters. He expects that guards will come running to assist the victim, but is surprised to find that nobody arrives:

“[...] When I took the lawyer, then he started screaming, and then I was worried I should be exposed. But it worked, it turned out all right.” (A4b)⁹²

The masking function of the diegetic music therefore allows the player more freedom of action, since sounds will not be heard by other people nearby. Since the player does not have to act in a careful manner in places with music, such areas may be desired areas for assassinating targets.

b) Non-Musical Earcons

Non-musical earcons are used for both responsive purposes and in connection with two degrees of urgency. In relation to the graphical user interface, *confirmative response* sounds follow opening menus, maps, as well as selections done in the inventory and the briefing. These are also found in the start menu where the player selects whether to load or start a new game, and where he can configure graphics, audio, and interface settings. In human-computer interfaces, it is common to have some kind of response to player commands, and the use of sound for this purpose is especially important in games where the visual perceptual system often is busy keeping track of specific game features. Lars explains the response value of such sounds:

“[...] It’s an indication function about your going through the inventory. Many games have this even when you’re only moving the mouse over, or points it over objects, and touch what you’re really interested in. And it seems to be to register that the computer knows what’s going on, since then you know whether the computer has locked itself or not.[...]” (L10)⁹³

Sounds that inform the player that commands are being executed and that the system still is running, work as an important function that emphasizes usability. It allows the player to receive immediate feedback on all player-initiated activities. Using sound for this purpose is not only helpful in situations where the visual system is busy, but it is also important for the sense of physicality that computer systems do not have. In this sense, the sound may provide more lifelikeness to the game’s virtual world:

“[...] It provides a somewhat physical feel, that what you’re handling is something physical. [...] Well, most games use it. To give the pixels more physics. Because, all in all, it’s only colours on a screen, or pixels. And, they have to utilize sound sometimes to give it a feeling that you, that something happens. [...]” (P15)⁹⁴

Providing a sense of physicality to the action, sound contributes to the sense of presence in the game world. As Petter points out, one gets the feeling of handling something physical, instead of manipulating icons on a screen. Consequently, sound even provides the impression that the inventory belongs to the virtual world instead of being an external system feature with no actual connection to the game environment. In this sense,

this use of sound also emphasizes the transdiegetic function of interface features by erasing the border between the system and the game world.

Another non-musical earcon used is the beep that follows written notifications. These notifications appear in the upper corner in a red, green or blue box, accompanied by a small electronic, but otherwise neutral sound. The colour of the box depends on whether the message informs the player about warnings, hints or merely notifications. These messages are system messages that belong to the interface, and fall in between the response and the urgency categories. The sound that accompanies these is the same in all three cases, but as noted above, there is one message marked in red which signals negative events, another in green that notifies the player about positive events, and a third in blue which reveals more neutral hints. All of these may take on the role both as urgency and response signals:

“Well, here there’re only these, well, hints and warnings, of course. Concerning for instance when they’ve found a dead person and stuff you often hear the shouts.” (A38c)⁹⁵

When the player receives a red alert that signals that a dead body has been found, this is a *warning* that guards are looking for him, but it is also a consequence of his past actions. In this respect, the warning also works a *negative response* to the player’s killing or to his attempt of disguising. Similar interpretations are available for blue and green messages. When a green message tells the player a target died from drinking poisoned water, this is a *notification* of the fact that an objective has been fulfilled, as well as a *positive response* to the player’s earlier poisoning. When the blue message points out that “butchers don’t carry guns”, this is triggered in response to the fact that the avatar puts on a specific disguise without dropping his guns, but it works as a *notification* that guards will react negative when searching the avatar. The use of sounds in this connection may seem superfluous since the player never has problems seeing them when they pop up. Compared to the rest of the screen in greyscales and more naturalistic colours, the bright red, blue and green boxes are clear eye-catchers, but Anders still appreciates the accompanying sound as an accessory marker with primarily aesthetic value:

“It’s nice to have a small sound. Just to inform that something happens on screen. But... now they’re not necessary like in Warcraft, where you have lots of sounds when something happens. When these pop up, you see them.” (A38b)⁹⁶

Nevertheless, Petter claims that the sounds are necessary, because it is the synthesis between the auditory and the visual aspects that is what makes him attentive towards the message. He is asked whether he notices the sound in this context, and whether sound is necessary here, and replies:

“Yes, I do that. I do that. Because the sound makes you attentive towards something happening in the corner. [...] I notice both [the sound and the coloured box], the sound is necessary, I would argue.” (P12)⁹⁷

Petter is convinced that sound is necessary for perceiving the wholeness of the message. The visuals are not enough, he claims. The differences between the informants' claims in this respect suggest that there are individual variations related to whether the sound seems necessary or not in this context.

c) Musical Earcons

The music in *HC* is in a special position compared to the music in *W3* since it is used as an information system. *HC* uses music as earcons in order to provide signals and responses to the player, and is the most important auditory information system in this game. The music is external transdiegetic since it originates from a point external to the game universe, but still addresses the avatar's actions. The adaptiveness of the music is commented on by most informants, and they are conscious about its function as both urgency and response signals. Petter mentions several important functionalities related to the music as information system:

"It's timed for... when something exciting happens, when there're guards nearby, and when I do something stupid. Those kinds of things. It's supposed to keep me in suspense." (P7)⁹⁸

First of all, the music works as a *notification* telling the player about hostile presence, and second, the music works as a *negative response* to his actions. Petter also points out that music may provide *confirmation* in response to a completed objective, which he explains when asked why a specific jingle is played when he pulls a dead victim behind him (P28)⁹⁹.

Other interesting pieces of information are provided by the use of music. Certain pieces of music will start playing when the player enters important locations where weapons can be found or special events may take place. In this respect music works as a notification informing about potential events and the presence of specific items. Lars explains:

"[...] And, inside the meat house [...], it was also like that. It wasn't, I doubt they had a stereo set playing this tragic music in there. So it was the game music there. Well, you're walking around and start... you don't run through it the first time, are these humans or is it perhaps pork." (L5)¹⁰⁰

Lars refers to an incident when a piece of music starts playing when he enters a meat house. Carcasses are hanging from the roof, and the sudden start of gloomy music makes Lars speculate whether the carcasses are remains of humans or pork. Also, at the specific location, both Petter and Lars start moving the avatar around trying to figure out whether something can be triggered in the room, something they both expect precisely because of the music. It is also interesting to see that Lars separates between diegetic and extradiegetic music in this quote by pointing out that he does not believe that this music is being played from within the game space. Nevertheless, he is still aware of the fact that this extradiegetic music has relevance for diegetic

space, since he interprets the music as providing him with information. In this sense, the informant is clearly aware of the transdiegetic function of music.

a) The Semantic Use of Voice

In *HC*, voices are typically shouts and screams, or short utterances spoken in a language other than English, and are used as iconic auditory icons that signal the presence of non-player characters and their attention level towards the avatar. In this sense, they signal a causal relation instead of containing important linguistic information. However, on some occasions voices are used to provide semantic information. In this paragraph, I will shortly outline the different instances in which voices are used for this purpose. As this never came up as a discussion theme during the interviews, there will be no direct references to player interpretations.

When the game needs to provide important linguistic information, this is commonly done through cut-scenes. Cut-scenes are small cinematic sequences in computer games. These appear when the player talks to a central key person, or is in the position eavesdrop on an important conversation. The information concerns game objectives or information relevant to solve a certain problem, and is typically accompanied by subtitles. The reason for presenting the information in this manner is that it guarantees that the player receives the information. If the conversation appeared as an in-game feature that the player could walk away from or not notice at all, the player would run the risk of never receiving the information at all.

Information about game objectives is also received in the start of each mission, where the avatar receives intelligence from the Agency. This is presented through text and images, and Agent 47's handler, Diana, reads the complete mission aloud. At any point in the game, the player can open his briefings menu and replay this information. In this situation, the use of voice is redundant, and the reason for having it is to provide a sense of presence and a feeling that this information is a recording on his PDA coming directly from the Agency.

The last way in which the voice is used to provide semantic information is rarely used. This use is non-subtitled voiceover, and seems to be a method of providing hints to the player about how to do a mission. In the beginning of the mission "Rendezvous in Rotterdam" the player hears Agent 47's voice saying "Gotta find that car. Gotta keep close to it." This is an interesting way of providing information to the player since it suggests that Agent 47 is a character with intentions independent of the player. However, since it works as a hint about what actions to take, the player will eventually adopt Agent 47's intentions in this respect.

6.2.2 The Atmospheric Function of Sound

We should keep in mind Nico Frijda's separation between *emotions* and *moods* (1993) when discussing the atmospheric function of sound. As noted in connection with atmospheric sounds in *W3*, it is moods more than emotions that create a sense of atmosphere in a game. However, it should be noted that atmosphere may be seen as the sum of all moods and emotions created by a certain situation. Thus, both object-oriented sounds, ambient sounds, as well as the visual and thematic sombreness, contribute to the specific atmosphere in the game.

a) Music

There are three kinds of music in *HC*. The first category is diegetic music. This music is part of the game world in the sense that it has a naturalistic relationship to an in-game source, and it is perceived to exist in the game world. The second kind of music is extradiegetic in the classical sense by being background music with no naturalistic source in the game environment. However, it adapts to specific situations and locations, and works as an information system. The last category is ambient music that merges with background environmental sounds. In "The Meat King's Party" we can identify two locations with diegetic music. Following the idea that atmosphere may be seen as the sum of all moods and emotions in a certain situation, all kinds of music contribute to the atmosphere of the game by tainting the allover interpretation of the setting, but only ambient music can be directly connected to Frijda's sense of mood due to the fact that it is not attached to objects or events. Concerning atmosphere, there is an interesting relationship between ambient and adaptive music, since these are different parts of the same musical work by following each other in a tonally and musically logic manner. This means that the music in different parts stimulates either emotions or moods in the player, since adaptive music appeals to emotions by providing action-relevant information, and ambient music appeals to moods by not having any specific focus. Both kinds of music have transdiegetic properties, but for different reasons. The adaptive music is transdiegetic because it is positioned extradiegetically, but provides information relevant for action in the game world. It also seems to communicate to Agent 47 indirectly by the fact that the player hears the music and can act on it through the avatar. The ambient music, on the other hand, works transdiegetically by being extradiegetic music that merges with the location-based ambient background noise. In this sense, it gives the impression of being natural sounds from the specific location.

The music in *HC* contributes to providing an unpleasant mood that affects the player's understanding of the sinister setting. Due to the ambient quality, the music is hard to notice, but it is still able to provide a sense of creepiness in the player.

"No, it's that kind you pick up in the back of your head, right. It's just the atmosphere... it only contributes to the atmosphere. So it increases the creepiness about being in a slaughter house." (P17a)¹⁰¹

Petter points out that the vague and a-melodious music is hard to grasp and listen closely to, and in this sense, the power of the music is to work on a subconscious and non-focused level of the player's mind. In this way, the music clearly adapts to Smalley's reflexive relationship between sound and listener (1996). The idea that the music works on a non-focused level is also supported by the way Anders refers to it. He uses metaphors to explain the mood supported by the music:

"[...] It's like... creating an atmosphere. Like, not really eerie, but well, it's a somewhat sinister tone to it. Almost the same as when you hear thunder... [...] It seems a little psycho. I think it... it seems like they have [added] small semi-eerie parts..." (A15a-b)¹⁰²

Anders underlines the atmospheric aspect of the music by talking about it in very abstract ways. He does not refer to qualities in the music, but to the mood he feels it provides. He also compares the mood to a natural phenomenon, namely distant thunder which metaphorically may be seen as a threatening feature suggesting that something unpleasant is about to happen. Although he talks about music in this respect, it is likely that his impression is coloured not by music alone, but by how it works together with the rest of the soundscape, as well as the theme for the game and the visual aspects.

The ambient music sometimes includes features that sound like distant screams and laughter, and in this respect, it draws on conventions from horror film. In *HC*, however, this atmosphere underlines the not-so-glorious theme of the game and the profession of an assassin.

"It has perhaps something to do with his view on the whole... it's supposed to be a flashback the whole thing. And that's perhaps what makes the game so gloomy. Because he remembers it this way, not necessarily because it happened this way." (G23e)¹⁰³

In his interpretation of the use of ambient music, Geir goes back to refer to the whole theme of the game. In the end of *Hitman 2: Silent Assassin* and in the introduction of *Hitman Contracts*, it is made clear that what happens in *HC* is a flashback to earlier days in Agent 47's professional life. Geir reflects on the possibility that the strange ambient noises also are parts of this flashback. Agent 47 remembers the whole situation this way, which is a good explanation why the whole game feels so gloomy. Geir's remark is interesting from a theoretical point of view, since his interpretation explains the sound as *focalization* (Branigan 1992:100-7). In this view, what we hear is rooted in the avatar's inner life, his memories, and his state of mind.

However, the musical focus changes during the scenario. Diegetic club music dominates the soundscape in parts of the building, and the change from eerie ambient music to up-beat diegetic music from a discotheque has some specific effects on the atmosphere of the scenario. This change also affects the player's understanding of his own possibilities for action:

“But I think it's more eerie out in the slaughter house section, it's clear that when there's a party, music will accompany it. But you can clearly notice the difference in... atmosphere. For example, it's precisely, in the other end [of the slaughter house] there's the risk of dying, and where all the people are dancing, chairs are put up, and it's a little more...” (R24a)¹⁰⁴

In the first part, Rasmus is nervous since the music suggests a risk of dying. However, as he starts hearing music from a discotheque, he believes that he is moving towards an area in which death is not lurking behind every corner. This is a civilian area, people dressed for party are having a good time, and it seems likely that guards will not shoot you unprovoked. However, Lars notices another interesting aspect about the presence of diegetic music, which is related to his own behaviour. The tempo, pace and rhythm of the club music influence his playing style. Lars has not played the game in the sense of an implied player, by the fact that he goes through it the violent way. He also does point out that he plays it as he would play a first-person shooter.

“[...] There is a special club music. Standard American club music. And that fits the mood very well, the only thing is that you may perhaps get a little carried away with that kind of music. Well, if you've been forced to shoot one man, you suddenly end up by killing five more. And for each one you kill, five new come running, and suddenly you've got a blood bath in there, and there you go. [...]” (L5)¹⁰⁵

The energy of the club music influences Lars, and he becomes in his own words “a little carried away” by the music. A reason for this may be that his preferred game genre is first-person shooters, where the music is up-beat and heavy, and supports action and shooting scenes. It is nevertheless interesting to see how energetic music may affect the player into more energetic and action-oriented behaviour.

The second piece of diegetic music found in this scenario is encountered when the avatar comes to the location of a murder scene. In a blood-splattered candle-lit room the player finds the body of a dead girl, accompanied by Paul Anka's hit song from the 60s “Put your head on my shoulder”. In this situation, the music works as *counterpoint* (Chion 1994:37-8), by providing contrasting information compared to what we see in the scene. When approaching the room, the player does not hear the music; it can only be heard after entering the room. It is also heard if the avatar peeps through the keyhole. Petter peeps through the keyhole, sees a candle-lit room and hears the music:

“[...] [To hear the music through the keyhole] is not quite realistic, but it works well for providing a mood, well, the sound image is part of the atmosphere in that room. And when you look into the room then you should get part of its atmosphere. If you only saw the stuff it would ruin the mood when you entered afterwards. Because you knew what you saw and thus the music wouldn't be registered in the same way.” (P20a)¹⁰⁶

The room would not be able to tell the same story if image and sound was separated. The mood depends on perceiving the synthesis of the two, because the image and the sound add atmospheric value to each other.

In this case it is not as if image is more important for the experience than the sound, or the other way around. Jonas is also moved by the mood provided by the music in this room, which he describes as creepy. He believes that the inclusion of the music makes the interpretation of the scene clear:

“[...] It describes the psychopathic mind of the Meat King’s brother. Well... it’s like the perfect world, right. Which is put up against this grotesque display. But, at the same time, well... he has an altar built for her, he actually does love her, so... [...] That music’s a clear remark to that tragedy. Really, it’s quite horrible. [...]” (J29g-h)¹⁰⁷

Jonas easily interprets the scene as a tragedy because of the music. The music is a romantic little tune in stark contrast to the grotesque scene, and to Jonas the music underlines the emotions behind the whole incident. The counterpoint use of music has what Rasmus calls an ironic function (R28b)¹⁰⁸, and in Jonas’ view this is what enables him to see the tragedy. In this respect, specific atmosphere in this situation could not have been created by either sound or image, but it only comes into being when sound and image appear together.

b) Realistic Soundscape?

Although the visual perspective used in *Hitman Contracts* allows for more faithful replication of natural sound, the informants do not find the soundscape particularly realistic. However, they do find it credible for a computer game featuring a professional assassin on mission, and in this sense, the soundscape appears neither as realistic nor nonrealistic:

“Well, it’s not unrealistic but... well, it doesn’t strike me as totally realistic either. Shooting sounds, that is the sound effects on the shooting is on the other hand quite convincing. They’re not as loud as they should be, but that has to do with user friendliness.” (L14)¹⁰⁹

Still underlining that the game has convincing use of sound on specific features, Lars suggests that it is not realism or naturalism that is central for this game. Instead he refers to perceptual fidelity. However, Jonas tries to explain exactly what it is that makes sounds in *HC* seem convincing and credible, and he refers to the relationship between sounds and the events that they are attached to:

“It’s very much related to... realism. So I was sitting there trying to register things that made... well, the realistic sounds. The rain sound is very good, very good. And the meat axe... well. I’ve no idea how one sounds like, but... It does sound like you’re chopping up something there. [laughter]” (J6b)¹¹⁰

The word used by Jonas is realism, but it seems that he is talking about a sense of credibility related to the function of the sound. This is underlined by the point that he does not really know what a meat axe sounds like when chopping meat since he has never heard one in real life, but that the sound is convincing for chopping in general. It is important to note that the sound also refers to the function of the sound: it can be used to chop things up. In this sense, credibility in this sense refers to whether or not the particular sound

feels suitable not only for the perceived source, but more specifically for what the object in question can do. Thus, the issue is more specifically related to a functional form of fidelity.

Anders and Rasmus point to another auditory feature that imitates real world sounds in a satisfactory manner. This is how sound perspective is used in order to help the player orient himself, and create a sense of presence:

“Well, Hitman’s tried to recreate what sounds you hear, distances and how you’re situated in relation to the sound. Especially this, that you can enter... the sound of rain is louder at the exit or at the door. And disappears more when you enter. You hear yourself walking. You hear people talking in the distance, and talking louder when they’re approaching, so it’s like... they try to recreate real life much more.” (A42)¹¹¹

“Well, it’s realistic, and it works as an extra feature that enables you to relate to what happens in the space, because often when you play you can’t really see what’s going on. But then perhaps you can hear someone walking or something. So at least you can find out if guards stand about and stuff... And that’s what important in this game.” (R10b)¹¹²

Both informants explain the realism of the sound in terms of functionality in relation to how it informs the player about the relative location of other objects and events in relation to avatar. However, while Rasmus takes this as a sign of trying to make the sound seem realistic, Anders consistently uses the word *recreate* instead. For Anders, the sound in this game is clearly an *imitation* of how sounds work in real world environments. Rasmus, on the other hand, notes that sound is used for orientation purposes when the visual space does not allow for a full overview of what happens. In this sense, the sound works to increase the range of perception by providing access to areas outside the line of sights. This also related to how sound contributes to a sense of *presence* in the game world. Sound is described as a surrounding feature that tells the player about the spatial layout of the environment and what goes on in it. To feel present in a space requires the possibility to sense the space around oneself, and this feeling is ensured by enabling the player to hear sounds also from somewhat distant sources.

6.2.3 Sound & Orientation

Sound is also used for orienting purposes in *HC*, which has been most clearly revealed in the part of the player studies in which the informants played without sound. We will have a look at the general reactions towards playing without sound, as well as at how attention and apprehension seem to be affected. Compared to *W3*, *HC* is less dependent on the presence of sound, although the informants do point to some situations in which the absence of sound makes successful playing difficult.

a) Playing Without Sound

Since Anders, Petter and Lars had participated in the *W3* sessions and knew the procedure of the interview session, and not at least that sound would be turned off, it is most interesting to see what Rasmus, Jonas and Geir say about their reactions towards the sound being removed from the game. Geir claims that he becomes more distanced, loses his ability to orient himself, and that playing becomes much more boring. He feels out of control, since the lack of sound seems to isolate him from certain kinds of information:

“You get much more distanced. Because you don’t get... you don’t get any feedback from the surroundings. [...] That’s actually it, [the sound] contributes to placing you in... when you hear a door open up behind you, or hear a door opening and there’re no doors before you, you think it’s behind you. But... it becomes like, you don’t want to end up in this situation.” (G25)¹¹³

He describes a sense of helplessness in that one of his access points suddenly has been removed from the game. He points specifically at the disappearance of response signals that earlier seemed to attach him to the game world. Without these, he becomes alienated from the virtual world. This alienation also contributes to increased paranoia, since the player no longer knows what may be lurking in the off-screen locations:

“Yes, first you get like plugs in your ears, and it was just lack of hearing. But after a while then, then... like you mentioned a little later it’s like... I get much more paranoid. I become actually a little more scared when there’s no sound, because you need to hear if things are... around you, as it were. Where things are.” (J26)¹¹⁴

When auditory information suddenly becomes inaccessible, Jonas is made aware that there is much information that he normally utilizes for orienting himself and for getting a sense of what is going on in the environment. He claims that the awareness of non-player character’s presence and the sense of distance to objects and events disappears, a situation that is even more frightening than the eerie and gloomy atmosphere provided by the soundtrack, since he loses all sense of control of off-screen space.

It is not only the awareness of what is around that disappears in the absence of sound. The sense of a living environment is also gone, and the artificialness of the game world becomes much clearer:

“It’s like [gun scenes] don’t function right, because it’s like... you get, you get reminded that this is actually a computer game. So when there’s no sound there’s just like two animated figures standing there shooting at each other. [...]” (R13)¹¹⁵

The sound provides the environment and its inhabitants a sense of life, and when the sound is removed the informant is reminded about the fact that what he sees are just graphics and pixels, and that the figures shooting at each other are animated features only. This point parallels the findings of how the units in *W3* become lifeless numbers on the screen instead of valuable individuals.

b) Attention & Apprehension

What happens to the informants' attention and apprehension in the absence of sound? It is interesting to see that the level of attention does not decrease, although it does change. When losing one of the two perceptual outputs from the computer game, Rasmus reports increased visual attention. The game still demands that the player focuses on the game, and in the absence of auditory output the visual system becomes more heavily loaded, and the player has to concentrate more on what he sees (A36)¹¹⁶. Rasmus explains that the balance between auditory and visual attention changes. He has still the same high level of attention as before, but now the auditory part of it disappears, and what remains is the visual attention. And as with the deaf, the visual perception becomes sharpened because of the imbalance. Lars supports this by pointing out that sound often can be a distraction:

" [...] It's very chaotic situation, and when the sound was on I played chaotically. But now when the sound's turned off and I became more systematic it was partly because the immersion in that chaos was equal to zero. It's almost the same as in roleplaying games. If you don't immerse yourself into the character, you can per definition play more effectively. But it becomes much worse [role-] playing." (L27a)¹¹⁷

Since Lars plays the game in an aggressive manner, the scenario becomes very chaotic. Civilians and guards are running around screaming, accompanied by action music. In this situation, sound becomes yet another feature of distraction, and consequently, when the sound is turned off, distractions decreases, and Lars feels that it is easier to concentrate. In addition, his immersion into the game also becomes less in the absence of sound, and this enables him to play the game in a more calculated way. He compares the feeling to playing pen and paper roleplaying games, where "being in character" or playing the role of a specific personality may exclude some behaviours and, consequently, some strategies. In the same respect, sound in a computer game will influence you somehow emotionally, with the consequence that a player may play a game less calculated and more coloured by the general mood of the game. However, when this mood disappears from computer games, or when the personality of a character in a roleplaying game is set aside, the player will be able to play the game in a more calculated, balanced and strategically advantageous way. Lars goes further in his argument and adds that his sense of control increased in the absence of sound:

"[The sense of control] actually increased. Usually it would decrease quite a lot. But in return when the sound disappears it's like when you're blind, all other perceptions are sharpened. And... the sound is very helpful in games, but right here it's distracting and nothing else." (L26a)¹¹⁸

He emphasizes that the feeling of increased control is a specific case for this specific traversal of the game due to the game's chaotic responses to Lars' behaviour. His point, however, is that sound is an important feature in games, and in this precise situation it had the effect of making the player more distressed than in an ideal situation; thus, the removal of the sound becomes helpful.

6.2.4 Hitman Contracts: A Summary

This section has analysed the functions of sound in *HC*, based on actual players' experiences of the game. The informants demonstrate broad understanding of the role of sound in the game, and separate music and diegetic sounds as two different systems of providing usability information, and in this sense, music has been categorized as an earcon, while diegetic sounds from the game environment has been categorized iconic auditory icons. The music adapts to specific situations, and works clearly as either responses or urgency signals related to player actions. The usability function of diegetic sounds, on the other hand, tends to be dependent on the specific situation.

The heavy use of both adaptive music and environmental sounds in *HC* indicates that the game conforms to aesthetic standards of the cinema, but functionally, these sounds are used to combine the sense of a living virtual world with usability functions. The music earcons merge into the setting due to its atmospheric qualities, and the usability function of the iconic auditory icons becomes masked since the sounds seem to be motivated by a sense of realism. The informants have a sophisticated understanding of this dual role of game audio, and are especially attentive towards the transdiegetic role of music in this respect.

Most central for *HC* are the atmospheric and the orienting functions of game audio. Sound puts emphasis on the players as part of the specific game world, and works to provide them with a sense of presence. This is also evident in the use of sound for orienting purposes. The sound seems to surround the player in a manner similar to real world sound, and the player may therefore successfully react to sounds in the same manner as he would in the real world. The atmospheric and orienting functions are further emphasised when sound is turned off. In the absence of sound, the informants report that they feel alienated from the game universe, and that they feel out of control, since they lose their only connection to offscreen space. In this sense, game audio is important for creating a sense of presence in the game world both emotionally and functionally.

6.3 Memory of Game Audio: Recall & Recognition

There were two instances of testing the informants' memory of game audio, one related to the recall of game audio, and another related to the recognition of game audio. *Recall* is the process of retrieving something from memory without having a direct reference to what one is trying to remember beside what might be in one's own mind, while *recognition* is the process of identifying something one has earlier experience with. In other words, *recall* involves the naming of a previously experienced event, and *recognition* only involves evaluating whether an event is familiar or not (Eysenck & Keane 2001:177). In the study of game audio, the informants

were involved in a *recall process* in which they were supposed to talk freely about what sounds they could remember from the game, and a *recognition process* in which they were allowed to listen to some isolated sounds that they were supposed to identify and contextualize.

The first instance of memory testing was positioned initially in the session. Introductory to the session, the informants were told for the first time that the study concerned the relationship between audio and gameplay specifically, followed by a conversation about which auditory features the informants could recall from the game. Starting off with recalling the audio of a game may have been confusing to the informants, but the purpose of starting the session in this manner was twofold. The working hypothesis was that sound is a feature that the player might have few articulated thoughts about because of its non-visual and often subtle quality. One of the reasons for introducing the theme in this way was that I wanted the players to familiarize themselves with the topic of the interview, and raise their awareness of sound preparatory to the playing phase of the session. This was expected to make them feel more comfortable speaking of sound later in the session. The second reason was that making the informants talk about the soundscape before playing as well as after, would provide perspectives from two different experiential points in time. This would enable a comparison of the player's memory of sound to how they understand sound in context.

The second instance of memory testing came after the playing part of the session. By playing sounds from the game in question in isolation, I was testing the informants' ability to recognize sounds out of context. They were supposed to say what the sound referred to, and how they would react to this kind of auditory information. The purpose of this was to make the informants understand what kind of information I was looking for when they were asked to explain to me what was going on in the video-capture.

According to cognitive psychology, recognition memory is generally better than recall memory (Eysenck & Keane 2001:175), something which also is demonstrated in this study. However, the informants in this project are generally very good at both. This can be explained by the fact that we were talking about a case that is both cherished and familiar for the informants. It may therefore have been easier for them to connect audio in the game to specific familiar situations that they know from the game. However, in the following, the two studies will be discussed separately.

6.3.1 Recalling Game Audio

When asked about what they can recall of the sound in *W3*, the informants verbally start a process of recollection. In the beginning they describe the soundscape vaguely and in very general terms, but during the

process of describing, they move on to more specific uses of sound. In this sense, they seemed to cognitively activating a process of refreshing their memory and starting a larger process of association. This ability to talk about what kinds of information the sound communicates in retrospect also suggests that experienced players develop a cognitive link between the sound and what it means. In this respect, when the meaning of a sound is learned, the player will not understand the sound and its meaning as separate, but the sound and its meaning merge into one cognitive entity. Hearing a specific sound, the player will then automatically know the meaning without having to listen for its semantic or linguistic properties.

One issue that was easily recalled was the use of auditory stereotypes in *W3*. Stian describes very accurately that the use of music follows the different playable races, and points out that the music is not only distinguished by different kinds of melodies, but also by different kinds of mood that stereotype the specific race:

“[...] It’s... the night elves have the more mysterious, Celtic feel. While... the orcs have this savage, running around on the plains beating things and so on. And... well, there’s music for what each race stands for really, humans really have that proud knight thing, while the undeads almost have a more horror movie music. So there’s a very good atmosphere connected to the race you choose. [...]” (S-2b)¹¹⁹

Stian recalls that this musical stereotyping familiarizes the different races, in addition to the providing the player with hint about what kinds of game mechanical abilities that are in focus with the different races. Petter also recalls the stereotyping, and points to the voices of recognition in this respect, which he describes as “humorous”:

“[...] Then there are these pompous knights: “no-no-no, no-no-no”. Silly peasants and things like that. So there is a blend of a strict Command & Conquer soundscape found in the background noise, and attempts of being humorous found in the voice-acting. So it’s quite fun, you don’t take it as seriously as other games.” (P2)¹²⁰

The reason why the informants can recall the stereotyping so clearly may be due to the fact that they are caricatures of different hierarchical roles in a fantasy feudal system. This feature becomes a trademark of the game, at the same time as it has a functional value. This combination of stereotyping and functionality provide a special emphasis to the sounds. The humorous aspect enables Petter to recall that there is also a more serious tone to the audio in this game, which is found in the background ambience that strives towards a greater sense of perceptual fidelity and naturalism.

Other functional sounds are also easily recalled. Anders points to the use of sound as an important usability feature in *W3*:

“In Warcraft, there’s a rich sound picture. There’s wood chopping and... lots of sounds telling you danger is near. And there are many funny sounds you can provoke by clicking on certain spots.” (A1)¹²¹

He mentions that sound works both as an *urgency signalling system* that informs about upcoming situations, and as a *response system* that in Anders’ example rewards the player with funny sounds. In this sense, both

the reactive and the proactive functions are easily recollected, possibly due to their very central informative role in this game. In addition, the use of the *voice as warning system* has been stuck in the memory of most of the informants. Richard (R3)¹²², Anders (A4)¹²³ and Petter (P5)¹²⁴ all recall the high priority urgency message “we’re under attack”, which is the most urgent and critical warnings found in the game. There is no doubt that this kind of message is there to inform the player about a very specific and dangerous situation, namely that enemies are present and attack buildings or troops. This is possibly also the most important reason why this sound is recalled so easily. However, the fact that the message uses the human voice communicating a message with linguistic content may also serve as part of the explanation.

The informants’ memory of the sound in *HC* is vaguer, possibly because the audio also communicates in a more subtle manner in this game than in *W3*. Since there is a clear focus on Smalley’s reflexive relationship (1996) in *HC*, the sound draws on the players’ passive listening and moods. When the sound communicates in this delicate manner, it may be hard to actually create a cognitive model of it in the mind, and in this sense, the sound in *HC* may be harder to recall. Nevertheless, as more specific questions were asked, the informants’ memory seemed to increase. Interestingly, one of the most recalled features of *HC* is actually the mood emphasised by the discreet soundscape. Petter recalls music as supportive for the genre by claiming that music underlines a specific mood that requests him to behave in a specific manner. For him, passive listening is the most important focus for the music in *Hitman Contracts*:

“[...] I take it relatively easy in relation to that music, [it] requests me to take it easy, that I think my moves through, that I don’t rush into a room without checking what’s in there first. And the music and the sound give me a kind of... requests me to proceed with caution and be silent. It’s not like ordinary shooters where the sound is loud and a lot of heavy music... then you’re just requested to run around and shoot everything that’s there. Here it’s more, take it easy, think your actions through, keep track on the map, keep track on movements, sneak after people.” (P3)¹²⁵

Petter recalls the specific mood of the music, and how the music not only is suitable for the specific genre, but also how it indirectly influences his behaviour and choice of actions when playing the game. For Petter, the mood suggests that he plays in a calm and calculated way, and that he should think before acting.

However, the adaptive aspect of the music is also recalled by most of the informants, possibly due to its functional aspect that provides the player with information relevant for his choice of actions. Geir points out that music works in a subtle manner that often is hard to discover:

“Music is often a feature you don’t notice very much. [...] But it does of course have a function. [...] Yes.... It becomes rather, well, the music is there almost all the time, I think I remember. But it becomes more, yes what should I say? There’s more accent [to it] when something happens which is supposed to be more action-driven.” (G2)¹²⁶

Geir first claims that music is something one typically does not notice, and here he supports Gorbman’s claim (1987) that music in audiovisual media tend to be “unheard”, and in this game this may also often be the truth

since the music often is ambient music that merges with background noise. However, Geir also points out that the music is functional by adapting according to stressed situations. Although the claim could be due to expectations connected with the informant's experience with computer games, it also demonstrates how the memory of music gradually comes back to him. His first thought is that music works subtly, but when thinking about it he must admit to himself that there probably is a functional reason behind the music.

Not surprisingly, it is the informants who participated as informant on both games that have clearest memory of the game's soundscape, probably because they have a comparative viewpoint, but also because they already knew the procedure of the session. Lars makes an analysis of the sound's informative value in the game, and he recalls the game as one in which the player should strive towards keeping the sound level to a minimum. Since guards tend to use their voices when they are suspicious towards the avatar, and the general noise level becomes higher during fights, increased sound level and volume is equal to danger in this game. By connecting sound to danger, Lars suggests that the urgency functions are the most important feature for him. He states:

"[...] In the beginning you encounter swat teams. And they start making remarks here and there sometimes. But usually your meeting with them is very short; either they die or you die. It... you get into a sort of a panic then, because you absolutely don't want to start over again here. [...] And the sound in general is like... yes, you don't like the sound of machine guns. The sound of machine guns means you're dead. [...]" (L3-4)¹²⁷

The player is stressed by suddenly hearing the voices of guards, which means that the avatar's alibi is broken and that they are after him. Consequently, the player must kill or get killed. The same idea relates to the sound of guns. For Lars, these sounds are urgency signals that inform him about immediate danger, and the fact that the situation needs that the player behaves even more carefully or tactically.

6.3.2 Recognizing Game Audio

In the recognition process, the players listened to different sound signals that refer to specific events in the games. When listening to sounds in isolation, the informants either recognize the sound, or they start a process of association based on what they believe the sound refers to. Often the sound can be easily recognized, but out of context the immediate interpretation of the sound may deviate from the actual situation in which it is found. This means that an informant may admit having heard the sound before in the game, but he may not have a clear memory of when or where the sound was heard. In such cases, the informants often start a process of reasoning about the situation that the sound refers to. This reasoning is based on the informants' knowledge of the game and the game mechanics, which means that the reasoning process goes into high detail of the situation in which the sound refers to, and how the informant decides to interpret and act

on that situation. However, in some of the below cases, the challenge is not whether or not a sound is recognized, but whether a situation can be recognized based on a specific, situational based sound.

a) *Warcraft III*: Diegetic Sounds from Battle

The first isolated sound from *W3* played to the informants was sounds of a battle in which night elves and their towers were being attacked by a group of undeads, mainly melee units. The informants were in general able to identify the sound as a battle involving several different units, possibly because the use of iconic auditory icons may have made the association process easy, since they only needed to identify the sounds in order to recognize them. However, out of context some of the informants had difficulties deciding the details of what was going on. Nevertheless, the level of recognition is impressive, and most of the informants were not only able to identify the sound as battle, but they could also mention some of the races or units involved, even though the sound is only played for 9 seconds with no corresponding image.

Lars (L5)¹²⁸ and Stian (S5)¹²⁹ do not agree on who is fighting here. Both identify swords, but while Lars interprets one of the fighting groups to be orcs and does not mention hearing any archers at all, Stian can hear archers and dismisses orcs altogether since they do not have any archers. Both of the informants understand the sound and the situation it refers to very well, and association seems to be an important part of the identification process. It is interesting to see that Stian is reasoning about what he hears, and based on knowledge of game mechanics, he concludes that orcs cannot be part of the fight since this team does not have archers.

Since the sound of battle is heard without any situational data to support it, Anders contextualizes the sound. He points out that it means different things dependent on whether the player himself is in an offensive or defensive position:

“A building is under attack. [...] Then I'll find out.... Well, it depends on where I am in this battle. If I'm the one attacking, I know [my troops] are doing good stuff, and if I'm the one being attacked it's a bad thing. In that case I would try to add troops, retreat, get something done, or just get in someone to repair while the enemies attack.”
(A7)¹³⁰

He points out that these kinds of event sounds may work in two informational ways. To hear the sounds of battle when unprovoked is a typical warning sign, but if the sound appears as a result of one's own attack, the sounds work as response on one's own action. In the first case, the player might get stressed out and will react on the situation immediately. In the second case, the player takes the sound as a confirmation on a command just given, and may go back to do other things on another part of the map.

One of the informants recognizes the sound immediately, but has problems identifying the situation in which it is found. Instead of hearing sounds from a battle, Petter identifies the sound file as a production process connected to one of the buildings:

Petter: "Yes, it's one of the buildings working."

Interviewer: "No, as a matter of fact, it's not."

Petter: "What? It isn't?"

Interviewer: "No, it's probably bad sound quality, but it is actually fighting. You want to play it again?"

Petter: "It sounds like, is it the barracks then?"

Interviewer: "No, it's when.. it's in a fight. So I have some... there's elves versus undeads actually. And I think the elves brought flying units."

[Plays the sound again.]

Petter: "Oh, yes, okay. Crap, I was wrong."

Interviewer: "But why did you think it was..."

Petter: "Hammering, I heard hammering. Hammering on iron. And in that case people work, at least at my place."
(P7a-e)¹³¹

Petter immediately recognizes having heard the sound, but he has problems connecting his memory to a specific situation. Instead he goes into a process of association that makes him identify the sound as something other than it actually represents. Petter explains that the reason for his conclusion is that he hears the sound of hammering on iron, which may be due to low sound quality, as well as the fact that the sound is played out of context. However, as Petter states that it has been a long time since he last played the game, his memory may fail him. It should also be noted that by recognizing a diegetic sound with a naturalistic source in the game environment as a usability oriented transdiegetic sound of recognition, Petter confuses an iconic auditory icon with a non-arbitrary auditory icon sounds. This suggests that he listens for functional sounds more than sounds that seem to belong naturally to the diegesis.

b) *Warcraft III*: Response from a Military Unit

The second sound played to the informants from *W3* was the responding voice of a military unit, the human foot-soldier *footman*. The recording illustrates the footman being selected, and then commanded to move somewhere. The selection is confirmed by the footman's statement "yes, my liege", whereas the command is confirmed by "orders?". Thus, it is a typical example of how the voice in the game is used as a usability feature in the format of a response. This function is obvious to the informants, which all state that this is a unit which is given orders and responds to them. One reason for why it is easy to recognize and identify the sound, is probably because of the use of the human voice, which is an auditory feature that easily sticks to our memory.

None of the informants are in doubt what race we are listening to, and most of them are also certain it is the specific unit *footman*. The quality of the voice and the specific utterance give specific information not only

about race, but also what kind of unit we deal with. Richard also points to another important aspect of the denotation of the sound by underlining the humorous aspect:

“It is a human footman. You’ve obviously selected him several times. (laughter) Just to hear whether he has something funny to say. What I’m thinking, well, I think funny. Just select him to listen to everything he says. That’s what’s funny about Warcraft.” (R10a)¹³²

From experience, the informant has found that the units in *Warcraft III* produce a verbal statement of annoyance if they are selected many times repeatedly. In this respect, the units do not only give the player general feedback and contextual information, it also states something quite specifically that points to the unit as an individual with specific emotional reactions towards the player. Richard hears that the unit is selected several times because of the difference between the two utterances. While “yes, my liege” is a neutral confirmation on selection, “orders?” is posed in a questioning mode as if the unit is waiting further instructions. The more the player clicks on the unit, the more impatient it becomes, and starts asking the player for actual orders following the mouse-click. The footman will eventually say “don’t ask – don’t tell” as if giving up the hope that the player ever will follow up on the initial request.

This identification is result of recognition and not what the informant associates with the specific sound due to two reasons. First of all, he identifies both race and type of unit. Although the sound is an example of the voice used as a non-arbitrary auditory icon, the listener needs to know the game well in order to identify the sound as attached to this specific unit. In addition, he immediately recognizes the questioning mode. This last point could only have been identified by a person who has played the game extensively, and knows the different kinds of responsive sounds that each unit produces.

c) *Warcraft III*: Diegetic Sounds of Wood Chopping

The third sound file from *W3* played to the informants was the sound of workers chopping wood. The recording was done at the very beginning of a game session, and there are not very many wood choppers working at this early stage. It is interesting to see that no informants had problems identifying the sound, although it is a short and subtle sound related to a diegetic process in the game world. Besides, during playing this sound will likely disappear in the presence of other sounds. However, although the sound is an iconic auditory icon, it is hard to decide whether the identification is result of recognition or a process of association. Nevertheless, the informants have different understandings of its functionality, and the interpretations in this respect seem to be based on their knowledge of the role and importance of resource collection in this game.

On the most descriptive level, it was stated that the sound signalled that workers are doing their work. In this respect, it is a symptom of an important ongoing progress, which is of crucial strategic importance for a strategy game: resource collection:

“No, here comes the lumber. Well, er... It tells me actually that wood is on the way. But there is only one chopper, so I would probably reckon that I needed more.” (N8b)¹³³

Nils sees the urge for increasing the number of workers to gain a better strategic position. Hearing the wood chopper in the background is important for the player's knowledge of the status of their resources. Hearing one, on the other hand, underlines an urgent need for more workers. When listening to sounds in isolation, the informant has the opportunity to interpret the sound more than he does during playtime. But it is important to note that he interprets it according to the knowledge he already has about the game and its soundscape, and is thus able to point out more hidden functionalities than he otherwise would be able to do.

Anders' reaction to the sound is biased by the fact that he believes not hearing this sound very often. As well as noting that it is a sign of someone collecting needed resources, he points to the contextual function of the sound: it might also be sign of workers astray, something a player may notice more readily than when workers are in their right places.

“[...] Or if you're in one of the scenarios where you're surrounded by forest, this can actually be a bad sound. Or if you, and if you play, if you played the scenario for some time it might be the case that you, that these workers have gone astray and started to work other places you don't really want them to be.” (A9b)¹³⁴

Hearing sounds of chopping in the wrong places is a bad sign that means that workers may be situated in an area where they can be easily targeted by enemies, or worse – if they chop away some of the forest that actually works as protection against external dangers, the player's entire base might be in danger. In this sense, the chopping of wood may also work as a notification.

d) *Warcraft III*: Response from a Civilian Building

The fourth sound file played for the informants was the sound of selecting a civilian building; more specifically it is the human farm that is selected. The function of this building is to produce food for the workers and soldiers. In the spirit of farms generally, the player hears hens clucking and cows mooing when the building is selected in the format of a non-arbitrary auditory icon. The building is not one being selected too often, since what it produces is automatically registered without the player taking any action. However, the player might select it to find out the production rate of the exact building, but there are better options for finding this out:

“Yes, it is a farm. And it belongs to humans. So... well, it tells me that I can get information about how much food I've got and how much I spend. And then I'll see that the food, I can actually see that on top of the screen, but you're kind of informed about how much you have of different things. [...] No, you tell me [why I would like to

select a farm]. You would rather select the stronghold, because that's where it usually says... well, you can select the enemy's at least. Then you'll get approximate information. But... no, select a farm? Funny sounds? (laughter)" (N9)¹³⁵

The sound from the farm is not a sound commonly heard when playing the game, but still none of the informants had problems identifying it. As other more frequent sounds are in general well remembered, it is as seen above, not always easy to recognize sounds in isolation. There is therefore good reason to believe that less frequent sounds in isolation are more difficult to identify. However, the reason why the sound still is easily identifiable is the fact that the elements in the sound file can easily be associated with civilian activities, and more specifically with farming and primary industries.

However, instead of concluding that this is the sound of a farm, there is another likely interpretation that seems just as likely for those who do not remember the sound but only makes a guess. Stian's first suggestion is that "now you selected a critter" (S8a)¹³⁶, but he does correct himself at once the sound is replayed. Friendly animals such as sheep do walk around the map, and selecting one of these will produce sounds in a similar vein to other selected features. In this sense, Stian's first remark is not an unlikely interpretation. However, the sound is easily recognized for those who pay attention to the sound: if the source of the sound was a cow, then only the moo would be heard, but when it is supported by hens cackling the informant understands that this cannot be the case. In any case, this demonstrates the ambiguity of sounds removed from their visual context (Truax 2000:124), and opens for the likely interpretation that specific game sounds are most easily recognized by players with a certain experience with the specific game. In addition to remembering the exact sound in relation to a situation, the experienced players will also have knowledge of the specific game's structure and mechanics, and may more readily relate a sound to an appropriate in-game situation, although they perhaps do not remember the exact situation of a specific sound.

e) *Warcraft III*: "Our town is under attack!"

The last sound file from *W3* played to the informant was the most easily recognized, as it included specific semantic information about the situation. It is the voiceover of a clearly distressed male human that states that "our town is under attack". This is a high priority urgency signal, as it in all respects calls for the player's attention, not only by featuring a human voice communicating a very specific meaning, but also by being supported by a red mark on the mini-map in the lower left corner. Since this sound presents a very semantic clear message, it could also be easily identified through an associative process. However, since this sound was also one that most informants also were able to recall, it is likely that the sound is recognized.

None of the informants have problems identifying the sound, and the situation related to it, as well as the fact that this is a warning that needs immediate reaction. According to most of the informants, the first action taken is to locate the problem at once this message is displayed (A-11b, L-9b¹³⁷, R-13c)¹³⁸ Once the sound is registered, the informants tend to take a glance to their mini-map to see exactly where the attack is. Based on more specific information gained from the mini-map, the informants will evaluate whether this certain attack is something to be dealt with immediately or not.

“Most often I’ll check, first I look at the mini-map just to see the approximate size of the attackers. If there is only a small red dot, then I usually... then I let them be smashed by my towers. If I see some kind of big dot down there in red or whatever colour the enemies are, then I jump to the town to check, take a look at how big the forces are, see if I have to withdraw my forces to take them out, or if the base’s doing fine. And then I start double-clicking on all kinds of defence structures, so they’ll... all the burrows should be adjusted so they can start shooting and stuff. Then I start... then I activate my defences.” (S9b)¹³⁹

The response pattern demonstrates intimate knowledge with the game, as the informants are all clear on their procedure when this warning is heard. The warning sound comes first; then they will check for visual information about what is going on. In a strategy game like *W3*, it is always crucial to be in control of the situation, but the warning signal informs the player that he is not. Checking the map for location and size of the attacking forces is the most immediate way to re-establish the sense of control, and to be able to evaluate whether immediate action must be taken by the player, or the existing defence structures will be able to handle the attack.

From a theoretical point of view, Anders has an interesting remark related to this voiceover warning. His spontaneous statement is that “there are troops in the area that notify you” (A-11b)¹⁴⁰ about the urgent situation. As researcher, I found this interesting, and I wanted to follow up on this, but now Anders seems uncertain about his own conclusion:

“No, now I’m a little uncertain whether it is or not... or if it is generic sound that notifies you when you’re under attack.” (A11)¹⁴¹

Both his first evaluation of the use of voice, and his following uncertainty picks up a hot potato in relation to sound, sources, and spaces in computer games. It shows a certain awareness not only of extradiegetic space, but also of the fact that the distinction diegetic vs. extradiegetic is even more complicated in games than in films. In his first statement, Anders interprets the sound as diegetic, as if someone within the game space warns the player about it. However, his uncertainty when starting to think about it, reveals that he sees that there is a spatial conflict here. In the first place, if the voiceover is diegetic, it challenges the idea that diegetic characters are oblivious of a space outside the virtual space. At the same time, the voice is stylistically created for the specific race, not only to suit its mood, but also to give the sense of being one of them through the use of the stressed voice of a male. In this sense, it is hard to dismiss the warning to be

extradiegetic, also because it gives specific information about a specific in-game event. It is therefore a good example of a sound's transdiegetic function.

f) *Hitman Contracts*: Sound of a Voice: Denied Entrance

The first sound file played for the *HC* players is taken from "Rendezvous in Rotterdam", the fifth scenario of *Hitman Contracts*. The voice belongs to a Dutch-speaking guard who watches the entrance of a building the player wants to enter. When the avatar approaches the door, the guard says something in Dutch, and ends his line by saying "no entrance." While none of the informants understand the Dutch content, most of them hear the end words, and are able to identify the situation and make a following evaluation of it. In this case, it is not so much a recognition process that is in question as an understanding of the specific message. Most of the informants recognize the situation as one where the avatar is denied entrance and that they have to come up with alternative methods in order to enter the building. The game has several standard ways to solve this problem. Petter goes into detail about different methods through which the current problem can be solved, and sums up three of them:

"[...] The first thing is, shit, I have to find something to let me in, or I have to find another way in, or in pure frustration I murder the guy. But that happens rarely. [laughter] But after five hours of playing and you still can't get past him, then you shoot him." (P8c)¹⁴²

The first solution is to find items that can help him get past the guard. This may include a way to distract the guard, or some kind of disguise that makes the guard let the avatar through. The second solution demands that the player finds another entrance. The third solution is the violent one, and also the less satisfactory one in relation to what the game requests. In the first place, to kill a guard is risky, not only because the player might get caught, but also because the body must be hidden and may be discovered later by patrols. Also, after the scenario is completed, the player gets a rating connected to how discreetly and stealthily he has accomplished the mission. Since each kill will lower this rating, killing guards is not desirable in this game. Petter fulfils the role of an "implied player" well by following these instructions by the game. It is also interesting to see that most of the informants mention finding a disguise is a likely solution. This underlines how the game uses this as a typical method of getting to places the avatar otherwise would not be able to reach. When having the proper disguise, the player can walk about and do things that otherwise would seem suspicious, but as long as the proper outfit is on, the avatar may enter buildings, carry guns, etc. without being noticed. Since this is a very central aspect of the game, many of the informants bring this up.

Rasmus makes another point about the utterance, which is related to the sound itself more than the situation. He notices a peculiarity about the use of Dutch as language in the spoken line, and believes that it is used to increase the sense of presence to the actual setting:

"I couldn't hear what he said, it sounds Russian to me. Or Bulgarian or something. [...] But it is probably to get a somewhat local feeling. Well, if all spoke perfect English with an accent, then it could only, it wouldn't be very realistic in a Rotterdam harbour." (R7d)¹⁴³

Rasmus mentions realism, but he seems to talk about whether the situation is convincing or not. English-speaking persons in non-English communities lack credibility for Rasmus, and it suggests that the speaker believes that the person spoken to is not a native speaker of the local language. For Rasmus, this is unlikely at the entrance of a secret club in the Rotterdam harbour. However, it is important to notice that this directly concerns the sound as such. The earlier examples are concerned with the situation to which the voice hints about, and which follows the use of the voice. From this we can conclude that it is often not the sound itself that is an influence on player behaviour and actions, but the situation to which the sound is part. In this sense, we may say that the sound points to a situation, which again opens for different kinds of actions and reactions.

g) *Hitman Contracts: Violent Action Music*

The second sound played to the informants from *HC* was a piece of music that starts playing when Agent 47 has shot a guard. Other guards nearby are alarmed, and run to locate the shooter. However, the music stops after a while as the guards cannot find anyone when the avatar has hidden in the shadows. Judging from the emphasis on the game's urge for being as silent as possible, this kind of music is not wanted. Thus, it is likely that it is not often heard by players. Also, some scenarios have somewhat different action music, so although the informants might have heard action music earlier, they might not have heard this specific piece.

Most of the informants are able to connect the pace, rhythm and clear melody of the music to some kind of stressful situation, although they are not able to pinpoint it to a specific scenario. Lars' description is the most accurate, and also a very honest one, as he underlines that he cannot remember having heard the specific piece at all, and that this is what he associates with the music:

"It... well, now I can't remember that sound from the game at all. But what I'd connect with it is either a scene where I had to fight or an escape scene." (L7a)¹⁴⁴

Both fight and escape correspond to the actual event, as the music is triggered by the player's shot and would continue during the following shooting scene between the avatar and the guards. The music would also continue until either party was dead, or the player was able to get the avatar into safety, which is the case in

the actual example. Geir relates the music to running, or running out of time, while Rasmus supports Lars' view that this might be some kind of chase music. However, Rasmus notes that it is very traditional in this respect, and that it just as well could have been found in a film:

"Er... I think I've heard it before, but I can't assign it to a scenario. I know it's something, it reminds me of some kind of chase music. If it's chase or something else, Russian soldiers or something. I don't think it's extremely exciting. Well, it's quite classical, like, standard chase music. There's nothing to it that makes it belong to Hitman. It could just as well be a film, I think." (R9a)¹⁴⁵

Rasmus underlines that the music itself speaks of a general type of situation known from audiovisual media. It is not the specific musical piece that points to something in the game, but to generic situations from mainstream audiovisual media. It is interesting that the pace, rhythm and general feel of the music trigger associative processes in both Rasmus and Lars, who produce valid interpretations that are quite close to the actual situation. This is of course due to the fact that all informants are highly familiar with the use of music in audiovisual media, and know how these connect specific kinds of music with specific types of events.

h) *Hitman Contracts*: Signal Messages

The last sound from *HC* played to the informants was the beep that follows written notifications. The sound used is a non-musical earcon, a synthetic and abstract sound with no specific associations connected to it. It is quite neutral and very brief, so the sound file played consisted of the signal played twice, in order for the informants to be able to attend to it. The briefness of the sound as well as its neutrality makes the sound non-descript and possibly also hard to identify. Nevertheless, the sound is easily associated with the interface, possibly because there are few other situations to which the sounds seem suitable, but not many recognized it as the sound connected to the coloured notification boxes. Geir, Petter and Rasmus pinpointed the sound directly to the actual situation, while Anders and Lars connected the sound to the map and low health respectively.

"Isn't that something like "objectives updated" or something? [...] You've done something you were supposed to. Alternatively, you're starting a scenario."(G9a-b)¹⁴⁶

Geir is hesitant about the accuracy of his memory, and due to this, association is the guiding principle when he identifies the sound. He also notices that this sound appears when starting a new scenario. Immediately after the scenario has loaded, the player receives a message in the upper corner telling him that new objectives are available, and that entering the briefing menu will reveal what these are. The informants are thus able to connect the message to usability functions, possibly because of its neutral quality that is easiest related to computer interfaces that often use similar signals.

Rasmus notes that this little message is very useful when the player is in a busy situation, but underlines that the sound itself is not what makes him notice the message. The box with the clear colour is what actually draws attention:

"[...] It's like if you just did something, and now you've started a busy scene, then you can hear it becomes updated. And you can see the small, very visible blue or something above. [...] [I notice] the blue box, because it's very minimalistic the interface they've chosen. It's just your health down in the corner and your... then there aren't more really. So if there is a colour blue, you notice it immediately. [...]" (R8)¹⁴⁷

He explains that the blue frame is very visible since the rest of the interface is so minimalist. This makes the blue frame even more visible; even when the player is busy in a violent situation, he will notice this. But he thinks the sound is superfluous. It is not a sound he really pays attention to, and he has never reflected on its presence or its quality. Also, he believes he could very well manage without it, since the visual aspects about the notification is seeking his attention so successfully.

It is interesting to see that they all remember the sound in its positive context. Why is this so? Perhaps positive messages are more noteworthy and memorable than negative or neutral notifications. Memory is selective, and the informants' memories seem to have selected the positive aspects around the game play situation as such.

6.3.3 Memories of Sound in Other Games

As a concluding theme for the conversation, the informants picked up to three games that they found interesting in relation to sound. The games were freely chosen, but some of the informants had earlier in the interview mentioned other games. In those cases, the informants were asked to follow up on these games, and compare their soundscapes to that of *W3* and *HC*. The informants were generally very capable of mentioning games in which they found the sound important, but many of them had problems going into details about how the sound worked in the other games. Problems were also encountered when they tried to compare other games to the game in question with specific focus on the functionality of the sound. The problems support the fact that it may be hard to recall and keep hold of memories of sound without any specific situation to connect it with. But the mere fact that they are able to recall soundscapes, and talk about the specific atmosphere they create also supports the idea that sound may be easier recalled when there is a situation and a context to connect it with.

However, it is also easier to remember sound that is used in a novel or unfamiliar way, as Petter demonstrates by two of his examples, namely *Star Wars Galaxies* and *Sid Meyer's Pirates!* Petter has played the MMORPG

Star Wars Galaxies extensively in the period leading up to the interview, and he points out that it is possible to play the game music as a musician in the game. *Sid Meyer's Pirates!* has a dancing sequence where the player must follow the rhythm of the music to succeed. It is also possible to exchange the music for any music the player wants, and configure the avatar's dance move accordingly. These are situations in which sound is used in non-standard ways, but Petter is clearly fascinated by these novel combinations of music and gameplay, which demonstrate that using game sound in experimental ways is interesting and attracts players (P37-39).

Another aspect that several informants point out, though, is the general soundscape and how sound is used for atmospheric purposes. A game which is chosen by Richard (R40), Stian (S43) and Anders is *Doom 3*, in which they all report being scared by the soundscape. Anders underlines how the game utilizes auditory techniques he previously knows from horror movies:

"[...] In *Doom 3*, there's a great focus on sound, that's what scares you. Well, it's dark, and then there's a hissing sound behind you, and you turn around and then it turns out to be only a gas leakage, and then the actual monster stands behind you again screaming, right. [...] And they use the unfair techniques like something falling down from the roof making a sound behind you that makes, right, when you know that now, now there must be a monster around, and you jump in the chair and there's nothing. It's the good old horror movie techniques. And they work." (A43h-i)¹⁴⁸

Doom 3 utilizes the player's experience from other games which tells that sounds provide information about offscreen events in the environment, and that the player should be certain to react to them in order to succeed in the game. *Doom 3* turns these expectancies upside down and fools the player into reacting to the wrong sounds. Anders calls it horror movie techniques, but it is actually horror movie techniques taken a step further. The player is not limited to sit passively like a film viewer and watch the protagonist react to different sounds – the player is the one to get through with it and evaluate what are the correct reactions in all situations.

Stian (S42) and Lars compare the audio in *Halo 2* with the audio in *W3*, and both suggest that it is the action movie feeling of the game that makes the difference. While the adaptive music of *Halo 2* is what Lars points to first, what he describes best is how the use of voices differs between the games:

"*Halo* has voice-acting in the same manner, just that, but you don't exactly click on people there. In *Halo* it's more when you're close to other marines they start doing things, such as commenting on stuff the way you can imagine marines would do. And since you're the hero you actually are, and not quite ordinary, they do anything to show off in your presence. [...] I think *Warcraft* is very good especially on humans, because there it is, well, you have a small hierarchy, peasants are gullible and naïve and willing to work, and also jump out and die for you. Soldiers are a little more like, er.. they seem to be more clear-headed." (L35a)¹⁴⁹

Lars points out a difference in autonomy between the units in *W3* and the non-player characters in *Halo 2*, which is strengthened by the specific use of sound. *Halo 2* has non-playing characters that support the player in action, and they act and talk directly to the avatar when they are close to him. The game tries to create an illusion of a naturalistic universe by the use of dynamic characters that behave and sound like individuals with

a certain relationship to the avatar. *W3*, on the other hand, also utilizes voices of recognition to individualize the units and make them appear human. However, since the utterances produced by the *W3* units are immediate responses to player actions, and the same lines are produced over and over again, they appear as having clear usability functions. In this sense, the non-player characters in *Halo 2* seem more autonomous and intelligent than the units in *W3*.

Several of the *HC* informants compare the game to the *Metal Gear Solid* series, which is considered being the origin of the stealth game genre due to its agent theme in which stealth often is an optimal strategy. Lars points to *Metal Gear Solid* as a game which is similar both in terms of genre and the use of music, but believes that *Metal Gear Solid* communicates to the player in a more direct sense. Compared to this game, *HC* becomes almost too subtle in its communication (L29a¹⁵⁰). Geir has also noticed this auditory difference between the two games, but his memory tells him *Metal Gear Solid* exaggerates the sound in order to make the game sound more impressive (G12)¹⁵¹. Rasmus points to similarities in the voice-acting between the two games, and emphasises that since both games have distinct characters in the role as agent, the developers of both have ensured that the actors behind the voices of these character have voices that fit the hardened action hero in both games (Ra31)¹⁵².

Since Petter, Lars and Anders also participated in the *W3* study, it is intuitive for them to compare the sound of *HC* to the sound of *W3*. Lars finds this the time to moderate his initial critique of *W3*'s soundscape, and emphasises that different game genres need to utilize different conventions concerning the implementation of sound (L28)¹⁵³. In this respect Petter specifies that *W3* is noisier and that the sounds in this game draw more attention than the sound of *HC*, which he believes has a more serious and realistic feel (P39)¹⁵⁴. Anders goes even further and suggests that the use of sound in *HC* underlines its existence as virtual environment, while *W3* conforms to the usability paradigm:

"Well... the sound in Hitman is more there to place you where you actually - like Hitman. You have the disco music when you're in the discotheque and you hear how it fades out, you have much more the distance sound. While in Warcraft sounds are there to.. to inform that things are ready and so on. [...] They have this feature of distance to sound related to where you focus your attention on some things, but usually you hear sounds just as clearly regardless of where you are. (A40)¹⁵⁵

Anders describes how *HC* is a game that places the player in the middle of the environment, cast in the role as the avatar, while *W3* provides the player with necessary information about all events regardless of his visual orientation and proximity to the events in question. In this sense, he points out that the orientational function of sound is most important in *HC*, while the usability function has heavier emphasis in *W3*.

6.3.4 Summary: Memories of Game Audio

Although the two games focus on different uses of sound in the sense that *HC* masks usability sounds as motivated by the virtual world, while *W3* makes diegetic sounds stand out from the virtual world by giving them clear usability roles, players' memories of audio in the two games is more or less equal. The players' familiarity with the games makes them very able to both recognize and recall how audio is used.

Reviewing the informants' ability to recall game audio, we find that the original hypothesis claiming that computer game players are generally quite unaware of music and sound in games must be rejected. Although the informants have initial difficulties in producing clear memories, they are able to provide a good understanding of the role of sound when having discussed the topic a little. Recall seems to be easier when asked about specific kinds of sounds, such as music or the use of voices. In this sense, contextualization in and familiarity with the games in question are important for the process of recall. It is interesting to see the informants' recall memory is focused around functional aspects of the sound. The *W3* informants focus on how the voices are used for communicative purposes, while the *HC* informants focus on the use of adaptive music.

In connection with recognition of game audio, there is no problem for experienced players to identify and contextualize sounds from familiar games. However, in many cases it may be hard to say whether it is an associative process or their ability to recognize the sound that helps them in the identification process. This is especially the case when the auditory signal is an auditory icon, since the associations to sounds in the real world make the identification process easier. However, in some cases when auditory icons are used, the listener still needs to know the game mechanics in order to understand exactly what event or unit a sound refers to. In any respect, when the player has identified a sound they have no problems describing situations in which that sound was heard, and how they would react to that situation according to the game's overall mechanics. This finding supports the view of ecological psychoacoustics that contextualized sound is easier to remember and understand.

In connection with recalling sound in other games, it is important to keep in mind that the informants' memories of sound are subjects to associative processes. This means that it is reasonable to assume that the informants point out these games not because they remember detailed information about the role of the sound, but because they remember that the game sound was noticeable somehow. This is also supported by the fact that the informants' comparisons are quite vague, and that an informant such as Petter points to games that utilize sound in an unconventional manner. Another thing that supports this is that the

comparisons between *W3* and *HC* by those who played both contain greater details than the other comparisons.

6.4 *Hitman Contracts vs. Warcraft III: Comparative Remarks*

The empirical studies have been carried out for the sake of making a theory about how game audio relates to player action in computer games, and the studies have uncovered different functionalities in relation to this. These can be categorized as *atmospheric* functions, *orienting* functions, and *usability* functions.

In both *HC* and *W3* are sound used for atmospheric functions, although in different ways. *HC* creates an atmosphere by focusing on different kinds of music that merge with each other and with the ambient background sounds of the environment. By making the music adapt to different situations, the game ensures that each situation and location have music that fits the context. When the music merges with the ambient environmental sounds, the music communicates subtly by giving the impression of being natural to the environment at the same time as it emphasises a specific mood. In this sense it has an external transdiegetic feature since it is situated externally from the game universe although it gives the impression of being heard by characters in the game. On the contrary, *W3* situates the music in an extradiegetic position with no relevance for the course of events in the game. Instead it works as a background feature that tries to provide the general feeling of the specific team played. *W3* emphasises moods in another manner. By letting every unit in the game have its own unique and distinct voice, the game emphasises the identity of the units in a stereotypical and exaggerated manner. In this sense, the units become caricatures of a medieval military hierarchy, and the game appears as a humoristic version of a fantasy world.

As a general remark in connection with atmosphere, it is interesting to see that in the case of both games, the sense of presence in the game universe seemed to disappear when the sound was removed from the game. The game world become less lifelike, and the events and objects in the game world lose their sense of physicality. The absence of sound also makes it much clearer to the players that the game and the game world are constructs and artefacts. In this way, sound is a powerful feature in terms of defining the game world as a coherent space for action.

The orienting functions of game audio are also evident in *W3* and *HC*. In *HC*, the sound seems to surround the avatar in a similar manner to how sound surrounds human beings in our everyday environment. This means that there are a lot of sound sources placed outside the visual range of the avatar, and distance to sound sources are marked by differences in volume. Sound also works for orienting purposes in *W3*, but in

this game, the sound does not communicate to the players as if they were characters in the game world. Instead, sound is used in order to make the player have control over all areas simultaneously, regardless of the distance to events. Sound works instead as a control system that via notifications and responses from the units, and the use of voice-overs to inform the player about a change in status in all available areas.

It is important to point out that also the orienting role of sound in both games is affected when the sound is removed. In addition to removing all feedback from the environment, the player cannot any longer sense the presence of offscreen objects and events. Consequently, the sense of control disappears, and although the player is still able to play the game successfully, it becomes much harder doing so. However, some of the informants report an increase sense of control in the absence of sound. It becomes easier to play the game in a calculated manner since the sense of presence in the world disappears and the player becomes emotionally detached from the game universe.

The research has also demonstrated how game audio are used for usability purposes such as providing *reactive* and *proactive* messages to player activities. These messages are communicated to the player through the use of two kinds of auditory signals. *Auditory icons* can be recognized as sounds adopted from real-world events and used for a communicative purpose. *Earcons* are aestheticized sounds and musical pieces created artificially for communicative purposes. While auditory icons are easily recognized as corresponding to a real-world event, earcons must be learned before they can be recognized. *W3* and *HC* utilize both of these signals for reactive and proactive purposes, but in very different ways.

Below are overviews of how sound signals are used in both games, and what usability functions these have based on the above player studies. The first overview points out that *earcons* in *W3* tend to be *external transdiegetic* and *responsive*. They are external transdiegetic since they have no direct connection to sources within the game world, but are relevant for events taking place within that world.. The *level fanfare* that works as a low priority urgency message breaks with this, and emphasises that earcons also can be low priority urgency messages found in an internal transdiegetic position. However, due to the diegetic origin of this low priority urgency signal (the bright light surrounding the hero unit is its origin), we could accept the idea that characters in the universe of Warcraft experience this game system feature as existing in their world as a physical signal marking a person's advancement in skill, and in this respect the sound should be interpreted as an iconic auditory icon.

Earcon	Non-arbitrary Auditory Icons	Semantic Use of Voice	Iconic Auditory Icons
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Confirmation</i>: interface click (external transdiegetic) - <i>Rejection</i>: disharmonic squeak (internal transdiegetic) - <i>Neutral information</i>: upkeep gong (external transdiegetic) - <i>Low priority urgency</i>: level fanfare (internal transdiegetic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Confirmation</i>: unit – “All right” (internal transdiegetic) - <i>Inquiry</i>: unit – “What do you want” (internal transdiegetic) - <i>Low priority urgency</i>: units and buildings make a sound when produced (internal transdiegetic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Instructions</i>: “We need more gold” (external transdiegetic) - <i>Low priority urgency</i>: “Summoning complete” (external transdiegetic) - <i>High priority urgency</i>: “Our forces are under attack” (external transdiegetic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Detailed information</i>: overview in chaotic situations (diegetic) - <i>Low priority urgency</i>: secure player awareness of activities and processes (diegetic) - <i>High priority urgency</i>: warning about events (diegetic)

Figure 8: Sound signals and their usability functions in Warcraft III.

Non-arbitrary auditory icons in *W3* are always *internal transdiegetic* by being produced by units and buildings that exist in the game world while directly addressing the player who has no game-internal existence. Like the earcons, these signals tend to be responsive, but in some cases they may provide low priority urgency messages. This means that auditory icons, like earcons, never are connected to events that need immediate attention. On the other hand, the *semantic use of voice* in *W3* has a proactive focus by delivering urgency messages as well as instructions which are characterized by having both reactive and proactive roles. These are *external transdiegetic* by not being connected to an identified diegetic object, but instead taking on the role as voiceover system messages commenting on diegetic events.

It is characteristic for *iconic auditory icons* in *W3* that they are connected to *diegetic* objects and events in the same causal manner as the corresponding real world sound and its referent. Since the auditory signal is based on a natural relationship between sound and referent, the referent seems to produce the sound due to physical circumstances, and the sound gives the impression of not being communicative for any purpose. This makes the sound *symptomatic*. In this respect, iconic auditory icons do not have defined usability functions, but their informative role depends instead of the situation. This means that in some cases, the iconic auditory icons produce more detailed information than visual information can do alone (i.e. what weapons the enemy is fighting with), while in other cases, the sound may provide different degrees of urgent information (i.e. provide awareness of an event, or warnings if the event happens at a critical spot).

Iconic Auditory Icons	Non-musical Earcons	Musical Earcons	Semantic Use of Voice
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Confirmation</i>: knife hits (diegetic) - <i>Rejection</i>: knife misses (diegetic) - <i>Low priority urgency</i>: sound of distant voices (diegetic) - <i>High priority urgency</i>: guard shouting (diegetic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Confirmations</i>: menus and inventory sounds (external transdiegetic). - <i>Low priority urgency</i>: mission updates in green box. Hints in blue box (external transdiegetic) - <i>High priority urgency</i>: warnings in red box (external transdiegetic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Confirmations</i>: the player did something successfully (external transdiegetic) - <i>Rejections</i>: player did something unsuccessfully (external transdiegetic) - <i>Urgency</i>: player enters important area. Combat situation (external transdiegetic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Cutscene voice</i>: communication between characters is displayed in a cutscene (diegetic) - <i>Briefing menu voiceover</i>: the player/avatar receives mission objectives (internal transdiegetic) - <i>Agent voiceover</i>: focalized information from avatar (internal transdiegetic)

Figure 9: Sound signals and their usability functions in *Hitman Contracts*.

The second overview points out the usability of the different auditory signals in *HC*. In this game *iconic auditory icons* are *diegetic* in the same sense as iconic auditory icons in *W3*. They are used both for reactive and proactive purposes, and in the case of urgency sounds, the priority level depends on the exact situation. However, iconic auditory icons in this game can be easily separated into usability functions although they are symptomatic by appearing non-communicative. This means that although the specific usability function may vary, in some cases a sound has a specific usability role (i.e. the sound of a knife that hits and misses).

Non-musical earcons in *HC* are *external transdiegetic* since they are system messages marked as such by being attached to coloured messages or to the interface while also referring to events in the game world. They focus on *urgency* functions, but they also exist as confirmative responses when the player chooses options from the menus. The *musical earcons* are also *external transdiegetic* by being placed in the game as background music that adapt to certain situations. They also work both proactively and reactively by providing the player with information about specific locations and about the player's performance.

The semantic use of voice is rare in this game, and is only used to convey specific pieces of information. They always seem to have a direct relationship to the game world, but since their function is to provide the player with important pieces of information, they have an *internal transdiegetic* touch. Cutscene information is the only truly diegetic semantic use of voice, which adopts the style and the relationship to the virtual world from films. The briefing menu is from one point of view diegetic by posing as an in-game diegetic feature (an assassin's PDA) addressing the avatar. From another point of view, however, it is internal transdiegetic by being a system feature that addresses the player with game objectives, at the same time as it seems to be an in-game diegetic feature. When the avatar's voiceover is used to provide hints, the sound is diegetic by being focalized version of a character's thought, but in the same way as Agent 47's PDA it can be seen as internal

transdiegetic since functionally, the voice is there to provide the player with hints about how to complete the mission.

We see that in *HC*, the degree of urgency very often depends on the situation. Whether a sound should be interpreted as a warning or a notification relates to the player's appearance and the guards' level of attention. Also, the usability functions in this game are not always evident, because they are masked either as symptomatic sounds from the environment or as background music based on the same conventions as narrative film music. Another interesting observation is that *HC* only in rare and specific cases utilizes *internal transdiegetic* sounds. The reason for this is the presence of an avatar which works as an interface between the player and the game world, and which all sounds may be directed towards. In this respect, it seems that diegetic entities react towards the presence of another diegetic entity instead of towards a player situated external to the game space.

W3, on the other hand, utilizes internal transdiegetic sounds to a large degree. This is the result of the player having no avatar, and thus communication that regards the player directly addresses the player situated external to the game world. Also, it is important for the game never to create doubt about what the sound refers to, due to the player's distance to diegetic action, the high tempo of the game, and the fact that there are a lot of processes that need to be managed simultaneously. Concerning usability, the game utilizes sound for such purposes in a very direct way, and does not attempt to mask the functionality in any respect. The game operates with a very detailed response system, and separates clearly between two priority levels in relation to urgency signals. This game also separates between four kinds of auditory signals which focus on different kinds of functionality, which is illustrated in the figure below:

This figure takes into account that there are some sounds that have *reactive* and *proactive* properties at the same time, and describes the relation between reactive and proactive signalling functions as a continuum where traditional *response sounds* are the purest reactive sounds, while *high priority urgency sounds* are the purest proactive sounds. *Instructions* are defined as sounds that have equal reactive and proactive properties.

In this figure, we see how the use of *earcons* are balanced towards having reactive functions; *non-arbitrary auditory icons* tend to be reactive but may also have low priority urgency purposes; the *semantic use of voice* has proactive purposes; while *iconic auditory icons* may have both reactive and proactive functions.

7. Conclusions

This thesis has investigated game audio functionality in computer games with focus on its relationship to actions and events in games, and has demonstrated that sound is functionally connected to both player actions and other events in the game world. Game audio provides proactive and reactive information that the players utilize in order to orient themselves and when evaluating what actions they should take. Although it is possible to play a game successfully without sound, the effort is greater since it becomes difficult to register information that the visual system has a hard time attending to. In demonstrating the functional aspect of game audio, this thesis has also revealed that sound connects the world of computer usability with the virtual world of the game. As a functional combination of two different worlds, computer game audio works to create a sense of presence in a living virtual environment, at the same time as it supports the usability of the game system. This combination distorts the sense of a coherent virtual world, and breaks with the common separation between diegetic and extradiegetic spaces, and has therefore been explained as the *transdiegetic* function of game audio.

The research is based on the investigation of the use of sound in the stealth-based action game *Hitman Contracts* and the real-time strategy game *Warcraft III*. The games have been analysed with respect to how audio relates to player actions and other events, and empirical players of the games in question have been interviewed and observed while playing in order to study the experience and comprehension of audio in these games. Also, a game audio development team has been interviewed to get insight into the intentions and purposes behind the inclusion of a specific kind of game audio. By investigating two games that give the player different kinds of access to the game world, and that present different challenges on part of the player, the thesis has demonstrated that game audio can be realized in very different ways while also keeping some common basic functional roles. This chapter will summarize the specific functions of game audio identified in this study, and also emphasise other interesting findings that the present research has uncovered.

7.1 The *Transdiegetic* Function

The perhaps most important discovery in this project is the *transdiegetic* function in computer games. Disrupting the traditional divide between diegetic and extradiegetic space, the *transdiegetic* function merges the usability features of a game with those features that support the sense of presence in the virtual world, thereby creating a communicative interface feature that allows the player access to the game world while

maintaining the sense of a coherent virtual world. In connection with game audio, the transdiegetic function works in two ways. When working from an *internal* position, it allows game audio with a perceived source within the game world to take on system message properties by directly addressing entities external to the game world, typically the real world player. Alternatively, the transdiegetic function works from an *external* position, from which it allows game audio with no conceptual source in the virtual world to address entities and events inside the game world. In this sense, the transdiegetic function overrides the traditional division between diegetic and extradiegetic sounds, by providing them both with a system message function where they become parts of the interface at the same time as they belong to the virtual world. In the case of diegetic sound, it becomes an integrated and natural part of the game world at the same time as it is an interface sound supporting the player's access to the game world. In the case of extradiegetic sound, it becomes a commenting aesthetic feature that has a dramatic and mood-enhancing role while also being interface sounds that provides specific information relevant for actions and events in the game world.

In connection with game audio, the use of two techniques support and make possible the transdiegetic function. These techniques are the use of *auditory icons* and *earcons*. Since auditory icons are real world sounds adopted for a communicative purpose, they are useful when integrating the usability function with the virtual world. In this sense, the sound seems to be motivated by being natural to the game environment, at the same time as it provides the player with information relevant for the improved usability of the system. On the contrary, earcons may be said to work the other way around. The use of artificially created and aestheticized sounds for communicative purposes contributes to a certain auditory message becoming very noticeable or event disturbing. Such sounds may therefore draw attention to themselves even when they are directly linked to specific situations in the game world, which is exemplified by the negative responsive squeak that accompanies illegal actions in *W3*. However, the use of game music as earcon does not seem disturbing because it utilizes conventions from film music and contributes to the mood of the game. This demonstrates that when earcons are conventionalized or made familiar in any one setting, they become accepted as belonging to that world.

By conforming to the theories of auditory display studies, computer game audio is utilized as a semiotic system. This is demonstrated by the fact that the sound signals are used for communicative purposes in order to point to specific events or situations besides themselves. However, this does not mean that game audio can be said to refer to a specific visual object, but that the sound refers to a situation as a whole. When the player hears the footman unit in *W3* say "orders?", the sound does not work as a reference to the footman, but to a situation in which the unit has been selected and is waiting for further commands. When the player hears

the music in *HC* change from soft ambient music and into a fast-paced melody, this is not a reference to the guards who are hunting Agent 47 down, but to a critical situation in which Agent 47 is being hunted down.

It should be noted that the transdiegetic function has important implications not only for game audio, but for the understanding of computer games in general. It concerns how the player comes to understand games as a separate field of reference, and how communication can take place within different frames of reference at the same time without creating confusion in the player (Thorhaug 2003). Connecting the level of the interface with the level of the virtual world, the transdiegetic function is also relevant for describing the relationship between avatar and player, and how the interface and system messages work as information systems in computer games. In this sense, the transdiegetic function is defined as the ability of game features to connect the virtual world with the interface, thereby creating a new frame of reference that invites the player into the game world while maintaining the sense of a game world separate from our own world.

7.2 Other Functions

Although the transdiegetic function is the overarching function of game audio, there are several important subcategories. Most closely related to the transdiegetic function are the *usability functions* and the *atmospheric function* of game audio. As a usability feature, sound works to provide the player with information relevant for actions and events in the game. Sound may have a *reactive role* where it appears immediately after a player action and works as a response signal, or it may have a *proactive role* where it works to provide urgent information about an upcoming situation that the player needs to evaluate. Different games and different genres may prioritize the reactive and proactive roles differently, and due to the transdiegetic function, the usability role of game audio may often be masked by being music that follows the drama of the situation, or by being integrated into the game world as diegetic sound. In such situations, usability sounds may also support the atmospheric function of game audio. In the case of music, it may adapt to the situation, thereby being connected to usability by providing reactive or proactive information to the player, while also supporting a specific mood presented by musical features such as genre, instrumentation, tempo or pitch. When usability sounds are integrated into the virtual world of the game, they may also have an atmospheric role by supporting the sense of presence in the game environment and making the virtual world seem more lifelike. However, the atmospheric function of game audio does not always have to be connected to usability. A lot of sounds such as ambient sound and music primarily support a sense of atmosphere or mood. Instead of being present in the game to influence player action, they are there for the primary purpose of providing a

sense of presence in the game world. Such sounds are often present as background noises with no specific connection to a source.

Game audio also has important *orienting functions* which were most clearly revealed by the players comments on how they experienced playing computer games with the sound turned off. Because of the informative properties, the orienting functions of game audio are also connected to usability. In addition to having the ability to point out the direction and distance to objects and events, sound may inform the player about the presence of specific, and potentially threatening, objects. In this respect, sound may also work as an attractor that draws attention towards events and objects in the environment. It is also interesting to see that sound works as a control system that provides the players with information about situations outside their line of sight. In this way, audio enables the player to keep track of events in the game world, especially in the sense of orienting the player that certain processes are complete or still going on. Another orienting role of game audio is to provide information that the visual system may have problems registering. In this respect, audio may provide more detailed information than graphics. A last important role of game audio which is connected to the orienting functions is that sound may *identify* objects in the game world, and more specifically, it may be used to indicate the value of objects. As a system of recognition, sound may have properties that signal its relative power compared to other objects, or its status in relation to the player as enemy or friend.

These functions demonstrate that game audio relates to actions and events in different ways. Audio provides specific information related to player actions and events in the game environment, and it also provides the player with better understanding for the dynamics of the game system by pointing out what events and actions are important.

7.3 Comparative Observations

Although the above functions of game audio may be traced in most computer games, the studies of two very different games have revealed that different genres focus realize game audio functionality in separate ways. The reason for this is that they represent different kinds of challenges. *W3* emphasises its own existence as a user system and a computer application while also drawing on conventions from classical strategy board games. *HC*, on the other hand, attempts to create a credible virtual environment more similar to that we find in cinema. This is further emphasised by the fact that the player's access to the two games are of very different kinds: in *W3*, the player has no extension into the game world, but moves instead pawns around on a map, but in *HC*, the player acts directly in the game world through the avatar. This affects the realization of sound in

these games: In *W3*, sound works to extend the player's visual perception, while in *HC* sound has a supportive role related to the situation as a whole. In this respect, *W3* focuses on usability purposes where sound is used as an informative system that provides detailed response and urgency messages, while *HC* is primarily based on conventions from film in which the emotional aspect and the use of sound for dramatic purposes are in focus.

The differences in challenge and positioning of the player also affect the use of transdiegetic sounds. *HC* utilizes *external transdiegetic* sounds to a great degree, but never takes advantage of internal transdiegetic sounds. This is illustrated by the heavy use of music that, classically speaking, would be called extradiegetic, but which is used in this game to provide both reactive and proactive information relevant for what happens in the game world. *W3*, on the other hand, uses *internal transdiegetic* sounds actively, in addition to taking advantage of external transdiegetic sounds. The internal transdiegetic function is demonstrated by sounds with diegetic sources that directly addresses the player. The reason for this difference is that contrary to *HC*, there is no avatar in *W3*. The presence of an avatar as a personification within the virtual world makes it possible for entities within the game to address the avatar. This means that guards in *HC* may shout at Agent 47, thereby containing the communication within the game world. This is, however, not possible in *W3*, where the absence of an avatar forces in-game entities to address the player directly. This means that a unit in the game must speak directly to the player who is situated outside the game world, thereby disrupting the sense that the game world is a coherent and separate space of action.

More specifically, this difference means that the games focus on different uses of sounds. *HC* combines the *reflexive* and the *indicative relationship* between sound and listener, and utilizes therefore sound for atmospheric and informative purposes simultaneously. This allows the game to communicate through a typical mood-enhancing auditory feature such as music. *HC* may therefore communicate certain kinds of information to the player in a subtle manner. The use of iconic auditory icons also supports the subtle communication by letting sounds seem motivated by the realism of the game world. *W3*, on the contrary, focuses on the *indicative relationship* between sound and listener by utilizing easily recognizable sounds such as voices and non-arbitrary auditory icons. The messages found within these types of signals are easily communicated because they do not mask the sounds as atmospheric background sounds or sounds that are only present due to a naturalistic purpose. In this sense, although both games utilize sound for both purposes, *HC* puts most emphasis on the atmospheric function, while *W3* gives more attention to the usability functions of game audio.

7.4 Methodology & Empirical Studies

A very fruitful part of this project has been the player observations and conversations. Due to the careful interview design, the player studies have revealed invaluable information about how the players interpret and relate to auditory information in *HC* and *W3*. The fact that the informants were able to provide very detailed information about how individual sounds work in the game context is interesting in several respects. It is interesting for computer game studies in general because it tells us something about how players understand the role of sound within the game system, and how they see computer game audio as an important communicative system that provides information relevant to player actions, events in the game environment, and about the game mechanics. Moreover, the procedure used in the empirical studies is also interesting for computer game research in general. The combination of interviews, observations, and conversations about the recorded playing has proved useful for research on actual computer game players and how they understand their own role in the playing situation. The player studies are also interesting to auditory research in a greater context since it is a study of the use of audio in an actual situation. In this respect, the study supports ecological psychoacoustics since it has revealed that auditory information may be easily remembered, easily recognized and easily learned as long as the listener understands the setting and the relevance for the audio in question.

Although the game audio developer interviews only have addressed the developers of one of the games, it has proved fruitful on a general for understanding level what terms and constraints game audio developers work under, and how this frames the actual audio development of a game. The technical and the creative constraints demonstrated by the audio developers illustrate general problems that all game developers face, and are relevant for the understanding of the conditions under which both games have been created. Also, the game audio developers' understanding of the role of sound in games in general is something that concerns both of the games in this study. In this respect, the game audio developers' intentions of a specific audio design and attitudes towards sound in general have helped me develop a player interview guide specifically designed for the study of game audio in context.

7.5 Future Research?

As a last comment for the summary of this thesis, it is important to point out which of the projects observations and methods may be interesting to develop further. First of all, it is the methodological aspect. The specific interview design developed for the player studies is an interesting way to do empirical game research, since it

not only studies games and gameplay in context, but it allows the player to study it in a close to normal setting. There are no interruptions, and depending on the resources available, it is possible to do similar studies at the informant's home or at cybercafés. Also, due to the video capturing, it is possible to make the players explain and interpret their own gaming activity in retrospect, either immediately after playing, or at a later point in time. A fortunate side effect of this kind of research is that the video captures provide the researcher with a second source of data in addition to the recorded conversations. The video captures may be studied more or less closely related to what kind of research is being undertaken. Nevertheless, when doing research on actual player behaviour, gameplay and the understanding of the game system, an analysis of this kind of information is invaluable.

There are of course also theoretical observations done in this project that deserve further attention. First of all, it is the fact that game audio conforms to the theories of auditory display studies. This means that game audio is a semiotic signalling system and that game audio developers, to an even greater degree, should use auditory display theories when designing audio for games. A related research project could explore the relations between auditory display studies and game audio design both in a comparative perspective and in order to find out what the two can learn from each other. However, a project derived from the findings in this thesis and which would be a further development of this precise study would be to further investigate the concept of the *transdiegetic*. The transdiegetic has been the concept specifically explanatory for game audio functionality and why it is realized as a merging between usability system and virtual world. But it is still not relevant only for game audio. It has also relevance for computer game studies in general since it explains why the graphical user interface does not feel disturbing, it explains inventories and other kinds of menus, and not least – it explains the dual role of computer game audio.

References

Literature

- Aarseth, Espen (1995): "Dataspilletts diskurs. Mellom folkediktning og kulturindustri", in *Perifraser*. Department of Comparative Literature, University of Bergen.
- Aarseth, Espen (1997): *Cybertext. Perspectives on Ergodic Literature*. Baltimore, London: The Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Aarseth, Espen (2000): "Allegories of Space: The Question of Spatiality in Computer Games". In Eskelinen, Markku and Raine Koskimaa (eds.) *Cybertext Yearbook 2000*, University of Jyväskylä.
- Aarseth, Espen (2004): "Genre Trouble: Narrativism and the Art of Simulation", in Wardrip-Fruin, Noah & Pat Harrigan (eds.): *First Person. New Media as Story, Performance, and Game*. Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press.
- Altman, Rick (1992): "Four and a Half Film Fallacies", in Altman (ed.): *Sound Theory, Sound Practice*. New York, London: Routledge.
- Avedon, Elliot & Brian Sutton-Smith (1971): *The Study of Games*. New York, London, Sydney, Toronto: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Bateson, Gregory (1972). *Steps to an Ecology of Mind; Collected Essays in Anthropology, Psychiatry, Evolution, and Epistemology*. San Francisco: Chandler Pub. Co.
- Bessel, David (2002): "What's That Funny Noise? An Examination of the Role of Music in *Cool Boarders 2*, *Alien Trilogy* and *Medievil 2*", in King, Geoff & Tanya Krzywinska (eds.): *ScreenPlay. Cinema/videogames/interfaces*. London/New York: Wallflower Press
- Binmore, Ken (1992): *Fun and Games. A Text of Game Theory*. Lexington, Mass., Toronto: D.C. Heath & Co.
- Blauert, Jens (2001): *Spatial Hearing. The Psychophysics of Human Sound Localization*. Cambridge, Mass., London: MIT Press.
- Bordwell, David (1985): *Narration in the Fiction Film*. London: Routledge.
- Bordwell, David & Kristin Thompson (1997): *Film Art. An Introduction*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

- Bowen, Glenn A. (2006): "Grounded Theory and Sensitizing Concepts", in *International Journal of Qualitative Methods* 5 (3). Available: http://www.ualberta.ca/~ijqm/backissues/5_3/pdf/bowen.pdf [31.01.07]
- Brandon, Alexander (2004): "Adaptive Audio", report from *Interactive Audio Special Interest Group*. Available: <http://www.iasig.org/pubs/features/adaptaudio/adaptiveaudio.htm> (31.01.07)
- Brandon, Alexander (2005): *Audio for games. Planning, Process, and Production*. Berkeley: New Riders.
- Branigan, Edward (1989): "Sound and Epistemology in Film", in *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism* 47:4, Fall 1989. The American Society for Aesthetics.
- Branigan, Edward (1992): *Narrative Comprehension and Film*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Bregman, Albert S. (2001): *Auditory Scene Analysis. The Perceptual Organization of Sound*. Cambridge, Mass., London: MIT Press.
- Caillois, Roger (1961): *Man, Play and Games*. New York: The Free Press of Glencoe Inc. (English translation)
- Chion, Michel (1994): *Audio-Vision. Sound on Screen*. New York: Columbia University Press. (English translation)
- Csikszentmihalyi, Mihaly (1990): *Flow. The Psychology of the Optimal Experience*. New York: Harper & Row Publ. Ltd.
- Csikszentmihalyi, Mihaly (1998): *Finding Flow. The Psychology on Engagement with Everyday Life*. New York: Basic Books.
- Davidson, Donald (1980): 'Agency', in Davidson: *Essays on Actions and Events*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Demaria, Rusel & Johnny L. Wilson (2004): *High Score! The Illustrated History of Electronic Games*. 2nd ed. Emeryville: McGraw-Hill/Osborne.
- Drewes, Thomas M. & Elizabeth D. Mynatt (2000): "Sleuth: An Audio Experience", in *Proceedings from International Conference on Auditory Display 2000*. Available: <http://www.cc.gatech.edu/~everyday-computing/publications/sleuth-icad2000.pdf> [31.01.07]
- Eskelinen, Markku (2004): "Towards Computer Game Studies", in Wardrip-Fruin & Harrigan (eds.): *First Person. New Media as Story, Performance, and Game*. Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press.
- Eysenck, Michael W. & Mark T. Keane (2000): *Cognitive Psychology. A Student's Handbook*. 4th edition. Hove & New York: Psychology Press.

- Frasca, Gonzalo (2001): "Simulation 101: Simulation vs. Representation", in *Ludology.org* [online]. Available: <http://www.ludology.org/articles/sim1/simulation101.html> [31.01.07].
- Friberg, Johnny & Dan Gärdenfors (2004): "Audio Games: New Perspectives on Game Audio", Proceedings from *ACE conference 2004*, Singapore, June 2004. Available: <http://www.cms.livjm.ac.uk/library/AAA-GAMES-Conferences/ACM-ACE/ACE2004/FP-18friberg.johnny.audiogames.pdf> [31.01.07]
- Frijda, Nico (1993): *The Emotions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Gentikow, Barbara (2002): *Hvordan utforsker man medieerfaringer? Kvalitativ metode for (ferske) medieforskere*. Bergen: Department of Media Studies, University of Bergen.
- Gibson, James (1979): *An Ecological Approach to Visual Perception*. Hillside NY Lawrence Earlbaum Associates.
- Gorbman, Claudia (1987): *Unheard Melodies? Narrative Film Music*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Gripsrud, Jostein (1999): *Mediekultur, Mediesamfunn*. Oslo: Universitetsforlaget.
- Guillaume, A., C. Drake, M. Rivenez, L. Pellieux, & V. Chastres (2002): "Perception of Urgency and Alarm Design", in *Proceedings from ICAD 2002*. Available: http://www.icad.org/websiteV2.0/Conferences/ICAD2002/proceedings/04_AGuillaume.pdf [31.01.07]
- Heeter, Carrie & Pericles Gomes (1992): "It's Time for Hypermedia to Move to Talking Pictures", in *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*, Winter 1992. Available: <http://commtechlab.msu.edu/publications/files/talking.html> [31.01.07]
- Huizinga (1949): *Homo Ludens. The Sociology of Culture*. Routledge and Kegan Paul (English translation).
- Iser, Wolfgang (1978): *The Act of Reading. A Theory of Aesthetic Response*. Baltimore, London: Johns Hopkins. (English translation)
- Jakobson, Roman (1960): "Closing statement: Linguistics and poetics", in Thomas A. Sebeok (ed.): *Style in Language*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Jankowski, Nicholas W. and Fred Wester (1991): "The Qualitative Tradition in Social Science Inquiry: Contributions to Mass Communication Research", in Jensen, Klaus Bruhn and Nicholas W. Jankowski (eds.): *A Handbook of Qualitative Methodologies for Mass Communication Research*. London, New York: Routledge.

- Juul, Jesper (1999): *En kamp mellem spil og fortælling*. MA thesis from Copenhagen University. Available: <http://www.jesperjuul.net/speciale/EnKampMellemSpilOgFortaelling.pdf> [31.01.07]
- Juul, Jesper (2002): 'The Open and the Closed: Games of Emergence and Games of Progression', in in Mäyrä, Frans (ed.): *Proceedings of the Computer Games and Digital Cultures Conference, June 6-8, 2002. Tampere, Finland*. Tampere: Tampere University Press.
- Juul, Jesper (2005): *Half-Real. Video Games Between Real Rules and Fictional Worlds*. Cambridge, Mass., London: MIT Press.
- Jørgensen, Kristine (2003a): *Aporia & Epiphany in Context: Computer Game Agency in Baldur's Gate II & Heroes of Might & Magic IV*. MA thesis (hovedoppgave). University of Bergen. Available: <http://www.ub.uib.no/elpub/2003/h/705002/Hovedoppgave.pdf> [31.01.07]
- Jørgensen, Kristine (2003b): "Problem Solving: The Essence of Player Action in Computer Games", in Copier, Marinka & Joost Raessens (eds.): *Proceedings from Level Up: Digital Games Research Conference 2003*. Utrecht: University of Utrecht. Available: <http://www.digra.org/dl/db/05150.49599.pdf> [31.01.07]
- Jørgensen, Kristine (2005): "Game Sound Functionalities". Paper presented at *17th Conference for Nordic Media Research*, Aalborg Aug 11-14 2005.
- Jørgensen, Kristine (2006): "Lyd som grensesnitt: når dataspillet's lyd blir funksjonell", in *Mediekultur nr. 40: Lyd og Medier*. Aarhus University.
- Jørgensen, Kristine (2007, forthcoming): "On Transdiegetic Sounds in Computer Games", in Fetveit, Arild & Gitte Stald (eds.): *Northern Lights 2006*. Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag.
- Keller, Peter & Catherine Stevens (2004): "Meaning From Environmental Sounds: Types of Signal-Referent Relations and Their Effect on Recognizing Auditory Icons", in *Journal of Experimental Psychologic: Applied*. Vol. 10, No. 1. American Psychological Association Inc. Available: http://marcs.uws.edu.au/people/stevens/pubs/Keller_Stevens_JEP_App.pdf [31.01.07]
- Klevjer, Rune (2002): "In Defense of Cutscenes", in Frans Mäyrä (ed): *Proceedings of the Computer Games and Digital Cultures Conference*. Tampere: Tampere University Press. Available: <http://www.digra.org/dl/db/05164.50328> [31.01.07]
- Konzack, Lars (2002): "Computer Game Criticism: A Method for Computer Game Analysis", in Frans Mäyrä (ed): *Proceedings of the Computer Games and Digital Cultures Conference*. Tampere: Tampere University Press. Available: <http://www.vrmedialab.dk/~konzack/tampere2002.pdf> [31.01.07]

- Kramer, G., B. Walker, T. Bonebright, P. Cook, J. Flowers, N. Miner, J. Neuhoff, R. Bargar, S. Barrass, J. Berger, G. Evreinov, W. Fitch, M. Gröhn, S. Handel, H. Kaper, H. Levkowitz, S. Lodha, B. Shinn-Cunningham, M. Simoni, S. Típei (1999): *The Sonification Report: Status of the Field and Research Agenda*. Report prepared for the National Science Foundation by members of the International Community for Auditory Display. ICAD, Santa Fe, NM. Available: <http://icad.org/websiteV2.0/References/nsf.html> [31.01.07].
- Langkjær, Birger (1997): *Filmlyd & filmmusikk. Fra klassisk til moderne film*. Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag.
- Langkjær, Birger (2000): *Den lyttende tilskuer. Perception af lyd og musik i film*. Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag.
- Laurel, Brenda (1991): *Computers as Theatre*. Addison Wesley.
- Lombard, Matthew & Theresa Ditton (2000): "Measuring Presence: A Literature-based Approach to the Development of a Standardized Paper-and-Pencil Instrument". Project abstract submitted for the presentation at *Presence 2000: The Third International Workshop on Presence*. Available: <http://spacepioneers.msu.edu/private/kidwai/research/litpresence02.doc> [31.01.07].
- Maasø, Arnt (1994): *Lyden av levende bilder*. IMK report no. 14 from Department of Media and Communication, University of Oslo.
- Maasø, Arnt (2002): "Se-hva-som-skjer!" *En studie av lyd som kommunikativt virkemiddel i TV*. Ph.D. dissertation from Department of Media and Communication, University of Oslo.
- Marks, Aaron (2001): *The Complete Guide to Game Audio. For Composers, Musicians, Sound Designers, and Game Developers*. Lawrence, Kansas: CMP Books.
- McAdams, Stephen & Emmanuel Bigand (eds.) (1993): *Thinking in Sound. The Cognitive Psychology of Human Audition*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- McCormick & Sanders (1986): "Auditory, Tactual, and Olfactory Displays", in *Human Factors in Engineering and Design*. International Student's Edition. Singapore: McGraw-Hill.
- McKeown, Denis (2005): "Candidates for Within-Vehicle Auditory Displays", in *Proceedings of ICAD 05*. Available: <http://www.idc.ul.ie/icad2005/downloads/f118.pdf> [31.01.07].

- Menshikov, Aleksei (2003): "Modern Audio Technologies in Games", article based on paper presented at *Game Developers Conference 2003*, Moscow. Available: <http://www.digit-life.com/articles2/sound-technology/index.html> [31.01.07].
- Murray, Janet (1997): *Hamlet on the Holodeck The Future of Narrative in Cyberspace*. MIT Press.
- Neuhoff, John G. (2004): "Ecological Psychoacoustics: Introduction and History", in Neuhoff (ed.): *Ecological Psychoacoustics*. San Diego, Ca.: Elsevier Academic Press.
- Neumann, John von & Oskar Morgenstern (1944): *The Theory of Games and Economic Behaviour*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Nyre, Lars (2003): *Fidelity Matters. Sound Media and Realism in the 20th Century*. Volda: Volda University College/Haugen Bok.
- Patton, Michael Quinn (2002): *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods*. Thousand Oaks, London, New Delhi: Sage Publications Ltd.
- Pidkameny, Eric (2002): "Levels of Sound", in *Video Game Music Archive*. Available: <http://www.vgmusic.com/information/vgpaper2.html> [31.01.07].
- Poole, Steven (2000): *Trigger Happy. The Inner Lives of Videogames*. London: Fourth Estate.
- Rollings, Andrew & Ernest Adams (2003): "Attempting to Define Gameplay", in Rollings & Adams: *Andrew Rollings & Ernest Adams on Game Design*. New Riders. Online: <http://www.peachpit.com/articles/printerfriendly.asp?p=98123&rl=1> [31.01.07]
- Ryan, Marie-Laure (2001): *Narrative as Virtual Reality. Immersion and Interactivity in Literature and Electronic Media*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Sanger, George Alistair (2003): *The Fat Man on Game Audio: Tasty Morsels of Sonic Goodness*. New Riders.
- Schafer, R. Murray (1977): *The Soundscape: Our Sonic Environment and the Tuning of the World*. Rochester, Vermont: Destiny Books.
- Smalley, Denis (1996): "The Listening Imagination: Listening in the Electroacoustic Era", in *Contemporary Music Review*, Vol. 13, Part 2.
- Sorkin, Robert D. (1987): "Design of Auditory and Tactile Displays", in Salvendy, Gavriel (ed.): *Handbook of Human Factors*. New York, Chichester, Brisbane, Toronto, Singapore: John Wiley & Sons.

- Steuer, Jonathan (1992): "Defining Virtual Reality: Dimensions Determining Telepresence", in *Journal of Communication*, 42, No. 4 (Autumn 1992). ABI/INFORM Global.
- Stockburger, Axel (2003): "The Game Environment from an Auditory Perspective", in Copier, Marinka & Joost Raessens (eds.): *Proceedings: Level Up: Digital Games Research Conference*. Utrecht University.
- Suied, Clara, Patrick Susini, Nicolas Misdariis, Sabine Langlois, Bennett K. Smith, & Stephen McAdams (2005): "Toward a Sound Design Methodology: Application to Electronic Automotive Sounds", in *Proceedings of ICAD 05*. Available: <http://www.idc.ul.ie/icad2005/downloads/f93.pdf> [31.01.07]
- Thorhauge, Anne Mette (2003): "Playing While Making Sense", paper presented at the *Plaything Conference*, Sydney 2003. Available: http://www.dlux.org.au/fs03/media/anne_mette_thorhauge_web.pdf [31.01.07].
- Walton, Kendall L. (1990): *Mimesis as Make-Believe. On the Foundations of the Representational Arts*. Cambridge, Mass., London: Harvard University Press.
- Weske, Jörg (2000): "Digital Sound and Music in Computer Games", paper from *Neue Medien im Alltag* project, TU Chemnitz. Available: <http://www.tu-chemnitz.de/phil/hypertexte/gamesound/index.html> [31.01.07].
- Whalen, Zach (2004): "Play Along – An Approach to Video Game Music", in *Gamestudies* 4,1. Available: <http://gamestudies.org/0401/whalen/> [31.01.07].
- Whitmore, Guy (2003): "Design With Music in Mind: A Guide to Adaptive Audio for Game Designers", in *Gamasutra.com*, May 29, 2003. Available: http://www.gamasutra.com/resource_guide/20030528/whitmore_pfv.htm [31.01.07].
- Yin, Robert K. (2003): *Case Study Research. Design and Methods*. Thousand Oaks, London, New Delhi: Sage Publications.

Web sources

- Blizzard Entertainment (2002): *Warcraft III: Reign of Chaos* official website: <http://www.blizzard.com/war3/> [31.01.07].
- Wikipedia (2001-2006): *Wikipedia's site on real-time strategy*: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rts> [31.01.07].
- Wikipedia (2001-2006): *Wikipedia's site on stealth-based games*: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stealth_game [31.01.07].

Games

Acclaim (1996): *Alien Trilogy*. Probe

Acorn, Al (1972): *Pong*. Atari.

Ascaron Entertainment (2004): *Sacred*. Ascaron Entertainment

Atari (1980): *Asteroids*. Atari.

Atari (1980): *Missile Command*. Atari.

Bethesda Softworks (2002): *The Elder Scrolls III: Morrowind*. Bethesda Softworks.

Black Isle Studios (1999): *Planescape: Torment*. Interplay.

Blizzard Entertainment (2004-2006): *World of Warcraft*. Blizzard Entertainment.

Blizzard Entertainment (2002): *Warcraft III: The Reign of Chaos*. Blizzard Entertainment.

Bushnell, Nolan (1971): *Computer Space*. Atari.

Cryo Interactive (1992): *Dune*. Virgin Interactive.

Eidos Interactive (2006): *Tomb Raider Legend*. Eidos Interactive.

Ensemble Studios (1997): *Age of Empires*. Microsoft Game Studios.

Higinbotham, William (1958): *Tennis for two*. Brookhaven National Laboratory.

Io Interactive (2000): *Hitman: Codename 47*. Eidos Interactive

Io Interactive (2002): *Hitman 2: Silent Assassin*. Eidos Interactive.

Io Interactive (2003): *Freedom Fighters*. Eidos Interactive.

Io Interactive (2004): *Hitman Contracts*. Eidos Interactive.

Io Interactive (2006): *Hitman Bloodmoney*. Eidos Interactive.

Ion Storm (1998): *Thief: The Dark Project*. Eidos Interactive.

Ion Storm (2004): *Thief III: Deadly Shadows*. Eidos Interactive.

Konami (1987): *Metal Gear*. Nintendo.

Konami (2000): *Metal Gear Solid*. Microsoft Game Studios.

Lawson, D.H. & John Gibson (1983): *Stonkers*. Imagine Software.

Maxis (2000): *The Sims*. Electronic Arts.

Namco (1980): *Pac-Man*. Namco

NC Soft (2004-2006): *Lineage II: The Chaotic Chronicle*. NC Soft.

Nintendo (1985): *Super Mario Bros*. Nintendo.

Nintendo (1987): *Final Fantasy*. Nintendo.

Nintendo (1987): *The Legend of Zelda*. Nintendo.

Russell, Steve, J. Martin Graetz & Wayne Witanen (1962): *Spacewar!* MIT

Sony (2000): *Medieval 2*. SCEA

Square Enix (1997): *Final Fantasy VII*. SCEA.

Taito (1978): *Space Invaders*. Midway

UEP (1997): *Cool Boarders*. Sony

Wright, Will (1987): *Sim City*. Maxis.

Appendix 1: Table of Contents: Digital Appendix

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Appendix 2: Endnotes: Informant Quotes in Original Language

- ¹ SDB-2: [...] Og fordi... lyd interesserer mig... jeg interesserer mig for hvordan lyd opstår, og hvordan... de så og sige skabes og noget. Og... så jeg lægger meget mærke til noget, altså for eksempel nogle gange når man går nede ved vandet så kan man tydelig høre vandet. Men andre gange når man går der nede så kan man ikke høre vandet. [...]
- ² PA-5: [...] Og jeg er meget bevidst om.. at undgå og genere, det kan godt være irriterende at have for meget lyd med, lyd som ikke er relevant, eller som ikke giver rigtig stemning, rigtig stemning. Eller som bare lyder dårlig. Så er det noget, der lyder dårlig, gør jeg alt for at omgå det, at det ikke er med. [...]
- ³ SDA-3b: [...] Der var overhovedet ikke musik på det, det var kun hans stemme, [...] det var helt stille, det var fokus, respekt, der var.. der var dybde i det fordi man kom hen til kærnen i hvad, det egentlig var han, hvad er det egentlig han sidder at snakker om. [...]
- ⁴ SDB-3c: [...] Altså lyd er jo ret specielt fordi da kan man... man kan sådan vælge hvad man vil høre næsten. [...] man kan vælge at lægge mere mærke til nogle lyde end til andre lyde. [...]
- ⁵ PB-2c: Nei, man er ikke så opmærksom på det [lyd]. Måske ikke som på de ting man ser.
- ⁶ SDA-8: [...] Hvis du lige pludselig bliver rigtig rigtig bange på gaden for eksempel, og du begynder at løbe. [...] Så det i en sådan situation er vi meget visuelle, og meget fysiske fordi vi kan mærke vi er oppe at kører inde i vores krop. Men hvis der er en der spørger dig bagefter, hvordan lød det da du løb nedad gaden, så kan vi ikke svare. [...] Og det er lidt det samme der sker når man spiller et spil, at man har jo nogle ting der tager opmærksomheden fra hinanden. [...]
- ⁷ PA-11: [...] Man kan føre spilleren ind, i en stemning som forstærker den situation. [...] Man kan give nogle hint, og man kan også nærmest belønne hvis spilleren har gjort noget rigtig. [...]
- ⁸ PB-2a: [...] Bare tag i dagligdagen når man går ude så er det så er det jo noget man bruger til at orientere sig med og til at få et billede av omgivelserne også nogen... Så det er lige meget et redskab til bare at navigere rundt, det er også til at fortælle om, ja alt hvad der sker, om der sker noget farlig, og om hvad for et forum eller kontekst man befinder sig i. Så man får – og det er måske mere ubevidst men man får en hel masse viden baseret på de lyder omkring. Så er det jo også med på at skabe en række stemninger for en. [...]
- ⁹ PA-2: Ehm... ja men det fortæller mig.. hvor jeg er hen.. det fortæller mig om.. om jeg skal være opmærksom på nogle ting. [...]
- ¹⁰ PB-7: [...] Vi prøver jo at genskabe det som hører når man er ude i hverdagen. Måske mere eller mindre overdrevent, men vi.. for det første prøver vi at beskrive omgivelserne rent lydæssig bare for at få noget information om hvad sker der, hvor er man hen, og og så videre. Samtidig bruger vi det så til også at hvad skal man si piske en stemning op.
- ¹¹ PB-9: [...] I Hitman gør vi meget ud av at lyden er rimelig autentisk og vi prøver selvfølgelig at bearbejde dem lidt sådan at vi får det udtryk, vi gerne vil have. Men det er indenfor nogle rammer – det bliver jo aldrig taget sådan for langt [...].
- ¹² PA-6: [...] skaber lydbilledet når du spiller, det ændrer sig i forhold til hvad, du foretager dig. [...]
- ¹³ C1-b: [...] Man ved ikke rigtig, hvornår folk, de... når forskellige steder hen, hvor lang tid det tager for folk at nå de forskellige steder hen. [...]
- ¹⁴ PB-10a: [...] Det er ikke... det er ikke noget det er ikke noget man ikke har set før at man har et eller andet makabert scenarie og så har man lydbilledet er i virkeligheden passer ikke til. Men det er mere sådan hvad skal man si at understrege det det forrykte i situationen eller hvad man skal si.
- ¹⁵ SDA6: [...] Det betyder selvfølgelig også at lyden bliver dårligere, og det er sådan nogle ting vi bliver nødt til at gøre fordi da kan vi for eksempel spille musikken i cd-kvalitet, og så kan vi ha alle fodskridtslyderne i en lidt dårligere kvalitet. Men det er der ikke så mange som kan høre når musikken den spiller. Og sådan ligger vi hele tiden og kalkulerer kvalitet frem for hvad der virker. [...]

¹⁶ PA23: [...] Altså, det er, det er et ønskværdig scenarie det at det er med helt fra starten, men men det er det.. det er det sjældent. Så det er noe som kommer.. i.. et stykke inne i processen, så kommer lyden inn i bildet. [...] Altså... altså, jeg tror at typisk så kommer det sent hvor man rent faktisk er begynt at se hvordan gameplayet skal være. [...]

¹⁷ SDA-23: [...] Men også begynner man at fokusere på nogle ting, som man ved, skal være der. Og man kan sige, man ved, der skal være nogle dører, for eksempel. [...] Og man begynner også at utvikle nogle ting, som.. som også hører med, til det job, ja, det er jo ligesom at utvikle og blive [...] dygtigere til nogle ting, og have åpne øjne for hvad der sker andre steder. [...]

¹⁸ PB-28: [...] Det er meget snak frem og tilbake, man kikker på spillet og prøvespiller banen i genneom og lydert som de synes, og sådan noget... snakker de da om hvad fornogle ting man kunde tænke sig at ændre og sådan noget. [...]

¹⁹ C-14: [...] Jeg siger så, jeg synes vi skal spille den her musikk her, så bliver det så porgrammeret, så får jeg så en verion av spillet hvor jeg så tester om jeg synes det virker godt eller ei. Eh, men altså, det er sådan, jeg sidder og kommer opp med alle ideerne til hvor musikken skal spille, og ligesom... så tweaker vi det så. [...]

²⁰ PB-21: [...] Formålet er at fortælle spilleren hvad det er, der sker.. lydmæssig også. Og for at skabe stemning der passer til situationen [...].

²¹ PA-17-18: Altså, gameplasmæssigt så... altså, er det med til at hjelpe, typisk er det en hjelp... for at gjøre det lettere at gjennomføre den her missionen. Så det er klart at.. jeg forventer at spilleren bruker lyden når han spiller, og at man ikke ignorerer den. Ideen er at man får [noget] ud av at have lyden med, gameplasmæssigt også. [...] Men typisk... sådan som vi haver implementeret det så kan man godt få nogenlunde det samme opplevelse altså gameplasmæssigt uden lyd. [...]

²² SDB-11b: Altså, vi har brukt det på den måte, at hvis det for eksempel at Hitman kommer ind på et område hvor der er vagter, og så vaktene de går og snakker sammen, for at man skal bli oppmerksom på at der er noe der inde på de områdene man skal passe på, ikke. [...]

²³ PA-11: [...] Man kan give nogle hint, og man kan også... nærmest belønne hvis spilleren har gjort noget riktig. [...]

²⁴ PB-14b: [...] At høre på personer der står inde bag en dør som en hører, så ved man, at der er nogen bag den her lukkede dør. [...] Det er selvfølgelig advarselsskiltene [...] men som så er noget lyd som også bliver brukt til at fortelle spilleren, at der er noget bestemt der er skedt. [...]

²⁵ PB-19c: [...] Det er sådan et forsøg på at få spilleren til at tro på, at han rent faktisk befinner sig hvor han nå gjør. [...]

²⁶ C-2: [...] Føle sig, at han ligesom connecter med spillet, at han haver nogle følelser for historien. [...] At pludselig alle de karakterer og det der foregår i spillet, det er ikke bare noget, som man løber igennem for at komme til den neste bane. Men det er noget, hvor man begynner lige pludselig at.. at få sådan en, en hel følelse av at være i verden. [...]

²⁷ PA-12d: [...] når man gjorde noget rigtig (i Freedom Fighters) så var der, hørte man sådan i baggrunden.. nogen der sagde "yeah" og Når man gjorde noget rigtig. Men det ville virke forkert i et spil som Hitman... hvor man måske skulle bruke noget musikk. [...]

²⁸ SDB-14a: [...] Altså nå, Hitman det er jo sådan... meget... ja, jeg ved ikke om man kan sige et, altså et stealth-spil hvor man skal snige sig rundt. Så det er viktig at lyden, den er med til at guide spilleren. Han for eksempel står stille og venter, ja, men så kan han høre at der går noen længer rundt om hjørnet.

²⁹ PA-19: Musikken er typisk afhængig... altså hvilket område man er i. Og typisk afhængig af om man er optaget eller ikke optaget. Typisk afhængig af, om man lige har gjort et eller andet som var en oppgave på den her bane. Mens det gjør man måske ikke så meget med environment-lyde. [...]

³⁰ C-7: [...] Så når man som spiller gjør visse ting i spillet så er der forskjellig musikk der trigger på forskjellige tidspunkter. Hvis man for eksempel går ind i, der er en sådan swimming pool i Budapest bath hotel så skifter musikken til nogle meget mere avslappende lyder, swimming pool-aktig, så hvis man går ned i poolen, og så ligger det en sådan fyr i swimming poolen der og sover eller flyder lidt der, og slapper av. Så hvis man går der ned og, man sniger der ned og man dræber ham, så skifter musikken så. Ligesom for at

understøtte at man har gjort noget der er korrekt, kan man si. Men hvis samtidig hvis man prøver at dræbe ham og man bliver opdaget, så skriger han fyren der og så kommer vagterne løbende, og så skifter musikken til noget mere actionaktig hvor man nu skal se at passe på, og nu er det virkelig ved at være i gang noget. [...]

³¹ C-7: [...] Så det handler meget om, om sådan ting også, hvis man tager noget, hvis man skifter tøj på noen av banerne for eksempel, for eksempel den første banen når man tager SWAT-tøjet på. Så skifter musikken.

³² PB-15c: [...] ikke et opstillet regelsæt som man kan slå op i manualen og sige, når de her lyder kommer, så har man gjort noget rigtig, ikke. Ligesom noget, man skal opdage, slik som man gør i spil.

³³ PA-9a: Ubehag.... mørkt... Altså ubehagelig generelt.

³⁴ PB-10a: Ja, dystert, makabert, og måske en liten smule morbid [...].

³⁵ SDA-11: [...] Et lidt drømmeagtigt univers. Hvor man maler meget på billedet, om man så små sige, ikke. [...]

³⁶ G23e: Det har vel gjerne med hans syn på hele.... det er jo liksom flashbacks hele greien. Og det er jo det som gjerne er med på å gjøre det så dystert. Fordi han husker det på den måten, ikkje fordi det nødvendigvis var på den måten.

³⁷ PB-16a: [...] Lyden av dører der åpner og lukker kan jo og også brukes av spilleren til at være opmærksom på at der var en anden karakter her i området eller om han er farlig eller ufarlig [...].

³⁸ PA-16b: Altså, man kan, for eksempel, der er en person der siger ind på dig, en vagt som kommer omkring et hjørne. Så kan man høre hans fodtrindslude. Og da har vi vaglt en passende afstand for hvor langt væk man kan høre den her lyd, så du kan nå at gøre opmærksom på at der kommer altså en person op. [...]

³⁹ PB-8a: [...] Der er noget ren information som som bliver leveret bare på en skærm med nogen tekst hvor der så er tale til. Og så er der nogle nogle små filmsekvenser hvor der kan være noe dialog mellem noen personer som ofte også for at videreggi noget information og for at sette spilleren ind i situationen. Og så er der så når man spiller ude på banen er der så nogle smalltalk-ting som de forskellige karaktererne går og siger uden at det egentlig betyder noget, men bare sådan for at det skal skabe lidt liv og lidt stemning. Og så haver man de udbrud som karaktererne kommer med når de ser Hitman med en pistol for eksempel eller de finder en død person eller noget. Og det bliver så brugt for at fortelle spilleren at... [...] vakterne har opdaget dig. [...] Så så er der også så er der også Hitmans replikker og og det foregår i samarbejde med med den person eller karakter i spillet som som han får sin mission av. [...]

⁴⁰ PB-19c: [...]Så... det der med at skabe en en stor.. mengde av folk der står. Da skal man snyde lidt, man måske skal ha for eksempel bare med en hel masse baggrundsmumlen i, og så krydre det med at have nogen forståelig tale en gang i mellem. [...]

⁴¹ PA-13: [...] Vi prøver at gøre det realistisk, hvor langt væk vi kan høre den her lyd, avstandstæmninger i forhold til virkeligheden, hvor langt kan man høre de her ting vekk, og så videre. [...] [I forbindelse med stemmer] gjør det ut fra at, det er nogen viktig information , så derfor kan det ikke være realistisk, så man måske gerne ville have det. [...]

⁴² S25a: [...] Det er liksom en sånn. Eg holdt nesten på å si at det.. du sporer av på en måte. Akkurat som eg holder på å vri på et sånt rør, eller rattet frampå der og så.. *yyh* Det er en sånn lyd, han passer liksom ikkje inn i noen som helst sammenheng med ka som skjer på brettet. Det er liksom ikkje noen av de som kommer der som kommer til å få noen sånn mekanisk lyd i seg. Så det er rett og slett en fin, han er fin på den måten at han beviser at det er noe som er utenfor brettet, ikkje inne i selve spillet, men utenfor fronten.

⁴³ N14a: [...] Og då går eg ganske raskt over. Det er så lenge siden eg har spilt, men det er jo sånn du ser forskjell når eg spiller mye så er det liksom den der, ratatatata. Og da kan klykkelyden være ganske grei, for å få høre at du faktisk har fått med deg personen.

⁴⁴ N14b: Nei, for da, du... da tror du kanskje du har tropper du ikkje har. Så det at det er en nøytral lyd, det..

⁴⁵ L17: Altså de er såpass irriterende, synes ikkje har noe der å gjøre. Altså, de følger ikkje de andre lydene i spillet i det hele tatt. Eg tror det er bedre å ha de der enn å ikkje ha en lyd i det hele tatt, for ellers blir det sånn trykte eg på noe her i det hele tatt. For ellers

blir det sånn, trykte eg på nokke? Ja, han oppgraderer. Fint. Men de kunne godt hatt hvilken som helst annen lyd enn et jævla museklikk.

⁴⁶ S21: [...] Og då må eg tilrettelegge meg, være mye mer sparsommelig med sløsinga min. Så begynner eg med en gang å regne ut litt i hodet ka eg kan kjøpe og ka eg har råd til å kjøpe og såne ting. Så... men når eg har han.. når han går den motsatte veien, sånn.. då pleier eg egentlig bare være happy for då får eg mer penger. Eller av og til er trist når det skjer, for kanskje eg taper et slag eller noe sånt.

⁴⁷ S10b: [...] Og så er det alltid, det er den lyden når han levler, weeweewee, då vet eg at det skjer noe spennende.

⁴⁸ A15a: Ja[...] At du har lyden av, holdt på og si, mer spørrende, ja, ka vil du, og holdt på og sei, bekreftende lyd, ja, eg gjør..

⁴⁹ A6a: Eh, det at du får lyd når du setter i gang å bygge en tropp eller en bygning eller noe sånt, så vil du få en lyd når den er ferdig. Det er veldig.. veldig greit og så få. For du vil gjerne fokusere på forskjellige områder og så hører du lyden av det du nettopp har bygget som ble ferdig og då kan du, går du tilbake og fokuserer på den troppen der. Samme med bygninger og.. og når du er under angrep. Så.. så får du beskjed.

⁵⁰ A16[...] Hvis du jobber med en del, gjør en del ting så får du summoning complete eller building complete, så... vil du kanskje begynne å tenke, ka var det eg egentlig bygget nå som skulle vært ferdig. [...].

⁵¹ R16: [...] altså mens jeg driver på med noe annet så hører jeg liksom, okei nå begynner det kanskje å hope seg opp etterhvert, så da hører jeg liksom det oppstår. Liksom I stand ready hele tida. Da merker jeg, ja, okei. Nå, nå har jeg hørt det mange ganger, nå har jeg cirka en sånn hær.

⁵² S17a: Nei, når eg hører build more burrows så, det kommer an på kor tid i spillet det er. Hvis det er sånn som no, i oppbygningsfasen. Då er det, då må eg handle på det med en gang. Hvis eg venter i ti sekunder med det så betyr det at det er ti sekunder eg ikkje får bygget mer. Men det er en liten irritasjonsfaktor altså det at hver gang eg hører det, så er det, faen, nå kan eg ikkje bygge menn på en stund. [...] Men i slutten av det, når eg har fått opp burrows og alt det der, at eg har nitti maks og det som... då er det bare en indikasjon som sier bare det til meg at, okei no har du produsert for mye menn, då er det bare å gå ut og få noen av de slaktet og forhåpentligvis vil du ta ned basen deres samtidig.

⁵³ P15b: Plagsomt! Eg har ikkje, eg kommer ikkje til å få gull, eg synes eg skulle få litt kreditt faktisk. [...] Sånn som nå må eg vente på mer gull, for det at sånn som det er her nå så begynner det å bygge seg opp kø ved gullgruva. Så er det då, då må eg liksom, okei, eg må bare vente, så eg finn noke anna, eg finn nokon å dille med. Så hvis det er en veldig treig bane så finner eg en sau å trykke på.

⁵⁴ A27c: [...] Hvis eg hadde bygget her nede på kartet en rekke med, med defenses. Og blokkert alle inngangene. Så ville eg jo sett at.. det var der nede, og då ville eg egentlig bare ignorert det. Dessverre så regnes forsvarsbygninger som town, og då får du den lyden. [...]

⁵⁵ S14: [...] det kommer selvfølgelig situasjoner der du kanskje ikkje vet at du har tapt hele hæren, og så står de gjerne og hakker på deg, og då er det veldig nyttig å ha det. Men maskinen vil jo aldri kunne være avansert nok til å vite om du tror du har kontroll over situasjonen eller ikkje. [...]

⁵⁶ A15c: [...] Eg var, eg var nede her og gjorde noe, så hørte eg lydene lenger oppe. Som gjorde at eg sånn, woops.

⁵⁷ L18: [...] Hvis eg er ute med en håndfull menn og helten min er på jakt etter litt xp til.. å få levle han opp, og eg ikkje hører noe fra byen så ville eg ignorert hele byen. Hatt tre tusen gull og tre tusen trær og fem bygninger liksom.

⁵⁸ R27: Ja, jeg kan, kjenner iallefall igjen angrepslydene og dødsskrikene til en del av unitene. Så jeg merker, hvis jeg hører masse sånn buegreier. Litt sånn lyder fra bueskytere som angriper, så vet jeg at de angriper nå, så hvis jeg plutselig hører dødsskriket til en av heltene, så tenker jeg haha. (latter) Der klarte bueskyterne min og ta han ut.

⁵⁹ R7: Jo, altså når de snakker, på en måte de gjenskaper, liksom de får jo litt stemning av, følelse av kultur. De forskjellige rasene, de snakker gjerne, de har forskjellige måter å snakke på. Og orkene høres litt sånn barbariske ut og menneskene er sånn edle

skapninger som går rundt og, nattalvene snakker på en veldig sånn mystisk måte og... så det får jo, det gir jo stemning og karakter til de forskjellige rasene.

⁶⁰ R8a: Ja, du.... for meg virker det som at det ikke er så, liksom... ja, vi blir angrepet, men det går sikkert greit, og det er ikke så farlig. (latter) Mens hos orkene så skriker de, we're under attack! Og det er liksom, alle mann på posten og hopper ut av sengen og nå skal vi slåss.

⁶¹ R15a: Så diskret stemme? Ja, jeg merker det. Det er jo, som sagt, alt er bare ganske rolig. Så man blir liksom avslappa. Det er ikke noe, det er ikke noe stress.

⁶² L21a: Han er jo mer utpreget og det er liksom, sånn eg har tenkt med Warcraft er at jo høyere unitene er, altså om det er en swordsman, en ridder eller helt, så jo høyere opp i rankene han er, jo mer holier than thou er uttrykkene hans. En bonde er liksom sånn, yes lord, mens paladinen er mer sånn.. eh,ja.. for land and country, basically, for king and country, James Bond hele fyren.

⁶³ P30b: Det gir de personlighet basically. Det gjer meg en... eg veit ikkje, altså det går, det går på ka, korleis eg... eg velger å oppleve de. Altså det er litt sånn. En peon vil eg ikkje bry meg om egentlig. Han er en idiot, en dum liten bonde. Mens eg vil være mykje meir glad i en hero eller noe slikt som har en framtoning som eg har lyst å.. han virker meir nyttig.

⁶⁴ L11: Førsteintrykket er jo at de er stakk dum. Noe som bønder egentlig skal være i sånne spill som ikkje er helt hundre prosent seriøs på alle punkter. Det andre som er litt bra er jo det at du får ikkje lyst å bare sette de i veien for fienden for at de skal... i vanlige strategispill så putter du bare de mest umulige troppene dine foran, så de blir kvernet (?). Men her er det litt sånn, de er dum og uskyldig. Du vil ikkje ofre de.

⁶⁵ N13a: Altså han er jo liksom det der at du, du er ikkje trygg. Selv om det er helt i begynnelsen. Og, også ja. For det er liksom den der, det er akkurat som, mye det samme som de bruker i Vil du bli Millionær, den der hjerterytmen. For å få spenningen opp. [...] Tempoet har en del å si, men det at det er sånn lyder som går kraftigere i rytmen gjør at du får litt mer den der intense følelsen.

⁶⁶ A24: Egentlig ikkje annet enn at det begynte å spille en musikk når ingenting annet skjedde plutselig. Som gjorde at eg ble litt mistenksom, skjer det noe nå. Når det skjer noe etter første angrepet, så.. eller andre angrepet. A25: [...] Og det vil du mest sannsynlig se og her... når den musikken kommer så begynner eg å se litt rundt på kartet, sjekke grensene.

⁶⁷ R4: [...] Men også noe jeg la merke til, altså musikken, det skifter mellom dag og natt, da skifta musikken. Da har du også bakgrunnsmusikken, også er det sånn, hvertfall en del lyd som... vanlig sånne lyder også som forandrer (mumling)[3:44], bare sånn begynte å høre ugler om natta og sånne ting, mens om dagen så var det høner og litt sånn forskjellig sånn. Så blir det en sånn spesiell stemning av det.

⁶⁸ A43e: Ja, altså.. fuglekviser og sånn er jo bare for å liksom vise at det... bare for å gi mer stemning. Du merker jo.. du merker og at, det er mer fravær av fuglekviser i et sånt landskap som dette enn i en tykk skog. Det merket eg når eg spilte disse her... elves, for første gang, så var det mye mer lyd, og mye mer skoglyder, og du merker de forsvinner jo mer av skogen forsvinner.

⁶⁹ S4: Eh... ja, temmelig standard. Eg, eg er så vent med lyden at det er... Men... det var temmelig like lyder annet enn, rett og slett de hadde standardlydene sine. Eg klarte liksom ikkje å høre de der lydene av trehugging og smelling av metall og sånt. Så det... eg hørte liksom bare de viktigste, sånn, du har ikkje gull, og.. bygningen din er ferdig liksom.

⁷⁰ P31: [...] Du, du blir liksom fullstendig i mørket, uten lyd. [...]

⁷¹ N46: Ja. Du blir liksom... kappet av en fot. [...]

⁷² A30: Du blir blind. Rett og slett. [...]

⁷³ N48: Det er liksom det at du blir halvert fordi du mister halvparten av sanseintrykkene dine. Fordi du har syn og lyd.. du har liksom, ja. Du har to sanser du bruker hovedsaklig, og det er syn og det er hørsel. Og du mister vel den ene og den er ganske vital blitt i spill. Og sånn som her, så er det liksom...

⁷⁴ N38: Eg visste at eg synes det er kjedeligere å spille uten lyd. Men eg var ikkje klar over at eg syntes det påvirket spillet så pass mye. Men det er sånn eg har sett folk spille Counter-Strike uten lyd og det funker jo ikkje. (latter)

⁷⁵ A39: Hmm... lyden kan av og til ta vekk litt av konsentrasjonen. Du sitter og gjør noe og så hører du at en bygning du har ventet på er ferdig så vil du gjerne hoppe til den med en gang der du egentlig kanskje burde gjort flere ting. Så, så den kan hjelpe på å... og det kan bli litt for mye av og til. [...]

⁷⁶ S36: [...] Det blir liksom, du blir mer systematisk, det blir nesten som tall rett og slett. At det, den uniten falt, den uniten falt, og så mast eg en og sånn, det blir liksom ingen feeling bak at det er noen faller liksom.

⁷⁷ A22: Eh, eg merker det først og fremst på lyd kombinert med mini-map. Først lyd, og som indikerer at noe er galt, og så ned på mini-mappen for å se kor.

⁷⁸ L31b: Mini-mappet blir ikkje detaljert nok, den eneste gangen eg bruker mini-mappet er for å finne ut hen det er baser ting vi kan... altså prøve å finne ut hen motstanderen har gjort seg, som er ganske enkelt på det brettet der. Hvis eg skal ha nye gullgruver så er det et fint sted å ta som utgangspunkt. Men eg bruker det bare til orientering. [...]

⁷⁹ A31a: Eg bruker det mye mer. Eg bruker mye mer mini-mappet, eg holder mye mer øye med her nede og ser kor tropper, og eventuelt om det blir slåssing. Akkurat nå er mini-mappet det eneste eg kan bruke for å se om det blir angrep her.

⁸⁰ P33a: Det blir med ein gang viktig. Fordi at der, der får du en sånn grafisk framstilling av her skjer det noke, i en form av en sånn pulsering i ein eller annen farge. Så den vil då erstatte lyden på mange måter. Fordi at då ville du ha fått beskjed om at hei, eg er ferdig å jobbe eller hei, eg er her. Nå er eg nødt å sjå på kartet og sjå når noke pulserer. Liksom, "a gold mine is running low" kunne du sjå den pulseringen der nede.

⁸¹ R26b: Jeg la merke til at jeg måtte begynne å se på de beskjedene som stod nedi her mye mer, og det var irriterende noen ganger og så var det ikke alltid jeg fikk med meg ting når det skjedde.

⁸² P27: [...] Tekst det kan bare, det går fort forbi. Lyd kan bli, der får du det inn på en annen måte. Augene dine dekker et heilt skjerm bilde her, ikkje sant, og du skal.. du er aktiv og jobber med det. Så lyd.. bruker en heilt annen sans, gjør deg oppmerksom på en heilt annen måte enn hvis det bare hadde vært en liten tekst nedi der så hadde eg ikkje sett det hvis eg fulgte med på de der.

⁸³ R34: Ja, noen ganger så sitter jeg sånn, ofte så hører jeg sånn, trykker, så hører du bare not enough gold, så trykker jeg kanskje en eller to ganger. Men der så var det bare, trykk-trykk-trykk-trykk-trykk-trykk. Ah, shit. (latter) Det kom ikke opp noe. Så det tok meg litt tid å.. litt lengre tid å... få ting med meg.

⁸⁴ P32: Som eg ikkje fikk gjort? Det ville være feil å sei. Altså.. eg får jo gjort alt, men eg vil ikkje være like obs på ka eg kan gjøre. Og på ka eg bør gjøre. Sant for eg hører ikkje, eg får ikkje varselen om at noke er gale eller noe holder på å skje. [...]. Sant og eg vil få opp enkeltelementer og eg kan sjå på kartet at eg slåss, men eg kan ikkje følge noe spesifikt.

⁸⁵ S33: Hm... ja faktisk, de første sekundene når eg ... første sekundene så ble eg sånn, litt sånn der, oi, ka skjedde no liksom. Men eg vente meg fort til rett og slett, så blir... eg blir mye treigere i reaksjonen, det er eg sikker på. Men... eg vet ikkje, det.. [...] blir ikkje den aller største forskjellen egentlig. Eg, eg er så vant med ka som skjer, eg er så vant med kommer det en flekk inn der så angriper eg på den måten, og då må eg gjøre det og det, så...

⁸⁶ A10: Det... holdt på å si lyden er jo veldig grei for noe som flyr igjen luften. Altså lyden av kitchen.. lyden av en kniv og.. skulle ikkje forundre meg om de brukte samme lyden der faktisk. Kniv og den der meat hooken. Og det er greit for då får du vite at du har gjort noe. Og så i og med at... ja, der var den igjen. Også det, lyden av at eg ikkje treffer noe og.

⁸⁷ R14b: Eh... Jeg synes også man påtager sig sådan rolle når man spiller Hitman så ved man godt at man er morderen. Folk får alltid en bange følelse når man tager pistolen frem. Så... jeg synes det er fint at de reagerer, det er fint at man.. at man ligesom får en respons når man går rundt og tager pistolen frem. Så da rober alle og skrigger eller det kommer sådan musikk eller et eller andet. De snakker til mig, det snakkes rundt mig, ikke. [...]

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- ⁸⁸ A4a: Eh, forskjellen på stealth og vanlig modus, og springe holdt eg på å si, run-modus. Eg merket spesielt godt når eg snek meg inn og så åpnet eg ene døren, så åpnet den seg mye stillere enn når eg går vanlig. Samme gjelder fotskritt og hele den greien der.
- ⁸⁹ A13: Ja, altså det hjelper deg og så, du vet at det er noen i det fjerne. Og det er jo typisk og.. at du kan høre om det er noen i det andre rommet kanskje. Så det og så ha avstand til lyder, det er veldig greit.
- ⁹⁰ G15b-c: No er eg oppdaget, no har eg to alternativer. [...] Ja.. altså. Det har jo veldig mye med situasjonen å gjøre då, fordi du vet at de leter etter deg. Hvis du bare hadde gått nedover gaten og de hadde begynt å rope etter deg så hadde du gjerne ikkje tatt det så tungt.
- ⁹¹ J16b: [...] Då var det jo veldig vekkende for nysgjerrigheten liksom. Ka det er som egentlig foregår her. Eg tror faktisk ikkje eg.. forbandt alle elementene så godt sammen. Eller...
- ⁹² A4b[...] Når eg tok han der advokaten så ropte han litt, og då var eg litt bekymret for om eg kom til å bli oppdaget. Men det gikk jo, det gikk bra.
- ⁹³ L10: [...] Det er en sånn markeringsfunksjon om at du går gjennom inventoryet. Mange spill har det selv om du bare beveger musen over.. eller peker han over objektet du.. og er borti det du egentlig er interessert i. Og det er vel for å registrere at maskinen vet ka som foregår, for då vet du om maskinen har låst seg eller ka. [...]
- ⁹⁴ P15a: Det er ganske greit egentlig. Men, eg trur ikkje det er nødvendig men det hjelp... det gjer det en litt sånn fysisk følelse, at det er nokke fysisk du tukler med. [...] Ja, altså de fleste spill bruker jo det. For å gi pikslene en.. mer fysikk. Fordi at det, det.. når alt kommer til alt så er det liksom bare farger på en skjerm dette her, eller bare piksler. Og det, du må bruke lyd av og til for å gje det en følelse av at du, det er nokke som skjer. [...]
- ⁹⁵ A38c: Nei, altså her er det bare sånne, ja hints and warnings, selvfølgelig. Når det gjelder at de for eksempel har funnet en død person og sånn så hører du gjerne ropingen.
- ⁹⁶ A38b: Det er greit å ha en bitteliten lyd. Altså bare for å gi beskjed om at noe skjer på skjermen. Men... nå er de liksom ikkje nødvendig sånn som i Warcraft og sånn, der man har mye lyd når noe skjedde. Når de der popper opp så ser du de.
- ⁹⁷ P12: Ja, det gjør eg. Det gjør eg. For den lyden gjør jo oppmerksom på at det skjer noe oppe i hjørnet.[...] Eg legger merke til begge deler, lyden er nødvendig. Vil eg påstå.
- ⁹⁸ P7: De, de.. den er vel tima for å, for å... når det skjer nokke spennende, når det er vakter i nærheten, og når eg finner på nokke tull. Sånne ting. Den skal gjøre meg mer spent.
- ⁹⁹ P28: Det var vel, det hadde vel med at eg hadde klart et mission.
- ¹⁰⁰ L5: [...] Og... inne på meat houseet, det slaktehuset der inne, der var det og litt sånn. Det var jo ikkje, eg tviler på at de hadde stereoeanlegg der inne som står og spiller sånn tragisk musikk der inne då. Så det var vel mer spillmusikken der. Jo, så du går liksom rundt og begynner å... du løper ikkje gjennom det første gangen, er dette mennesker eller er dette kanskje ikkje griser.
- ¹⁰¹ P17a: Nei. Det er sånn man plukker opp i bakhodet, ikkje.. det er bare stemningen, det kun hjelper på stemningen. Sånn at det øker creepynessen ved å være i et slakteri. [...]
- ¹⁰² A15a-b: [...] Det er liksom litt sånn stemningsskapende. Litt sånn, ikkje akkurat skummelt men altså, det er litt mer sånn dyster tone over det. Samme som du hører nesten torden sånn... [...] Ja, den er litt sånn psycho. Eg tror det, det virker som det er sånne små semiskumle biter de har liksom...
- ¹⁰³ G23e: Det har vel gjerne med hans syn på hele.... det er jo liksom flashbacks hele greien. Og det er jo det som gjerne er med på å gjøre det så dystert. Fordi han husker det på den måten, ikkje fordi det nødvendigvis var på den måten.

¹⁰⁴ R24a: Ja. Men jeg synes den er mere dystre ude i det der slagteri-afdeling, det er jo klart når der er en fest så er der nogen musik med den. Men man kan tydelig mærke forskellen sådan i... i stemning. For eksempel, det er, lige præcis, i den ende der det er fare for at dø, (?) og der alle menneskene står og danser. Der er det ligesom sat nogle stole op og der er sådan lidt mere...

¹⁰⁵ L5: [...] Så der er det sånn egen klubbmusikk då. Standard amerikansk clubmusic. Og det passer veldig på vegne med feelingen då, det eneste er at du kan kanskje bli litt carried away med sånn musikk. Altså hvis du først er tvunget til å skyte en mann, så ender du plutselig opp med å drepe fem til. Og for en du dreper kommer fem nye løpende, og plutselig har du blodbad der inne, og då har du det og. [...]

¹⁰⁶ P20a: [Å høre musikk når du kikker gjennom nøkkelhullet] er jo ikkje helt realistisk, men det funker fint for at det gir en følelse, altså lydbildet er en del av stemningen i det rommet der. Og når du ser inn i rommet så skal du få en del av stemningen der. Hvis du bare hadde sett de greiene der så hadde det ødelagt mooden når du kom inn etterpå. For du visste ka du såg og så ville ikkje musikken registreres på samme måten.

¹⁰⁷ J29g: [...] Det beskriver jo det psykopatiske sinnet til broren her da til Meat King liksom. Altså... det er jo den der perfekte verdenen liksom sant. Og som settes opp mot det groteske bildet her. Men, men samtidig altså.. det er jo et alter bygget for hun, han elsker jo hun egentlig, så... [...] Den musikken legger hardt til akkurat den tragedien. Aldeles... det er, det er ganske forferdelig. [...]

¹⁰⁸ R28b: Jeg synes det understreker det der værelset (?). ulekre, truende, for der er blod over det hele, og han har er rimelig seriøst merkelig han der, ikke. Jeg synes det passer til å understreke litt det der, sådan... ironi, eller ikke ironi, men altså sånn at det er sådan, understreker den stemning der, den meget sådan ulekre fetthish-stemning. Det er liksom litt sjov at der får... musikken, at det er helt naturlig for dem at man bare klemmer folk opp med kjøttkroer.

¹⁰⁹ L14: Nja, han er ikkje urealistisk men... altså han slår meg ikkje som sånn dønn realistisk heller. Skytelydene, altså lydeffektene på skytingen derimot er ganske overbevisende. De er ikkje så høy som de burde vært, men det har jo litt med brukervennlighet å gjøre.

¹¹⁰ J6b: Det går jo veldig mye på... realisme. Så eg satt og prøvde å få med meg liksom ting som gjorde at.. altså de realistiske lydene. Regnlyden er veldig fin, veldig fin. Og kjøttøksen.. jaja. Eg har ikkje peiling på kordan det høres ut, men... det høres, det høres ut som du kutter nokke der ja. [latter]

¹¹¹ A42: Altså, Hitman har jo prøvd å gjenskape akkurat det der med hvilke lyder hører du, avstander og kordan du befinner deg i forhold til lyden. Spesielt på det der, det at du kan komme.. lyden av regnet er sterkere ved utgangen eller ved døren. Og forsvinner mer når du går inn. Du hører lyden av deg sjøl gå. Du hører folk snakke i det fjerne, og snakke høyre når de kommer nærmere, så det er sånn, litt sånn.. de prøver å gjenskape det virkelige liv mye mer.

¹¹² R10b: Ja. Altså, det er realistisk, og så er det sådan en ekstra ting der gjør at man sådan kan forholde seg til hva der skjer i rommet, fordi titt nå når man spiller så kan man ikke riktig se hva der foregår. Men så kan man måske høre at der går noen eller noe. Så kan du hvertfall finne ut av om der står noen vakter og noe... Det er jo det som er viktig i det her spillet.

¹¹³ G25: Man blir jo enda mer distansert då. For det at du ikkje får noe... du får ikkje noe feedback av omgivelsene liksom. [...] Ja.. det er jo egentlig det, [lyd] er jo med på å plassere deg i... det når du hører en dør åpne seg bak deg, så eller hører en dør åpnes og det ikkje er noen dører foran så antar du at det er bak. Men.. så blir jo det, du vil jo ikkje komme i denne situasjonen.

¹¹⁴ J26: Ja, først så fikk eg liksom bare dotter i ørene, og det var bare mangel på hørsel liksom. Men etterhvert så, så.. som du nevnte litt senere så går det veldig mye på at... eg får rett og slett mer noia. Bli faktisk litt mer redd når det faktisk ikkje er lyd der, fordi at du trenger lyd til å høre om ting er.. rundtomkring holdt eg på og si. Kor ting er.

¹¹⁵ R13: Det er som om [skydescenerne] ikke fungerer riktig, fordi det bliver som om... så får man, så bliver man rigtig påmindet om at det er sådan computerspil altså. Så når der er ikke nogen lyd på så er der bare sådan, to animerede figurer der står og skyter på hinanden.

¹¹⁶ A36: Eh, mye høyere [oppmerksomhetsnivå], eg må konsentrere meg mer på det som skjer rundt.

¹¹⁷ L27a: [...] Det er en veldig kaotisk situasjon, og når lyden er på så spilte eg veldig kaotisk. Men no etter at lyden ble skrudd av og eg ble mye mer systematisk så var det til dels fordi at innlevelsen i det kaoset var jo lik null. Det er jo nesten det samme som et rollespill. Hvis du ikkje lever deg inn i rollen, så kan du per definisjon spille mer effektivt. Men det blir jo mye dårligere spilling.

¹¹⁸ L26a: [Følelsen av kontroll] økte faktisk. Vanligvis så ville han sunket ganske lavt ned. Men til gjengjeld når lyden forsvinner så er det det samme som når du blir blind, då skjerper jo de andre sansene seg. Og.. lyden er veldig hjelpsom på spill, men akkurat her så er han distraherende og veldig lite annet.

¹¹⁹ S2b: [...] Det er jo, night elves får den litt mer mystiske, keltiske følelsen. Mens det.. orkene får den rett og slett det rå, løpe rundt på sletter og hamre løs på ting og sånn. Og... nei, det er rett og slett musikk til ka hver rase står for, menneskene har fått virkelig sånn stolte riddergreier, mens det, undead har fått den der sånn skrekfilm musikk nesten. [...]

¹²⁰ P2 [...] Og så er det disse her pompøse ridderne, no-no-no, no-no-no. Dumme bønder og slike ting, så... Det blir en blanding av litt sånn her strikte Command & Conquer-type lydbilde som er meir sånn i bakgrunnsstøyen, og meir forsøk på å være humoristisk på voiceoveren. Så det er jo gøyt då, du tar det jo ikkje like alvorlig som andre spill.

¹²¹ A1: I Warcraft, ehm... Det.. er et rikt lydbilde. Det er, holdt på og sei, hogging av trær og... mye lyder som som gir beskjed om at det er fare på ferde. Så er det mye gøy lyd du kan provosere frem selvfølgelig hvis du klikker på visse steder.

¹²² R3: Ja ja, selvfølgelig, når basen din blir angrepet så hører du jo en advarsel om at we're under attack eller noe tilsvarende som du, som gjør at du lettere kan reagere på det som skjer.

¹²³ A4: Ja, altså.. i.. blant annet roper de ut "we're under attack", så du får jo de varslene der. Og de forskjellige typene, holdt på og sei, troppene, når du velger de så hører du fort om du har valgt feil tropp og. Rett og slett på grunn av lydene de lager når du har selectet de.

¹²⁴ P5: De er jo et varsel på ka som foregår. Og så.. så det er liksom sånn.. når maskina gjer meg sånn her basically voice-acting så gjer det meg en mykje bedre feedback enn hvis eg bare hadde sett en liten tekst oppi hjørnet, så eg blir meir konsentrert om spillet, blir meir, eg blir meir hengt igjen i spillet.

¹²⁵ P3: Det... er at eg.. eg tar det relativt med ro med tanke på den musikken,[det] oppfordrer at eg tar det med ro, at eg tenker gjennom ka trinn, at eg ikkje stormer inn i et rom uten at eg sjekker ka som er der inne først. Og musikken og lydene gjer meg en sånn.. oppfordrer meg til å gå forsiktig fram og til å være stille. Altså det er ikkje slik som i vanlige skytespill der lyden er høg og mykje tung musikk og.. då blir ein bare oppfordret til å springe til om og skyte det som er der då. Her er det meir, ta det med ro, tenk gjennom handlingene, følge med på kartet, følge med på bevegelser, snike deg etter folk.

¹²⁶ G2a: Musikken er gjerne sånn som man ikkje legger så mye merke til. [...] Men det har jo selvfølgelig en funksjon. Jaa... altså det blir vel helst.. altså musikken er jo der stort sett hele tiden mener eg å huske. Men altså det blir jo selvfølgelig mer, ja ka skal vi si, det blir jo mer trøkk når det skjer noe, som liksom det skal være driv i.

¹²⁷ L-3-4: [...] I begynnelsen så kræsjer du med swat teams. Og de begynner jo å slenge ut noen kommentarer her og der av og til. Men vanligvis så er det så veldig kort møte med de, enten så dør de eller så dør du. Det... du er litt panisk for der, for du har absolutt ikkje lyst å begynne på an igjen på det her. [...] Og lyden generelt er sånn at... ja, du liker ikkje lyden av maskingevær. Lyden av maskingevær er lik du er død. [...]

¹²⁸ L5: Det hørtes ut som en møljekamp med masse sverd involvert. [...] Eh, det er enten humans eller orcs som de er etter, for eg mener at eg har hørt den lyden når eg spiller.

¹²⁹ S5: Ja, det er en fyr med sverd som hogger på en med pil og bue. [...] Siden eg vanligvis er ork så har ikkje de pil og bue, så då pleier eg bare å være veldig fornøyd med at eg har fått en med sverd frem til deres...

¹³⁰ A7: Det er angrep på en bygning. [...] Då vil eg finne ut ka... jaja, det spørs jo kor eg er i kampen då. Altså, hvis eg er den som går til angrep så vet eg at de holder på å gjøre gode ting og hvis eg driver og blir angrepet så er det en dårlig ting. Då vil eg prøve å få tropper til, altså få vekk, få gjort noe, eventuelt bare få noen inn til å reparere mens de står og slår på det.

¹³¹ P7a: Ja, det er ein av bygningene som jobber.

Q7b: Nei, det er det faktisk ikkje.

P7b: Hæ? Er ikkje det?

Q7c: Nei, men det er sikkert litt dårlig lyd, men det er faktisk slåssing. Skal vi ta det en gang til?

P7c: Det ligner på, er det brakkene då?

Q7d: Nei, det er når... det er i en kamp. Så har eg noen... det er alver mot undeads faktisk. Og eg tror alvene har med seg noen flygeting.

[Spiller lyden igjen.]

P7d: Å ja, okei, greit. Crap, I was wrong.

Q7e: Men ka, på hvilket grunnlag var det du trodde det var...

P7e: Hamring, eg hørte hamring eg. Hamring på jernet. Og då jobber man gjerne. I alle fall heime hos meg.

¹³² R10a: Det er en sånn menneske-footman. Har tydeligvis trykka en del ganger på han. (latter) Bare for å høre om han har noe morsomt å si. Hva jeg tenker da, ja da tenker jeg moro. Bare sitte å trykke på han for å høre alt han har å si. Det er det som er morsomt med Warcraft.

¹³³ N8b: Nei, nå kommer tømmeret. Altså, nei.. eh, ja. Det sier vel meg egentlig at det er skog på vei. Men det er en chopper, så eg tenker sannsynligvis at eg måtte hatt fler.

¹³⁴ A9b: [...] Eventuelt hvis du er i et av scenarioene der du faktisk er omringet av skog så kan det faktisk være en dårlig lyd. Eventuelt hvis du, og hvis du spiller i, altså har kommet et stykke ut i scenarioet så kan det være at du, at disse her arbeiderne dine har gått sin vei og har begynt å jobbe andre steder, og du ikkje helst vil ha de der.

¹³⁵ N9: Ja, det er en farm. Det er og til humans. Så det... ja det sier meg at nå, da kan eg lese info om kor mye mat eg har og kor mye eg bruker. Og da ser eg at maten, det kan eg vel egentlig bare se oppe på skjermen, men du får liksom litt kor mye du har var ting. [...] Nei, si det. Du trykker heller på strongholdet, for der pleier det å stå... nei, altså du kan trykke på en fiende sin i alle fall. For da får du se infoen hans noenlunde. Men... nei, trykke på en farm? Gøye lyder? (latter)

¹³⁶ S8a: Nå valgte du en critter.

¹³⁷ L9b: Det første eg gjør hvis eg ikkje ser noe på skjermen då ser eg rett ned på kartet og ser om det blinker. Og så får eg få snuten bort og se ka pokker det er som skjer.

¹³⁸ R13c: Som oftest er det lyden. Først så hører jeg lyden, så ser jeg på mini-mappet, så ser jeg at det blir noe rødt, så ser jeg at det blinker. Vanligvis. Som oftest er man helt opptatt med den screenen, og ser ikke som oftest på mini-mappet unntatt når man angriper eller blir angrepet, akkurat når lyden kommer opp.

¹³⁹ S9b: Eh, som oftest vil eg sjekke, først ser eg på mini-mappet bare for å se liksom noenlunde størrelse på de som angriper. Hvis det bare er en liten rød flekk, så pleier eg.... så kan de egentlig bare bli knekt av tårnene mine eller noe sånn. Hvis eg ser liksom en sånn stor flekk nede der av rød eller ka farge motstanderne er, så hopper eg då inn i byen og sjekker, tar en kikk på kor stor styrken er, ser om eg er nødt, så trekker hjem mine styrker for å ta de, eller om basen klarer det fint. Og så begynner eg å dobbeltklikke på alle slags mulige forsvarsbygninger, sånn at de skal, alle burrowsene skal få innstilt seg så de kan begynne å skyte på de, og såne ting. Så begynner eg, så setter eg i gang forsvar.

¹⁴⁰ A11b: [...] For det er jo tropper i det området der eller, som gir beskjed. [...]

¹⁴¹ A11d: Nei, nå, nå er eg litt usikker på om det er det, eller.. om det er generisk lyd som gir beskjed når, når du er under angrep.

¹⁴² P8c: Den kan være todelt, for det første, faen, eg er nødt å finne nokke så eg kan komme meg inn, eller eg må finne en annen vei inn, eller i rein frustrasjon myrder fyren. Men det er sjelden. (latter) Men etter fem timers spilling og du klarer faen ikkje komme forbi han, då skyter du han.

¹⁴³ R7d: Jeg kunne ikke høre hvad han sagde, det lyder russisk for mig. Altså bulgarsk eller noget[...] Det er måske for å få et lille lokalt forhold, altså.. hvis alle snakket perfekt engelsk med accent så kunne det bare være, det ville ikke være vældig realistisk på en sådan Rotterdam-havn.

¹⁴⁴ L7a: Den... altså no kan ikkje eg huske den lyden fra spillet i det hele tatt då. Men det eg gjerne ville forbundet med den er enten en scene eg måtte kjempe eller fluktscene.

¹⁴⁵ R9a: Ehm.... jeg synes jeg har hørt den før, men jeg kan ikke lige sidde en bane på den. Jeg ved, det er noget sådan, det minder mig om noget sådan chase-musik. Om det er jagt eller et eller andet, russiske soldater eller sådan noget. Jeg synes ikke den er overvældende spændende. Altså den er sådan lidt klassisk, noget sådan, lidt standard chase-musik. Der er ingenting som gør at den lige hører til Hitman. Det kunne ligeså godt være en film synes jeg.

¹⁴⁶ G9a: Er ikkje det et eller annet sånn objectives updated eller noe sånt? [...] Du har gjort noe som du skulle gjøre. Eller alternativt du starter på et brett.

¹⁴⁷ R8: Det er når den opdaterer den der... objectives. Da sier det doot. Det er sådan hvis man fik lige gjort noget, og nå er man i gang med en tæt scene, så kan man høre den bliver opdateret. Og så kan man se den lille, meget tydelige blå eller sådan på toppen [...] [Jeg mærker] den blå boks, for det er meget minimalistisk, altså interface de har valgt. Det var kun lige din health nede i hjørnet og så ens... ellers var det ikke mere rigtig. Så hvis der kommer en farve blå, så lægger man mærke til de med det samme. [...]

¹⁴⁸ A43h: [...] I Doom 3 så er det jo veldig stor vekt på lyd, det er jo det som skremmer deg, altså det er mørkt og så kommer det en hisselyd bak deg og så snur du deg og så var det egentlig bare en gasslekkasje og så står det virkelige monsteret bak deg igjen og skriker, sant. [...] Og så bruker de de feige triksene som at noe faller ned fra taket og sier klang bak deg som får at, akkurat når du vet at no, no må det være et monster her, og så hopper du i stolen og så er det ingenting, liksom. Det er sånne gode gamle skrekkfilm-triks. Og de virker.

¹⁴⁹ L35a: Halo har jo voiceacting på samme måte, bare at, men du klikker ikkje akkurat på folk der. På Halo så er det mer det at du er i nærheten av andre marines og de begynner å gjøre ting, så kommer de med sånne der kommentarer som du liksom kan forestille deg at marines ville kommet med. Og siden du liksom er den helten du er då, og ikkje helt vanlig, så gjør de alt de kan for liksom å briefe litt i ditt nærvær. [...] Warcraft synes eg har veldig bra spesielt på menneskene, for det at der er det, altså du har et lite hierarki, bønder de er godtroende og naive og de er villig til å jobbe og forsåvidt hoppe ut og dø for deg. Soldater de er litt mer sånn, eh.. de virker litt mer klartenkt.

¹⁵⁰ L-29a: [...] Og uansett så er [musikken] veldig intens og oppfordrer til det.. panikk og lite tenking. [...] Så det støtter veldig mye opp om samme type... som Hitman gjør. [...] Men Hitman er et veldig bra spill som egentlig har veldig bra lyd. Og for eksempel det, det er sånne små hint med lyden gjennom hele spillet. For eksempel det at lyddemperen, det våpenet er mye mer altså... mye bedre og til og med høyere enn de fleste andre våpen. [...]

¹⁵¹ G-12f: [...]Der er det den sinnsyke lyden når han går som aldri ville vært laget [i Hitman]. Men den er så kul at du aksepterer det liksom. Det høres ganske bra ut når han går nedover en gang og du hører den lyden. Selv om det er utrolig teit for det er jo ingen andre som hører han.

¹⁵² Ra-31: [...] Hvis vi og snakker om han, der har Hitmans stemme, han der voiceactoren, han er meget god faktisk. Jeg kan også, i Metal Gear Solid, der har de også en sådan erketype & agent-mand i hovedrollen. Og der er det meget viktig, for at bygge ens ego når man har en ret sådan maskulin og cool stemme, liksom man har også med ham i Hitman. Så derfor synes jeg at han er velvalgt også.

¹⁵³ L28a: Eh.. no var eg jo ikkje så veldig positivt innstilt med lydbildet til Warcraft i forrige uke då. Men eg mener egentlig at det, det er alt med ka for et spill du er ute etter då, men eg er mer komfortabel med lydbildet til Warcraft enn Hitman. For det.. Warcraft er [...] kontrollbordet der du har menyene [...]. Den gir veldig sånn.. gotisk, tragisk følelse.. som eg er egentlig, eg synes at spillet ikkje følger helt bra opp til tider då. [...]

¹⁵⁴ P39a: Hm.. det er to vidt forskjellige spill då. For meg så er lydbildet Warcraft mykje meir... prangende på en måte altså... meir og meir bråkete, skal tiltrekke mykje meir oppmerksomhet. Og det skal være mykje meir blant anna. Her er då, her er stillheten en god ting, den, den rolige musikken. mindre folk skriker og bæljer rundt deg, jo bedre er har du det. Lydbildet egentlig mer realistisk og. Og setter deg mykje meir i en stemning der det at her er det snakk om mennesker, og... altså meir sånn realistisk, du ikkje og flirer heile tiden og du sitter ikkje slik å.. det er spenning.

¹⁵⁵ A40: Ja, altså... lyden i Hitman er mer der for å plassere deg der du virkelig, altså som Hitman. Du får diskomusikken når du er i diskoen og du hører kordan han forsvinner, du har avstandslyden mye mer. Mens i Warcraft så er det lyder for å.. mye sånn, informere om ting er ferdig og alle de tingene der. [...] Det eneste, de har jo litt det der med avstand fra lyd fra kor du holder din oppmerksomhet på en del ting, men som regel er det lyder som du hører like høyt uansett kor du er.